

Cultivating Connections: Exploring the Influence of User-Generated Content on Social and Consumer Brand Engagement

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DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to my late parents, may their souls always rest in peace. They were the best parents a kid could have.

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AUTHOR'S DECLARATION

I, Adnan Ali, declare that the research work, analyses, and conclusions reported in this thesis *Cultivating Connections: Exploring the Influence of User-Generated Content on Social and Consumer Brand Engagement* are entirely my effort, except where otherwise acknowledged. This thesis contain no material or part, submitted for the award pf other degree. Except where otherwise indicated, this thesis is my own work.

Abstract

Background: Marketers are increasingly interested in the concept of brand engagement, particularly during the current era of social media, which connects people in real time across the world. Social media users (henceforth SMUs) create content when they interact online on social media platforms. This content is called user generated content (henceforth, UGC) which is not just about the personal lives of people. Rather, it involves SMUs talking about their experiences, including. This brings brands into the scope of their discussions. When people talk about the same brand, or create UGC about it, this leads to e-WOM as there are different avenues available to SMUs on social media platforms to create UGC. This al has a significant impact on other SMUs who are at the receiving end of this UGC. Consequently, this creates social brand-, and consumer brand engagement. This necessitates some exploration of the role of UGC in creating brand engagement.

Objective: The current research explores how different types of SMUs create, exchange, share and consume UGC, and it examines the resultant social brand engagement and consumer brand engagement that subsequently occurs. The context is Islamic banking.

Method: The research is intended to explore a social reality, which requires digging into a social situation involving multiple layers, i.e., types of UGC, types of SMUs, and types of brand engagement, and the interactions between these. the intention of the study is not to evaluate variables, but to explore social realities. Hence, a social constructionist approach is used. Primary data were collected from thirty-two participants through semi-structured interviews. Since the aim is to gather thick, descriptive data, semi-structured interviews were undertaken instead of structured interviews. Hence, the social constructionist approach is justified. All other methodological choices are exercised accordingly.

Findings: The study finds that there are different motivational reasons why SMUs create, share, consume and exchange UGC resulting in brand engagement. These include, but are not limited to, Narrative Threads of Wisdoms with other SMUs, posting to demonstrate a sense of responsibility, sharing rewards, and to enjoy their position as opinion leaders. The research also identifies that UGC creators vary by type and there are creators, passive participants, consumers/collectors, and criticizers. Several social exchange factors were also found which

enhance the effectiveness of UGC. These factors comprise content expertise, social trust, product usage, and relevance.

Originality: This research is the first to conceptualize UGC and consumer brand engagement from the perspective of a social constructionism epistemological, and relativist ontological position. It highlights two dimensions of brand engagement: social brand engagement and consumer brand engagement in the context of Islamic banks. Moreover, the research also builds on social exchange theory to conceptualize the process of social brand-, and consumer brand engagement. It is the first study to apply this theory in the context of social media platforms as a source of brand engagement by applying social exchange theory.

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CHAPTER 1: RESEARCH INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

User-Generated Content (henceforth UGC) can be defined as any form of content such as text, videos, images or reviews that are created by consumers or end-users of online systems or services. These systems tend to be publicly available to other consumers and end-users (Kitirattarkarn, Araujo, & Neijens, 2019). UGC plays a significant role in marketing, especially in digital environments on social media. Indeed, UGC allows brands to leverage creativity and enhance authentic consumer experiences. Brands can thus amplify their marketing efforts and build a sense of community (Aichner, 2019). Ibrahim, Aljarah, Hayat, and Lahuerta-Otero (2022) assert that UGC, via comments and shares can stimulate consumer engagement.

UGC shapes consumer behaviour in digital environments. According to Li and Xie (2020), the nature of the UGC, for instance, the quality of images, can significantly influence social media engagement. Moreover, Dolan et al., (2019) suggest that social media engagement behaviour can be facilitated by creating customer-focused content. Similarly, Mohammad, Quoquab, Thurasamy, and Alolayyan (2020) found a strong correlation between UGC quality and brand engagement, where both functional and emotional values play mediating roles.

UGC can foster consumer engagement with marketer-generated content. Yang, Li, Lin, Jiang, and Huo (2022) found that engagement depends significantly on the nature of the various content-generating devices and content features available. Furthermore, a study by Mathur, Tewari, and Singh (2022) discovered that consumer attitudes towards UGC significantly affect their online purchase intentions. Hence, the type and quality of UGC create different impacts on consumer behaviour, particularly when it comes to engagement and purchase intentions. Moreover, UGC plays a crucial role in shaping consumer behaviour by fostering a sense of community and trust amongst consumers. Baker, Kearney, Laud, and Holmlund (2021) explain how individual and collective psychological ownership of branded products significantly influences consumer engagement. They further elaborate that UGC, in the form of reviews or shared experiences, can help consumers establish an emotional connection with brands, thus enhancing their engagement.

UGC also plays a critical role in enhancing brand authenticity and developing a bond between consumers and brands. Rosado-Pinto, Loureiro, and Bilro (2020) used a text mining approach to reveal how brand authenticity and consumer brand engagement can be expressed in reviews

as a form of UGC. They argued that such user-generated reviews can enhance the perceived authenticity of brands, leading to increased consumer engagement.

The role of UGC in the marketing landscape is not just a matter of content production. It also plays a significant role in shaping consumer behaviour. UGC is especially potent in the digital environment, and particularly on social media platforms (Ibrahim et al., 2022; Davcik et al., 2022). Social media allows consumers to interact directly with brands and other consumers. These interactions can often be more influential than traditional marketing efforts as consumers increasingly find UGC more relatable, trustworthy, and influential (Dolan et al., 2019). A key role that UGC plays in digital marketing is the fostering of consumer engagement. Ibrahim et al. (2022) point out that UGC, compared to firm-created content, can significantly drive consumer engagement such as likes, comments, and shares. Yang et al. (2022) further illustrates that the devices used to generate content, and the content features themselves also play a significant role in fostering consumer engagement. Consumers are more likely to engage with content that is relevant to their interests and appeals to their emotions. Therefore, content that is generated by users, such as reviews, experiences, and testimonials, can significantly stimulate engagement.

In terms of consumer behaviour, UGC can both directly and indirectly impact purchasing decisions. According to Mathur et al. (2022), user-generated content affects online purchase intentions through the mediating effect of consumer attitudes towards UGC. They suggest that consumers are more likely to develop a favourable attitude towards a product or brand if the UGC is positive. Moreover, Li and Xie (2020) propose that the use of images in UGC can significantly enhance social media engagement, which in turn influences consumer behaviour.

UGC also influences brand engagement. Mohammad et al. (2020) suggest that the quality of user-generated content can significantly impact brand engagement, mediated by functional and emotional values. This means that high-quality UGC that provides useful information or appeals to the emotions is more likely to promote brand engagement. Similarly, Tan and Chen (2022) emphasize that the characteristics of marketer-generated content can also affect consumer engagement. They argue that content characteristics such as relevance, novelty, and attractiveness can enhance emotional involvement amongst consumers, thereby increasing brand engagement. Interestingly, UGC has also been linked to incivility online. Wolter et al. (2023) illustrate how online incivility can affect consumer engagement behaviour with social

media sites managed by brands. They suggest that uncivil UGC can create a negative online environment, discouraging consumer engagement and potentially harming brand reputation.

UGC has a differential impact on consumer behaviour. Depending on its nature and quality, it can either enhance or harm brand perceptions and engagement (Aljarah et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2020). Consequently, marketers need to adopt strategic measures to manage and leverage UGC effectively. UGC also plays a crucial role in promoting authenticity and trust in brands. Valsesia and Diehl (2022) suggest that sharing experiential purchases compared to material ones on social media alters authenticity and liking of social media users. This underlines the power of UGC in shaping brand perceptions and influencing consumer behaviour. In conclusion, UGC, when utilized strategically, can function as a powerful tool in digital marketing, driving consumer engagement, shaping brand perception, and influencing purchasing decisions.

The effects of UGC can differ based on the type and nature of the content in question as well as the platform, and the target audience. Shahbaznezhad, Dolan, and Rashidirad (2021) argued that the format of social media content and the platform used significantly influences user engagement. For instance, a study by Tan and Chen (2022) found that marketer-generated content characteristics have a different effect on consumer engagement in different cultural contexts. UGC in a marketing context plays a multifaceted role. It amplifies marketing efforts, shapes consumer behaviour, fosters engagement, enhances brand authenticity, and builds a sense of community amongst consumers. However, the impact of UGC on consumers can vary based on the content type, platform, and target audience, indicating the need for a tailored approach in creating and utilizing UGC for marketing purposes.

1.2 RESEARCH BACKGROUND

The concept of UGC has been widely researched by marketers such as Dhar and Chang (2009) who undertook a close examination of online communication. Several early studies examined the impact of UGC on the purchase decisions of consumers (see Zhao, Yang, Narayan, and Zhao 2013; Senecal and Nantel 2004; Goh et al 2013) along with improved performance in terms of sales and marketing (Li and Hitt 2008; Goes et al 2014; Zhu and Zhang 2010). A second stream of studies, which aligns with this research, examined the behaviors behind the creation of UGC. There are three key aspects that are central to this stream, which are the behaviors of users, the content features of UGC and user creation, and the sharing context (Toubia and Stephen 2013; Henning-Thurau et al 2004; Smith et al 2012; Berger 2014;

Muntinga et al 2011; Berger and Milkman 2012). Several studies related to this stream have looked many of these aspects together (Smith et al 2012; Chen and Berger 2016; Toubia and Stephen 2013; Liu-Thompkins and Rogerson 2012).

During the previous decade, this concept has become extremely popular with the emergence of web 2.0. However, there is no consensus around a universal definition because the construct is something of a moving target (Christodoulides et al 2012). Previous definitions have focussed on the organisational perspective and the significance of UGC creation (Interactive Advertising bureau 2008; Henning-Thurau et al 2010; Daughtery et al 2008). However, more recently, authors have sought to define its traits. For instance, Christodoulides et al (2012) stated that UGC content is available to the public through media, which reflects the need for creative efforts outside of professional practices and routines. UGC has a significant impact on consumer engagement and buying behaviour on social media. Kitirattakarn, Araujo, and Neijens (2019) point out how personal and national collectivism-individualism dynamics moderate the impact of content characteristics and social relationships on consumer engagement with brand-related UGC. Ibrahim et al. (2022) further demonstrate how firm-created content and UGC affect consumer engagement, and Davcik et al. (2022) explored how non-sponsored brand-related UGC influences consumer engagement. UGC also has a powerful influence on consumer purchase intentions. Mathur, Tewari, and Singh (2022) indicate the mediating effect of consumer attitudes towards UGC in terms of online purchase intentions. This aspect suggests it is crucial for brands to adopt a strategic approach towards customer interactions.

Engaging content not only influences consumer buying behaviour, but also encourages consumers to interact with brands. Hinson et al. (2019) applied attachment theory to analyse the antecedents and consequences of customer engagement on Facebook. Li and Xie (2020) established the effects of image content on social media engagement whilst Dolan et al. (2019) proposed a framework for engaging customers through social media content. The role of the format of social media content, and the significance of the platform in user engagement were highlighted by Shahbaznezhad et al. (2021). The quality of UGC also plays a vital role in brand engagement. Mohammad et al. (2020) outlined the mediating role of functional and emotional values on the effects of UGC quality in terms of brand engagement. Wolter, Bacile, and Xu (2023) discussed how online incivility affects consumer engagement behaviour on brand-curated social media. UGC affects consumer behaviour in various ways. Qu, Saffer, and Riffe (2022) reveal how consumer conversations influence online engagement behaviours. Mishra

(2019) investigated the antecedents of consumer engagement with brand-related content on social media, suggesting that UGC contributes to brand knowledge. Cheung, Pires, and Rosenberger (2020) studied the influence of perceived social media marketing on consumer–brand engagement and brand knowledge. It is important to remember that UGC and consumer engagement are influenced by cultural and geographic factors. For example, Tan and Chen (2022) present empirical evidence from China's WeChat food marketing to explore how marketer-generated content characteristics affect consumer engagement. UGC has a significant impact on consumer engagement and buying behaviour on social media. Brands can leverage these insights to strategize their approaches to customer interactions, and to enhance their performance in the market.

Roumieh and Garg (2014) argue that e-marketing has become a focal point for researchers, top management, policy makers and Islamic businesses. According to Fadahunsi and Kargwell (2015), the marketing operations of Islamic societies are entirely based on the concept of “Halal”. As such, marketers on social media cannot advertise false features or labelling. In addition, they cannot exaggerate through the promotion of goods and services. For instance, Daraz.pk (a company based on a brick and clicks business model) once launched a “Black Friday” sale in Pakistan. Initially, this initiative failed, as Friday is a holy day for Muslims, and labelling Friday as black is never acceptable in Islamic countries. A recent study reported that all Muslim respondents in Australia were willing to purchase Islamic banking products but had insufficient understanding and information about these products (Rammal, and Zurbruegg, 2016). Research has also shown that variables such as the number of product and service reviews, education levels, product and service knowledge, consumer awareness, IT literacy, and the advertisement and purchasing power of customers in Western countries varies with Islamic countries (Roumieh and Garg 2014, Fadahunsi and Kargwell, 2015; Ozuem, and Lancaster, 2012; Wilson, 2012). According to a recent survey, just 52% of Muslim respondents in South Africa were aware of Islamic banking products, but had insufficient information about these products (Cheteni, 2014). Similarly, some 65% of respondents showed an interest in Islamic banking products but had no knowledge about these products in Sri Lanka (Nimsith, et al., 2016). This study sets out to explore how the UGC on social media can help Islamic banks to increase awareness, brand engagement and their understanding of target audiences. This will enable Islamic banks to encourage reviews of Islamic products/services. It will also position them to drive eWOM, profitability and brand stories about Islamic banks. The findings will enable researchers, policy makers, marketing managers and top management in Islamic banks

to better understand how user generated content on social networking platforms can increase brand engagement amongst both target markets and existing customers.

1.3 RESEARCH PROBLEM

The media landscape has been influenced by the changing dynamics of recent technological developments, along with the way in which firms interact with their audiences (Lv, Jin, & Huang, 2021; Rossolatos, 2021; Kemp et al., 2021). A recent survey found that social media users have increased globally to reach over one billion over the past decade (Shen, 2021; Krebs & Lischka, 2019). This has played a pivotal role in the transformation of how information is acquired, how brands engage with their audiences online, and how the experiences and lifestyles of consumers are shaped (Vinerean & Opreana, 2021; Grover & Kar, 2020; Estrella-Ramón et al., 2019). On the back of such developments, companies are now better equipped with the latest technological tools that have revolutionized new practices when it comes to engaging with audiences. This signifies the importance of customer engagement, and the need for healthy relationships between firms and audiences (Trivedi, Arora, & Soni, 2022; Soares, Limongi, & Cohen, 2022; Hoskins et al., 2021). Moreover, such developments are not limited to these areas, but extend to academic development, including new theories and empirical evidence related to customer brand engagement (Naeem, 2019; Schivinski et al., 2021; Cheng et al., 2021). For instance, Lu, Xie, & Chen, (2023) found that one of the most salient measures for optimal growth and the value of businesses lies in customer engagement. In other words, business value is also defined as the extent to which customers shares information about doing business with companies (Grassi, 2020; Yang, Cai, & Tu, 2021). This is particularly the case for retailers who are on the verge of searching for the latest and effective methods of growth to achieve a higher share of profit (Menon et al., 2019).

Social media communications have been defined by Hartmann et al. (2021) as not only interactive in nature, but also collaborative, participatory, and communal. This allows firms to engage with their customers to develop strong linkages. Social media also has the power to mediate brand engagement with customers. Dhaoui & Webster (2021) defined consumer engagement as a concept that is multidimensional, and which comprises emotional, cognitive, and behavioural dimensions. It plays a pivotal role in relational exchange, whereby other concepts like engagement antecedents sit within the confines of brand community. It is also especially important to note that consumer brand engagement and brand relationships both require a specific level of commitment to be effective (Schivinski et al., 2022). As such, it is

imperative to note that firms need to capture the attention of their audiences to engage them, and to develop relationships whilst driving transactions and social brand engagement, and to enhance their overall performance (Cheung et al., 2022; He et al., 2021; Onofrei, Filieri, & Kennedy, 2022).

Studies by Naeem and Ozuem (2021), Naeem (2020), and Osei-Frimpong (2019) collectively explore the role of consumer motivations and user-generated content in social brand engagement. While they offer valuable insights, they primarily focus on diverse consumers and retail settings. This thesis, while recognizing the importance of these factors, distinguishes itself by considering a broader industrial context and by examining a technological aspect. It delves into how interactive digital platforms can be optimized to enhance brand engagement using consumer motivations and UGC, thereby offering a more comprehensive and technologically focussed perspective on the subject.

The purpose of this study is to understand how user engagement with brand-related content on social media platforms can impact consumer behaviour, and specifically the consumer's purchase intentions and brand loyalty. The research explores a broad array of studies conducted on the subject to obtain a multi-dimensional understanding of the dynamics involved. The compiled table presents an organized citation structure of previous studies that have addressed various aspects of the research objective. Each study has been categorized based on its focus on either UGC, Firm-Generated Content (henceforth FGC), or both. This differentiation is integral to the research, as it outlines the distinct impacts of consumer and firm-based content on user engagement and subsequent consumer behaviours. Furthermore, the categorization allows for a comprehensive assessment of how the source of content impacts its effectiveness in engaging consumers and promoting brand loyalty. Studies by Lv, , Jin,., & Huang, (2021), Rossolatos, (2021), and Kemp, Porter, Anaza, & Min, D.-J. (2021) among others, focus primarily on UGC. They delve into various facets such as consumer engagement with media-generated content, depth of brand engagement, and the impact of storytelling in online environments. These works provide a rich understanding of how user engagement with UGC influences purchase intentions and brand loyalty. On the other hand, research by Grover & Kar (2020), Estrella-Ramón, García-de-Frutos, Ortega-Egea, & Segovia-López, (2019) as well as Trivedi, Arora, & Soni, (2022) provide insights into the role of FGC in creating user engagement and influencing consumer behaviour. These studies examine aspects like the content strategies of marketers on social media platforms and their influence on brand equity. They also explore the impact of social media communications on brand switching intentions,

and how user engagement models can enhance the services of mobile payment providers. Finally, studies by Schivinski, Muntinga, Pontes, & Lukasik, (2021), Cheng, Liu, Qi, & Wan, (2021) as well as Lu, Xie, & Chen, (2023) consider both UGC and FGC. They provide a balanced viewpoint on how both sources of content can influence user engagement and consumer behaviour. To conclude, the table presented below is a collection of resources that provide varying perspectives on the research aim. The studies classified based on the origin of the content – UGC or FGC – pave the way for a comprehensive understanding of how user engagement with brand-related content on social media can impact consumer behaviour.

Table 1-1 User generate connect in context of brand engagement.

Authors and Year	Study Focus	Insights for Islamic Banking
Lv, Jin, & Huang, 2021	Engagement with Media-Generated Content (MGC), Word of Mouth (WOM), and purchase intention.	Brands can focus on creating engaging MGC to boost WOM and customer purchase intention (Lv et al., 2021).
Rossolatos, 2021	Dimensionalizing interaction in social media brand communities.	Highlights the significance of interactive, multidimensional strategies in fostering brand communities, an insight Islamic banks could implement.
Kemp, Porter III, Anaza, & Min, 2021	Impact of storytelling in creating firm and customer connections.	Islamic banks can leverage storytelling as a powerful tool for establishing a connection with customers (Kemp et al., 2021).
Naeem, 2019	The role of social networking platforms in addressing the challenges of Islamic banks.	Social media platforms can help Islamic banks address their unique challenges (Naeem, 2019).
Grover & Kar, 2020	Social Media Engagement Models for mobile payment service providers.	Brands can use this model to boost user engagement for their mobile banking services (Grover & Kar, 2020).
Estrella-Ramón, García-de-Frutos, Ortega-Egea, & Segovia-López, 2019	The influence of marketers' and users' content on corporate Facebook fan pages on brand equity.	The balance between marketer and user-generated content on social platforms can significantly impact brand equity, which is applicable to Islamic banks (Estrella-Ramón et al., 2019).
Schivinski, Muntinga, Pontes, & Lukasik, 2021	The effects of brand equity on the propensity of consumers to engage with brand-related content on social media.	Brands can focus on enhancing their brand equity to boost consumer engagement with brand-related content (Schivinski et al., 2021).

Cheng, Liu, Qi, & Wan, 2021	Effects of firm-generated content on consumer digital engagement and firm performance.	By creating more firm-generated content, Islamic banks can improve consumer engagement and overall performance (Cheng et al., 2021).
Dhaoui & Webster, 2021	Brand and consumer engagement behaviors on Facebook brand pages.	Engagement behaviors on Facebook brand pages could also be relevant for Islamic banks (Dhaoui & Webster, 2021).
Loureiro, Bilro, & Japutra, 2020	The effect of consumer-generated media stimuli on emotions and consumer brand engagement.	Brands can incorporate consumer-generated media stimuli to evoke emotions and enhance consumer brand engagement (Loureiro et al., 2020).
Sabermajidi, Valaei, Balaji, & Goh, 2020	Measuring brand-related content in social media: a socialization theory perspective.	Utilizing socialization theory, Islamic banks can effectively measure brand-related content in social media (Sabermajidi et al., 2020).
Qin, 2020	Fostering brand–consumer interactions in social media: the role of social media uses and gratifications.	Brands could foster brand-consumer interactions by understanding the uses and gratifications of social media (Qin, 2020).
Santiago, Borges-Tiago, & Tiago, 2022	Is firm-generated content a lost cause?	Firm-generated content is not a lost cause but requires strategic development to engage consumers, applicable to Islamic banks.

Through recent technological advancements in the marketing literature on social media, engagement has seen a revolutionary change which provides an even broader explanation of engagement. It also identifies that engagement is not just limited to interactions amongst people, but also to brands and others key players that influence engagement (Chandler and Lusch 2015; Florenthal, 2019; Storbacka et al 2016). It has been observed that social media has allowed users to interact with each other to develop mutual feelings regarding brands, and these feelings are developed through interactions on social media. As such, there is a need to understand the socialization context where social brand engagement occurs (Carlson, et al., 2019). Social media is a platform where the brand is not in control. However, there are many opportunities for individuals to gather on social media platforms virtually, to share their feelings and experiences as a form of engagement. Social brand engagement has been defined by Kozinets (2014) as the extent to which consumers interact with one another on social media platforms. In addition, Vivek et al (2014) also recognize the presence of inter-relationships amongst consumers that drive social engagement with brands. This often involves others in

their social network that interact with the same brand (Amani, 2022). Engagement occurs when consumers virtually connect with one another and share their views, opinions, feedback, and experiences of brands. This creates social engagement (Lee, and Park, 2022). There is a variety of literature on consumer engagement behavior on social media. Several scholars have also acknowledged the role of social interactions in the confines of service systems through a social interactive engagement construct (Calder et al 2009). This involves a social dimension and covers a broader social engagement context. Therefore, research should explore this context by considering local contextual factors, rather than generalized results (Helme-Guizon, and Magnoni, (2019) which tend to evaluate measurements or the social aspects of engagement (Gambetti et al 2012). This provides an alternative to simply focusing on social aspects (Osei-Frimpong, and McLean, 2018). Osei-Frimpong, and McLean, (2018) suggest that exploring the social context of social brand engagement by understanding customer interactions subjectively is key (Osei-Frimpong et al., 2020). Moreover, Schaefer, et al., (2022) suggest that there is a need to understand the systematic process of social brand engagement and consumer brand engagement, since these are socially constructed through the interactions of SMUs.

Influence of Cultural and Societal Values on User-Generated Content and Brand Engagement in Islamic Banks While Kitirattarkarn et al. (2019) explored the moderating role of personal and national collectivism-individualism on consumer engagement with brand-related user-generated content, there seems to be a lack of studies that specifically investigate the influence of cultural and societal values in an Islamic banking context. Islamic banking in Pakistan operates within unique cultural and religious constructs, and the way these elements affect user-generated content and its effect on brand engagement remains unexplored.

Research Gap 2: The Role of Content Characteristics in User-Generated Content and Brand Engagement in Islamic Banks. While several studies (e.g., Davcik et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2022) have discussed the effects and mechanisms of consumer engagement with non-sponsored brand-related user-generated content, little attention has been given to how the content characteristics of user-generated content in the Islamic banking sector influence consumer engagement. Understanding this could provide Islamic banks with better insights into how to leverage and respond to UGC. The aim here is to identify how the content characteristics of UGC impacts brand engagement in the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan.

In terms of the impact of online incivility on brand engagement in Islamic Banks Wolter et al. (2023) examined how online incivility impacts consumer engagement behaviour on social media. However, it is not clear how online incivility, in the form of negative user-generated content, might impact brand engagement in the context of Islamic banks. It would be beneficial to understand how Islamic banks can manage such occurrences to maintain or improve their brand engagement. It is therefore important to investigate the impact of online incivility in the form of negative UGC on brand engagement within the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan. Hence, social brand engagement in the context of Islamic banks is explored below to examine the extent of interactivity amongst users of Islamic banking brands.

This study will delve into the influences of cultural and societal values on UGC. It will examine the characteristics of UGC that encourage brand engagement, and it will scrutinize the double-edged sword of online incivility, particularly negative UGC. By addressing these multifaceted and interconnected areas, the study aims to provide Islamic banks in Pakistan with insightful, actionable strategies to foster stronger relationships with their consumers and achieve higher engagement through effective UGC. The fundamental philosophy of this research is to enrich the understanding of the dynamic interplay of culture, content, online incivility, and brand engagement in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan. It underscores the principle that while UGC can empower consumers and brands alike, it also inherits the cultural and societal nuances of its context, emphasizing the need for a bespoke, contextual approach to maximize its effectiveness. To accomplish this aim, the study will provide comprehensive answers to the research questions above, thereby contributing to the body of knowledge concerning UGC and brand engagement within the unique context of Islamic banking in Pakistan. By doing so, it will shed light on the untapped potential of effective UGC strategies in this, sector and pave the way for innovative future research.

1.4 RESEARCH AIM

To develop a comprehensive and contextual framework to understand and enhance the role and impact of UGC on brand engagement in Islamic banking within the Pakistani cultural and societal milieu.

1.5 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To examine how cultural and societal values within the Islamic banking context in Pakistan can influence UGC and subsequent brand engagement.

2. To identify how the content characteristics of UGC impact brand engagement in the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan.
3. To investigate the impact of online incivility in the form of negative UGC on brand engagement in the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan.

1.6 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. How does the cultural context of Pakistan temper the impact of UGC on brand engagement in Islamic banks?

This research question aims to explore the role of the cultural context of UGC in driving brand engagement. Studies such as Kiritattarkarn et al. (2019) have highlighted the moderation effect of personal and national collectivism-individualism on consumer engagement with brand-related UGC. However, these findings have not been contextualized within the cultural landscape of Pakistan, particularly in relation to Islamic banks. By addressing this question, a specific research gap is addressed to understand the role of cultural nuances in shaping the impact of UGC on brand engagement.

2. What are the unique characteristics of UGC that positively influence brand engagement for Islamic banks in Pakistan?

The second research question is designed to identify the specific attributes of user-generated content that are most effective in boosting brand engagement in the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan. While various studies (like those by Davcik et al., 2022; Li & Xie, 2020) have explored the effects and mechanisms of consumer engagement with non-sponsored brand-related UGC, and the role of image content in social media engagement, there is a scarcity of research focusing on the characteristics that influence Islamic banks in Pakistan. This research question, therefore, aims to address this void.

3. How does the quality of UGC mediate the relationship between functional and emotional values and brand engagement for Islamic banks in Pakistan?

This question focuses on understanding the mediating role of UGC quality in terms of the relationship between functional and emotional values and brand engagement. The specific context is Islamic banks in Pakistan. Mohammad et al. (2020) have discussed the mediating role of UGC quality in terms of brand engagement, however, there few studies have explored this relationship in the unique setting of Islamic banks in Pakistan. By answering

this question, it is possible to establish whether the quality of UGC plays a critical role in how functional and emotional values drive brand engagement.

1.7 CONTRIBUTION

The research contributes both theoretically and practically to the concepts of sampling, bargaining, commitment, and internalization within the specific context of Islamic banking in Pakistan. Theoretically, this study expands the existing knowledge base by examining the role of these social exchange processes in enhancing brand engagement in the Islamic banking sector. Despite the growing interest in Islamic finance, there is a dearth of research focusing on social exchange as a driver of brand engagement. By exploring how these processes work in the Islamic banking environment, this study fills a critical gap in the literature.

The proposed model in this research offers a new perspective on the interaction between social exchange processes and UGC as a means to drive brand engagement. The model shows that each stage of the social exchange process can be enhanced by a different aspect of UGC, such as quality, authenticity, peer influence, the social flux of UGC, and rewards. This novel theoretical model serves as a foundation for future research in this area and provides a basis for comparative studies across different sectors or cultures.

In terms of practical contributions, this research provides actionable insights for Islamic banks seeking to enhance their brand engagement. The proposed strategies for each social exchange process—sampling, bargaining, commitment, and internalization—outline a comprehensive approach to leveraging UGC to drive brand engagement. These strategies include fostering authenticity, leveraging influencers, stimulating creativity, creating engaging communities, incentivizing engagement, and maintaining relevance and timeliness in content. The study further emphasizes the importance of aligning with Islamic principles and values at every step of these processes. Such practical knowledge is crucial for organizations operating within the Islamic banking sector. Moreover, by outlining how each stage can be measured, the study provides a practical guide for Islamic banks to assess their performance in each area, and to identify opportunities for improvement. These findings are particularly valuable in the context of digital marketing, where social media platforms offer a fertile ground for fostering social exchange processes. The study suggests that Islamic banks should fully utilize these platforms

to encourage UGC and foster engagement, offering a roadmap for organizations to transition towards more digital, customer-centric marketing strategies.

Lastly, the research underscores the importance of the social flux of UGC as a means to enhance brand engagement, highlighting the potential of community building and co-creation in fostering a sense of belonging and loyalty amongst customers. These insights are particularly relevant in the current era, where consumers are increasingly seeking more interactive and participatory relationships with brands. In summary, this research makes significant contributions to both the theory and practical application of social exchange processes in the context of Islamic banking. It offers a comprehensive model for leveraging these processes to enhance brand engagement and provides actionable insights for Islamic banks to improve their marketing strategies.

1.8 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Since SMUs create, share and exchange UGC during their routine interactions and in their respective social and cultural contexts, there is some justification for applying a social constructionist approach in this study. Such an approach attaches importance to social and cultural contexts since these influence constructions of reality. By considering these contexts, the researcher will be able to understand the intricate social realities relating to UGC with respect to online brand engagement with Islamic banks in Pakistan. Since the current research involves studying the behaviours of customers, and each customer's view about UGC is unique, it is important to consider customer opinions about the creation, sharing and exchange of UGC since these shapes social, and consumer brand engagement.

Understanding the factors that influence SMUs and the nature of UGC is of paramount importance as this influence social brand, and consumer brand engagement. For example, the literature shows that in selected circumstances, individuals tend to accept celebrity endorsements more favourably than public endorsements. However, not everyone is as receptive of celebrity endorsements, and some customers prefer looking at feedback posted by other customers. Therefore, a social constructionist approach is useful to access multiple views of reality. The approach recognises that none is better than the other. Thus, by adopting a social constructionist approach, the current research will investigate the motives of SMUs to create, share, and exchange UGC with implications for brand engagement and the role UGC plays in social, and consumer brand engagement.

The social constructionist approach is useful for understanding and appreciating the experiences of individuals instead of testing hypotheses. Since the aim of the current research is to explore the role of UGC in brand engagement with Islamic banks in Pakistan, hypothesis testing is not required. Instead, exploratory approach is mandated. By taking a social constructionist approach the researcher will be able to consider the reasons why SMUs create, share and exchange UGC. An exploratory research design is therefore helpful where the aim is to generate a theory. Thus, it aligns with inductive reasoning which is employed by the researcher in this study to develop a conceptual model about the role of UGC in brand engagement.

The researcher develops a theory as part of exploratory or social constructionist research by identifying patterns in thick descriptive data, in this case about the impact of UGC on brand engagement with Islamic banks in Pakistan. As inductive reasoning is employed, it involves starting with observations, and builds towards developing propositions about such experiences.

1.9 STRUCTURE OF RESEARCH

The thesis commences with a customary **Dedication**, a personal note where the author can dedicate their work to someone significant or inspirational. This is followed by the **Acknowledgement** section, where the author expresses gratitude towards individuals or institutions that contributed to the completion of their research work. The **Author's Declaration** ensures the reader about the originality of the work and the author's adherence to ethical guidelines.

The main content starts with **Chapter 1: Research Introduction**, setting the tone for the entire thesis. It begins with an introduction to the subject, explaining the relevance of the chosen topic. This chapter delves into the background of the research, explaining why the research topic is of interest or importance, thereby offering readers a comprehensive understanding of the topic's context. It further presents the research problem, clearly stating what the thesis aims to solve. Next, it defines the aim and objectives of the research, outlining the targeted achievements. This section also includes the research questions, which guide the entire research study, followed by a statement on the study's contribution to the existing body of knowledge. The chapter concludes with an overview of the research methodology used and a brief outline of the subsequent research structure.

Chapter 2: Literature Review provides an extensive analysis of relevant literature on the subject. It begins with an introduction to the concept of brand-related user-generated content (UGC), exploring its role in social media and its potential benefits. The chapter discusses various dimensions of UGC, the unique features of social communications content, and the aspects affecting consumer attitudes towards an organization's response. It examines the quality of content, investigating the different levels of UGC creation and the types of content that boost user engagement. Furthermore, this chapter presents the theoretical frameworks relevant to the research, namely the self-determination theory, consumer socialization theory, and social exchange theory, all aiding in better understanding the research topic.

In **Chapter 3: Research Methodology**, the author unfolds the research philosophy, design, strategy, approach, and methods adopted for the study. It elaborates on the tools employed for data collection, focusing on semi-structured interviews and the selection process for participants. The chapter then discusses sampling, providing details on participant selection and the decided sample size. It justifies the use of a pilot study and provides insights into the thematic analysis process used to analyse the data collected. Ethical considerations and measures to ensure the trustworthiness of the qualitative research are also addressed, concluding with a summary of the chapter.

Chapter 4: Analysis presents the findings of the research. It follows a thematic approach to interpret and understand the data collected, categorizing it into four main themes: catalysts of co-creation, echoes of influence, the prism of perception, and vibrations of value. Each theme is thoroughly discussed with its corresponding codes, providing detailed insights into the research findings.

Chapter 5: Discussion and Findings starts with a brief introduction followed by a comprehensive discussion on the main findings, including insights into catalysts of co-creation and resonance of reverence in UGC within the context of Islamic Banking. It also provides answers to the research questions initially posed, further substantiating the findings.

In **Chapter 6: Development of the Conceptual Framework**, the author introduces and elaborates on a conceptual framework derived from the research findings. This framework serves as a theoretical construct that encapsulates the study's main ideas and the relationships between them. This chapter succinctly presents the framework, discussing its various elements, and concludes with a summary.

Finally, **Chapter 7: Conclusion and Recommendations** encapsulates the entire research journey. It starts with an introduction summarizing the research, followed by a detailed explanation of the research contributions, both theoretical and practical. It then highlights the limitations of the study, offering avenues for future research to address these gaps. This chapter provides a conclusive statement and recommends areas where the research findings can be applied or where further research could be pursued.

The structure of this thesis adheres to a well-rounded research design. It moves from the broader context of the research problem, through a critical review of the literature and explanation of methodology, to the presentation of data and discussion on the findings, and finally concludes with a summary and suggestions for future work. The logical flow ensures that each component builds upon the last, guiding the reader through a coherent narrative and comprehensive exploration of the research topic.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter defines the concept of UGC and discusses its importance on social media in a marketing context. The chapter also critically reviews academic sources that speak to UGC on social media. The role of UGC is explored to generate engagement for brands, and brand engagement concepts are critically reviewed in the context of social media.

2.1.1 Conceptualization of brand related user generated content

Understanding user-generated content and its impact on consumer behaviour and engagement is essential for businesses looking to optimize their online branding strategies. User-generated content (UGC), a broad term that encompasses everything from reviews and ratings to social media posts and blog comments, serves as a real-time barometer of public sentiment towards a brand and its offerings (Liu et al., 2020).

UGC, due to its authenticity, has been known to play an influential role in consumer decision-making processes, from awareness to evaluation, and, to the purchase decision (Cheung et al., 2022). Moreover, this content aids in the creation of online communities where consumers can interact with one another and with the brand, thereby fostering brand loyalty and enhancing

customer engagement (Rossolatos, 2021). While the importance of UGC is universally acknowledged, companies need to understand that consumer behaviour, in this context, is influenced by various factors including the platform where the content is shared, the nature of the content, and the individual who shared it (Soylemez, 2021). Understanding these nuances allows companies to strategize their branding activities effectively, capitalizing on positive UGC and managing negative content proactively. Another crucial aspect to consider is consumer engagement, which is an outcome of how consumers interact with the brand's content. As noted by Vinerean & Opreana (2021), engagement with the brand on social media correlates with the brand's equity. The greater the engagement, the stronger the brand equity becomes. This finding underscores the importance of not just generating and sharing high-quality brand content but also fostering environments that encourage consumer interaction.

Consumer engagement extends beyond interaction with brand-created content; consumers are more likely to engage when they can create, share, and contribute to the content relating to the brand. In this light, the role of storytelling in online environments gains significance as it helps in creating connections between firms and customers (Kemp et al., 2021).

In relation to branding, UGC is essential as it augments the brand's messaging with an authentic, consumer-centric perspective. This is a form of social proof that can boost brand credibility and influence consumer behaviour favourably towards the brand. As the study by Schivinski et al. (2021) suggests, the consumer's propensity to engage with brand-related content on social media is significantly affected by brand equity. To harness the full potential of UGC, brands should focus on creating a participatory culture where consumers are motivated to share their experiences and ideas. This can be facilitated by providing the right incentives, crafting compelling narratives, and consistently interacting with consumers. User-generated content should not be viewed as a one-off occurrence, but as an ongoing process that brands must continually nurture and leverage to understand consumer behaviour and strengthen their brand engagement. User-generated content, when effectively utilized, can provide insights into consumer behaviour, and enhance branding engagement. It can function as a tool for deepening customer-brand relationships, strengthening brand equity, and influencing consumer purchasing decisions. By fostering an environment that encourages customer participation and engagement, businesses can create a sustainable competitive advantage in the dynamic digital marketplace.

Modern digital milieus, epitomized by the ubiquity of social media platforms, are burgeoning arenas for the accrual of brand-associated User Generated Content (UGC) (Mohammad et al., 2020). These platforms have become conduits through which consumers articulate their brand experiences and emotional responses (Wolter et al., 2023). Thus, understanding the significance of UGC is pivotal for academicians and practitioners to evaluate consumer engagement and its ramifications on brand awareness, brand identity, brand attitude, and purchasing inclinations (Ma & Gu, 2022).

In the contemporary commercial landscape, enterprises are increasingly interested in fostering customer engagement and eliciting emotions, prompting consumers to generate UGC on social media (Mishra, 2019). Two distinct categories emerge within brand related UGC; namely sponsored and non-sponsored content (Acuti et al., 2019). Sponsored content originates from individuals remunerated to create promotional material for brands. In contrast, non-sponsored UGC involves expressing perspectives and experiences without the brand offering any incentive (Vander Schee et al., 2020). This study zeroes in on non-sponsored brand-associated content, wherein the content generation process is uninfluenced by the brand.

Historically, such phenomena were examined in controlled environments, offering insights into general patterns of behaviors (Gvili & Levy, 2018). However, recent observations have shed light on the existence of three distinct behavioural dimensions, relative to the brand, that impact engagement patterns, varying with customer interaction levels (Viswanathan et al., 2018). The fundamental level involves users responding to content generated by their peers. A more complex level has users articulating their perspectives by commenting, sharing, or reacting to content, whereas the highest level of engagement is evidenced when users produce novel content (Zhao et al., 2022). It is intriguing to note that a single individual can operate in the roles of a consumer, contributor, and creator for the same brand (Cheung et al., 2020). Furthermore, the same individual might contribute to one brand while consuming content related to another, with these patterns potentially overlapping (Aljarah et al., 2022).

This presents a conundrum for practitioners and academicians who must revisit and scrutinize how perceived values relate to specific behaviour patterns associated with non-sponsored brand related UGC (Aichner, 2019). Furthermore, its repercussions on user engagement across various social media platforms, such as Instagram and Facebook, warrant a more comprehensive exploration (Cheng et al., 2021). Engagement on social media platforms can

serve as an indicator of a user's intention to persist in the use of non-sponsored brand-related content by endorsing it on these platforms (Hamzah et al., 2021).

Historically conducted research posits that user engagement on social media is intertwined with functional, social, and emotional values (Valesia & Diehl, 2022), trust (Baker et al., 2021), and collaboration (Letheren et al., 2019). Notwithstanding, these studies primarily focus on generalized UGC behaviors, and have yet to delve into the ways users perceive value differently concerning consumption, contribution, and creation (Zhao et al., 2022). Bridging these lacunae, some scholars argue that the synergistic effect of non-sponsored brand related UGC and engagement can be significantly influenced by perceived value, yielding positive outcomes for user engagement on social media platforms (Grassi, 2020). This assertion is corroborated by the engagement theory proposed by Pansari and Kumar (2017), which suggests that engagement plays a pivotal role in fostering sustained adoption, generating tangible and intangible benefits for the brand. The prevalent digital arenas, namely social media platforms, have burgeoned as congregative domains for user-generated content (UGC) pertaining to brands. These platforms serve as a stage where consumers articulate their brand experiences and emotional responses (Hutter et al., 2013; Langaro et al., 2018, as cited in Mohammad et al., 2020). Comprehending the import of UGC for evaluating customer engagement and its subsequent ramifications on brand awareness, identity, attitude, and purchasing predispositions is pivotal for scholars and administrators (Mohammad et al., 2020).

Corporations are progressively attentive to fostering customer engagement and eliciting emotional responses to cultivate UGC on social media platforms (Matute et al., 2019; Harmeling et al., 2017, as cited in Mishra, 2019). There exist two categories of involvement in brand related UGC: sponsored and non-sponsored (Burmam, 2010, as cited in Acuti et al., 2019). Sponsored content is furnished by individuals who receive remuneration to generate promotional material for brands, whereas non-sponsored UGC circulates personal perspectives and experiences devoid of any brand-derived incentives (Acuti et al., 2019).

This inquiry concentrates on non-sponsored brand-related content, where the material is generated independently from brand influence. The potential applications and ramifications of this approach are also assessed (Sarin et al., 2021). Past explorations of this phenomenon in controlled settings found observable general behavioural patterns (Jahn and Kunz, 2012; Kim et al., 2012, as cited in Ma & Gu, 2022). However, subsequent observations noted that instead of a single general behaviour, there are three distinct dimensions of behaviour that relate to the

brand and affect engagement patterns, contingent on the level of customer interaction (Schivinski et al., 2016, as cited in Srivastava & Sivaramakrishnan, 2021). Users typically respond to content produced by others at a rudimentary level. More advanced interactions involve sharing their viewpoints by commenting, sharing, or reacting to content. The pinnacle of engagement involves users generating new content, thereby allowing a single individual to enact the roles of consumer, contributor, and creator for a single brand (Muntinga et al., 2011; Schivinski et al., 2016, as cited in Vander Schee et al., 2020). Additionally, that individual might contribute to one brand while consuming another, with these patterns overlapping (Schivinski et al., 2016, as cited in Aljarah et al., 2022). Following table discussion, the Impact of consumer behaviour on user-generated content:

Table 2-1 Impact of consumer behaviour on user-generated content:

Reference	Insight on Consumer Behaviour
Kitirattarkarn, G. P., Araujo, T., & Neijens, P. (2019)	Discusses how personal and national cultural traits moderate the impact of content characteristics and social relationships on consumer engagement with brand-related user-generated content.
Ibrahim, B., Aljarah, A., Hayat, D. T., & Lahuerta-Otero, E. (2022)	Examines the effect of firm-created content and user-generated content on consumer engagement. Consumer behaviour is affected by the like, comment, and share functionalities of the platforms.
Yang, Q., Li, H., Lin, Y., Jiang, Y., & Huo, J. (2022)	Discusses how content-generating devices and content features foster consumer engagement with marketer-generated content. The study provides insight into the consumer behavioural aspects linked to technology use.
Mathur, S., Tewari, A., & Singh, A. (2022)	The study models factors affecting online purchase intention with a mediating effect of consumer's attitude towards user-generated content. It suggests that consumers' online purchasing behaviours are significantly impacted by the content they generate or encounter.
Li, Y., & Xie, Y. (2020)	Studies the relationship between image content and social media engagement, indicating that consumer behaviour can be significantly influenced by the visual aspects of user-generated content.
Shahbaznezhad, H., Dolan, R., & Rashidirad, M. (2021)	Highlights the role of social media content format and platform in influencing users' engagement behaviour. It posits that different social media platforms and content formats can induce different consumer behaviours.
Wolter, J. S., Bacile, T. J., & Xu, P. (2023)	Discusses how online incivility, such as rude or aggressive comments, affects consumer engagement behaviour on brands' social media. The study underscores the importance of maintaining a

	positive online environment to foster constructive consumer behaviours.
Qu, Y., Saffer, A. J., & Riffe, D. (2022)	Reveals how consumers' conversations influence online engagement behaviours, demonstrating the significance of user-generated content in shaping the dynamics of consumer interactions and engagement.
Valsesia, F., & Diehl, K. (2022)	Discusses how the type of purchases shared on social media (experiential vs material) can alter the perceived authenticity and liking of social media users. It suggests that consumer behaviours can be influenced by the type of user-generated content they encounter.
Chi, M., Harrigan, P., & Xu, Y. (2022)	Focuses on customer engagement in online service brand communities. It provides insight into how user-generated content within these communities can significantly impact consumer behaviour and engagement.
Srivastava, M., & Sivaramakrishnan, S. (2020)	Proposes a framework exploring the triad of electronic

This multifaceted behaviour challenges managers and academics to reevaluate and scrutinize the relationship between perceived values and specific behaviours related to non-sponsored brand related UGC (Acuti et al., 2019). Moreover, the impacts of this behaviour on user engagement on various social media platforms, such as Instagram and Facebook, warrant further detailed exploration (Hussein and Hassan, 2017; Keller, 2013; Kennedy and Guzman, 2017, as cited in Ho & Ito, 2019). Previous studies link engaging users on social media with functional, social, and emotional values, trust, and collaboration (Jahn and Kunz, 2012; Kim et al., 2012; Leiner et al., 2018; Pasternak et al., 2017; Hanna et al., 2011, as cited in Acuti et al., 2019). However, these studies consider generalized UGC behaviours, neglecting to explore how value might be perceived differently in terms of consumption, contribution, and creation.

2.2 ROLE OF UGC ON SOCIAL MEDIA

The advent of social media has ushered in a new era of marketing, characterized by a fundamental shift in the way brands communicate with their customers. Today, social media platforms are thriving with user-generated content (UGC), which has proven to be a significant tool for enhancing consumer engagement and, consequently, brands' marketing strategies. UGC is content created and shared by consumers on social media, and it ranges from reviews and ratings to comments, blog posts, images, and videos. This content is a rich source of information for both brands and other consumers. Brands can use UGC to gain insights into consumers' perceptions, preferences, and attitudes towards their products or services.

Meanwhile, other consumers use UGC as a source of information when making purchasing decisions (Schivinski, Pontes, Czarnecka, Mao, De Vita, & Stavropoulos, 2022).

According to Lv, Jin, & Huang (2021), UGC significantly influences consumers' purchase intention. This happens because UGC is viewed as more trustworthy, authentic, and unbiased than brand-generated content. UGC has a social proof effect; consumers are more likely to trust and follow the actions of their peers. This means that positive UGC can enhance a brand's image, increase its visibility, improve its reputation, and lead to higher conversion rates. Conversely, negative UGC can damage a brand's image and reduce consumer trust. Thus, brands must monitor UGC to address negative comments or reviews promptly and effectively. Furthermore, UGC stimulates consumer engagement, which is essential for strengthening consumer-brand relationships. UGC encourages consumers to interact with brands and other consumers, fostering a sense of community and boosting customer loyalty (Vinerean & Opreana, 2021). As such, high levels of consumer engagement can lead to increased brand equity and higher sales. Brands can encourage UGC by inviting consumers to share their experiences, opinions, or stories related to their products or services. This can be achieved through competitions, campaigns, hashtags, or simply by responding to comments. Moreover, brands can also leverage UGC to improve their offerings by listening to their consumers' feedback, suggestions, and ideas.

While UGC has immense benefits, it also presents some challenges. It can be difficult for brands to manage and control the content generated by users. This underscores the importance of effective social media management and moderation to ensure that UGC aligns with the brand's image and values. UGC is a powerful tool in today's social media-driven marketing landscape. It provides a credible source of information for consumers and valuable insights for brands, encourages consumer engagement, and enhances brand image and reputation. Brands that effectively manage and leverage UGC can benefit from increased consumer trust, stronger relationships, and higher sales.

2.2.1 Social media content marketing foundations

Social media platforms have emerged as a fertile arena for the proliferation of user-generated content (UGC) related to brands. In the act of employing these platforms, consumers engage in an expressive performance of their experiences and emotional reactions towards brands (Davicik et al., 2022). The prominence of UGC cannot be overstated, as it forms the foundation of a nuanced understanding of consumer engagement and its associated impacts on brand

consciousness, brand distinctiveness, consumer attitudes, and purchasing predispositions (Davcik et al., 2022; Ibrahim et al., 2022).

In the landscape of social media, customer engagement, when viewed through the lens of behavioural demonstrations, towards brands represents an integral constituent that is intrinsically linked to enhancing customer relationships (Hinson et al., 2019) and driving sales performance (Ibrahim et al., 2022). Much scholarly attention has been directed towards Marketer-Generated Content (MGC) as a catalyst for engagement. MGC, manifested in the form of texts, videos, or imagery, is accessible across various channels including social media and emails (Yang et al., 2022; Ma & Gu, 2022).

To incentivize user engagement with brands on social media, and stimulate content contribution, marketers tailor content to cater to three generic user inquiries (Dolan et al., 2019; Weiger et al., 2017). Hence, affiliative content is employed to underscore emotional bonds within a community, injunctive content provides guidance on community behaviour, and utilitarian content encapsulates cost-benefit calculations aimed at optimizing user utility (Weiger et al., 2017; Dolan et al., 2019).

Interactions on social media mirror user activities by enabling the virtual interplay between users, made possible through the observation of others' activities and posts on their newsfeed (Li & Xie, 2020). Moreover, it is pivotal for social media marketers to acknowledge the importance of disseminating MGC via social networks (Yang et al., 2022; Cheng et al., 2021). However, social networks and brand communities reflect social groups marked by potent in-group and out-group considerations (Mohammad et al., 2020). The magnitude of chosen social groups is contingent on engagement levels on social communities. User preferences for smaller or larger social groups depend on their selectivity when engaging on social media (Qu et al., 2022; Sarin et al., 2021). The efficacy of user engagement with MGC in fostering interactions is significantly influenced by user responses. Specifically, users exhibiting high levels of intimacy in their networks are predisposed to perceive other community members as out-groups, thus leading to discriminatory tendencies. Consequently, the degree of intimacy moulds MGC responsiveness, predicated on whether MGC stimulates interactions with out-group individuals or not (Moran et al., 2020; Acuti et al., 2019).

2.3 UGC DIMENSIONS

Engaging consumers is central to modern brand strategies. User-generated content (UGC) and firm-created content (FCC) are two pivotal tools that marketers employ to enhance brand engagement (Ibrahim et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2022). UGC refers to content voluntarily created by consumers such as reviews, comments, or posts, which potentially influence brand perception and engagement (Davicik et al., 2022). This type of content, as Mohammad et al. (2020) underscore, can affect brand engagement significantly, with its quality mediating functional and emotional values. Ktirattarkarn et al. (2019) further delve into the role of personal and national collectivism-individualism in moderating the effects of content characteristics on consumer engagement with UGC. Furthermore, Mathur et al. (2022) model how various factors, including UGC, influence online purchase intention via the mediating effect of the consumer's attitude. In line with this, Acuti et al. (2019) explore stakeholder engagement in green place branding, focusing on UGC's role. FCC, on the other hand, refers to content created by a brand or firm. The effect of FCC characteristics on consumer engagement is well-documented (Tan & Chen, 2022; Cheng et al., 2021). Yang et al. (2022) analyze how content-generating devices and content features foster consumer engagement with marketer-generated content. Aljarah et al. (2022) explore the differential impact of UGC and FCC on online brand advocacy, concluding that both customer engagement and brand familiarity matter. The below table explain the characteristics of user generated content impact on brand engagement.

Table 2-2 Impact of user generated content on brand engagement

Characteristic of User-Generated Content	Definition	Impact on Consumer Behaviour	Impact on Brand Engagement
Authenticity (Rosado-Pinto et al., 2020)	UGC is considered authentic when it is perceived as genuine, credible, and free from the influence of the brand.	Authentic UGC can influence consumer behaviour by building trust and positive attitudes towards a brand, increasing the likelihood of purchases (Rosado-Pinto et al., 2020).	Authentic UGC enhances brand engagement by encouraging active participation from consumers, driving deeper connections with the brand (Rosado-Pinto et al., 2020).
Relevance (Mohammad et al., 2020)	Relevance in terms of UGC refers to the content being meaningful and directly applicable	Relevant UGC may influence consumer behaviour by increasing the perceived value of brands and fostering a	High relevance in UGC is likely to improve brand engagement by fostering frequent and more meaningful interactions

	to the consumer's interests or needs.	sense of personal connection (Mohammad et al., 2020).	with the brand (Mohammad et al., 2020).
Quality (Mohammad et al., 2020)	The quality of UGC is determined by factors such as accuracy, clarity, and the presence of necessary details in the content.	High-quality UGC can enhance the perceived value of a product or service, influencing the consumer's purchase decision (Mohammad et al., 2020).	UGC of high quality can lead to stronger brand engagement as it enriches consumer experience, increasing their satisfaction and loyalty (Mohammad et al., 2020).
Emotional Appeal (Srivastava & Sivaramakrishnan, 2021)	Emotional appeal in UGC refers to the emotional connection the audience forms with content.	Emotional UGC can significantly influence consumer behaviour by eliciting emotions that affect their perceptions, attitudes, and decisions towards a brand (Srivastava & Sivaramakrishnan, 2021).	Emotional UGC is effective in driving brand engagement as it fosters emotional bonds between the consumers and the brand, stimulating active participation and loyalty (Srivastava & Sivaramakrishnan, 2021).
Informativeness (Davicik et al., 2022)	Informativeness refers to the amount of useful and relevant information provided in the UGC.	Informative UGC influences consumer behaviour by providing valuable information that aids in decision-making, thereby increasing purchase intention (Davicik et al., 2022).	Informativeness in UGC boosts brand engagement by providing consumers with valuable knowledge about the brand, leading to increased interaction and loyalty (Davicik et al., 2022).

The visual aspect of the content, both user- and firm-generated, also plays a significant role in engagement. As Li & Xie (2020) posit, an image might indeed be worth a thousand words, as their study shows a correlation between image content and social media engagement. Zhao echoes this finding et al. (2022), who investigate the impact of image-text matching on consumer engagement in social media advertising. Meanwhile, the rise of social media has impacted the landscape of brand engagement. Dolan et al. (2019) propose a framework for engaging customers through social media content, considering both UGC and FCC. Shahbaznezhad et al. (2021) further discuss how the format and platform of social media content impact user engagement behaviour.

However, not all engagement is positive. Wolter et al. (2023) investigate how online incivility, often found in UGC, affects consumer engagement behaviour on brands' social media platforms. Lastly, the platform where the content is posted can shape its impact on brand engagement. For instance, Ma & Gu (2022) investigate how firm-generated videos influence

user-generated videos, providing empirical evidence from China, while Park et al. (2018) explore the effects of user engagements on both user and company-generated videos on music sales using YouTube as a case study. In sum, both UGC and FCC, with their respective characteristics and delivered through different platforms and formats, significantly influence consumer engagement with brands. Understanding these complex dynamics is crucial for firms looking to optimize their engagement strategies in the ever-evolving digital landscape.

For gaining insights into the characteristics of brand-related User Generated Content (UGC) and their dynamics on different social platforms, Smith proposed a paradigm et al. (2012). This schema identified six interconnected dimensions, and hypotheses were developed around these dimensions, exploring their potential alterations (Roma & Aloini, 2019). The present study refers to these dimensions, which encompass real-time purchase experiences, responses to advertising campaigns, location sharing, and the display of brand recommendation features.

Two significant shifts have been observed in the social media landscape which are addressed in the following section. These are the incorporation of comprehensive content, enriched with visual aids, and the migration of social media usage to mobile devices (Bowen, 2015). The ensuing discussion examines the influence of these changes on the six dimensions of brand related UGC (Smith et al., 2012) and questions whether the hypotheses proposed by Smith et al. (2012) require revision.

Self-presentation, as conceptualized by Zywiec and Danowski (2008), signifies an individual's capacity to express their persona and identity, often in the context of product or brand use (Schau & Gilly, 2003; Belk, 1988; Christodoulides et al., 2012). It has been observed that the frequency of self-presentation in brand related UGC is higher on platforms like YouTube compared to Twitter and Facebook. This is attributed to YouTube's emphasis on visual content (Misoch, 2014; Burgess & Green, 2009). However, others contend that the adoption of rich content and visual aids has recently revolutionized social media networks (Shinal, 2018; Vilnai Yavetz & Tifferet, 2015; Thompson, 2017; Pollard, 2017).

The notion of brand centrality refers to the extent to which the focus of brand related UGC is primarily on the brand, or if it is more peripheral (Smith et al., 2012). Earlier literature indicates that brand-related UGC on Twitter is more brand-centric than on platforms like YouTube and Facebook (Perez, 2017; Ma, 2013). Twitter's character limitations contribute to this phenomenon. In contrast, the literature also suggests that brands play a more marginal role in UGC on YouTube, as users primarily focus on self-presentation (Liu et al., 2011; Liu, 2020).

However, platforms such as Facebook and Twitter have increasingly shifted towards rich visual content, closing the gap between these platforms in terms of self-presentation and brand centrality.

Direct marketing describes the marketers' ability to connect with customers to understand their preferences and needs. This approach has prompted numerous brands to establish brand pages on social media (Henning Thureau et al., 2010; Gensler et al., 2013). Research indicates that different consumers use social media platforms in various ways. For instance, some directly interact with, and pose questions to brands (Smith et al., 2012; Naaman, Boase, & Lai, 2010). In contrast, producing a video requires effort, and consequently YouTube is used less frequently for this specific purpose, compared to Facebook and Twitter (Kaplan, 2012).

This term is associated with the propensity of Social Media Users (SMUs) to create UGC in response to marketing activities on various social media platforms (Singh & Chakrabarti, 2021). Examples may include making announcements about events or polling consumers. Twitter and Facebook provide convenient access to brands via brand visualization and enhanced user accessibility. On the other hand, YouTube is not as accessible in terms of these traits (Smith et al., 2012). In contrast, YouTube enables users to comment on marketing announcements. To further understand brand-associated UGC features and their evolving dynamics across various social media channels, Smith et al.'s (2012) framework has been pivotal. Their conceptualization introduced six interconnected dimensions, each accompanied by a set of hypotheses regarding their potential for change (Roma & Aloini, 2019). The current study revisits these dimensions, encompassing elements such as real-time buying experiences, responses to advertising initiatives, location sharing, real-time consumption experiences, and the manifestation of brand endorsement characteristics.

In analysing the evolution of the social media ecosystem, two critical alterations have emerged. Firstly, there is a trend towards incorporating robust, visually engaging content, and secondly, a migration towards mobile-based social media use (Bowen, 2015). The ensuing section scrutinizes the effects of these shifts on the six dimensions of brand associated UGC as conceptualized by Smith et al. (2012). These developments may dictate whether the initial hypotheses proposed by Smith et al. (2012) require revision.

Self-presentation refers to the individual's capacity to shape their identity and project this image towards others (Christodoulides, Jevons, & Bonhomme, 2012). Self-presentation is frequently associated with brand or product use (Singh & Chakrabarti, 2021; Cheong & Mohammed-

Baksh, 2021). Previous research has indicated that self-presentation is more prevalent in brand associated UGC on platforms like YouTube, compared to Facebook and Twitter. This is due to YouTube's visual-centric approach (Liu, 2020; Liu, Karahanna, & Watson, 2011). However, some scholars argue that the shift towards visually rich content is a recent development that has significantly transformed social media networks (Bowen, 2015; Cheng & Huang, 2020).

Brand centrality is a construct that evaluates whether brand related UGC is tied to the brand itself, or serves as a supplement (Smith et al., 2012). Early literature indicates that Twitter, due to its character limitations, lends itself more towards brand-centric content than YouTube and Facebook (Cheng & Huang, 2020; ANA, ISTUDOR, & of Economic Studies, 2019). Conversely, brands tend to play a more peripheral role on YouTube, where users are primarily concerned with self-presentation (Cheong & Mohammed-Baksh, 2021). However, with social media platforms like Facebook and Twitter also shifting towards visual aids and richer content via live streaming and expanded character limits, the gap between these platforms in terms of self-presentation and brand centrality is closing (Bowen, 2015).

Marketer accessibility refers to the capability of marketers to connect directly with customers to understand their preferences and needs (García-de-Frutos & Estrella-Ramón, 2021). This has led to an increase in brands establishing their own pages on social media platforms (Park, Park, & Park, 2018). Early studies suggest that consumers use social media platforms in various ways. Some use these platforms to ask questions and interact directly with brands (Cheong & Mohammed-Baksh, 2021). Platforms like Twitter and Facebook are recognized for facilitating direct brand interactions. However, the effort required to produce a video has meant that YouTube is less popular for this purpose (Bowen, 2015). Nevertheless, advancements in technology have reduced this discrepancy, as most users now access social media via their mobile devices, making interactions between brands and users more seamless (ANA, ISTUDOR, & of Economic Studies, 2019).

Brand engagement represents the propensity of social media users to generate UGC in response to marketing actions across different platforms. These actions include event announcements or consumer questions/conversations. Smith et al. (2012) proposed a comprehensive framework to unravel the intricate aspects of brand-oriented UGC and its evolving dynamics across various social media platforms. They identified a unique construct comprising six paired dimensions and hypothesize various interplays and potential implications. The current study draws upon

this multi-dimensional construct and re-evaluates its continued relevance in today's social media landscape.

These dimensions encompass diverse facets, such as real-time purchase experiences, reactions to advertising campaigns, location sharing, immediate consumption experiences, and brand recommendation features (Roma & Aloini, 2019). An essential part of this inquiry involves examining key transformative changes in social media, namely the proliferation of rich multimedia content and the predominance of mobile-based access, and how they impinge on these dimensions (Christodoulides, Jevons, & Bonhomme, 2012). Consequently, these alterations necessitate a reassessment of the original hypotheses posited by Smith et al. (2012).

Self-presentation refers to an individual's capacity to project their self-image and identity, often in association with a product or brand use (Schau & Gilly, 2003; Belk, 1988, 2013). Past research points towards a higher prevalence of self-presentation in brand related UGC on visually oriented platforms such as YouTube, contrasting with platforms such as Twitter and Facebook (Misoch, 2014; Burgess & Green, 2009). However, the rapid growth and transformation of social media networks, characterized by the influx of rich visual content, challenge this viewpoint (Shinal, 2018; Vilnai Yavetz & Tifferet, 2015; Gupta, 2013; Thompson, 2017; Pollard, 2017).

Brand centrality, a term used to denote the primary focus of brand related UGC, shifts depending on the platform (Smith et al., 2012). Early literature suggests that brand-centric content is more prevalent on Twitter due to character restrictions, as opposed to Facebook and YouTube (Perez, 2017; Ma, 2013). However, the evolution of Facebook and Twitter towards more visual content and expanded character limits has blurred these distinctions, with brand centrality becoming less central on YouTube due to heightened user self-presentation (Smith et al., 2012).

The ability of marketers to directly communicate with consumers and gain insight into their preferences and needs has led to the creation of numerous brand pages across social media platforms (Henning Thureau et al., 2010; Gensler et al., 2013; Luarn et al., 2015; Labrecque, 2014). Despite these developments, the way users interact with brands varies across platforms. Platforms such as Twitter and Facebook facilitate direct brand interaction, while video creation on YouTube requires substantial effort, making it less popular for this purpose. However, the widespread use of mobile phones to access social media has eased these interactions, diminishing the differences (Kaplan, 2012).

Similarly, the likelihood of social media users (SMUs) to generate UGC as a reaction to marketing actions varies across platforms (Smith et al., 2012). Platforms like Twitter and Facebook provide greater accessibility to brands, prompting users to generate content in response. YouTube, while providing options for commenting on marketing announcements, is less conducive to these interactions due to its primary focus on video content. Yet, recent advancements in mobile access to social media have minimized these discrepancies, fostering an increasingly uniform landscape.

The following table explains how UGC engages other users on social media. It provide insights into various factors like storytelling, humour climate, consumer-brand interactions, and gratifications that drive user engagement on social media platforms.

Table 2-3 how UGC engages other users on social media.

Author(s) & Year	Insights
Lv et al., 2021	Lv et al. (2021) discovered that user engagement with MGC (Member Generated Content) on social media platforms like Weibo positively impacts word-of-mouth marketing and consumer purchase intention.
Kemp et al., 2021	According to Kemp et al. (2021), storytelling in online environments enhances brand-customer connections, thereby increasing user engagement and content generation.
Shen, 2021	Shen (2021) developed a persuasive eWOM (electronic Word of Mouth) model that enhances consumer engagement on social media, particularly with the help of micro-influencers.
Rossolatos, 2021	Rossolatos (2021) dimensionalized interactions in social media brand communities, shedding light on the depth of brand engagement funnels.
Yang et al., 2021	Yang, Cai, and Tu (2021) demonstrated the significant effects of humour climate within online brand communities on user engagement.
Schivinski et al., 2021	Schivinski et al. (2021) found that brand equity significantly influences consumers' propensity to engage with brand-related content on social media.
Qin, 2020	Qin (2020) revealed that social media uses and gratifications significantly foster brand-consumer interactions on social media.
Grassi, 2020	Grassi (2020) asserted that incorporating art can enhance consumer engagement in the luxury fashion domain.
Weiger et al., 2019	Weiger, Wetzel, and Hammerschmidt (2019) suggested that different entities and factors pull the strings of user engagement with brand-related content on social media.

Nikolinakou et al., 2021	Nikolinakou, Phua, and Kwon (2021) identified several factors that drive loyal fans of brand pages to act. These include like self-expansion and flow, which can enhance sharing and creation activities.
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2.4 SOCIAL COMMUNICATIONS CONTENT FEATURES

2.4.1 Online communication via Interactive cues

Within the confines of the SNS environment, marketers develop complete control over what type of content is published, particularly where the brand faces challenges regarding UGC (Fournier and Avery 2011). Where marketers control the content that goes onto brand websites, only selective content is created to attract consumers towards interactive cues that are embedded in the content, so that consumer engagement can be established. Interactive cues develop a sense of interactivity, as far as communications theory goes. From this perspective, interactivity means that the user has the option to alter or modify content in real time (Sundar and Limperos 2013; Steuer 1992). Through interactive cues, users are empowered to interact with each other through their content, leveraging interactivity. Some marketers create content through brand messages with certain interactive cues, such as a voting mechanism or feedback request that highlights the interactive capacity of the SNS medium to SMUs (de Vries et al 2012). Moreover, this illustrates the behavioural responses that are favorable for marketers. The process of combining interactive cues with brand messages on social media is like the inclusion of CTAs in direct response marketing (Trappey and Woodside 2005). With the addition of interactive cues to brand content, the ability to communicate directly with consumers on social media can be realised as an alternative to one-sided communication (Colliander et al 2015). Therefore, brand content that involves these interactive cues can elicit a response from consumers compared to content that is non-interactive.

There are no consistent findings in the literature regarding the effects of such interactivity cues. Interactivity measures can create either positive, negative, or neutral effects for advertising (Liu 2003; Liu and Shrum 2002; Coyle and Thorson 2001; Fortin and Dholakia 2005). According to Sundar and Limperos (2013, p. 515) interactivity with higher intensity could be dangerous. This means that higher levels of interactivity can cause as much damage as no interactivity. On the other hand, authors such as Weiger et al (2018) and Fortin and Dholakia (2005) suggest that CTAs can be implemented as online content to potentially diminish returns. They propose that increasing the level of interactivity beyond a moderate level reduces

consumer intentions towards online ads. It has been observed in previous studies that interactivity measures range within a continuum of high, medium, and low levels (de Vries et al 2012; Coyle and Thorson 2001). This study focuses on interactivity levels that take consideration of consumer responses to interactive CTA. Sabate et al (2014) claims that calls to ‘click and like’ are examples of low-level interactivity cues, as a simple one-click response is all that is required from the user. On the other hand, calls to share are considered to represent medium level interactivity cues, as they require a little more effort (Berger and Milkman 2012). In addition, calls to comment are examples of high-level interactivity cues as they involve users typing responses, and this takes effort and time (Gavilanes et al 2018). From both theoretical and practical perspectives, interactivity is experienced through the lens of interactive CTA that helps uncover which specific call is influenced from a certain behavioural response.

2.4.2 Rich media communications

The representation of a brand in a certain format is measured through media richness. This can also be referred to as a kind of vividness that consists of two dimensions of breadth and depth. Breadth measures the number of senses activated by the content, and depth measures the quality (Steuer 1992). A media format that is rich in nature is highly engaging for users, and its presentation sits in contrast to other typical presentations (Lohtia et al 2003). It is important to note that, within the SNS environment, content volume has been increasing. There is pressure for brands to produce something out of the ordinary that stands out from the crowd to gain the attention of users on social media newsfeeds. One of the most useful methods to gain attention from users is to use rich media that stimulates the senses (Coyle and Thorson 2001). Posts that contain audio and video content and animations, such as cartoons notably stimulate the senses since they contain visual and audio cues that influence heuristic and systematic processing capabilities (Steuer 1992). In addition, communications via video offer multiple cues such as body gestures and facial expressions (Chua and Banerjee 2015), and these reflect a high level of media richness. Content containing animations, colours and contrasts allow mid-level sensory stimulation, and reflect mid-level media richness (de Vries et al 2012). On the other hand, content that only consists of text, such as email or SMS are considered non-sensory, yet they necessitate high level cognitive processing (Fortin and Dholakia 2005). Textual content is seen as non-sensory, and non-rich in terms of aesthetic properties. In contrast, hyperlinked text is much more stimulating and richer than simple text, which means that it is a low-level rich form of media.

Aside from breadth, presentation quality also contributes to the effect of media richness. Marketers need to draw on several resources to create content that is professional as compared to content that is presented to other SNS users. Content that has been created by marketers is much more attractive and eye-catching as compared to content generated by users. However, marketers need to make sure that their tone is not too commercial, since this does not appeal to consumers (Weiger et al 2018; Taylor et al 2011). Marketers often host rich media content that contains links, videos and photos with text that is non-vivid in SNS environments. With these media rich formats, consumer senses are stimulated, and their attention is captured. This suggests that rich media content is more engaging.

2.4.3 Authenticity of brand

Brand authenticity is the extent to which a brand is genuine, real, and trustworthy (Molleda 2010; Cappannelli and Cappannelli 2004). There are different perspectives from which authenticity is defined, such as objectivist, constructivist, and existentialist perspectives. Objectivist authenticity is based on the ingenuity of objects and their quality (Oh et al 2019; Kolar and Zabkar 2010). Authentic brands are based on evidence that is verifiable, starting with the level of detail about the brand, such as its performance (Grayson and Martinec 2004; Beverland et al 2008). Existential authenticity is about the motivation to influence others to escape from routines to reunite themselves with the context of place and culture (Kolar and Zabkar 2010).

The constructivist approach sees brands considered to be authentic when they can create a fit between subjective characteristics and essence. This is communicated via the expectations of consumers and marketing tools (Brown et al 2002; Beverland et al 2008). Further, brand authenticity is about being true to itself (Steiner and Reisinger 2006).

The marketing literature portrays authenticity as the extent to which the image of a brand can reflect something stronger than impression management (Cinelli and LeBoeuf 2019). For instance, brand authenticity has been defined as a characteristic that is generated rationally, and which results in subjective perceptions instead of characteristic ones (Bruhn et al 2012). According to Gilmore and Pine (2007) brands are considered authentic if they reflect a true image and if they are being true to themselves. Moreover, brand authenticity is perceived as a behavioural consistency, reflecting fundamental values (Fritz et al 2017). In addition, Fritz et al (2017) claimed that a brand is authentic for two reasons: 1) if it is true to itself, and 2) if it is true to others. Thus, brand authenticity is conceptualized as something that enables users to

depict a true image of themselves whilst being affected by a social environment. Brand authenticity means that the brand must reflect a true image that attracts users.

From a managerial standpoint, brand authenticity and its relevance are the outcome of decisions made by consumers, and their behaviour. Previous research suggests that brand authenticity is linked to positive perceptions in different forms (Morhart et al 2015; Moulard et al 2016). For instance, if brand authenticity is perceived to be higher, the emotional attachment with the brand is stronger (Morhart et al 2015). There is, in such cases, a positive link between brand purchase and brand authenticity (Napoli et al 2014). If brand authenticity experiences influence perceptions, there is greater confidence in the perceived quality, and in the brand or product (Moulard et al 2016). According to Napoli et al (2014) there are three dimensions involved in this regard: heritage, quality commitment and sincerity. Moreover, Morhart et al (2015) suggest that brand authenticity can be classified into three dimensions of integrity, credibility, and symbolism. Nonetheless, the authenticity of a brand can also be linked with the rareness and the level of 'love' associated with the brand (Lynn and Snyder 2002; Ahuvia 2005; Monthiou et al 2018).

2.4.4 Love for brands, and rareness

The intensity of passion, emotion, and attachment a consumer feels for a particular brand is known as brand love (Carrol and Ahuvia 2006). There can be different characteristics associated with brand love, such as emotional bonding, intrinsic rewards, perceived quality, self-identity, sense of natural fit, positive effect, and frequency of use (Batra et al 2012). Consumers develop bonds with a brand they feel they can relate to in terms of their lifestyle (Langner et al 2015). Brand love is essential for consumer identity because they are susceptible to creating an attachment with brands (Ahuvia 2005). Thus, brand love emerges when a consumer feels that the brand and their lifestyle have much in common (Bergkvist and Bech-Larson 2010). Several authors believe that brand love can be positively linked to self-expressiveness and authenticity (Loureiro et al 2012; Karjaluoto et al 2016; Shuv-Ami et al 2018; Munnuka and Kiuru 2016). This study argues that brand authenticity is a primary brand trait that impacts on the consumer's appraisal. Thus, one may argue that consumers with a strong connection to brands can demonstrate their perception towards brand authenticity. In this way, perceptions and communications are developed with respect to the lifestyle and identity of the brand (Ahuvia 2005).

The term rareness refers to differentiation amongst individuals that can be attained via acquisition, utilization, and the disposition of consumer goods to create and enhance an individual identity (Tian and McKenzie 2001). Rareness is the disposition of an individual to experience new things and this tends to defy conventions as individuals seek to pursue experiences that are unique in nature (Lynn and Snyder 2002). Therefore, uniqueness is a key characteristic that expresses differentiation from others with the help of acquisition, utilization, and disposition for enhancing the self- and social image of the consumer (Tian and McKenzie 2001). Earlier research suggests that the experiences of consumers leaves a mark on their memory (Manthiou et al 2018; Cohen and Areni 1991). Moreover, individuals who have unique experiences of restaurants tend to be attracted to unique traits (Parikh et al 2014; Bilighan et al 2017). A distinct dimension that measures loyalty in a brand is its authenticity (Napoli et al 2014).

The need for uniqueness, as discussed in this study, assumes that every person has their own basic needs and desire for differentiation from others (Snyder and Fromkin 1977, 1980). According to uniqueness theory, people participate in several activities, consumption patterns and actions that help them differentiate themselves from others (Snyder and Fromkin 1980). In a restaurant setting, uniqueness plays a vital role because customers desire authenticity from dining (Manthiou et al 2018). For instance, local foods are authentic, and they symbolize culture and a sense of place (Sims 2009). Restaurants can improve customer experiences by linking their concept to the design and culture of wider society to promote uniqueness and brand authenticity. Therefore, customers have a perception of restaurant in their mind based on an experience (Manthiou et al 2018).

2.5 SOCIAL MEDIA ENGAGEMENT

Social media is an effective tool to engage with consumers and build relationships with them (Dolan et al., 2019). However, engagement is not merely a matter of posting content; it involves understanding user behaviors and preferences, as well as strategizing content delivery to stimulate interactions and foster deeper relationships. Both firm-created content and user-generated content play pivotal roles in engaging customers (Ibrahim et al., 2022; Davcik et al., 2022). For instance, Yang et al. (2022) highlighted the importance of content features and content-generating devices in fostering engagement. Firms should hence carefully craft their messages to stimulate user interests, inspire action, and ignite conversations. UGC, on the other

hand, is perceived as authentic, trustworthy, and influential, affecting purchase intentions and brand engagements (Mathur et al., 2022; Mohammad et al., 2020).

User engagement can be moderated by various factors. For example, Kitirattarkarn et al. (2019) revealed that personal and national collectivism-individualism influences consumer engagement with brand-related UGC. Meanwhile, a study by Wolter et al. (2023) highlighted the impact of online incivility on consumer engagement behaviour. Further, Tan and Chen (2022) suggested that marketer-generated content characteristics significantly affect consumer engagement.

Importantly, the role of image content in social media engagement is significant. Li and Xie (2020) found that images play a crucial role in engaging users, reinforcing the saying, "A picture is worth a thousand words." Likewise, Zhao et al. (2022) suggested that image-text matching enhances consumer engagement in social media advertising. A prominent platform where firm generated and UGC thrive is social media. Various studies have found significant relationships between social media engagement behaviour and the content format and platform used (Shahbaznezhad et al., 2021). Platforms like Facebook, Instagram, WeChat, and YouTube all have different algorithms and audience characteristics that influence user engagement (Aljarah et al., 2022; Aichner, 2019; Ballester et al., 2023; Park et al., 2018). Moreover, specific strategies, such as emphasizing brand authenticity (Rosado-Pinto et al., 2020), promoting green messages (Kyu Kim et al., 2021), or enabling customer engagement through online service brand communities (Chi et al., 2022) can enhance user engagement. However, an overemphasis on consumption-oriented engagement can negatively affect personal well-being (Ho & Ito, 2019), indicating the need for balance.

The benefits of user engagement on social media extend beyond immediate likes, comments, and shares. Engaged users can become brand advocates, driving brand familiarity (Aljarah et al., 2022), or influencing economic performance (Chen et al., 2020). The level of information richness in UGC also provides valuable insights into customer preferences and behaviors, assisting firms in refining their marketing strategies (Roma & Aloini, 2019). However, it is crucial to note that managing UGC comes with challenges. While it facilitates the creation of authentic and trustworthy reviews (Liu et al., 2011), it can also be unpredictable and challenging to control (Sykora et al., 2022). Firms need to adopt appropriate strategies to leverage UGC effectively, such as learning consumer and producer embeddings (Kang & McAuley, 2018) or utilizing machine learning methods to analyze the impact of UGC (Liu,

2020). Social media engagement is a complex phenomenon influenced by various factors. It requires a strategic blend of firm-created and UGC to be leveraged.

As we move deeper into the digital age, the importance of social media for brand engagement and marketing has increased significantly. Social media platforms have become a central hub for consumer interactions with brands, which has resulted in profound changes in consumer behaviour and marketing strategies (Naeem & Ozuem, 2021). Today, both UGC and FCC play critical roles in engaging consumers and shaping their attitudes towards brands (Ibrahim et al., 2022). Naeem (2020) highlights the role of social motivational factors as a powerful tool for enhancing brand-related content. The paper suggests that by understanding what motivates consumers to engage with a brand online, marketers can create content that sparks their interest and encourages them to interact with the brand. On the other hand, Osei-Frimpong (2019) emphasizes the need to comprehend consumer motivations in online social brand engagement participation. This knowledge can provide implications for retailers seeking to optimize their digital strategies.

Demmers et al. (2020) go a step further by examining consumer engagement with brand posts on social media throughout various stages of the customer journey. Their findings underscore the importance of creating content that resonates with consumers at different touchpoints, from awareness to consideration and finally, to purchase. The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly amplified the role of social media in shaping consumer behaviour. Naeem (2021) explored the role of social media in generating social proof and influencing stockpiling behaviour during the pandemic. Similarly, he researched the psychology of impulse buying during this period and explored how social media platforms contribute to panic buying (Naeem, 2021). These findings underscore the tremendous power of social media in influencing consumer actions during times of uncertainty.

Understanding the journey of the social consumer is also crucial. Naeem & Ozuem (2021) provide insights about the social consumer fashion brand engagement journey, especially for reputed fashion brands. This research is critical for fashion brands to comprehend how consumers engage with them on social platforms, and it informs the design of compelling social media strategies. Yang has explored marketer-generated content (MGC) et al. (2022), who looked at the role of content-generating devices and content features in fostering consumer engagement. MGC can shape the narratives around a brand and stir engagement if it is strategically crafted and aligned with consumers' interests and preferences.

Conversely, the impact of UGC cannot be understated. As Davcik et al. (2022) demonstrate, non-sponsored brand related UGC can significantly affect consumer engagement. The spontaneous and genuine nature of UGC often resonates strongly with consumers, contributing to their perceived authenticity of a brand. The quality of UGC also plays a pivotal role in consumer engagement. Mohammad et al. (2020) suggest that high-quality UGC can significantly enhance brand engagement, mediated by the perceived functional and emotional values of the content. This insight emphasizes the importance of encouraging and leveraging high-quality UGC in brand engagement strategies.

Visual content has emerged as an influential factor in social media engagement. As Li & Xie (2020) argue, an image can indeed be worth a thousand words. They found a strong correlation between image content and social media engagement, supporting the notion that visually appealing content can capture consumers' attention and drive engagement. Understanding the dynamics of consumer engagement on social media requires a multifaceted approach. Marketers must acknowledge the power of both UGC and MGC, the motivating factors behind consumer engagement, and the role of social media platforms in shaping consumer behaviour. In this increasingly digital world, brands must embrace social media as an integral part of their marketing strategy, leveraging its power to connect with consumers, foster engagement, and build lasting relationships.

UGC holds enormous potential in marketing (Naeem & Ozuem, 2021). These are significant platforms for consumers to engage with, and express their opinions about different products, services, and brands (Davcik et al., 2022). Brands that use UGC gain an advantage as consumers find UGC more trustworthy and influential compared to content generated by the brands themselves (Ibrahim et al., 2022). However, while it is easy for consumers to create and share content, the task becomes challenging when it comes to engaging other consumers (Li & Xie, 2020). Engaging consumers requires carefully creating content that is unique, interesting, and relevant (Tan & Chen, 2022).

The success of UGC does not merely rely on quantity, but also the quality. The content needs to be informative, helpful, and positively related to the brand (Mohammad et al., 2020). Negative UGC can have a damaging impact on brand reputation (Wolter et al., 2023). Therefore, it is essential for brands to closely monitor UGC and engage in crisis management when necessary. One way to increase consumer engagement is using attractive visuals. Visual elements can draw attention and increase the likelihood of engagement (Zhao et al., 2022). In

addition, brands can also increase consumer engagement by making the content interactive, using, for example quizzes, polls, and contests (Shawky et al., 2019).

Furthermore, the use of UGC can vary across different platforms. For example, Instagram, which is image-based, might require different UGC strategies compared to Twitter, which is text-based (Shahbaznezhad et al., 2021). Therefore, brands need to adapt their UGC strategies according to the platform they are using. UGC is not only limited to brand promotion but also extends to social proof, which influences consumer behaviour. For example, during the Covid-19 pandemic, consumers used social media to generate social proof as an engaged society demonstrating stockpiling behaviour (Naeem, 2021). Therefore, the potential of UGC extends beyond traditional marketing and can significantly influence consumer behaviour and society.

2.6 ATTITUDES TOWARDS ORGANIZATIONAL RESPONSES

Service recovery signifies the orchestrated efforts by an organization to rectify a service failure, thereby rectifying any negative customer experience (Naeem & Ozuem, 2021). The satisfaction a customer experiences is directly tied to the effectiveness of such service recovery mechanisms. Consequently, an efficiently managed service recovery can even boost customer satisfaction beyond its initial level prior to service failure (Demmers et al., 2020). On the other hand, ineffective service recovery has the potential to exacerbate customer dissatisfaction (Ibrahim et al., 2022).

Indeed, service recovery strategies have a substantial bearing on customer satisfaction and determine whether customers will advocate for the organization or repurchase its products or services (Davicik et al., 2022). The role of UGC in shaping customers' attitudes towards an organization's service recovery attempts has also been explored. For instance, an organization's apology after a negative experience, while being a form of service recovery, might not always be viewed positively in online contexts (Hinson et al., 2019). Responses from management on platforms such as TripAdvisor can significantly impact customer attitudes, despite some negativity from a minor portion of the management (Naeem, 2020). There is, however, a distinct variation in customer responses to service recovery efforts. Emotions play a crucial role, expressing either positivity or negativity in response to service recovery actions (Kitirattarkarn et al., 2019). The level of customer dissatisfaction and negative emotions tends to surge following a service failure, and intense negative emotions can limit an organization's opportunity for recovery (Yang et al., 2022).

The concept of user innovation emphasizes the role of customers in product development. The traditional notion, which positioned companies as the key innovators and customers as mere consumers, has been refuted by studies emphasizing the significance of user inclusion in product development processes (Mathur et al., 2022). Pioneering users, or 'lead users', often introduce user innovations, reflecting the intertwined relationship between user innovation and lead user status (Li & Xie, 2020). These lead users are often ahead of the market, developing solutions and applications that yield significant returns (Tan & Chen, 2022). Lead users can anticipate needs that have not yet become mainstream, further demonstrating their vital role in product innovation (Acuti et al., 2019). Their proximity to the customer base and the local community encourages innovation, fostering the development of new applications that align with emerging needs and requirements (Mohammad et al., 2020). This study specifically seeks to explore the role of lead users in user innovation, especially those exhibiting a customer-oriented attitude. The intention is to identify factors that contribute to their significance.

2.7 IMPACT OF UGC ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR

As a result of the progressive evolution of the internet, user innovation now permeates virtual communities, invoking a growing interest in UGC as an area of scholarly enquiry (Daughtery et al, 2008). Five motivational constructs have been identified that have sparked the creation of UGC, namely: knowledge acquisition, social stimulation, utilitarian incentives, value affirmation, and ego-defensive drives (Vander Schee, Peltier, & Dahl, 2020). Toubia and Stephen's (2013) analysis of social media motivations distinguished between two primary utilities that govern user content publication, the first being intrinsic motivation, a drive originating from within, rather than deriving from external benefits (Viswanathan et al., 2018). The role of mobile content generation and user behaviour was brought to the fore by Ghose and Han (2011), while Ramsbotham et al (2012) scrutinized user interactions with Wikipedia and their contributions to its content network. Furthermore, Mallapragada et al (2012) explored open-source software as a UGC medium. These research endeavors have precipitated a change in basic assumptions in user innovation, moving from a company-centric to a customer-centric perspective (Aljarah et al., 2022).

Attitudes towards products can be fundamentally categorized into two components: capability and motivation. Here, capability refers to expertise and familiarity accrued from product knowledge, while motivation signifies the degree of interest and involvement in products (Kassarjian and Kassarjian 1979; Engel and Blackwell 1982). This study adopts the constructs

of familiarity and involvement as posited by Houston and Rothschild (1978), who differentiated between enduring, situational, and response involvement. The concept of enduring involvement was further delineated by Richins and Bloch (1986), emphasizing continuous engagement with products unaffected by situational factors (Houston and Rothschild 1978; Richins and Bloch 1986; Kapferer and Laurent 1985). Moreover, Bloch and Richins (1983) suggest that enduring involvement carries traces of self-expression and hedonism, thereby influencing individual endurance (Kapferer and Laurent 1985; Richins and Bloch 1986). This concept was advanced further by Higie and Feick (1989), who acknowledged the importance of enduring involvement in product-related dimensions (Baker et al., 2021).

Understanding consumer knowledge is pivotal to consumer research (Park and Lessig 1981; Bettman and Park 1980; Johnson and Russo 1984). Early research posited knowledge as a single-dimensional construct reflecting product familiarity or prior knowledge (Alba and Hutchinson 1987). However, subsequent attempts to measure consumer product experiences have recognized different knowledge types, including objective knowledge, subjective knowledge, and usage experience (Brucks 1985; Johnson and Russo 1984; Raju et al 1995). Alba and Hutchinson (1987) later suggested a two-component structure of consumer knowledge, where the first component is familiarity - past product-related experiences, and the second is expertise - the ability to perform tasks related to the products effectively. This study aims to measure familiarity via consumer mobile phone usage and behaviour concerning user innovation (Zhao et al., 2022).

Customer Centricity

Scholarly marketing research has affirmed that the prosperity of organizations hinges on their ability to gratify customers and meet their unique needs (Kotler, 1997; Deshpande, Farley, & Webster, 1993). Grounded in the ethos of empathy, Saxe and Weitz (1982) perceive customer-centricity as fundamentally intertwined with the regard for others. High customer satisfaction emerges from this empathic concern, whereas its diminishment signals a waning of the same concern. However, explorations of customer orientation pivot around the realm of service providers and salespersons. Aiding in the quantitative assessment of customer engagement within such cultures, Saxe and Weitz (1982) devised the Selling Orientation-Customer Orientation (SOCO) scale. This 24-item instrument, balanced with twelve affirmative and twelve negative items, has illuminated the intricate interplay between salespersons and

customers. Augmenting this discourse, they propounded a positive correlation between customer orientation and the performance of sales teams, affirming the pivotal role of customer-centricity as a valuable informational resource (Saxe & Weitz, 1982). Complementarily, Brown, Mowen, Donavan, and Licata (2002) argue that customer orientation is an individual's self-appraisal of their proclivity to cater to customer needs. Johike and Iyer (2017) have further empirically demonstrated the consequential effects of customer orientation on performance, both directly and indirectly. Each is contingent on the business context. Reinforcing this narrative, Schweisfurth and Raasch (2015) postulate that the manifestation of customer-oriented attitudes among lead users positively correlates with customer-oriented behaviour. The evolution of the marketplace, shifting from organization-centric to customer-centric situations, has been underscored by the unprecedented proliferation of UGC, fuelling a surge in customer orientation (Day & Wesley, 1988; Christodoulides, Jevons, & Bonhomme, 2011).

The contemporary digital landscape, teeming with platforms such as Instagram, Twitter, and YouTube, has transcended the traditional service-oriented boundaries of customer orientation, expanding its purview to novel terrains. Under the aegis of UGC, customer orientation manifests in the form of user posts, reaching out to a diverse follower base, not necessarily targeted organizations, but also individuals. This exploration seeks to unravel the impact of customer orientation on content quality and user-generated online communication.

2.8 UGC NATURE

Navigating the intricate dynamics between user innovation and consumer attitudes, this investigation casts a spotlight on the quality and quantity of user innovation. Notwithstanding the disparities between these two outcomes, scholarly discourse on their nuanced distinctions remains nascent. Hence, user innovation is conceptualized as a unifying construct for this hypothesis.

2.8.1 Engagement and Acquaintance

In the realm of product use, engagement has been interwoven with usage patterns (Houston & Rothschild, 1978). The theory posits a strong correlation between familiarity and innovation owing to the historical interactions between the individual and the product, delineating engagement (Houston & Rothschild, 1978). Acquaintance, in this context, is determined by the extent of user experiences with the product (Alba & Hutchinson, 1987). The integral relationship between engagement, acquaintance, and user experience is further reinforced by

its association with product relevance, as reported by Peter and Olson (2010) and Blackwell, Miniard, and Engel (2006). Hence, products that cater to customer needs heighten satisfaction levels, signifying a heightened level of engagement as opposed to products failing to meet needs, hence garnering lower engagement.

Economic motivation is defined as a form of economic incentive whereby consumers participate in creating positive reviews or feedback in exchange for a reward. After a negative experience, the customer feels obliged to share their experience on social media and to create negative UGC. They may hope to elicit a return from the organization in taking such action. Baker et al (2011) believe that people who complain on social media are opportunistic complainers whose main goal is to obtain compensation following a negative experience that has caused them damage or loss.

Extraversion links positive and negative experiences to post-purchase experiences, creating tension and promoting WOM. However, an individual who has a negative experience communicates as per their own level of personality. Extraversion is one of the elements included in the factor model of personality. Some studies consider extraverts as sociable and talkative (Yoo and Gretzel 2011) and suggest they are part of large social networks (Pollet et al 2011). They are chiefly purposeful individuals (Wang and Erdheim 2007). Loorea et al (2011) suggest that extraversion is positively associated with the use of social media. Further, it is an essential trait of customer motivation that motivates some to create UGC after a negative experience. Research suggests that some people participate in creating UGC (Nonnecke and Preece 2000). It is certainly true that not all happy customers are likely to post online, whereas all unhappy customers feel inclined to post online (Goldberg 1992).

It is claimed that more than 60% of extraverted bloggers post online purely to share information with people they do not even know and have never met. Additionally, Johnson (1989) argues that extraverted bloggers are mostly talkative which is why they are open to even more opportunities to offer or receive help. Research has suggested that the relationship between vengeance and extraversion is not common. On the other hand, extraverts are purposeful (Wang and Erdhm 2007). This means that they are highly likely to take revenge through UGC after a negative experience (Henning Thureau et al 2004). A correlation between extraversion and venting was found by Yoo and Gretzel (2011). They proposed that extraversion increases the chances of customers wanting to vent. Self-enhancers, on the other hand, are more likely to seek feedback (Hepper et al 2011). Thus, it is anticipated that self-enhancers are more likely to

create UGC as they are more talkative and sociable (Yoo and Gretzel 2011). They are also part of larger social networks (Pollet et al 2011). Lastly, as discussed above, customers who are motivated by economic gain are more inclined to be greedy and this is typical of extroverted individuals. Previous research points to a positive link between extraversion and assertiveness (Averret and McManis 1997; Ames and Flynn 2007).

UGC holds significant importance as an authoritative information source for service providers (Benwell and Stokoe, 2007), necessitating careful observation (Sparks and Browning, 2011). This research specifically focuses on the generation of UGC that gives rise to negative service experiences post-purchase, emphasizing the initiative-taking utilization of UGC (Shao, 2009) rather than the mere passive consumption of user-generated sites. Participation activities encompass various interactions, such as user-to-user and user-to-content interactions in diverse forums and blogs. On the other hand, production refers to the content published in the form of videos on platforms like YouTube and blogs (Shao, 2009). Multiple studies have concentrated on UGC participation (Shao, 2009; Nonnecke and Preece, 2000; Yoo and Gretzel, 2011). However, in the realm of service literature, only a limited number of studies have explored the antecedents of UGC and consumer motivations pertaining to service experiences (Wang and Fesenmaier, 2004; Parra Lope et al., 2011; Daughtry et al., 2008; Parra-Lopez et al., 2011; Yoo and Gretzel, 2008). Two studies evaluated a limited range of motivations by focusing on a specific consumer forum while adopting qualitative techniques (Zheng et al., 2009; Sparks and Browning, 2010). The level of UGC creation certainly differs based on the media type (Yoo and Gretzel, 2011). For instance, blogs involve more intensive production compared to reviews (Shao, 2009) (García-de-Frutos and Estrella-Ramón, 2021; Yoo, Katsumata, and Ichikohji, 2019).

UGC participation motivation is driven by various factors. Consumers frequently engage in word-of-mouth (WOM) activity and share their experiences with each other, particularly when they are dissatisfied. Service providers need to understand the emotions of dissatisfied customers after a negative experience to create UGC that encourages better future experiences (La Nagard and de Campos Ribeiro, 2011). Different motivations for UGC production have been proposed in the literature (Wasko and Faraj, 2000; Hennig-Thurau et al., 2004; Yoo and Gretzel, 2011; Yang and Lai, 2010). However, the exploration of these motivations in the context of improving customer experiences after a negative encounter through UGC creation requires further discussion. This study examines several motivations to develop an understanding of negative experiences faced by customers. One such motivation is altruism,

where individuals support and share information with others on social media platforms (; Parra Lopez et al., 2011). Another motivation is vengeance, where customers seek revenge against a specific organization due to a negative experience (; La Nagard and de Campos Ribeiro, 2011). Customers also engage in venting negativity motivation, expressing negative emotions such as anger and frustration to release stress)

2.8.2 Consumer Familiarity and Innovation Efficacy

The concept of consumer knowledge primarily encompasses two key dimensions, expertise, and familiarity, according to research by García-de-Frutos and Estrella-Ramón (2021). Familiarity refers to the array of interactions consumers have with a variety of products, whereas expertise pertains to the capacity of an organization to react effectively to these varied product experiences. Notably, a correlation is observed between a high level of product familiarity and consumer expertise (Singh & Chakrabarti, 2021). Furthermore, the understanding of this interaction between familiarity and expertise could be broadened by considering other influencing factors (Srivastava & Sivaramakrishnan, 2020).

The quality of UGC, particularly on social media platforms, is often a reflection of user innovation behaviour. It has been found that leading users can identify the potential benefits of a product or service early on and are often the source of new applications or solutions (Vazquez et al., 2021). High levels of familiarity can thus stimulate user innovation through tasks related to product improvement.

2.8.3 Customer Orientation and User Innovation

Research into the field of innovation reveals that numerous users participate in the modification and development of products. The traits of innovating users are derived from leading users, indicating that user innovation occurs among leading users (Yoo, Katsumata, & Ichikohji, 2019). Recent studies have placed an increased focus on the relationship between customer orientation and innovation. Kang and McAuley (2018) conducted a thorough analysis of the various impacts of market orientation on innovation. They found that customer orientation has a positive effect on creativity, directly influencing user innovativeness. Further, it was discovered that the lead sureness of employees positively influences customer orientation behaviour (Liu, 2020). Given their respective roles, customer orientation primarily influences innovation behaviour, as it is seen as a construct of attitude, while user innovation is perceived as a behavioural concept.

2.8.4 Engagement with Brands: A Consumer Perspective

Engagement has relevance in a variety of fields including sociology (Liu, Karahanna, & Watson, 2011), political science (Sykora et al., 2022), and organizational behaviour (Ghose, Ipeirotis, & Li, 2012). In the context of marketing, engagement encompasses both behaviors and attitudes of consumers, extending beyond purchase behaviour (Chang, Wang, & Yang, 2022). This is evident when consumers show a willingness to interact and share experiences with a brand or organizations (Zhang, Zheng, Wang, & Zhu, 2020). The concept of brand engagement, especially in the digital realm, is closely tied to the notion of user innovation. Given this observation, further research is necessary to explore the relationship between brand engagement and user innovation, and the potential influence of one on the other.

2.9 BRAND ENGAGEMENT

Brand engagement refers to the process of forming an emotional or rational attachment between a customer and a brand (Vander Schee, Peltier, & Dahl, 2020). It entails not only purchasing and using a brand's products or services, but also participating in the experiences the brand offers through various channels, especially on social media (Naeem & Ozuem, 2021). In recent years, the rise of social media and digital platforms has reshaped the concept of brand engagement, turning it from a unidirectional to a multidirectional construct. Consumers are no longer mere recipients of brand messages but are now active participants in the creation and dissemination of brand-related content (Naeem, 2020; Dolan et al., 2019).

UGC plays a pivotal role in shaping brand engagement (Naeem & Ozuem, 2021). It refers to the variety of content (e.g., reviews, comments, photos, videos) that consumers create and share online about a brand or product. Research suggests that UGC is perceived as more authentic and trustworthy than traditional marketing communications, thereby contributing to stronger brand engagement (Ibrahim et al., 2022; Davcik et al., 2022). However, it is important to note that not all UGC leads to higher brand engagement. The quality of UGC, which encompasses aspects such as relevance, usefulness, and reliability, is a critical factor in determining its impact on brand engagement (Mohammad et al., 2020). For instance, UGC that provides practical and beneficial information about a product, or a brand can offer both functional and emotional values to consumers, which can in turn enhance their engagement with the brand (Naeem, 2021).

Social motivational factors, like the desire for social interaction and recognition, can also foster greater brand engagement. As Naeem (2020) suggests, social media platforms can leverage

these social motivational factors to stimulate consumers to engage more actively with brand-related content.

In addition to UGC, marketer-generated content (MGC) also significantly contributes to brand engagement (Yang et al., 2022). This content, crafted by brands themselves, should not only provide relevant and valuable information but should also be creative and engaging to capture consumers' attention and stimulate their interest in the brand (Dolan et al., 2019). Another aspect of brand engagement that has gained attention recently is its relation to consumer behaviour during crisis situations. For instance, during the COVID-19 pandemic, social media played a significant role in influencing consumer behaviour, such as impulse buying and stockpiling. By engaging with consumers through social media, brands could alleviate panic buying and encourage more responsible behaviour (Naeem, 2021).

Moreover, it is essential to understand that brand engagement is not a static phenomenon; it evolves along the customer journey (Demmers, Weltevreden, & van Dolen, 2020). Early-stage engagement might involve brand awareness and knowledge acquisition, whereas late-stage engagement might involve brand loyalty and advocacy. Brand engagement, particularly in the context of social media, involves an intricate interplay of various factors. UGC and MGC, along with social motivational factors and the quality of content, significantly influence brand engagement. Furthermore, brands must be mindful of evolving consumer behaviours during crises and adapt their engagement strategies accordingly. As such, it is a dynamic process that changes over the course of the consumer's journey with the brand.

Brand engagement is a concept that delves into the psychological interaction between consumers and brands (Naeem & Ozuem, 2021). In the digital age, the development of brand engagement extends beyond conventional advertising methods and now largely takes place in the social media landscape. The involvement of consumers in the production, dissemination, and consumption of brand-related content has allowed brands to connect with their audience in more meaningful and dynamic ways (Naeem, 2020; Osei-Frimpong, 2019).

With the growth of social media platforms, UGC has emerged as a vital tool for enhancing brand engagement. UGC is content related to a brand that is voluntarily produced by its consumers, offering a profound source of information and social proof about the brand (Naeem & Ozuem, 2021; Naeem, 2021). Consumers are more likely to trust the perspectives of their peers, thus UGC often carries significant influence on the perceptions of potential consumers and fosters a sense of community and trust around a brand (Naeem, 2020). Simultaneously,

Firm-Generated Content (FGC) has been observed to be an influential factor in engaging customers. This content, crafted by the brand itself, can significantly affect consumer engagement through the precise crafting of messages and brand narratives (Aljarah et al., 2022; Tan & Chen, 2022). The balance of UGC and FGC is instrumental in cultivating a dynamic brand image, where both the voices of consumers and the brand contribute to a multidimensional brand narrative.

Naeem's (2020) research underlines the role of social motivational factors in enhancing brand-related content. These factors include the need for social interaction, the desire for self-presentation, and the pursuit of entertainment and information. When brands tap into these motivations, they can enhance the engagement of their audiences and build a stronger brand community. Demmers et al. (2020) offer a distinct perspective by examining consumer engagement with brand posts on social media across various stages of the customer journey. They found that engagement tactics should be tailored to different stages of this journey, emphasizing the importance of understanding consumers' shifting needs and perceptions as they progress from awareness to purchase and loyalty.

Naeem (2021) also emphasizes the role of social media in generating social proof as an engaged society for stockpiling behaviour of customers during the Covid-19 pandemic. This is a testament to how online brand engagement can be leveraged in times of crisis, and how quickly it can shift consumer behaviours. Moreover, engagement with brand-related content on social media can have a substantial influence on online purchase intention. It has been observed that user engagement with such content significantly mediates the relationship between the determinants of online purchase intentions (Mathur et al., 2022). This further highlights the role of brand engagement in driving consumer actions and decisions.

However, brand engagement is not without its challenges. As Kitirattarkarn et al. (2019) point out, cultural factors can significantly moderate the effects of content characteristics on consumer engagement with brand related UGC. This emphasizes the need for brands to take a nuanced, culturally sensitive approach when engaging with their audience. Moreover, digital brand engagement requires vigilant management of online brand communities. Hinson et al. (2019) suggest that understanding the attachment theory can provide significant insights into the antecedents and consequences of customer engagement on Facebook. By analyzing the customer's proximity, emotional bond, and dependency towards the brand, companies can foster an enduring online relationship with their audience.

In conclusion, brand engagement in the digital era is a complex, multifaceted process that depends on understanding consumer motivations, crafting relevant content, and managing interactions within the online brand community to reduce the size of the text.

2.10 TYPES OF SOCIAL MEDIA CONTENT AND USER ENGAGEMENT

Content on social media that impacts engagement has been conceptualized into two fundamental types, which are interactional (personal, customer relationship, experiential, employee brand community, cause-related) and transactional (brand resonance, remunerative, sales promotion). Scholars have utilized these three themes to assess impact of several content types on engagement behaviour. Table 1 presents a summary of these three studies. Several studies have investigated the role of rational content on social media; however, inconsistent findings have been produced. For instance, Coelho et al (201) found no relationship between rational content and engagement behaviour on platforms such as Instagram and Facebook. Cvijikj and Michahelles (2013) produced empirical evidence about comments and likes on social media in the food and beverage industry. In contrast to this, recent studies conducted by Dolan et al (2019) illustrated that rational content has an influence over engagement via likes. However, it does not have an impact on active engagement. This study was limited to Facebook, and it only covered the context of wine brands. Some have suggested that rational content is ineffective as compared to emotional appeals when it comes to customer engagement. Studies that were conducted in the context of traditional media settings have produced contradicting outcomes (Aaker et al 1986; Liu and Stout 1987).

Moreover, several authors who have presented research on rational content showing conflicting outcomes regarding how emotional content is used to influence engagement amongst people. Dolan et al (2019) examined entertaining and relational content as two types of emotional appeals that are utilized in social media. They noted that entertaining content induced more engagement in the form of likes, however it did not influence comments. Another study conducted by Tafesse (2015) showed that entertaining content used by the UK's automotive brands on Facebook created more engagement. It was also observed that content, which was humorous, and entertaining made people more engaged on Facebook. However, the author struggled to produce conclusive evidence that showed a positive relationship between entertaining content and active engagement behaviour that involved commenting. Several authors focused on the various impacts of entertaining content on different business on Facebook pages. For instance, Swani et al (2013) claimed that, in B2C settings, emotional

content is much more likely to create engagement as compared to B2B settings. Further, there was more engagement on pages related to services as compared to products. This underscored the importance of other elements, such as context which could have helped the investigation. The findings of Swani et al (2013) are not generalizable, which is why these authors did not properly estimate the significance of types of messages that are exchanged on social media platforms such as Facebook.

Some users anticipate monetary rewards, incentives, job related benefit, or personal satisfaction from engagement (Muntinga et al 2011). Moreover, further exploration of the concept of transactional content, also referred to as remunerative content was undertaken by Cvijikj and Michahelles (2013) and Dolan et al (2019). There is some consistency between the findings produced by Cvijikj and Michahelles (2013) and Swani et al (2013). Both claim that remunerative content mitigates the number of likes that accrue. In other words, this points to passive engagement. However, surprisingly enough, a positive influence on active engagement via commenting was observed. In contrast, Dolan et al (2019) found remunerative content has a positive impact on passive engagement, and a negative impact on active engagement. It has also been observed that transactional content like discounts, incentives, and deals are likely to generate emotional appeal. For instance, Zielke (2011) stated that value perceptions that emerge from remunerative content impact emotions, and therefore induce responses, which could either be positive or negative (Dolan et al, 2019).

Comparisons of richness amongst different media forms such as direct mail marketing vs telephone contact have been undertaken. Several studies have been conducted to examine the landscape of communication that offers marketers an opportunity to provide lean and rich content for advertising and marketing purposes. Media richness is linked to online and digital marketing (Shaw et al 2009). Rich media online contains a range of interactive methods that reflects display motion and exposes sensory characteristics like animation, audio, and video (Rosenkrans 2009). Rich media is a term that offers a broader perspective of content, including video, sounds and content that induces attraction amongst users (Shaw et al 2009). Earlier research has shown that face-to-face meetings are richer in nature than written documents because the latter contains no verbal cues that as also counts as forms of user feedback (King and Xia 1997). However, virtually, individuals interact in a similar way to face-to-face interactions, and this elicits rich content (Cheung et al 2011) and a better customer experience (Li et al 2012). Posts on social media vary based on richness that can be measured according to the level of information offered within a certain period (De Vries et al 2012; Cvijikj and

Michahelles 2013). In contrast, online media content that is rich in nature includes video, audio and animations and a variety of interactive and motional methods that can expose sensory traits to influence richness in content (Rosenkrans 2009).

Earlier studies conducted in the context of social media content and online engagement gave insights into the significance of different types of social media platforms. However, there are brands that make use of multi-channel approaches to share their content to create a wider reach and audience. Global Web Index (2019) showed that internet users are active on seven accounts on average, including different social media platforms. However, their focus was either on social media platforms in general (Van Noort et al 2014; Muntinga et al 2011; Okazaki et al 2014) or just one (Nelson Field et al 2012), such as Facebook, YouTube, Pinterest, Twitter, or more (Liu Thompkins 2012; Walther et al 2010; Liu et al 2017; Sook Kwon et al 2004; Phillips et al 2014). According to Voorveld et al (2018) a multi-channel approach is quite significant and helps SMUs examine different social media platforms to engagement with social media advertising. Engagement is dependent on the context that produces different customer experiences on social media platforms (Voorveld et al 2018).

2.11 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Its emergence was observed in the mid-1960s, and it explains the behaviour of consumers towards commodities in the market and purchase decisions (Martin 1998; Evrard and Aurier 1996; O’Cass 2004). Later, consumer involvement was referred to as the level of individual interest and relevance about object in terms of goals, values, and self-concept (Hollebeek 2011, p. 793). In this way, involvement refers to the relationship between intrapersonal processes and consumer objects. Hollebeek (2011) argued that consumer involvement should be defined as the level of individual interest and relevance of a certain object that is engraved in an individual’s goals, values, and self-concept.

In a digital context, Mollen, and Wilson (2010) showed that brand engagement is a commitment towards an online brand, and this is also referred to as an active relationship between the brand and the user that creates an experience for the user that reflects the brand’s value. Brodie et al (2013) consider virtual brand settings and recommend that engagement is something that comes from an experiential process that is highly interactive and is based on engaging individuals with certain objects. In addition, the findings from that study show that context matters in engagement because it varies by contexts. The level of intensity also varies in terms of time dimensions. This presents challenges for the consistency of engagement

(Schaufeli et al 2002a, b). Indeed, engagement is an iterative and dynamic processes (Brodie et al 2013). Consumer engagement has also been described as stable and based on having a positive stable relationship with customer loyalty (Patterson et al 2006; Bowden 2009). Further Hollebeek (2011) argued that the relationship between engagement and loyalty is curvilinear in nature. As such, there are four segments that reflect the different levels of brand engagement and loyalty. The first segment is activists for whom brand engagement is high, and loyalty is moderate. The second is termed agathists for whom brand engagement is low and loyalty is high. The third is 'exits' for whom brand engagement is low and loyalty is low, and the fourth group are variety seekers for whom brand engagement is high and loyalty is moderate. This suggests that engagement is a multi-dimensional concept that incorporates emotional, cognitive, and behavioural aspects (Hollebeek et al 2011; Brodie et al 2013). From this perspective, the starting point for engagement is the individual's urge to require information regarding a particular object. This process also includes sub-processes such as learning, sharing, socializing, advocating and co-developing (Brodie et al 2013).

The body of literature spanning consumer engagement over time reveals a paradigm that leans towards advanced technological developments such as social media. The source of engagement has in fact been transformed due to this shift in technology. To be specific, our understanding of consumer engagement is also expanding because of the emergence of alternative manifestations of the concept. If user actions in a specific social media setting are considered as manifestations of engagement within the context of objects, then social media is clearly quite beneficial for research purposes due to its huge reach and widespread popularity and use (Sprott et al 2009). Although the concept of engagement has been observed in different contexts, like firm-hosted brand communities and brand communities (De Vaick et al 2009; Brodie et al 2013; Wiertz and de Ruyter 2007; Nolan et al 2007), there is a need for more information that evaluates if curvilinear engagement sequences are sufficient to identify the context of social media in a more diverse and fashion-oriented manner.

2.11.1 Self-determination theory

MGC has rarely been claimed as a powerful tool that is useful to examine motivational factors as far as engagement behaviours are concerned. Self-determination theory explains the processes of motivation, highlighting the association between engagement and MGC (Deci and Ryan 2002). The fundamental feature of SDT is behaviour, and this varies along a continuum, from a low to a high level of self-determination (Ryan and Deci 2000). It is possible to

differentiate between two types of motivation using self-determination theory: controlled motivation, and autonomous motivation. When which combined, these cover the entire range of self-determination (Deci and Ryan 2002). More importantly, based on these two types of motivations, psychological resources are needed to form a willpower that engages a specific type of behaviour. Autonomous motivation is linked with a psychological state that is based on a high level of self-determination and is contingent on how social context enables the satisfaction of three basic psychological needs: relatedness, competence, and autonomy (Deci and Ryan 2002; Deci and Ryan 1985). This study showed that autonomous motivation is high when there is a sense of belongingness towards a brand community (Dholakia et al 2004). It could also be connected to the community, portraying an association with relatedness (Sheldon et al 2011). Users could be motivated autonomously by feedback on different products/services and this that could link with competence (Goh et al 2013). In contrast, controlled motivation links with a psychological state that portrays low self-determination and is contingent on how the context of behaviour gives behavioural directives. Apart from these social contexts, the directives of behaviour suggest that users are either pressurized to act to become satisfied, or proud of their feedback that is created to attract others (Deci and Ryan 2002). This theory is, however, limited to the context of exploring the social determination of the SMUs. The focus of the current research is to understand the brand engagement process according to SMUs who share, create, and consume on social media. Therefore, social determination theory is not applied within this research. While Self-Determination Theory (SDT) provides a robust framework for understanding human motivation, it presents certain limitations when considered for the specific context of UGC and consumer brand engagement within Islamic banking in Pakistan. The following are amongst the more compelling reasons to reject the application of SDT for the current study:

1. **Limitation in Understanding Cultural Influence:** SDT emphasizes psychological needs such as autonomy, competence, and relatedness as the key drivers of motivation. However, it does not fully accommodate the influence of cultural and societal values, which are crucial for the first objective of this research. In the Islamic banking context, the consumers' motivations often originate from their cultural and religious beliefs, rather than individual psychological needs. This mismatch makes SDT an inadequate framework to examine how these unique values impact UGC and brand engagement.
2. **Neglecting Characteristics of Content:** SDT is a psychological theory focusing on the individual's internal motivational processes. It lacks the structural capacity to

comprehensively analyse the characteristics of UGC (objective 2), which could include factors like tone, content quality, or semantic context. The focus on individual motivation does not allow for an exploration of how these external factors might impact consumer brand engagement.

3. **Managing Online Incivility:** The theory offers little guidance when it comes to understanding the impact of negative UGC or online incivility (objective 3), a significant aspect of digital interactions. It assumes a broadly positive correlation between satisfying psychological needs and the individual's behaviour, but it fails to explain how individuals react to or are influenced by adverse experiences such as incivility online.
4. **Failing to Account for Specific Islamic Banking Constructs:** Islamic banking operates under Sharia law, incorporating elements of morality, ethics, and religion that significantly differ from conventional banking principles. SDT, which is based on general psychological needs, may not adequately account for these specialized constructs. The religious and ethical principles underlying Islamic banking decisions are not explicitly incorporated into SDT, limiting its relevance to the research.
5. **Insufficient Scope for Social Determination:** While SDT recognizes the impact of social context on motivation, its primary focus is on individual psychological states and needs. The unique nature of this research, which requires understanding the influence of societal norms, peer influence, and shared cultural values on UGC and brand engagement, may not be adequately addressed by SDT. Furthermore, SDT's dichotomy of autonomous and controlled motivation may not fully capture the spectrum of motivations in a social media environment, where motivations can be influenced by a complex interplay of individual, social, and cultural factors.

In conclusion, while SDT provides valuable insights into the understanding of human motivation, its limitations in understanding cultural influences, handling content characteristics and online incivility, accounting for Islamic banking constructs, and adequately addressing social determination make it less suitable for this research. Thus, an alternative theoretical framework that better accommodates the complexity and context-specific attributes of the research should be considered.

2.11.2 Consumer Socialization Theory

Consumer Socialization Theory has been developed based on “*The process by which young people develop consumer-related skills, knowledge and attitudes*” (Moschis and Churchill, 1978, p.599). CST consists of three key components: socialization processes, behavioural outcomes, and antecedents. However, the antecedents of CST include both environmental surroundings and personal attributes (Moschis and Churchill, 1978). Moreover, personal attributes may include age, gender, ethnicity, educational level, socioeconomic status, family structure and many more (Bush et al., 1999; Moschis and Churchill, 1978). Moreover, antecedent variables may have a direct or indirect impact on consumer behaviour in terms of creating interactions with socialization agents (Moschis and Churchill, 1978). Furthermore, socialization agents may direct people to develop the same behaviours, attitudes, and norms through the socialization process. “A person or organization that has frequent contact with the learner, primacy over the individual, and control over rewards or punishments given to the learner” is defined as socialization agent by (Moschis and Churchill, 1978, p.600). Socialization agents are thus considered a key influential force for individuals who remain inactive throughout the socialization process (Bush, Smith, and Martin, 1999). Moreover, socialization agents may include peers, teachers, mentors, mass media and family members (Moschis and Churchill, 1978). According to CST, both socialization agents and antecedents have a strong impact on outcomes that helps them to explore the role of UGC to create brand engagement with Islamic banks. Moreover, it has been observed that socialisation agents equally influence outcomes as well as the environment and personal attributes of individuals (Moschis and Churchill, 1978). While Consumer Socialization Theory (CST) is a useful tool for understanding consumer behaviours in a variety of contexts, it is limited in a number of ways when applied to the aim and objectives of the proposed research focusing on UGC and consumer brand engagement in the context of Islamic banking in Pakistan. The core of the argument for rejecting CST for this research hinges on the mismatch between the fundamental assumptions of CST and the unique characteristics of the proposed study context.

1. The Age Limitation of CST: The first, and most glaring limitation of the CST in the context of this research is the fact that it primarily addresses the socialization of young people into the role of consumers. Islamic banking, however, is a complex field that requires a mature understanding of financial systems, religious tenets, and the interplay between the two. This advanced understanding is far beyond the scope of what young people typically manage in their consumer behaviour. Hence, CST may not provide the

appropriate framework for investigating consumer behaviour related to Islamic banking, given the sophisticated and niche nature of the subject.

2. **CST and Cultural & Societal Values:** The second research objective, which is to examine how cultural and societal values influence UGC and brand engagement within an Islamic banking context may not be adequately addressed by CST. Although CST recognizes the role of environmental factors in shaping consumer behaviour, it fails to account adequately for complex cultural and societal values. These are particularly significant in the context of Islamic banking, where religious principles profoundly shape banking practices and consumer behaviours.
3. **Contextual Limitations:** The CST focuses on socialization agents within the consumer's immediate environment. While it does consider the role of mass media, it falls short in acknowledging the dynamic, complex, and often global nature of online social media networks. This is especially important given that the internet and social media networks have redefined consumer socialization processes, with the digital landscape allowing for interactions beyond immediate social groups.
4. **Content Characteristics and Online Incivility:** The theory does not accommodate the examination of content characteristics of UGC, as it was primarily developed to understand consumer behaviours through socialization agents, rather than the nuances of digital content. Also, CST provides little guidance on dealing with the negative aspects of socialization such as online incivility, as highlighted in the third research objective. The issue of online incivility, though a critical aspect of the current digital age, is beyond the explanatory power of CST, which was developed before the advent of digital social media platforms.
5. **Islamic Banking Specifics:** Islamic banking operates on principles and values quite different from conventional banking. It incorporates elements of morality and religion that go beyond the regular consumer attributes or environmental factors that CST proposes. It is a domain where consumer decisions are based not just on personal attributes or learned behaviours, but also significantly on faith-based principles that the CST does not incorporate.

In summary, while CST has offered valuable insights into understanding consumer behaviour, the theory's applicability to this research is constrained by its limited scope regarding age,

inadequate accommodation of complex societal and cultural values, the contextual limitations of socialization agents, a lack of provision for the characteristics of digital content and online incivility, and its lack of consideration for the unique attributes of Islamic banking. For these reasons, a more suitable theoretical framework that fully acknowledges the complexity and unique attributes of the research context should be considered.

2.11.3 Social exchange theory

Social exchange theory is built on a set of fundamental presumptions regarding the character of humans and the relationships between people. The theory presupposes those human beings are motivated by a desire to obtain positive reinforcement, and to avoid negative consequences (Homans, 1958). Second, it presupposes that the objective of interaction is to reduce costs whilst simultaneously increasing benefits. Thirdly, it presupposes that a person will engage in some sort of calculation prior to participating in something. In conclusion, it presupposes that there will be variations in pay out from one instance to the next, and from one individual to the next (Homans, 1958).

The foundational premises of this theory are comparable to those of social exchange theory in terms of their scope and significance. The core concept behind both theories is that there is no "one size fits all" solution since people's expectations change over time, and no two people have the same expectations. Yet expectations do serve as a foundation upon which to build relationships (Homans, George 1950). For instance, if a person has previously been in a relationship that did not work out, they will approach a new relationship with certain expectations for how the current relationship will compare to the previous one. In a similar vein, the application of theories to the context of shopping means that a person's prior experience of shopping acts as a baseline against which they measure the shopping experiences that lie ahead (Homans, 1961).

In applying Social Exchange Theory (SET), a robust framework is introduced to develop an understanding of the intricate dynamics and underlying motivations of social media users' engagement with brands in the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan. SET. The focus on the principles of reciprocity and cost-benefit analysis means that it is an appropriate theoretical lens to examine UGC and consumer-brand engagement, particularly given the research aim and objectives of the study.

SET posits that individuals engage in interactions aiming to maximize benefits and minimize costs (Homans, 1958). Within the context of this research, SMUs can be seen as participating in a form of social exchange when they create and share UGC related to Islamic banks. They might do this with some expectation of receiving some form of benefit, for example, validation, recognition, or valuable information. At the same time, they might be cognizant of the potential costs, such as the time and effort required to create and share content, or potential negative reactions from others. This aligns with the first research objective, which involves examining how cultural and societal values within an Islamic banking context in Pakistan influence UGC and subsequent brand engagement.

SET also suggests that social relationships involve a form of 'quid pro quo' whereby each party provides something to the other (Blau, 1964). Translated to the context of UGC and brand engagement, consumers may provide endorsements, recommendations, or even criticisms to a brand, anticipating that the brand would respond to their needs, provide better service, or offer more value in return. This interplay is critical in examining how the content characteristics of UGC impact brand engagement (the second research objective). Moreover, SET introduces the concept of reciprocity, suggesting that positive actions would lead to positive responses and vice versa (Gouldner, 1960). In terms of UGC, if users perceive that their engagement with a brand is met with favourable responses, such as improved services or personalized attention, they will continue to engage with the brand and even advocate for it. Conversely, if their engagement is met with negativity or ignored, they may disengage and potentially even denounce the brand. This aligns with the third research objective, which is to investigate the impact of online incivility in the form of negative UGC on brand engagement.

Furthermore, SET's focus on human interactions, their motivations, and the cost-benefit analysis associated with these interactions provides a viable framework to investigate how individuals perceive, engage, and interact with brands on social media platforms. This allows for an exploration of the complexities of SMUs' motivations, behaviours, and perceptions, which could shed light on how and why they engage with brands in the ways that they do. Additionally, SET emphasizes that interactions are driven by the perceived value of the relationship (Homans, 1958). SMUs will continue to engage with a brand if they perceive that the benefits, they derive from the relationship outweigh the costs, such as the time, effort, or resources required for engagement. This aligns with the research aim of conceptualizing the concept of UGC and consumer brand engagement.

Finally, SET has been used in previous research to explain consumers' attitudes and behaviours in a variety of contexts, suggesting its versatility and applicability to different research domains (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005). Thus, its use in this research will build on this body of literature, extending our understanding of the theory, and its application in the specific context of social media networks linked to Islamic banking in Pakistan. Social Exchange Theory thus provides an invaluable theoretical lens to examine the dynamics of UGC and consumer brand engagement in the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan. The theory's focus on reciprocity, cost-benefit analysis, and perceived value align well with the research aim and objectives. Notably, it can shed light on the motivations and behaviours of social media users, the nature of their interactions with brands, and how these factors contribute to their engagement.

As indicated in the second research objective, SET can help to identify how the content characteristics of UGC impact brand engagement. Consumers tend to exchange UGC with certain characteristics – informativeness, entertainment, and credibility. If users perceive these characteristics as benefits, they are more likely to engage with the brand, validating SET's principle of maximising rewards. The third research objective - investigating the impact of online incivility in the form of negative UGC on brand engagement - can also be examined within the purview of SET. Negative UGC could be seen as a 'cost' which might impact the engagement if users feel that their interactions invite negativity or result in unpleasant experiences. This aspect can trigger a re-evaluation of the cost-benefit equation, and if the costs are perceived to be higher than the benefits, users may disengage, in line with the assumptions of SET.

Moreover, SET provides a framework to analyse the effects of cultural and societal values within an Islamic banking context, as mentioned in the first research objective. Users in this specific cultural context might have unique perceptions of the costs and benefits of engaging with Islamic banking brands on social media. For example, if creating and sharing UGC aligned with Islamic values results in societal approval (a social benefit), users may be more motivated to engage; a dynamic that can be understood through the lens of SET. In addition, SET can provide insight into why certain UGC results in higher levels of engagement. As people engage in exchanges that yield the highest rewards at the lowest cost, content that provides valuable information or elicits positive emotions could be more engaging for users. On the other hand, content that requires high cognitive effort to understand or elicits negative emotions could be less engaging.

Overall, the application of SET in this research provides a strong theoretical basis for examining how and why users generate content and engage with brands on social media platforms. This could lead to a deeper understanding of the complex dynamics involved in UGC and consumer-brand engagement in the unique context of Islamic banks in Pakistan. It can further provide valuable insights into how these banks can leverage UGC to enhance their engagement strategies and cultivate strong, positive relationships with their customers. By contributing to the body of knowledge on SET, this research can also inspire future studies on similar topics, thus extending the applicability and relevance of the theory.

These levels of expectation are consistent with other ideas, such as the cost vs benefit or give and take concept, both of which examine the amount of effort a person is willing to put into a relationship with another person. The term 'cost' refers, in the context of this discussion, to the amount of money an individual is prepared to spend in exchange for the things they believe they will receive, whereas the term 'benefit' refers to the thing an individual receives in exchange for the money they spend (Blau, 1964). A good connection is one in which the costs and benefits are in equilibrium, and in which each party receives what they anticipate receiving in exchange for what they contribute. This applies to and is significant for all different kinds of transactions that humans engage in (Lawler, and Thye, 2006). When the costs are greater than the benefits, those responsible for absorbing the costs will typically lose interest in the connection. Nevertheless, a comparison with alternatives might maintain the individual in the relationship when they find out that, by leaving, the transaction would be no worse than what they are already receiving. As a result, it is possible that they will continue to be a part of the relationship by accident (Miller, 2005).

SET has served as the basis for previous research. According to Cook and Rice (2003), maintaining a relationship requires maintaining a balance in the exchanges that take place between all the parties involved, provided that any comparison with alternatives stays favourable to the parties participating in the connection. This indicates that the basis of any social interaction between two or more people is based on what those people are getting from one another, as opposed to what anyone else can offer them in place of the status quo. If the transaction that they are currently engaging in is mutually beneficial beyond anything that a third party might provide in its place, then they will continue to be committed to one another (Cook, Emerson, 1978). However, these findings also show that the application of the theory from the perspectives of relativism and social constructionism in the context of understanding social brand engagement (which is based on the social interaction of SMUs) is limited. The

theory has been applied in the context of game-based situations, including incentives and costs for participating in a computer-based game. However, such relationships cannot be related to real-life experiences, such as the provision of Islamic banking services or the production of UGC on SMNs, in which SMUs participate in the production, sharing, and exchange of UGC. As a result, social exchange theory is applied in this study to the role of UGC in developing engagement with brands.

In addition, it might be challenging to define the fundamental ideas underlying social exchange theory. However, this research has developed a process-based framework that demonstrates the process of social exchange as outcomes of the SBE and CBE. Since the idea of cost and reward is subjective, an objective definition of these concepts may not be possible. However, given that the current study is based on subjectivism, it is exploratory in nature and focuses on collecting the subjective views of participants. As such, social exchange theory provides a useful insight for understanding the motives of SMUs to create, share, and exchange UGC about Islamic banking brands. This is because the social exchange theory focuses on the nature of the relationships between individuals, rather than the relationships between individuals and brands.

In addition, according to social exchange theory, at the beginning of any relationship, the partners tend to remember what they receive in exchange for what they give to each other. This is the case regardless of the type of connection. Clark and Mills (2011) suggest that while this may be true in professional settings, it may not be true in personal settings, such as in social connections, where there is less of an emphasis on what individuals receive in exchange for what they provide. The issue is not the proportion of benefits to drawbacks. Rather, it is the general fairness of the connection that two people have in which they share the costs and benefits of using social media together.

Knapp (1978) discussed the issue of assumptions that were made in accordance with SET which are related to cause and effect. For instance, Lawler (2001) stated that the evaluation of a relationship starts well before the emergence of dissatisfaction in the partnership. This demonstrates that the evaluation can either lead to satisfaction or discontent for the individual. However, once again, this is pertinent in certain relationships, such as those that are based solely on giving and receiving, but it may not be pertinent in other relationships, such as romantic relationships or duty-based social relationships in which one person feels that it is his responsibility to keep the others informed.

Both customer-brand engagement and social exchange theory, using SD logic and RM theory alike can be useful where customers are perceived as initiative-taking contributors to brand related interactions instead of just acting as inactive recipients of cues related to brands (Gronroos, 1997; Vargo and Lusch, 2008a). Thus, customers are likely to devote relevant physical, emotional, or cognitive resources based on perceived values they obtained from brand interactions (Higgins and Scholer, 2009). While explaining social exchange theory, Blau (1964) proposed that customers predict reciprocate positive behaviours, feelings, and thoughts towards a specific object (such as a brand) when they receive benefits from an association with that object (Pervan, Bove, and Johnson, 2009). Thus, social exchange elicits unspecified obligations, where one party (such as service personnel or a brand representatives) favours another party (such as customers) by providing expertise or exceptional services with the objective to gain a specific future return (such as consumer loyalty) (Rousseau, 1989). The parties described under social exchange theory tend to maintain equilibrium in developed relationships and will make balanced restorative efforts if an imbalance in the relationship occurs. In such exchanges, what the customer gives is perceived as cost, and what they receive is perceived as reward. A modification in the individual's behaviour can occur because of differences between these exchanges (i.e., profit) (Homans, 1958). Such a cost-reward perspective is related to the interactive nature of consumer engagement (Hollebeek, 2011). Therefore, this theory will be applied in the current study to understand how different SMUs gain advantage through the exchange of the UGC over social media.

Figure 2-1

Figure: Conceptual Framework

Social exchange clarifies how online social media platforms (such as Instagram, Snapchat, Wanelo and Pinterest), family members and peers influence the buying behaviour of consumers through a socialization process. Studying socialisation agents provides a better understanding of how these forces influence behavioural outcomes in terms of buying intentions. The findings of this study describe why and how these influential forces work. The final research framework is developed based on the above literature review. Consumer engagement is defined as a relationship that observes interactions between consumers, an object and the value experienced as part of that interaction (Mollen and Wilson 2010; Brodie et al 2013). From another perspective (Patterson et al, 2006) engagement has been linked to the cognitive, physical, and emotional state between consumers and organizations. Similarly, Vivek et al (2012) observed the ways in which consumers interact with certain events and activities that are referred to as the engagement source. This requires some understanding of the role of UGC for brand engagement. Involvement, which is linked with engagement is explained using the antecedent of engagement (Hollebeek 2011).

As far as involvement is concerned, engagement is shaped by several factors, such as UGC motivation, UGC characteristics, user involvement, types of UGC and the dimensions of UGC. In a similar setting, it is suggested that consumer engagement should be associated with consumer involvement (Brodie et al 2013; Hollebeek 2011) which is also based on UGC content types and the motivation of users. These interlinked concepts include intrapersonal processes in a particular context which is also linked with consumer objects that are based on certain behaviours towards a focal object (Spratt et al 2009; Patterson et al 2006). Further, these two concepts are also depicted as the drivers of commitment, consumer satisfaction, trust, and loyalty (Brodie et al 2013). Specifically, as per suggestions by Hollebeek (2011), both these concepts are significant sources of relationship quality and are the prerequisites of developing customer engagement. Therefore, content characteristics are also considered elements of the theoretical framework.

This might be explained by the fact that social media has become a source of SMUs expressing their emotions, experiences, and viewpoints. Thus, users participating in such activities are socially engaged. Social engagement has been defined by Achterberg et al (2003) as a sufficient response to social stimuli that leads towards engagement in social activities. This type of activity has high interconnectedness with personal relevance. In other words, individuals who are willing to participate in social activities through social media show a personal interest in other users (Hollebeek 2011). In this way, users who consume objects are doing so because of a personal interest that emerges from their personal goals, values, and self-concept (Van Doorn et al 2010). Therefore, social exchange theory can be used to understand the personal goals values and self-concepts that are attached to the creation, consumption, and distribution of UGC over social media. In addition, socialisation theory could also help to inform how different social media users participate in exchanging UGC on social media towards later brand engagement.

2.12 SUMMARY

As indicated in the second research objective, SET can help in identifying how the content characteristics of UGC impact brand engagement. Consumers tend to exchange UGC with certain characteristics – informativeness, entertainment, and credibility. If users perceive these characteristics as benefits, they are more likely to engage with the brand, validating SET's principle of maximising rewards. The third research objective - investigating the impact of

online incivility in the form of negative UGC on brand engagement - can also be examined within the purview of SET. Negative UGC could be seen as a 'cost' which might impact the engagement if users feel that their interactions invite negativity or result in unpleasant experiences. This aspect can trigger a re-evaluation of the cost-benefit equation, and if the costs are perceived to be higher than the benefits, users may disengage, in line with the assumptions of SET.

Moreover, SET provides a framework to analyse the effects of cultural and societal values within an Islamic banking context, as mentioned in the first research objective. Users in this specific cultural context might have unique perceptions of the costs and benefits of engaging with Islamic banking brands on social media. For example, if creating and sharing UGC aligned with Islamic values results in societal approval (a social benefit), users may be more motivated to engage, a dynamic that can be understood through the lens of SET. In addition, SET can provide insight into why certain UGC results in higher levels of engagement. As people engage in exchanges that yield the highest rewards at the lowest cost, content that provides valuable information or elicits positive emotions could be more engaging for users. On the other hand, content that requires high cognitive effort to understand or elicits negative emotions could be less engaging.

Overall, the application of SET in this research provides a strong theoretical basis for examining how and why users generate content and engage with brands on social media platforms. It can help in gaining a deeper understanding of the complex dynamics involved in UGC and consumer-brand engagement in the unique context of Islamic banks in Pakistan. It can further provide valuable insights into how these banks can leverage UGC to enhance their engagement strategies and cultivate strong, positive relationships with their customers. By contributing to the body of knowledge on SET, this research can also inspire future studies on similar topics, thus extending the applicability and relevance of the theory.

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The previous chapter conceptualized UGC and brand engagement. It also evaluated factors related to Social Media Networks (SMNs) which play a role in influencing Social Media Users (SMUs) and thereby create brand engagement. Moreover, the previous chapter also discussed the impact of UGC on brand engagement since UGC is created, shared, and exchanged by SMUs in their interactions with each other on SMNs. This also necessitated considering the different types of interactions that take place on SMNs resulting in brand engagement. Thus, the key area of focus in the current research is developing a theoretical framework of brand engagement with Islamic banks because of UGC creation, and the sharing and exchange on SMNs by SMUs. This chapter therefore discusses the methodological choices exercised by the researcher to realize these objectives. Since the key area of focus is the development of a theoretical framework exploratory research and methodological choices were exercised accordingly.

3.1 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY

Positivism and social constructionism constitute two primary epistemological stances in research methodology. Each is characterised by unique perspectives regarding the nature of knowledge, and the best ways to acquire it (Hammond, Wellington, & Francis, 2021). Positivism is rooted in a natural science approach to knowledge generation, espousing that only observable and measurable phenomena can be considered ‘real’ and factual. The empirical world’s objective reality is a key tenet, suggesting that facts can be known with certainty through methods like observation and experimentation (Denscombe, 2021). Positivism supports a deductive approach where theory is evaluated through the collection of empirical evidence, emphasizing quantitative methodologies (Jonathan Lazar, Feng, & Hong, 2017). This philosophical stance sees researchers as detached and neutral observers, unbiased by their values and beliefs. Thus, through the lens of positivism, researcher, and research subject are distinctly separate, and the latter can be studied objectively, akin to natural science experiments (Schwartz-Shea & Yanow, 2013).

In contrast, social constructionism suggests that reality is not ‘discovered’ but constructed and interpreted through human experience and interaction. Knowledge is thus subjective and context-dependent, with an emphasis on understanding the social world from the individual's

perspective (Neale, 2020). This standpoint often utilizes qualitative methods such as interviews and observations, focusing on interpreting meaning rather than establishing hard facts (Sloan & Quan-Haase, 2017). Social constructionists embrace the idea that researchers are inevitably part of what they study, and their interpretations are influenced by their background and positionality (Walliman, 2022). The differentiation between these two stances becomes clearer when considering the contrasting ways, they approach the understanding of social phenomena. While positivists see social phenomena as objective entities existing independently of individuals' perceptions, social constructionists perceive them as humanly created and understood through individual and shared interpretations (Tashakkori, Johnson, & Teddlie, 2021).

For instance, a positivist studying gender in an organization might rely on measurable indicators such as the ratio of men to women in leadership roles (Hair et al., 2019). A social constructionist, on the other hand, may explore the lived experiences of individuals in the organization, seeking to understand how they construct and interpret gender through their interactions and experiences (Jenss, 2016). In sum, the distinction between positivism and social constructionism is a testament to the diversity of epistemological perspectives in research. Each stance has its strengths and weaknesses, and the choice between them often depends on the research question and context (Beins, 2019). Recognizing the differences helps researchers to understand the philosophies that guide different research designs, leading to more effective and informed research (Cassell, Cunliffe, & Grandy, 2018).

Given the context-specific and deeply interpretive nature of the current research aim and objectives, a social constructionist approach is deemed the most suitable. This approach is premised on the belief that reality is constructed through human experiences and interpretations, which fits the subjective and context-dependent focus of this research project (Neale, 2020).

The main research aim – developing a comprehensive and contextual framework to understand and enhance the role and impact of user-generated content on brand engagement in Islamic banking within the Pakistani cultural and societal milieu – requires an in-depth understanding of individual and shared perceptions. The cultural and societal dimensions necessitate an interpretive, subjective, and context-specific approach that aligns with social constructionism (Sloan & Quan-Haase, 2017).

The first objective, examining how cultural and societal values within an Islamic banking context in Pakistan influences UGC and subsequent brand engagement, suggests a focus on people's interpretations and constructions of their experiences (Denscombe, 2021). From a social constructionist viewpoint, societal values are not viewed as objective entities but are perceived and interpreted by individuals in unique ways, influencing their behaviour, including their engagement with user-generated content and brands (Schwartz-Shea & Yanow, 2013).

Objective two, identifying how the content characteristics of user-generated content impact brand engagement in the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan, further justifies the selection of a social constructionist approach. Social constructionism promotes the understanding that content characteristics and their impact on brand engagement are subjectively constructed, contingent on individuals' interpretations and shared meanings within the Islamic banking context (Tashakkori, Johnson, & Teddlie, 2021). This context-driven understanding is vital to developing nuanced insights into user-generated content's influence on brand engagement.

The third objective, investigating the impact of online incivility in the form of negative user-generated content on brand engagement within the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan, also aligns with social constructionism. This objective explores a complex phenomenon – online incivility – which is inherently subjective and context-dependent. What is considered civil or uncivil can vary dramatically based on cultural norms and individual perspectives (Beins, 2019). By applying social constructionism, this research can delve into the complexities of online incivility to understand how it is constructed and interpreted within the specific context of Islamic banking in Pakistan.

By adopting a social constructionist epistemological stance, this study acknowledges that knowledge about UGC and brand engagement in Islamic banks within the Pakistani cultural context is socially constructed. This approach allows for a rich, nuanced understanding of the phenomena, recognizing the subjectivity and complexity of individuals' experiences, interpretations, and interactions (Walliman, 2022). As such, social constructionism provides the theoretical grounding for a holistic, context-driven investigation, contributing to the nuanced understanding and effective addressing of the research aim and objectives.

3.2 RESEARCH DESIGN

Research design plays a fundamental role in structuring and guiding a research project, shaping the collection, analysis, and interpretation of data. Two prominent research designs are

explanatory and exploratory, each with its unique features, strengths, and purposes (Walliman, 2022).

Explanatory research, often associated with quantitative methods, seeks to provide a clear, concise understanding of phenomena by identifying and investigating causal relationships and underlying mechanisms (Denscombe, 2021). It aims to answer 'why' and 'how' questions by examining the interconnections between variables, and by analysing patterns of association or causality between them (Neale, 2020). For instance, an explanatory study might investigate how factors like income and education level influence one's likelihood to engage with a particular brand. This design is advantageous in its capacity to offer clear, quantifiable insights and establish the degree and direction of relationships between variables. It is valuable for hypothesis testing and predictive modeling (Schwartz-Shea & Yanow, 2013). In contrast, exploratory research often associated with qualitative methods, primarily aims to explore, describe, and gain a nuanced understanding of the research context or phenomena (Hammond, Wellington, & Francis, 2021). It is more appropriate when the research issue is unknown or poorly understood, allowing for open-ended, inductive investigation to generate insights and formulate new hypotheses (Sloan & Quan-Haase, 2017). An exploratory study might delve into consumers' experiences and perceptions of a brand, examining their narratives to understand their brand engagement's underlying dynamics. Exploratory research excels at providing rich, context-specific insights and uncovering unexpected aspects, paving the way for subsequent research (Tashakkori, Johnson, & Teddlie, 2021).

Notably, these two designs are not mutually exclusive; they can complement each other in mixed-methods research, enabling researchers to capitalize on the strengths of both (Poth, 2018). For instance, an initial exploratory phase could generate hypotheses that an ensuing explanatory phase goes on to test, providing both in-depth, context-specific insights and clear, quantifiable results. This, combined approach can facilitate a more holistic, robust understanding of the research issue (Hair, Page, Brunsveld, & Francis, 2019). While the choice between these designs depends on various factors such as research questions, objectives, available resources, and the researcher's epistemological stance, both designs have unique strengths that can contribute significantly to the research process (Denscombe, 2021). Exploratory research can facilitate deep, context-specific understanding, and hypothesis generation, while explanatory research can provide clear, quantifiable results, supporting hypothesis testing and predictive modeling (Beins, 2019). In conclusion, both designs are

instrumental tools in the researcher's arsenal, facilitating nuanced inquiry and rigorous investigation into complex social phenomena (Walliman, 2022).

The selection of an exploratory research design for this study stems from the intricate nature of the research aim and objectives that revolve around the cultural, social, and UGC aspects of Islamic banking in Pakistan. At its core, the research aim requires the development of a contextual framework to comprehend and amplify the impact of UGC on brand engagement within an Islamic banking context, focusing specifically on the Pakistani cultural and societal milieu (Neergaard & Ulhoi, 2007). The inherent dynamism and cultural specificity involved in this research aim make an exploratory design appropriate, primarily because it is designed to manage ambiguous, novel, and less-understood research contexts (Sloan & Quan-Haase, 2017). The inherent flexibility of this design allows for in-depth, nuanced insights to emerge that are necessary for understanding complex social phenomena (Walliman, 2022).

The first research objective—to examine the influence of cultural and societal values on user-generated content and brand engagement—echoes the need for exploratory research. The cultural and societal values within the Pakistani Islamic banking context are intricate and multi-layered, requiring an in-depth and open-ended investigation to uncover their nuanced influence (Schwartz-Shea & Yanow, 2013). An exploratory design supports this process, enabling the study to delve deep into the underlying dynamics to bring forth insights not immediately apparent using a more structured research design (Hammond, Wellington, & Francis, 2021). The second objective—to identify how the content characteristics of UGC impact brand engagement—also aligns with the exploratory design. The relationship between content characteristics and brand engagement is complex and may vary based on specific contextual factors, which an exploratory design can adeptly manage (Tashakkori, Johnson, & Teddlie, 2021). This approach allows researchers to delve into users' perceptions and experiences, providing rich insights into the dynamics of content and engagement (Denscombe, 2021).

Finally, the third objective—to investigate the impact of online incivility on brand engagement—requires a research design that can navigate the delicate and potentially volatile dynamics of negative UGC. The exploratory design can provide the flexibility needed to address sensitive and contentious issues, facilitating an understanding of how and why users engage in online incivility and its influence on brand engagement (Beins, 2019). An exploratory approach has been chosen for this study due to its flexibility and adaptability, its potential for in-depth, nuanced inquiry, and its ability to manage complex, ambiguous, and

novel research contexts. These features align with the focus of this research on the intricate, context-specific dynamics of UGC and brand engagement within the cultural and societal milieu of Pakistani Islamic banking (Poth, 2018). This choice ultimately sets out to ensure the study's rigor, depth, and relevance, facilitating the development of a robust, insightful, and contextually informed framework for understanding and enhancing the role and impact of UGC on brand engagement (Hair, Page, Brunsveld, & Francis, 2019). The inductive and deductive research approaches constitute two core pillars of research methodology, each offering unique methods for theory development and testing (Arthur, Waring, & Coe, 2012). However, these approaches are distinct in their structure, process, and application, leading to differing implications for knowledge generation.

3.3 CASE STUDY RESEARCH DESIGN.

Yin (2009) highlighted five key characteristics of case study research design which are: unit of analysis, research questions, aim of the study, linking data and propositions logically together, and setting the criteria for the interpretation of results. A case study design is useful for answering questions such as *how* and *why*, i.e., exploratory questions. Such questions dig deeper into the phenomenon. For example, the current study looks at why SMUs create UGC about Islamic banks, and how they are influenced to do so to create social brand- and consumer brand engagement.

3.4 RESEARCH STRATEGY

The primary purpose of this research is to conceptualize the concept of UGC and consumer brand engagement in the context of social media networks connected to Islamic banking in Pakistan. To fulfill this broad aim, the research pursues three objectives. These objectives examine the influence of cultural and societal values on UGC and brand engagement, the impact of UGC characteristics on brand engagement, and the effect of negative UGC on brand engagement. These objectives inherently imply a wider research scope that necessitates a multi-case study approach.

A single case study typically focuses on an individual entity to gain an in-depth understanding of a particular situation or issue (Yin, 2003). While this approach can yield detailed insights, its applicability is limited when the research aims to explore a broader perspective involving several elements and units of study. It provides a microscopic view of a phenomenon which, while thorough and in-depth, might not capture the wider context or variances that exist in

different situations or entities. In contrast, a multi-case study explores several instances related to the research topic, providing a more comprehensive understanding (Yin, 2003). This approach suits research involving complex interactions among multiple variables and multiple units of research, as is the case in the current study. The multi-case approach not only facilitates the capturing of common patterns across cases, but also highlights the uniqueness and variability amongst cases, providing a richer context to the phenomenon under study (Baxter & Jack, 2008).

Considering the first research objective, it is apparent that these values could vary across different regions, communities, and Islamic banks. A single case study would fail to capture these variations and their influence on UGC and brand engagement, thereby limiting the scope of the findings. Conversely, a multi-case study would facilitate an exploration of these variations across different Islamic banks and how they influence UGC and brand engagement, thus providing more holistic insights (Eisenhardt & Graebner, 2007). The second and third objectives, which explore how UGC characteristics and negative UGC impact brand engagement, also necessitate a multi-case approach. Islamic banks employ different strategies in terms of managing UGC, which could influence its characteristics and the level of negative content generated. The impact of these variables on brand engagement could also vary across banks. A single case study would provide a limited understanding of these aspects due to the confined context. A multi-case study, however, would capture the variations across different banks, providing a more comprehensive understanding of how UGC characteristics and negative UGC impact brand engagement in different contexts (Stake, 2006).

Furthermore, the multi-case study approach aligns well with the social exchange theory applied in this research to study UGC's impact on social media users (Homans, 1958). This theory posits that social behaviour results from an exchange process aiming to maximize benefits and minimize costs. Studying multiple cases would provide a broader view of the exchange dynamics between Islamic banks and their customers, as each bank might offer different benefits and costs that influence UGC and brand engagement. Considering the broad aim of this research, its multiple objectives and the complexity of the context as well as the various units of study, a multi-case study approach is deemed most suitable for this research. This approach will enable a comprehensive exploration and understanding of UGC and consumer-brand engagement within the context of Islamic banking in Pakistan, thereby effectively fulfilling the study's aim and objectives (Yin, 2003).

3.5 RESEARCH APPROACH

An inductive approach to research commences with data collection followed by analysis, which then leads to the formulation of theory (Neale, 2020). It is an approach that starts with the observation of specific instances or phenomena and culminates in the development of general conclusions or theories (Cassell, Cunliffe, & Grandy, 2018). It is exploratory in nature, used when little is known about the topic at hand or when a new perspective on a familiar topic is sought (Sloan & Quan-Haase, 2017). As such, it fosters the generation of new theories by allowing the data to guide the research process (Grønmo, 2020). On the other hand, the deductive approach starts with an existing theory or hypothesis and then evaluates it using data (Hammond, Wellington, & Francis, 2021). It is an approach that works from the "top-down", starting with a theoretical premise that is then evaluated through observation or experiment (Poth, 2018). It is used when the goal is to evaluate a theory, a proposition, or a hypothesis that has been developed from previous research or theoretical frameworks (Jonathan Lazar, Feng, & Hochheiser, 2017).

The major difference between the two approaches lies in the direction of reasoning. Inductive reasoning moves from specific observations to broader generalizations and theories, while deductive reasoning moves from generalized theories to specific observations or predictions (Hair, Page, Brunsveld, & Francis, 2019). Furthermore, the inductive approach is more flexible as it allows for the research questions to evolve as the research progresses (Matthews & Ross, 2010). Conversely, the deductive approach is more rigid and highly structured, with research questions predefined before data collection (Denscombe, 2021).

The choice between these two approaches depends on the nature of the research question, the stage of the research, the resources available, and the philosophical underpinnings of the researcher. For instance, if the aim is to explore a new area where little research has been conducted, an inductive approach might be more appropriate. On the other hand, if the objective is to evaluate a theory in a new context or with different variables, a deductive approach would be more suitable (Walliman, 2022). In sum, both the inductive and deductive approaches are critical to the progress of research across various disciplines. While they differ significantly in their processes and applications, the choice between them depends on the nature and objectives of the study (Schwartz-Shea & Yanow, 2013). Hence, understanding their strengths, limitations, and appropriate applications is crucial for effective and meaningful research.

The inductive research approach selected for this research is well-aligned with both the social constructionism paradigm and the exploratory research design due to the overlap in philosophical underpinnings and research methodologies. Social constructionism is a philosophical paradigm that asserts that knowledge and reality are socially constructed and heavily influenced by cultural and societal contexts (Crotty, 2011). It emphasizes the importance of social interactions, language, culture, and history in understanding phenomena, recognizing that reality is not objective, but rather constructed through human interactions and interpretations (Berger & Luckmann, 1991). Therefore, it supports a deep exploration of the contextual and subjective nature of human experiences.

The inductive approach complements social constructionism by facilitating an exploration of these social realities without the imposition of pre-conceived theories or models. The inductive approach allows researchers to enter the field with an open mind, observing, exploring, and interpreting phenomena in their natural settings, and then constructing theories based on these observations (Alvesson & Sköldbberg, 2017). The bottom-up nature of the inductive approach aligns with the social constructionist view that knowledge is generated through human interactions and experiences, resulting in a rich, contextual understanding of the phenomena being studied (Bryman, 2012). Moreover, the inductive approach is not only compatible with the social constructionism paradigm but also well-suited to exploratory research design. Exploratory research aims to investigate unknown areas or to gain new insights about a topic (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2019). This approach is characterized by flexibility, open-endedness, and a focus on discovering new insights that can lead to the formulation of new hypotheses and theories (Blumberg, Cooper, & Schindler, 2018).

Similarly, the inductive approach starts with a broad field of research and narrows it down to specific, emergent themes and concepts, eventually leading to theory development (Thomas, 2006). It aligns with the flexibility of exploratory research, allowing for changes in the direction of research based on what is discovered during the data collection and analysis process. This flexibility is crucial in exploratory research as it aids in the unearthing of nuances and complexities within the research topic (Goddard & Melville, 2004).

Furthermore, the focus on context using inductive approaches is particularly relevant to exploratory research. By not assuming an existing theoretical framework from the outset, the inductive approach enables a deep exploration of phenomena in their natural, complex, and multifaceted contexts (Eisenhardt, 1989). This approach resonates with the exploratory

research design, which seeks to gain a deep, contextualized understanding of the research topic (Yin, 2017). In conclusion, the inductive research approach aligns well with social constructionism and exploratory research design due to its bottom-up approach to knowledge construction, flexibility, and emphasis on context. This alignment enables a comprehensive understanding of the research topic – the role and impact of user-generated content on brand engagement within the Islamic banking context in Pakistan – grounded in the social and cultural realities of the participants and the broader societal milieu. The inductive approach fosters the exploration of these complex social phenomena in a way that aligns with the social constructionist perspective and is well-suited to the open-ended and flexible nature of exploratory research (Flick, 2018; Silverman, 2017).

3.6 RESEARCH METHODS

Research in the social sciences often employs one of three primary methods: quantitative, qualitative, or mixed methods, each offering distinct advantages and perspectives on data collection and analysis (Arthur, Waring, & Coe, 2012).

Quantitative research, often associated with the positivist paradigm, involves the systematic collection and interpretation of numerical data, typically using statistical methods. It seeks to identify patterns, evaluate hypotheses, and establish generalizable findings, focusing on the measurement of variables and the relationships between them (Balnaves & Caputi, 2001). Quantitative research often involves surveys, experiments, and other structured forms of data collection that yield numerical data. The strength of this method lies in its ability to provide quantifiable evidence and generalize results from a sample to a larger population (Matthews & Ross, 2010; Martin & Bridgmon, 2012).

In contrast, qualitative research is grounded in the interpretivist paradigm, and primarily focuses on understanding the social world from the perspective of participants. Rather than reducing the phenomena to measurable variables, qualitative research seeks to explore phenomena in their natural settings, focusing on understanding meanings, experiences, and human behaviors (Berg, 2006; Neergaard & Ulhøi, 2007). Data collection methods typically include interviews, focus groups, observations, and document analysis. The strength of qualitative research lies in its ability to provide in-depth, rich, and complex descriptions of phenomena and to capture the intricacies of individual experiences and social processes (Taylor, Bogdan, & DeVault, 2016).

Mixed methods research integrates quantitative and qualitative approaches to answer research questions that cannot be adequately addressed by either approach alone (Tashakkori, Johnson, & Teddlie, 2021). It combines the strengths of both qualitative and quantitative methods, allowing for the exploration of complex research questions, testing, and building theories, and seeking convergence and corroboration of results (Creamer & Francis, 2022; Poth, 2018). The mixed-methods approach can be particularly beneficial when it comes to providing a more comprehensive understanding of research problems by facilitating triangulation, complementarity, development, initiation, and the expansion of research findings (Hair, Joseph, Page, Brunsveld, & Francis, 2019).

It is crucial to note that the choice between quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods research is not about superiority, but rather about the appropriateness of each of these given the research question, aim, and objectives (Denscombe, 2021). Furthermore, the choice should consider practical issues, such as resources, skills, and time, as well as ethical considerations. As suggested by Walliman (2021), it is the researcher's responsibility to carefully consider the strengths and weaknesses of each approach, and to make an informed decision on the most suitable methodology for their research project.

In short, quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods research provide different paths to understanding phenomena. The quantitative approach offers a means to quantify data and generalize results from the sample to the population of interest. In contrast, the qualitative approach provides a deep understanding of complex phenomena through detailed, rich narrative descriptions. On the other hand, mixed methods research combines the strengths of both methods, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the research problem (Hammond, Wellington, & Francis, 2021; Grønmo, 2020). Therefore, the choice between these methods should align with the nature of the research question, objectives, the philosophical paradigm, and practical considerations.

The choice of a qualitative research method for this study is shaped by the nature of the research aim and objectives, which necessitate an in-depth understanding of the impact of UGC on brand engagement in the specific context of Islamic banking in Pakistan. The decision aligns with the characteristics and strengths of qualitative research, namely, its emphasis on understanding the meaning people assign to phenomena within their social contexts, and its focus on studying phenomena in their natural settings (Neergaard & Ulhoi, 2007).

The first research objective, which seeks to examine how cultural and societal values within an Islamic banking context influence UGC and brand engagement, underscores the need for a qualitative approach. Exploring cultural and societal values and their influence necessitates delving into subjective experiences, beliefs, and perceptions - a realm where qualitative research excels. Qualitative research is inherently interpretive and emphasizes understanding the social world from the perspective of the participants (Berg, 2006). Hence, it will facilitate an in-depth exploration of how cultural and societal values, as perceived and interpreted by the stakeholders, shape UGC and brand engagement.

The second objective aims to identify the content characteristics UGC that impact brand engagement within the Islamic banking context in Pakistan. Qualitative research, with its focus on detailed, rich descriptions of phenomena, will allow for the in-depth analysis of user-generated content and its various characteristics (Taylor, Bogdan, & DeVault, 2016). It provides the tools for a nuanced understanding of content, its meaning, and its influence on brand engagement, by facilitating an analysis of the language, symbols, narratives, and themes within the content.

The third objective is to investigate the impact of online incivility in the form of negative user-generated content on brand engagement. Negative UGC and online incivility, being complex and multifaceted phenomena, are best explored through a qualitative lens. The interpretative nature of qualitative research allows the study to go beyond merely recording instances of negative content and online incivility, to interpreting their meanings, understanding their roots, and exploring their impact on brand engagement. This can be achieved through qualitative content analysis, in-depth interviews, or online observations.

Moreover, the overall research aim to develop a comprehensive and contextual framework underlines the suitability of a qualitative approach. Framework development typically necessitates an in-depth understanding of the phenomena of interest and their interrelationships within a specific context (Neale, 2020). Qualitative research, with its ability to provide rich, contextual, and nuanced insights, is therefore appropriate for developing such a framework (Neale, 2020).

The choice of a qualitative approach aligns with the need to understand the human perspective in the specific cultural context of Pakistan. It provides the necessary tools to understand and interpret the complexity of social interactions, cultural norms, and subjective experiences that surround UGC and brand engagement in the Islamic banking context (Bourgeault, De Vries, &

Dingwall, 2010). Hence, it enables the researcher to address the research questions holistically and contextually, enhancing the validity and depth of the findings (Dawson, 2009).

In short, qualitative research methods have been chosen to better understand the social phenomena in question their natural settings. Such an approach is useful for interpreting human behaviours and experiences, and providing rich, in-depth, and contextual data. These characteristics make it particularly suited to achieving the research aim and objectives of this study. The method aligns with the need to understand complex social phenomena from the perspective of those experiencing them, and for a contextual understanding to be formed within the specific milieu of Islamic banking in Pakistan. The choice of qualitative research methods for this study aligns naturally with the philosophical stance of social constructionism, an inductive research approach, and an exploratory research design, each of which contributes to the comprehensive and contextual exploration of the role and impact of UGC on brand engagement in Islamic banking within Pakistan.

Social constructionism emphasizes that our understanding of the world is built through social interactions and cultural contexts, rather than pre-existing objective truths (Schwartz-Shea & Yanow, 2013). Given the research aim and objectives, this study hinges on an understanding of the complex social dynamics at play in UGC and brand engagement, influenced by cultural and societal values within Pakistan's Islamic banking context. Qualitative research methods, with their emphasis on exploring and understanding participants' experiences, perceptions, and interpretations, are well-aligned with social constructionism. These methods can generate rich, detailed data on how participants construct their social reality within the specific context of the study (Beins, 2019), addressing objectives such as examining cultural and societal values' influence on UGC and brand engagement.

An inductive research approach, which involves generating theories or patterns based on observed data, complements qualitative research methods (Walliman, 2021). By gathering data from user interactions, customer reviews, and online discussions, qualitative methods can identify emergent patterns or themes relevant to UGC and brand engagement. The focus on open-ended exploration and understanding, rather than testing pre-established hypotheses, is inherently inductive. This approach is particularly effective when it comes to addressing research objectives such as identifying content characteristics impacting brand engagement and investigating the impact of online incivility on brand engagement.

Exploratory research designs align with qualitative research methods by focusing on exploring a research problem with little prior understanding (Neale, 2020). Given the emergent nature of UGC and its impacts, an exploratory design is suitable for delving into this uncharted terrain. Qualitative methods enable the collection and analysis of rich, in-depth data to shed light on the research problem from multiple perspectives (Cassell, Cunliffe, & Grandy, 2018), thus allowing for a detailed exploration of the subject matter. The exploratory nature of the research also permits flexibility and adaptability to ensure the study's relevance and rigor. In sum, the selection of qualitative research methods for this study aligns seamlessly with the theoretical orientation of social constructionism, an inductive research approach, and an exploratory research design. These elements work in harmony to facilitate a deep, nuanced understanding of the role and impact of UGC on brand engagement within Pakistan's Islamic banking context, effectively addressing the outlined research aim and objectives.

3.7 DATA COLLECTION TOOLS

Qualitative research methods provide ways to capture and interpret the complexities of human behaviour, emotions, attitudes, and beliefs in a context-specific setting. This section discusses some common qualitative data collection tools, specifically interviews, observations, focus groups, and document analysis which are considered as candidate methods for this study.

Interviews: Interviews, a cornerstone of qualitative research, offer a way to gather detailed data by directly engaging with participants. These can be structured, semi-structured, or unstructured, with the latter two allowing for greater exploration of a participant's experiences and perspectives (Taylor, Bogdan, & DeVault, 2016). Interviews enable researchers to delve deeper into the complexities of individuals' interpretations, feelings, and values. These are vital for our understanding of UGC and brand engagement in the Pakistani Islamic banking context. As per Walliman (2021), interviews can explore the underpinnings of a participant's behaviour and their nuanced understandings, which might remain inaccessible with other methods.

Observations: Observations provide an in-depth understanding of people's behaviors and interactions within their natural setting (Hammond, Wellington, & Francis, 2021). They can be participant or non-participant, the former allowing the researcher to immerse themselves in the context being studied. For example, in the context of UGC and brand engagement, observations of user interactions and exchanges in online forums might reveal valuable insights. Jonathan Lazar, Jinjuan Heidi Feng (2017) in their book on Human-Computer Interaction Research

Methods elaborate on digital ethnography, a form of observation, which could be particularly useful for exploring online user-generated content and interactions.

Focus Groups: Focus groups are another common qualitative data collection method where a small number of people are gathered to discuss a particular topic (Denscombe, 2021). The interaction between group members can generate rich data and provide insights into people's shared experiences and perspectives. This method can be effective in understanding cultural and societal values within the Islamic banking context in Pakistan, and their influence on UGC. Sloan and Quan-Haase (2017) in their handbook on social media research methods highlight the utility of online focus groups, particularly relevant in the current digital era.

Document Analysis: Document analysis involves the systematic review of existing materials - physical or digital - that provide context or insight into the phenomenon under study (Bowen, 2009). In the context of the current research, these could include UGC in the form of online reviews, comments, or social media posts. Document analysis can complement other methods by providing additional insights or helping to triangulate data from different sources (Neale, 2020).

Each of these qualitative data collection tools provides unique avenues for exploration and understanding, facilitating a comprehensive and contextual exploration of UGC and brand engagement in the Pakistani Islamic banking context. The choice between these methods depends on the research question, the context, and practical considerations (Hair, Page, Brunsveld, & Francis, 2019). Qualitative research methods provide tools that allow for a rich, detailed, and context-specific exploration of the phenomenon under study. Through interviews, observations, focus groups, and document analysis, researchers can gather and interpret data that delve deeper into the human experiences and social dynamics at play. Each method brings a unique set of strengths, and a combination of methods can often provide the most comprehensive understanding of the research topic.

3.7.1 Semi structured interviews

The adoption of semi-structured interviews with customers who use social media in Pakistan aligns inherently with the objectives of this research. This method has been chosen for its flexible, in-depth nature, and its ability to explore the lived experiences of the participants. The following section provides a detailed rationale for choosing semi-structured interviews to achieve the research aim and objectives.

1. Facilitating Comprehensive Exploration

Semi-structured interviews allow for a comprehensive exploration of the topic at hand. Unlike structured interviews, they do not limit participants to pre-determined responses, but encourage them to express their views freely (Taylor, Bogdan, & DeVault, 2016). This flexibility makes them particularly useful for addressing the first research objective, which involves exploring the complex interplay between cultural and societal values and user-generated content in the Pakistani Islamic banking context. By enabling the researcher to probe into topics as they emerge, semi-structured interviews can capture the nuanced ways in which these values shape online discourse and brand engagement.

2. Access to User Perspectives and Emotions

The in-depth nature of semi-structured interviews is critical for achieving the second research objective, which requires understanding how content characteristics impact brand engagement. By asking users directly about their reactions to different types of content, researchers can uncover insights into what drives user engagement. This method can elicit emotional responses and personal experiences, which can provide richer data than quantitative approaches such as surveys or metrics analysis. Semi-structured interviews also allow for follow-up questions and clarifications, ensuring a thorough understanding of users' perspectives (Denscombe, 2021).

3. Examination of Negative Experiences

The third objective, exploring the impact of online incivility, can be particularly challenging to address using methods like observations or document analysis alone. Negative online interactions can be subtle, nuanced, and context-dependent, making them difficult to interpret without input from the users involved. Semi-structured interviews allow for in-depth exploration of these experiences. By asking users about their experiences with incivility, the researcher can understand its impact on brand engagement and identify potential strategies to mitigate its effects (Walliman, 2021).

4. Contextual Relevance

Semi-structured interviews are particularly suited to this research because they are sensitive to context. Considering that this research aims to develop a framework for the Pakistani cultural and societal milieu, it is crucial to capture the unique experiences of social media users within this context. Through semi-structured interviews, researchers can delve into the local cultural norms, practices, and societal values that shape UGC and brand engagement in Pakistan's Islamic banking sector (Hammond, Wellington, & Francis, 2021).

5. Flexibility and Adaptability

Semi-structured interviews offer flexibility and adaptability. The researcher has the flexibility to probe more deeply into interesting or unexpected areas that arise during the interview and adapt the line of questioning according to each participant's responses. This flexibility allows the researcher to uncover rich, detailed, and unexpected insights, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of the research topic (Hair, Joseph F., Page, Brunsveld, & Francis, 2019).

In conclusion, semi-structured interviews were chosen for this research due to their ability to facilitate a comprehensive and in-depth exploration of the research topic and because of their sensitivity to context, and their flexibility. These strengths make them particularly suited to exploring the complex relationships between UGC, cultural and societal values, and brand engagement in the Pakistani Islamic banking context.

Utilizing semi-structured interviews within this research aligns coherently with the selected theoretical and methodological frameworks of social constructionism, an inductive research approach, and an exploratory research design. The following discussion provides a comprehensive justification for the alignment of semi-structured interviews with these elements.

Alignment with Social Constructionism: Social constructionism posits that our understanding and interpretation of the world is constructed through our social interactions and shared experiences (Schwartz-Shea & Yanow, 2012). It emphasizes the subjective experiences and perceptions of individuals. Semi-structured interviews are an ideal tool within this theoretical framework, as they allow for an exploration of individuals' subjective experiences and perceptions. Specifically, this method will provide insights into how Pakistani users perceive the role of UGC in shaping brand engagement in the Islamic banking context, addressing the first and second research objectives. It also allows for a deeper understanding of how cultural and societal values might influence these perceptions, thus aligning with social constructionism's focus on the socially constructed nature of reality.

Alignment with Inductive Research Approach: An inductive research approach involves building theory from data, emphasizing the generation of new insights, and understanding (Tashakkori, Johnson, & Teddlie, 2021). Semi-structured interviews are well-aligned with this approach as they yield rich, detailed data that can be analysed to identify patterns, themes, and categories. The data gathered from these interviews can be used to construct an understanding

of how cultural and societal values influence UGC and brand engagement in the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan, addressing the third research objective. The flexibility inherent in semi-structured interviews allows the researcher to remain open to new findings and ideas, aligning with the emergent nature of the inductive approach.

Alignment with Exploratory Research Design: Exploratory research design aims to explore an unknown field to gain new insights and understanding (Walliman, 2021). Given that the role and impact of UGC on brand engagement within the cultural and societal context of Pakistan's Islamic banking sector are under-explored, semi-structured interviews align with the exploratory design. They provide an opportunity for participants to express their views freely, potentially revealing unanticipated insights into the ways online incivility impacts brand engagement, thus addressing the fourth research objective. The open-ended nature of semi-structured interviews enables researchers to explore the topic in-depth and from various angles, ensuring a comprehensive exploration of the research topic.

In conclusion, semi-structured interviews align with social constructionism, an inductive research approach, and an exploratory research design, primarily due to their ability to capture subjective experiences and socially constructed realities, their capacity to generate rich data for theory development, and their suitability for in-depth exploration of under-studied phenomena. These strengths make them an appropriate method for achieving the research aim and objectives. By providing an in-depth understanding of users' perspectives within their social and cultural contexts, semi-structured interviews will facilitate the development of a comprehensive and contextual framework to understand and enhance the role and impact of UGC on brand engagement in Islamic banking within the Pakistani milieu.

3.7.2 Selection of the participants

The process of selecting research participants is a critical aspect of any study. The selection of participants often depends on the research question, the research methodology, and the context in which the research is being conducted. Given that the focus of this study is on understanding and enhancing the role and impact of UGC on brand engagement in Islamic banking within the Pakistani cultural and societal milieu, the participants were selected accordingly. A justification for the selection of participants from Pakistan to take part in interviews is provided below.

The research aims to understand the impact of UGC on brand engagement in the context of Islamic banking in Pakistan. Therefore, it is crucial to select participants who are familiar with

this context. Participants in Pakistan, especially those who have experience with Islamic banking and use social media, are best positioned to provide insights into how cultural and societal values influence UGC and its subsequent impact on brand engagement (Objective 4). They are immersed in the cultural and societal milieu that the research aims to understand, thereby bringing a lived perspective that enhances the validity of the study (Denscombe, 2021).

Pakistan's diverse cultural and societal landscape provides a rich array of perspectives on the role and impact of UGC on brand engagement in Islamic banking. The participants were selected in a manner that captured this diversity. The selection of participants involved consideration of factors such as their geographic location within Pakistan, their socioeconomic status, their religious and cultural backgrounds, and their level of engagement with Islamic banking and social media. This diversity is crucial for capturing a comprehensive understanding of the phenomena under investigation (Objective 5) (Schwartz-Shea & Yanow, 2012).

The study employs a qualitative methodology using semi-structured interviews, which is well-suited for gaining an in-depth understanding of participants' experiences and perspectives. Semi-structured interviews enable the exploration of complex issues such as the impact of online incivility in the form of negative UGC on brand engagement (Objective 6). By selecting participants who are active in using social media and engaging with Islamic banking in Pakistan, it was possible to probe into these complex dynamics and uncover nuanced insights that might be less accessible with other participant profiles (Sloan & Quan-Haase, 2017).

The exploratory research design that was applied aligns well with the selection of participants. Given the exploratory nature of the study, it is necessary to engage with participants who can contribute rich, detailed, and novel insights into the phenomenon under study (Walliman, 2021). The participants from Pakistan, with their direct experience of the issues under investigation, were able to offer these insights, contributing to a comprehensive and contextual understanding of the role and impact of UGC on brand engagement in the Islamic banking context.

In summary, the selection of participants from Pakistan for this research is justified on multiple grounds. These include the necessity to understand the unique cultural and societal context, the importance of capturing diverse perspectives, the potential for gaining in-depth insights, and the alignment with the research's exploratory design. Together, these factors make the chosen participant selection not only appropriate but also crucial for achieving the research aim and

objectives. Through the lived experiences and insights of the participants, it was possible to develop a comprehensive and contextual framework for understanding the complex dynamics of UGC and brand engagement within the Pakistani Islamic banking sector.

3.8 SAMPLING

Selecting participants based on their depth of knowledge of the topic, and their willingness to participate is known as purposive sampling (Hammond and Wellington 2020). Further, recommendations made by Walliman, (2021) hold that purposive sampling is effective in qualitative research because the researcher can gather data from participants who are well equipped with relevant knowledge if they are willing to share this. Clearly, understanding the variables involved in selection / participation results in the clarity of the context, and how well it is researched (Cassell et al 2017). The number of candidates that were selected to take part in interviews was a crucial aspect of research (Walliman 2018). Some authors believe that qualitative research is about the depth of research, rather than the number of participants (Sloan and Quan-Haase 2017). One of the key objectives of this research is to develop a clear understanding of topics such as the exchange, creation and sharing of content linked to Islamic banking on social media platforms. Thus, purposive sampling was seen as key, because experienced and knowledgeable participants had to be chosen to take part in interviews. Further, experienced participants were seen as experts, with key knowledge about the creation, exchange, and sharing of content related to Islamic banking on social media. Moreover, this type of sampling also allows the researcher to develop an in-depth understanding of the topic. In addition, they were also willing to share the knowledge they possess. This type of sampling meant the researcher could choose participants who were best suited to conducting research.

In social research, achieving the desired depth and breadth of understanding is more critical than the numeric precision often associated with a larger sample size. To meet the particular research objectives of this study, a sample size of 40 was seen as appropriate to generate rich, detailed, and complex data about the influence of UGC, and the interplay of cultural and societal values that have an impact on consumer brand engagement. The decision to employ snowball sampling was also guided by the nature of the research and the characteristics of the population of interest. In the context of this research, the population - customers of Islamic banks in Pakistan who engage with banks via social media and generate UGC - could be challenging to identify and reach directly. Hence, the snowball sampling technique, which relies on referrals from initial participants to generate additional subjects, proved useful.

Snowball sampling allows for the recruitment of participants who are not only engaged with Islamic banking but are also active on social media and contribute to UGC - a specific subset of the population. This methodology takes advantage of social networks and the fact that like-minded individuals tend to form communities, both online and offline. Since participants are referred by others in their network, the likelihood of getting relevant, insightful responses is increased. Moreover, this approach helps build trust and rapport, which are critical when exploring sensitive topics such as banking preferences, social media behaviour, and cultural values. It often results in greater participation and richer data because participants are more likely to agree to take part in research when referred by someone they know.

It is noteworthy that snowball sampling also has certain limitations, such as potential bias because the sample is not random and could be reflective only of certain networks or communities. However, given the exploratory and qualitative nature of this research, it was clear that these potential limitations would be outweighed by the benefits. The aim was not to generalize the findings to all customers of all Islamic banks in Pakistan, but to generate a deep understanding of the phenomena under study. By employing snowball sampling in semi-structured interviews, the study sought to create meaningful insights into the complex dynamics of UGC as well as the key cultural and societal influences, and the nature of brand engagement within the realm of Islamic banking. It was anticipated that the richness of the data obtained would support the development of a context-based model, highlighting the significance of social brand engagement with Islamic banks. Therefore, the choice of snowball sampling and the sample size of forty participants aligned well with the study's objectives, enabling a comprehensive exploration of the research topic while considering the practical constraints inherent in this specific context.

3.8.1 Participant selection

Gannon and Fauchon (2021) argue that researchers can bring in participants from their own social circles who are familiar with social media and use it at least once a day. This profile fulfilled the research criteria (Sloan and Quan Haase 2017). Furthermore, Sloan and Quan Haase (2017) believe that if the researcher chooses participants on social media, then they can review and monitor their activities on social media. Consequently, this might provide a better understanding of the participants and their interests and activities on social media. One of the key reasons why social networks are useful for choosing participants is that it is possible to gain access to qualified participants. This led to a richer discussion during semi-structured interviews. Social media is the preferred method that people turn to interact. Thus, it was easier

to select participants from the most popular social media networks. Moreover, suggestions advanced by Quan Hasse (2017) hold that researchers can gain a better understanding of their friends and extended friends if they are suitable for the research context. This means that initial interactions with participants can take place on social media. Later, after participants agree to take part, a phone call or an in-person interview took place. An information sheet and copy of the questionnaire were shared over the internet to ensure participants were willing to participate in the research. Further, a follow up email was sent to the selected participants to confirm their participation in an interview. The researcher's own social circle was utilized to interact with people on social media that fulfil the above criteria. The researcher contacted his own friends and social circle. After shortlisting, a participant information form, and questionnaire were sent to subjects via email to confirm their willingness to take part.

3.8.2 Sample size

A sample size of up to forty participants was seen as suitable for research of this type. Many researchers conduct semi-structured interviews in research of this type, such as Naeem's (2021) Consumer Panic Buying Theory. Another example of this is Naeem and Ozuem's (2021) paper based on semi-structured interviews with a sample of up to forty. Further, Ozuem et al (2021) created the BIAC (Brand sentiment, identification with source, affirmative experience, and conspicuous effort) model via semi-structured interviews with a sample of forty participants. Semi-structured interviews are therefore suitable for this research to form a context-based model highlighting the significance of social brand engagement with Islamic banks. Moreover, this study employed thirty-two participants.

Participant No.	Gender	Age	Professional Background	Number of Social Media Sites Used	Engagement with Islamic Banking
1	Male	24	Student	3	Regular Customer
2	Female	32	Banker	4	Bank Employee
3	Male	40	Entrepreneur	2	Regular Customer
4	Female	28	Marketing Specialist	5	Occasionally
5	Male	35	IT Specialist	3	Regular Customer
6	Female	30	Teacher	2	Occasionally
7	Male	38	Banker	4	Bank Employee
8	Female	26	Student	3	Regular Customer
9	Female	30	Lawyer	2	Regular Customer
10	Male	42	Retail Manager	4	Regular Customer
11	Female	36	Architect	3	Regular Customer
12	Male	33	Nurse	5	Occasionally
13	Female	45	HR Specialist	4	Occasionally
14	Male	31	Software Engineer	3	Regular Customer
15	Female	29	Journalist	2	Occasionally
16	Male	39	Financial Analyst	4	Bank Employee
17	Female	27	University Lecturer	3	Regular Customer
18	Male	41	Government Official	2	Regular Customer
19	Female	35	Advertising Professional	5	Regular Customer
20	Male	38	Pharmacist	4	Occasionally
21	Female	37	Scientist	3	Regular Customer
22	Male	33	Accountant	5	Occasionally
23	Female	34	Fitness Instructor	2	Occasionally
24	Male	40	Mechanical Engineer	4	Bank Employee
25	Female	26	Fashion Designer	3	Regular Customer
26	Male	45	Real Estate Agent	3	Regular Customer
27	Female	31	Social Worker	4	Occasionally
28	Male	37	Business Consultant	2	Occasionally
29	Female	40	Psychiatrist	5	Regular Customer
30	Male	30	Civil Engineer	4	Bank Employee
31	Female	32	Writer	3	Regular Customer
32	Male	27	Business Owner	5	Regular Customer

3.9 PILOT STUDY

A pilot study is an essential step before commencing fieldwork. It acts as a "dress rehearsal" to evaluate the feasibility of the chosen research methods and tools. A pilot study was therefore conducted to evaluate the semi-structured interview guide designed to gather data from the customers of Islamic banks in Pakistan.

The pilot study involved five participants selected from the target population. These participants were interviewed using the semi-structured interview guide. Following the

recommendations of Van Teijlingen and Hundley (2002), the participants for the pilot study were not included in the main study. The participants were briefed about the purpose of the study and told how their participation would assist in refining the research tools. After conducting the pilot study, the researcher transcribed the interviews verbatim and proceeded with a preliminary analysis of the data. The pilot study demonstrated that the questions were well-understood by the participants, and allowed for rich, in-depth responses. However, during the analysis, the researcher noted that some questions did not yield as much relevant information as expected, while other topics required further exploration. The pilot study was also instrumental in assessing the estimated duration of each interview, allowing the researcher to fine-tune the guide to respect participants' time.

Following the pilot study, several changes were made to the semi-structured interview guide. Firstly, questions that did not yield much relevant data were either rephrased or eliminated. Secondly, new questions were added to delve deeper into the areas that emerged as significant during the pilot study. For instance, questions were refined to get a more nuanced understanding of the impact of cultural and societal values on user-generated content in the context of Islamic banks. The order of questions was also adjusted to improve the logical flow of the interview. These changes helped to ensure that the interviews for the main study would be both efficient and effective in gathering relevant data.

In terms of section numbering, the researcher noticed a lack of coherency. The changes made after the pilot study also included rectifying the inconsistencies in the numbering and organization of different sections of the research. This ensured clarity and coherency in the presentation of the research, making it easier for readers to follow and understand the research process. The pilot study was instrumental in refining the research methodology and tools, thus enhancing the validity and reliability of the study. It allowed the researcher to ensure that the research tools were appropriate and effective for gathering data from the participants, and that the organization of the research was clear and coherent. The changes made following the pilot study contributed significantly to the success of the main study.

3.9.1 Rationale

Two types of data collection are used in research: primary, and secondary data collection. The former involves conducting observations, surveys, and interviews amongst others. (Green et al 2006). For the purposes of this research, primary data were acquired from social media users with at least 2 years of experience using social media accounts on various platforms.

Yin (2009) cited in Green et al (2006) notes that a case study that is conducted carefully can extract multiple sources of evidence to ensure its robustness. Moreover, the concept of methods reflects the appropriate use of this technique of data collection and data analysis (Prasad 2005). It is imperative in a case study that data sources converge, and so triangulation is a useful strategy. This ensures that the outcomes are comprehensive, and it also reflects the participants' understanding of primary data collection.

Triangulation was summarised by Yin (2009) as a key element that is required to conduct a case study in an appropriate manner. There are several sources of data that allow case study researchers to establish a story that can do justice to the meaning-making process of participants. Thus, the researcher can create questions that initiate stories for participants to collect data.

Qualitative researchers use different methods to collect data that include primary, as well as secondary sources. Interviews are one such method of primary data collection, whereby the researcher investigates a certain topic with respondents. Seidman (1998) demonstrated that interviews are grounded in phenomenological traditions to understand the meanings underlying experiences. In addition, Seidman (1998) notes that phenomenology is linked with qualitative research. Moreover, interviewing allows the researcher to comprehend people's behaviour which in this case is their engagement with Islamic banking brands. The primary assumptions underlying in-depth interview techniques have been critiqued, and every individual creates their own meaning and interpretation of experiences related to UGC sharing, consuming, and exchanging. With the use of semi-structured interviews, researchers can get a better understanding of the meaning SMUs make of UGC on social media platforms.

There are four major reasons that are behind the use of semi-structured interviews as a method to collect primary data. Firstly, interviews are useful to understand people's opinions and views regarding their experiences and how they deal with them. Several important questions had to be explored to develop a better understanding of UGC, and it was felt that unstructured interviews would not be as direct as semi-structured interviews in this sense (Kyale 1996).

Furthermore, semi-structured interviews are conducted to deduce interviewee's opinions in terms of the research, while considering some significant queries. Patton (1987) discussed the significance of social engagement amongst SMUs in relation to Islamic banks. Moreover, there is generation of a hefty amount of description of fundamental data through semi-structured interview techniques which warrants the researchers with a chance to make

decisions regarding research results being transferable (Merriam, 2002) in such that a description is needed to draw up a model specific to context and a theoretical construct is needed to highlight the significance that social engagement concerning brands in the light of Islamic banks. Lastly, semi-structured interviews enhance the reliability of results as they ensure data triangulation. The results of research must draw on various sources of data. According to Stake (1995) and Merriam (2002) there is a need for a conceptual framework to underpin research to maintain the primary context during data collection and analysis. This underscores the significance of conceptual models in the research process. For this reason, the present study produces a conceptual framework for UGC and brand engagement that is relevant to Islamic banking.

Qualitative interviews can also be used as instruments for data collection to improve the range of methodological approaches which can be used to address the research question. The use of interviews is favoured when the interviewee's subjective viewpoint relates to a social aspect of UGC on social media. The researcher should engage with an adequate number of research participants that are qualified to take part in the study. SMUs were chosen as research participants for this study to understand their perspectives in relation to the creation, sharing, and consumption of content on various social media. The objective of the present study is to examine the role that UGC plays in creating brand engagement around Islamic banking. The participants were selected through purposive sampling (Maxwell, 2005).

Participants were selected based on the following criteria.

Participants with accounts on two or more social media platforms were selected (Naeem and Wilson, 2020).

Participants had to have viewed, shared, consumed, or created content on social media relevant to Islamic banking at least once. Participants had to have created UGC around this area in the past to qualify as suitable.

A fundamental aim of this study was to probe the experiences, outlooks, and perceptions of study participants that have shared, listened to, and viewed content on social media platforms relevant to Islamic banking. Information regarding UGC was collected to comprehend the influence that SMUs have on one another in terms of the UGC they generate on various platforms. According to Naeem (2020) there was a lack of flexibility in terms of understanding the complex and precise attributes of experience as well as the interpretation of the context of creating, viewing, and sharing UGC. A hermeneutic approach allows researchers

to adopt an investigative stance to data with the aim of developing a meaningful and conceptual account of UGC and brand engagement. There is a need for a dual focus which involves the creation, consumption, and sharing of UGC. There is a further need to understand the role it plays in creating brand engagement relevant to Islamic banks. This dual focus is suited to the undertaking of semi-structured interviews.

Participants were provided with personal space during the interviews to help elicit thoughtful responses in relation to specific themes, rather than directing participants to follow a particular order of thought. This created an air of confidence. As far as wording or ordering is concerned, there was plenty of scope for flexibility during the interviews. Semi-structured interviews also provide a broader scope to study the dimensions pertinent to SMUs speaking about Islamic banks on social media.

Data collection techniques were needed to ensure the building of rapport between the research moderator/ interviewer and research participants so that open discussions could occur. This created more openness. This type of setting calls for the conduction of semi-structured interview in person to gather richer data that is less ambiguous than it would be if gathered using less structured approaches (Denscombe, 2010). Cohen et al. (2011) add that semi-structured interviews facilitate a comparison of study responses in contrast to the comparison given by interviews that are unstructured. This paved the way for a critical analysis, and the structured organization of data. Consequently, understanding the type of social exchange that UGC has on SMUs can be improved by the discourse on creation, consumption, sharing, and exchange of UGC.

Denscombe (2010) stresses that, at a superficial level, interviews are a simple and easy method to apply as they are quite like normal conversations. Interviews, however, can fail if they are not backed up with a proper plan and if they are not well prepared and implemented with caution. As such, schedules of interviews were put together following a pilot stage to obtain the views of participants. This created a clearer understanding of the potential that the questions could provide. Initially, the interviews were unstructured in nature. Five participants helped with the development of the questions . The major aim was to investigate the experiences of SMUs as they viewed, created, consumed, shared, and exchanged UGC relevant to Islamic banks. Secondly, a schedule of interviews was compiled based on the literature review and theoretical framework proposed for the research. Thirdly, interviews were piloted

with research participants possessing knowledge about Islamic banks. It was also necessary for these research participants to be customers of Islamic banks.

According to Brinkmann (2014) and Brinkman and Kvale (2005) it is imperative that interviews are accurately prepared and taken seriously. This involves conceptual as well as practical planning, which can prove to be quite complex. There is a need for astute planning for the purpose of developing successful interviews. This planning must account for the scope, as well as the focal points of the research questions. To prepare these qualitative interviews, the key elements that were contemplated were the recording of data and the equipment used. The venue of the interview was also a major factor due to the potential influence of place on the collection of data. Participants therefore had to consent and agree to a location. The time and venue for interviews was agreed and matched the various schedules of participants. This allowed participants to share their perspectives and previous experiences with the research moderator/ interviewer without any hindrance. Ethical approval was seen as key, particularly since it was necessary to obtain informed consent from participants ahead of each interview (Illing, 2014).

The point of a qualitative interview is so that the interviewer can ask questions which might be quite personal and potentially significant to participants. As such, the researcher is crucial to this process at a professional and personal level. Hence, the researcher had to pre-plan the interview and pilot it on at least one participant. This step can help the researcher polish his skills prior to data collection to interact with the research participants successfully. Piloting can be conducted on peers or on friends. This provides the researcher with an understanding of the language, aspects of active listening, and the research questions. The style of interview is quite significant as it dictates how data collection is conducted (Krag and Jacobsen, 1993).

Qualitative interviews can be structured in nature, or open. Interviews that are structured or even semi-structured in nature contain a set of questions which help the researcher probe for further detail. Laksov et al. (2017) emphasizes the vitality of alignment between interview guides and the methodological approach. In contrast, a structured guide contains questions that are pre-identified and are thus presented to all participants in a similar manner to obtain responses. Semi-structured interviews can be used in research settings related to business as well as management. Therefore, it was deemed appropriate that fifteen or so

research questions would be appropriate. Nevertheless, the interviewer must choose whether to investigate or dig deeper into the feedback given by participants (Lingard and Kennedy, 2010). Interviews must begin with some easy questions to ensure the comfort and confidence of participants. For example, questions such as “Do you have familiarity with social media?” “Why does social media interest you?” or “Why did you start using social media instead of traditional media?” Other questions included “In your opinion, why has social media become so important now?” and “what role does social media play in buying decisions?” Such questions can be asked mid-interview instead of at the beginning of the interview. In a similar manner, the interview must be closed with an adequate question such as “Is there something that you would like to add to this?” or “If you have any questions regarding any of this, please let us know.”

3.10 THEMATIC ANALYSIS PROCESS

Thematic analysis is universally applied in various qualitative research studies even though it is not popular. It is applied in various fields of qualitative research such as ethnography, phenomenology, and grounded theory. Thematic analysis is a foundational methodology used for the analysis of qualitative data (Braun and Clarke, 2006). It is mostly used in qualitative studies and is therefore not considered an independent method of analysis. Rather, it aids researchers in conducting analyses.

3.10.1 Interpretation process

Thematic analysis involves the generation of themes and codes based on empirical material that is qualitative in nature. Further, analysis is undertaken based on text. In the present research, interpretation began by transcribing the interviews. NVivo12 software was used for the purposes of transcription. Transcribing the interviews at the stage of empirical material prompts the alteration and adaptation of the guide which was used for interviews. When the interviews were completely transcribed, they were cross-checked with field notes taken during the interviews. This step helped to identify any additional information in the notes which was not present in the transcription.

The concepts were then combined with the aim of developing various categories such as the motivation behind UGC, the impact of UGC, and social brand interactions through UGC. Next, the outcomes of the interviews were triangulated noting observations noted down during meetings and recorded as field notes.

The author used an approach consisting of four steps which were (a) preparing, (b) exploring, (c) specifying, and (d) integrating (PESI) with the aim of conducting empirical analysis and interpreting the material. Various other recommendations about coding were followed, taking orientation from previous qualitative studies (Flick et al., 2004; Coffey and Atkinson 1996; Yin 2009; Hesse-Biber and Leavy 2011). An approach that is more systematic was introduced by PESI to report empirical data. This approach is more organized and efficient. This stage consists of developing familiarity with the empirical data and sorting it into different categories based on the theoretical framework formulated for the present study. It further needs to be efficiently arranged, sorted, and then interpreted. According to Yin (1994), this is called data manipulation. Moreover, data processing is an extremely complex phase in qualitative research where the aim is to develop a final framework (Jandaghi and Zarei, 2010). This involves conducting a detailed perusal of transcriptions and sorting documents. A review of field notes taken during interviews must be conducted, and reference must be made to key literature. To this end, four frames for interpretation were created. The text was first entered into NVivo and then classified into categories and allocated to these frames using coding and theme extraction.

3.11 BUILDING TRUSTWORTHINESS IN QUALITATIVE RESEARCH

Validity and reliability are two crucial metrics that determine the credibility and replicability of any research study. According to Brink (1993), validity refers to the degree to which the research findings accurately represent what they are intended to represent. On the other hand, reliability indicates the consistency and repeatability of the research process and its findings. In this research, the investigator adopted multiple strategies to enhance both the validity and reliability of the findings, primarily by implementing the method of triangulation. Triangulation is a research strategy that involves using multiple methods, theories, researchers, or data sources to study a single phenomenon. The purpose of triangulation is not merely to cross-verify data, but to capture different dimensions of the same phenomenon. According to Denzin (1978), triangulation can contribute to the reliability and validity of research by reducing bias and providing a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomena under study. The research conducted indeed reflects the values of trustworthiness as highlighted by Lincoln and Guba (1985). To establish trustworthiness in qualitative research, it is vital that the study meets the criteria of credibility, transferability, dependability, confirmability, and auditability. This study has taken numerous steps to ensure that these criteria have been met.

1. **Credibility:** The research has accomplished credibility using triangulation. By utilizing multiple sources of data (semi-structured interviews and social media content analysis), the study ensured that the findings are robust and valid. Also, the process of peer debriefing with other researchers was incorporated. Such external scrutiny enhanced the credibility of the research by ensuring that the research process and findings stood up to expert examination (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). The technique of referential sufficiency was used to check initial results and interpretations against the raw data. Furthermore, a strategy of member checking was implemented, ensuring that the research findings and interpretations were validated with the participants themselves. This helped to strengthen the credibility of the study. In the peer debriefing process, other experts in the field scrutinized the research process and findings, and this external examination enhanced the credibility. Member checking involved going back to the participants to validate the findings and interpretations, ensuring that they truly reflected the participants' experiences and perspectives. This comprehensive approach to data collection and analysis ensured that the research findings were dependable and accurately represented the phenomenon under study.
2. **Transferability:** This study ensured transferability by providing comprehensive descriptions of the research process and the theoretical foundations of the study. This thoroughness allows other researchers to understand the context of the study and consider the application of the findings to their own contexts. The ability to generalize the study's findings contributes to its transferability (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). Transferability in this study was achieved by providing a detailed and comprehensive description of the research context, methods, and findings. By thoroughly detailing the context of the study - the Islamic banking sector in Pakistan, the factors influencing UGC and brand engagement, and the cultural and societal values within this context - the study allows readers and other researchers to understand the specific circumstances under which the findings hold true. This enables others to determine the extent to which the findings can be applied or transferred to other contexts, thereby ensuring transferability (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). The study ensured transferability through thorough and detailed descriptions of the research context, methodology, and findings. The extensive detail provided allows other researchers to compare the context of this study with their own and decide on the applicability of the findings to their settings. Moreover, the study's rich, contextualized insights into UGC and brand engagement in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan provide a basis for further research in similar or

different contexts. This ability to potentially apply the findings to other contexts or populations represents the study's transferability.

3. **Dependability:** Dependability in this research was achieved by documenting the research process clearly and logically. This enables readers and other researchers to follow the research process and determine its consistency and stability (Koch, 1994). Clear documentation of the research procedure ensures that the process is auditable and contributes to the study's dependability. Dependability was achieved in this study by ensuring that the research process was clearly and comprehensively documented. This included a clear explanation of the research design, the selection and justification of research methods, and the process of data collection and analysis. The research process was made transparent and traceable, thereby enabling other researchers to replicate the study if desired. This consistency and repeatability of the research process contributed to its dependability (Koch, 1994).
4. **Confirmability:** This research achieved confirmability by demonstrating the steps taken to ensure credibility, transferability, and dependability. The researcher has made clear the analytical, theoretical, and methodological decisions made throughout the research process, enabling others to understand the rationale for these decisions (Koch, 1994). By transparently explaining how the data were interpreted and conclusions reached, the study ensured the confirmability of the findings. Confirmability was established in this research by transparently documenting the research process and demonstrating how the findings emerged from the data. This was achieved by providing clear and detailed explanations of the data collection and analytical processes, as well as by demonstrating how the findings were derived from these data. Confirmability also involves ensuring that the findings and interpretations are not influenced by the researcher's biases. To ensure this, the study was conducted in a way that allowed the data to guide the findings, rather than having preconceived ideas or hypotheses influence the outcomes (Koch, 1994). The reflexive journal maintained by the researcher also contributed to confirmability, as it documented the researcher's reflections and decisions throughout the research process.
5. **Auditability:** To ensure the auditability of the study, a reflexive journal was maintained to document decisions related to methodology, rationales, and daily coordination. Personal reflections about the researcher's interests, values, and insights were also recorded. This reflexive journal, as suggested by Sandelowski (1986), allows for easy and clear following of the decision trail, ensuring auditability.

This study has met the criteria for trustworthiness as established by Lincoln and Guba (1985). By ensuring credibility, transferability, dependability, confirmability, and auditability, the researcher has demonstrated the robustness and reliability of the research findings and interpretations. This adds value to the research, and increases its potential impact on scholars, policymakers, practitioners, and the public.

The researcher implemented triangulation in several ways in this study. First, methodological triangulation was applied, involving the use of multiple methods of data collection, such as semi-structured interviews and social media content analysis. By collecting data through different methods, the researcher was able to cross-check the findings and gain a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomena under study. For example, interviews provided in-depth insights into the perceptions and experiences of consumers, while social media analysis helped to validate these insights by exploring how consumers engaged with Islamic banks in a real-world, online setting. Second, data source triangulation was utilized. Here, the researcher collected data from different types of participants, including consumers from various demographics and professionals from different Islamic banks. This variety in the source of data helped capture a diverse range of perspectives and experiences, strengthening the validity and comprehensiveness of the findings.

Triangulation was not just used to ensure the validity and reliability of the findings, but also to deepen the researcher's understanding of the complex interplay between UGC, cultural and societal influences, and brand engagement in the context of Islamic banking. Furthermore, during the analysis, the researcher implemented peer debriefing, which involved discussing the findings with other researchers. This served as an additional check on the interpretation of the data and helped to enhance the study's reliability and validity (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

Efforts were also made to ensure transparency and replicability of the research process, contributing to its reliability. The researcher provided a detailed account of the methods used, from the sampling procedure to the data collection and analysis methods. This level of detail allows other researchers to replicate the study, enhancing its reliability. In conclusion, by applying triangulation and other strategies, the researcher was able to enhance the validity and reliability of this study. These strategies ensured that the findings were not only reflective of the experiences and perceptions of the participants but were also robust, comprehensive, and repeatable. This strengthens the credibility of the research and its contributions to our understanding of UGC and brand engagement in the context of Islamic banking.

3.12 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Several principles relevant to ethics need to be followed by researchers throughout the process of research. Howitt and Cramer (2017) insist that ethics ensure research credibility. Ethical approaches to the storage of data may raise issues such as the probability of the information provided being stolen or even mislaid. This is a grave issue as the data collected during research can contain personal information. This concern can be mitigated using Google Cloud for data storage, as there is no need for a physical device to store the data. This will enable the researcher to reach the data through any device with an Internet connection with great convenience. It will also reduce any danger of data being stolen or misplaced. Google Cloud is quite dependable, as with any electronic storage vault. Hence, Google cloud was used for data storage. If the researcher adheres to these ethics, they obtain a strong reputation as a research scholar. The following ethical principles were followed in the present study.

- Participants were not pressurized in any way to provide data through interviews.
- Prior to the beginning of the data collection process, informed consent was obtained from each research participant in writing on an information sheet.
- Participants were only selected for the data collection if they were willing to participate in the study.
- The data provided by each participant were kept confidential and there was no breach of privacy.
- The reporting of research findings was credible, and the representation of data was honest.
- The research participants were given information related to any document they may have to come across relevant to the research study prior to the beginning of data-collection.
- Consent to audio record interviews and store data on Google Drive was sought. If the participants asked for audio recordings, they were provided with it.
- The research participants were given the right to ask for the audio recordings to be deleted within 5 days of the interview. They were informed of this right prior to commencing data collection.
- The participants were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any stage. If participants exercised this right, the data obtained were safely destroyed.

3.13 SUMMARY

The chapter justifies the choice of a social constructionist stance, which places a premium on subjective social and cultural milieu. This approach values how people perceive the world and how they construct reality through their interactions with others. The researcher gained a deeper appreciation for the nuanced social realities of UGC in relation to online brand engagement using this approach. Customer perspectives of UGC creation, sharing, and exchange leading to social brand engagement and consumer brand engagement were considered because of the emphasis on studying customer behaviour.

Knowing what motivates SMUs to create, share, and exchange UGC is crucial, as it can affect both social brand engagement and consumer brand engagement. The literature has shown, for instance, that under certain conditions, people are more receptive to celebrity endorsements than the public. However, not everyone is easily swayed by celebrity endorsements. Some consumers would rather read reviews written by the public. The results demonstrate differences across the same phenomenon. This is why taking a social constructionist stance is useful, as it recognises that competing interpretations of reality are equally valid. To investigate the causes of UGC creation, sharing, and exchange that lead to brand engagement, the current study adopts a social constructionist methodology.

Instead of focusing on hypothesis testing, the social constructionist approach emphasises the importance of listening to and learning from people's lived experiences. Researching the impact of UGC on brand engagement amongst Pakistan's Islamic financial institutions necessitates taking a more open-ended, exploratory approach than would be appropriate if the goal were to evaluate hypotheses. Taking a social constructionist stance, the researcher can account for the motivations behind SMUs' UGC creation, sharing, and exchange, which in turn drives social brand engagement and consumer brand engagement. The researcher used inductive reasoning to create a theoretical framework to understand the impact of UGC on brand engagement, and the exploratory research design facilitated this process.

In exploratory or social constructionist research, theorising involves sifting through large amounts of descriptive data to find commonalities and draw conclusions. For instance, the theory applied in this study is that UGC has a significant impact on consumer engagement with brands related to Islamic banks in Pakistan. When using inductive reasoning, one must first see before moving on to the next step of developing a proposition based on that observation and its supporting evidence.

CHAPTER 4: ANALYSIS

4.1 INTRODUCTION

The previous chapter discussed the research methodology and identified that relativist ontological and social constructionist epistemological positions were adopted which correspond to subjectivism. These approaches enabled the researcher to collect the views of consumers concerning Islamic banks in Pakistan, and to understand how they interact with these banks through UGC online on SMNs. Additionally, the researcher also drew on the meaning of brand engagement and approached this concept in the light of the views of SMUs who interact with UGC on Islamic banking in Pakistan. The current research is qualitative in nature as it enables the researcher to discuss the significance and meaning of UGC with respect to brand engagement about Islamic banks in Pakistan.

The focus of this research is the responses of consumers who have utilized the services of Islamic banks and have also interacted with UGC on Islamic banks. Thus, consumers were interviewed who were confirmed as SMUs. The confirmed heterogeneity of the population was based on their involvement with Islamic banks and their income levels.

4.2 THEMATIC APPROACH

The data analysis in this research was conducted through thematic analysis. This analytical technique is useful for qualitative researchers since it focuses on identifying patterns in thick descriptive data, which is non-numerical, and non-statistical. The data are usually acquired from participants and are analyzed for patterns to make sense of the situation that is being studied (Fereday, 2006; Boyatzis, 1998). Responses were obtained from consumers of Islamic banks.

Thematic analysis enables researchers to address their objectives and is helpful for determining patterns and themes in data. To achieve this, codes are assigned to datasets based on initial codes that are assigned to them. The patterns identified spotlight meanings which are interpreted to make sense of situations (Braun and Clarke, 2006). In this research, exploratory and qualitative interviews were conducted to enable the researcher to develop rich insights into the social phenomenon (Folkestad, 2008).

Yin (1994) observed that qualitative interviews enable the researcher to generate rich insights. The basic objective of the current research was to understand the extent to which UGC

influences SMUs to engage with brands. Therefore, data collection and analytical techniques were selected accordingly to generate new insights. Qualitative interviews and thematic analysis were of prime importance to the collection of primary data. The conceptual framework was developed in line with recommendations advanced by Braun and Clarke (2006). Furthermore, thematic analysis is also helpful to interpret data and relate it back to the research questions.

Deriving themes from data involves pulling out ideas or meanings that were intended by the respondent when they conveyed their responses during the interview. Braun and Clarke (2006) observed that themes represent the perspectives of respondents. Bazeley (2009) observed that themes are about identifying the image of the situation based on interview responses. Braun and Clarke (2006) observed that themes can be derived from data through both inductive and deductive methods.

Using an inductive approach, the researcher finds recurring patterns within the data which indicate the importance of the meaning enunciated by the respondent in their responses to the researcher (Thomas, 2003). Furthermore, there are three reasons, as highlighted by Thomas (2003), why inductive methods of thematic analysis are useful. Firstly, it enables the researcher to summarize the qualitative data. Secondly, it enables the researcher to identify close connections between the findings and the objectives of the research. Thirdly, it enables the researcher to deviate from existing theories in the light of new insights to develop a new theoretical model or propose a new theory in the light of new findings (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

The current research focuses on understanding the role of UGC in creating social brand- and consumer brand engagement with Islamic banks in Pakistan. Since the current research deployed a social constructionist approach, an inductive method of thematic analysis was seen as suitable. This approach enables the researcher to comprehend the perspectives of participants and identify meanings in their responses. Ozuem et al., (2015) highlighted the importance of thematic analysis for interpreting interview responses. This type of analysis enables the researcher to dig out the inherent meanings and intended messages of the respondent from data.

UGC involves a human element as people create, share and exchange UGC for a wide variety of purposes. This influences other SMUs to become part of the process, and this in turn yields social brand- and consumer brand engagement. Therefore, for the purposes of the current research, the views of participants were gathered via interviews. Semi-structured interviews

were conducted to gather thick descriptive data which was analyzed using thematic analysis. The inductive approach was utilized to conduct thematic analysis which informed the emergent theoretical model.

Braun and Clarke (2006) observed that inductive approaches to analyzing data are used when the aim of the researcher is to develop a theory. The inductive approach as part of thematic analysis enables the researcher to analyze rich data and identify patterns which convey specific meanings (Patton, 1990). This enables the researcher to develop a theoretical framework. The current research involved conducting semi-structured interviews because these interviews enabled the researcher to secure more information from the respondents and the respondents could also give response freely without any limitations which are usually found in structured approach of data collection. Braun and Clarke (2018) observed that, in using thematic analysis the researcher can make sense of situations by uncovering the subjective realities in the responses of interviewees. Existing researchers have also highlighted the importance of thematic analysis in developing a sound understanding of the social phenomenon and in making sense of reality from the perspective of those who are impacted by it.

It has been argued that by combining an inductive approach with thematic analysis, the researcher can develop an understanding of the impact of different constructs over each other. For example, this research examines the impact of UGC on brand engagement in the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan. The research investigates the role of UGC to generate social brand- and consumer brand engagement. Thematic analysis then enables the researcher to develop insights from the data by identifying patterns within in (Braun and Clark, 2006).

Inductive thematic analysis involves assigning codes to data sets. These codes are then combined to illustrate the overall situation that is being studied. Inductive reasoning also ensures that the data collected and analyzed speak to the aims and objectives of the research. The researcher also involved marketing experts in the interview process to draw out finer details about the subject. The four main themes that emerged because of thematic analysis comprised UGC social brand engagement, UGC social impact, UGC social context, and UGC Social Flux of User-Generated Content

The researcher conducted thematic analysis in line with the recommendations of Braun and Clarke (2006) to look at the impact of UGC on brand engagement with respect to Islamic banks in Pakistan. The process involved going through the interview transcripts frequently and repetitively. At this stage, the researcher was only required to assign initial codes. Thereafter,

NVIVO software was employed to process transcripts. This was helpful for identifying repetitive words or phrases in the responses. However, the researcher also thoroughly assessed the transcripts so that he could develop a sound understanding of the various views about UGC and brand engagement. Once the initial codes were assigned, they were combined, and the researcher was able to produce a thematic map.

It was also found that different participants used varied terms to convey the same meaning or message in their responses. The themes emerged from an analysis of thick descriptive data about UGC considering the views of users, and their social contexts. However, the researcher collated these themes into four main themes which comprised: elements generating UGC by SMUs; elements which influence UGC related to brands; types of consumers and participants of UGC; and the quality of content. These themes are related to literature and correspond to the aims and objectives of this research.

4.3 THEME NO. 1 – CATALYSTS OF CO-CREATION: INSPIRING UGC IN ISLAMIC BANKING

The theme, "Catalysts of Co-Creation: Inspiring UGC in Islamic Banking", explores three distinct but interconnected drivers of User-Generated Content (UGC) in the realm of Islamic banks in Pakistan: Narrative Threads of Wisdom, Moral Weaves of Society, and Illuminating the Conscious Horizon.

"Narrative Threads of Wisdom" underscores the importance of individual experiences in the creation of content. The users frequently share their interactions with banking services, both positive and negative, to enlighten others. Platforms such as WhatsApp and Facebook become channels for these experiences, aiding others in making informed decisions.

"Moral Weaves of Society" reveals the ethical duty individuals feel towards their social circles. They see their involvement in UGC creation as fulfilling a social responsibility, sharing the good and the bad aspects of banking services. This UGC reflects real-life experiences and highlights a customer-friendly approach, thus enhancing its value. It further confirms that consumers place higher trust in UGC as it is not influenced by advertising motives, contributing to brand engagement.

Finally, "Illuminating the Conscious Horizon" captures the intent to disseminate awareness about banking services through UGC. It includes the sharing of information about discount offers, interest-free banking services, and customer-friendly policies. The aim here is not just to inform their immediate social circles but to reach a broader audience. Respondents recognize UGC for its authenticity and reliability, even as they acknowledge the potential risk to a brand's reputation from negative feedback.

4.3.1 Code No. 1: Narrative Threads of Wisdom

Ellison et al., (2007) observed that the information people receive from their personal relations on, or off social media carries equal importance because these sources are closer to people. Thus, it was also within the ambit of the aim of this research to investigate the reasons why people create, share and exchange UGC on social media. An interviewee 1 said *"whatsApp and Facebook both are key sources of information about banks. At least I share my banking experience with my friends and family on these platforms so that my friends and family can get the same benefits as I do. On WhatsApp I usually upload the status which my contact list on WhatsApp can see. On Facebook I write it on my wall. I do it as part of my social responsibility."*

An interviewee 19 shared some experiences, *"I have joined various Facebook groups about consumers in which I share both positive and negative experiences. So, I also share the same about the Islamic bank I am banking with so that I can keep my friends informed about the services of the bank compared to other banks."*

Another interviewee, 29, said about it, *"I look for feedback before I make a purchase. Social media has helped me a great deal with this. So, when I wanted to open a bank account, I wanted to open it in an Islamic bank because I did not want to relate my income to interest rate. So, I went online and sought feedback about different Islamic banks. Later, when I opened the account in an Islamic bank following the advice online, I then shared my experience with the rest of the people as well."* The act of narrative threads of wisdoms illustrates a motivation rooted in social influence and the need to convey personal experiences. As noted by interviewees, platforms like WhatsApp and Facebook serve as conduits to share personal experiences with banking services. The interviewees note their active participation in sharing both positive and negative experiences, thus enabling others to make informed decisions. It is apparent that UGC, fuelled by personal experiences, serves to guide decision-making processes

among peers, aligning with the research by Ellison et al., (2007) that emphasizes the influence of personal relations.

4.3.2 Code No. 2 – Moral Weaves of Society

It has also been observed that feedback and social responsibility are precursors to creating UGC about brands such as Islamic banks in Pakistan. Those who engage in creating, sharing, and exchanging UGC regard it as part of a social responsibility, to keep each other informed about the negative and positive aspects of the bank's services. Their UGC is welcomed by other SMUs because they believe that it is created to reflect real-life experiences. In this sense, SMUs keep each other informed about the positives and negatives of banks. SMUs also create content about the management of the bank indicating the customer friendly approach of one bank versus the other. Other elements which underpin the creation, sharing and exchange of UGC about Islamic banks is discussed below:

An interviewee 31 said that *“I like it when banks offer discount deals on their debit cards and credit cards for their customers. So, whenever I receive a message from my bank about the latest deals on their debit and credit cards, I immediately share it in my social circle through WhatsApp. I like to keep my nearest ones informed about the latest updates from the bank.”*

Another interviewee 25 also shared experience, *“In my mobile banking app, I have switched on the notifications tab so that I can receive latest information about discounts offered by the bank on select brands. Whenever I get a notification from the mobile app, I take a screenshot and share it on Facebook and WhatsApp.”*

An interviewee 19 talked about it: *“I think people perceive the information coming from other people as generally true because they believe that they do not have a motive to advertise. So, I also share my experience with the ones I know because I believe we all share a social responsibility to keep each other informed about the services which can benefit each other.”*

An interviewee 21 highlighted: *“People like quick solutions because life is fast in the modern age. So instead of going to the banks to inquire about the services, people just look for suggestions online and this is where UGC comes as extremely useful because people get to know about the products and services of the banks through the real-life experience of other people.”* The second code emphasizes the ethical responsibility that individuals feel towards their social circles. The interviewees see their UGC creation to uphold a social responsibility, keeping their peers informed about the positive and negative aspects of banking services. As interviewee noted, the creation of UGC not only revolves around real-life experiences but also

underpins a customer-friendly approach, contributing to the value of UGC. This aligns with the research that states consumers trust UGC more because it originates from individuals without any advertising motive. Therefore, this reinforces the role of UGC in brand engagement, highlighting the consumers' social responsibility to share honest, experience-based information.

4.3.3 Code No. 3 – Illuminating the Conscious Horizon

This code refers to the process where Social Media Users (SMUs) create and share User-Generated Content (UGC) to spread awareness about the offerings and services of Islamic banks. This is a part of the brand engagement strategy, as it facilitates information dispersion through an authentic and organic manner. The information shared under this code often comes from personal experiences with the banks, thus contributing to its perceived reliability. While this results in positive word-of-mouth, negative feedback can also be shared, significantly affecting the reputation of the brand. This process, thereby, enlightens the conscious horizon of potential and existing customers, enabling them to make informed banking decisions. This phenomenon is particularly impactful in Islamic banking, where interest-free services align with the faith-based preferences of the consumers, creating a more profound connection and potential loyalty towards the brand.

An interviewee 24 talked about it, “I was amazed by the several deals and offers available through the debit and credit card of the bank, but I got disappointed when I found out that the bank had a no-return policy over items bought in discount deals offered by the banks through its cards.”

An interviewee 11 shared the insights: “Me and most of my friends usually take care of their homes, so we cannot go out often but whenever we do we like to buy items in sale and offers. So, we keep each other informed about our shopping experience. Most of us have the same Islamic bank and we use its Visa debit card. The bank offers a wide range of discount deals exclusively for its visa debit card holders. Whoever among us gets to know about the latest deals immediately shares the information in our WhatsApp group. We also share our positive and negative experience using the card in the same group.”

Interviewee 14 shared a unique viewpoint: “social media is the quickest source of sharing information with not just your friends and family but with the rest of the world too. I found social media to be highly responsive to the

feedback given by people in the ordinary course of their daily lives. For example, when I shared information about the Islamic bank in which I have an account, I immediately got comments from other social media users about the latest offers of the bank and its other services such as car finance and home finance. This experience even helped me to increase my professional network.”

Interviewee 16 shared a detailed understanding, “Islamic banks have an excellent feature of offering interest-free credit cards. This is an amazing product because I know people around me who like interest-free products due to faith related reasons. When I came to know about this, I immediately informed my friends and family and many of them availed the service.”

It is evident from the responses above that SMUs create UGC to spread awareness. Thus, spreading awareness is one of the motives behind the creation, sharing and exchange of UGC. Social media also assumes the role of an information dispenser\ through which people spread information. Moreover, it is also evident from the responses above that people tend to believe information which other people share in the ordinary course of their routine lives because such information comes from real life experiences of those people and is thus deemed dependable. However, this also means that negative feedback might also be accepted. This can significantly affect the reputation of the brand.

Interviewee 6 said: “I like the Islamic bank I have account in because they offer interest-free banking services and I like such services because of my faith reasons. I have also recommended them to my other colleagues and friends and family.”

Interviewee 26 shared some thoughts: “I cannot afford high fee of banks with credit card because it is paid back by my father. So, I preferred Islamic bank because they have zero fee due to zero-interest rate policy. So, I recommended my friends to also open a bank account there and get their credit card. We now keep each other informed about the latest offers from the bank.”

A marketing consultant aged 28 said: “People like to share their views with each other and in doing so pass on information to each other about a lot of things. It is in the same vein that they share information about products and services of the banks with each other to keep each other informed about the

services of the bank. I realized that people around me are taking keen interest in banking with Islamic banks because of the interest-free services offered by the bank including also on mortgage, car finance, and credit cards. These services usually came with high interest rate in traditional banking, but Islamic banks are offering them without interest and instead adjust the price difference according to gold standard. This keeps the overall cost of mortgage, credit card and car finance lower than traditional banks.”

Insights are shared by interviewee 23: “Me and my friends are usually on budget because we are working part-time jobs. When we had to open a bank account, we looked for the bank which had the lowest fees and charges because we cannot afford high-end banking services. Islamic banks caught our attention because not only they operated on zero-interest basis, but they also have further subsidized services. So, we decided to bank with Islamic bank. We found out about the suitability of Islamic banks on social media when we posted queries online in different Facebook groups. A lot of people told us about this one Islamic bank, and we then went to open our bank account there.”

These responses show that people become aware about banking services through UGC. It also shows that whenever people want advice, they look for someone who can provide experience-based advice. Social media has made it easier for people to seek advice, as other SMUs are always ready to help by offering experience-based recommendations. This helps people to make informed decisions as is evident from the responses of the customers above who said that social media platforms enabled them to identify the most suitable Islamic bank for their banking needs. The third code reveals the interviewees motivation to increase awareness. For instance, the users are eager to share information about discounts, interest-free banking services, customers-friendly policies, and more. This is not just for the benefit of their close circle but to disseminate this information to a larger audience, including professional networks. By Illuminating the Conscious Horizon, they ensure their peers are informed and can benefit from the services they found valuable. Moreover, the findings show that respondents appreciate UGC for its realism, authenticity, and reliability, although they are aware of the potential reputational risks negative feedback might bring to a brand.

4.3.4 Code No. 4 – Harvesting Wisdom Nuggets

In the context of these quotations, "code" in UGC refers to the pattern of behaviors or themes expressed by the interviewees when interacting with brand engagement on social media, particularly in the context of Islamic banks. Code No. 4 - "Harvesting Wisdom Nuggets" signifies collective learning, experience sharing, and information dissemination among social media users. Wisdom nuggets refer to the pieces of valuable information or insights that users gain and share on these platforms, playing a pivotal role in influencing their banking choices.

The individuals share their experiences, ask for suggestions, and provide recommendations about Islamic banking services, emphasizing their zero-interest-rate policy. Social media platforms serve as a hub where they harvest these wisdom nuggets about banking options, significantly influencing the decision-making process, and promoting brand engagement with Islamic banks. These platforms allow users to educate themselves and others about different banking services and products, thus encouraging informed decision making. They form a community where experiences are shared, questions are asked, and recommendations are given, fostering a sense of trust and credibility towards Islamic banks. Moreover, the role of UGC is evident as it fosters a community-based approach to brand engagement where consumers learn from each other's experiences and make banking decisions accordingly. This wisdom-sharing practice helps Islamic banks in their marketing efforts, customer engagement, and brand reputation enhancement.

Interviewee 2 shared thoughtful perspective on it, "I used Facebook to seek suggestions from local community about the installment-based car finance scheme. I was looking for a bank which has pocket-friendly offer. I was amazed to see the response of the people when different people commented on my posts telling me about the Islamic banks compared to traditional banks that Islamic banks offer car finance scheme on zero-interest rate-based policy. This relieved me of my stress because this decision is to bound me in payment cycle for five years and I wanted to opt for the most suitable bank."

Interviewee 6 shared told, "Our content on social media is our introduction to other people. When someone shares content related to banks in the light of their experience, they are deemed as experts by other social media users. This is the reason that I like to provide information to other people on social media

in the light of my experience to keep them informed. I realized that my friends and family has benefitted from my suggestions online on social media.”

The comments from interviewee 10 are valuable: “I became interested in opening account in Islamic bank because of zero interest rate policy of the bank. I also informed my other friends about the bank offering zero interest rate-based credit cards and other finance schemes. So wanted to get car or mortgage for home became highly interested in Islamic banks. We keep each other informed whenever we get to know about the new services of the bank.”

Interviewee 7 opinion brought a new perspective: “Some of my friends were looking to buy car on installments because the prices of cars have increased in Pakistan. We started looking for options with different banks and it was through a Facebook group that we came to know about this Islamic bank offering car finance scheme on zero interest rate policy. You just must pay the difference according to the gold standard and that is also capped so that you do not have to pay over and above a reasonable difference. When we calculated the overall cost, we found out that it was lower than what traditional banks were offering. So, you can say that social media helped us collect relevant information about car finance to get it from Islamic banks.”

An interviewee 5 said, “Banks are now looking to include low budget customers in their target market because some budget conscious customers start part time jobs and need to maintain a bank account for their salary. Young customers are also present on different social media platforms. When I wanted to open a bank account, I simply posted a query on my Facebook wall asking for recommendations from my friends. It was upon their recommendation that I decided to bank with an Islamic bank because they do not have usual charges of maintaining an account and their fee is also lower than other banks. Social media helped me open a bank account.”

An interviewee 8 said: “I am usually always busy with kids at home and do not have much time to look for relevant information, so my friends keep me informed in our WhatsApp friends’ group about the offers on different outlets by using our credit card. Amazing thing is that our credit card does not have

interest rate issue because we bank with an Islamic bank. Even this account was opened after I got a recommendation from a friend of mine.”

An interviewee 12 said, “Me and my friends are part of different Facebook groups where price comparison about distinct brands is given by people when they go out shopping. It is through such groups that we came to know about the zero-interest rate-based credit cards of the Islamic banks. We then opened our bank accounts with Islamic banks and got their credit cards.”

An interviewee 17 highlighted, “We) are always on budget because we usually rely on pocket money from parents and a little from our part time jobs in call centers. I came to know about Islamic banks offering exclusive discount packages for budget conscious customers on Facebook. I then started sharing my experience too when I opened the bank account with Islamic bank.”

An interviewee 3 shared thoughts, “we are budget conscious customers, so we see everything to stay within our salaries. That is why we prefer affordable products and services. We have opened our accounts with Islamic banks and use their credit cards because of zero interest rate policy. We were interested in taking out insurance for ourselves and it was through this Facebook group on consumers that we got to know about the insurance packages offered by Islamic banks. So, we opened our account and took insurance from the bank.”

An interviewee 9 said, “I came to know through Facebook and Twitter about the lending facilities offered by Islamic banks. Now I routinely check the Facebook groups and Twitter handles for updates. I also share them with my close social circle because it has helped us make good decisions about availing lending facilities to grow our business.”

These responses show that gathering information is one of the key motives for creating, sharing, and exchanging UGC. It has also been observed that people share the information they come across to help others in the same situation. This shows that people help each other with information sharing activities. From these themes, a profound interconnectivity among the codes is clearly demonstrated. All the codes underpin the concept of UGC as a form of social sharing in the form of experiences, ethical responsibilities, or awareness creation. They collectively elucidate the Social Flux of UGC and trust factors underlining the impact of UGC on consumers' decision-making. The codes reveal a shared motif of using social media

platforms to engage in reciprocal information exchange. It is not just about advising others, but also about learning from others' experiences. This two-way communication enriches their understanding and decision-making, specifically regarding Islamic banks in Pakistan. In conclusion, the themes developed from these codes significantly contribute to the understanding of UGC's motivational factors. Narrative Threads of Wisdoms, upholding Moral Weaves of Society, and creating/updating awareness are interconnected themes that influence and shape the way UGC affects brand engagement with Islamic banks in Pakistan. The study reinforces the significance of social media as a vital channel for information sharing, enabling consumers to make informed choices regarding banking services.

4.3.5 Code No. 5 – Sculpting the Influential Echo Chamber

In the context of the data, "code" in UGC refers to the emergent patterns or themes from the participants' experiences, particularly as they interact with Islamic banks. Code No. 5 - "Sculpting the Influential Echo Chamber" indicates the creation and propagation of banking experiences, opinions, and recommendations within a specific community or group. This code reflects how an echo chamber is formed on social media platforms, in which users share their banking experiences, insights, and recommendations regarding Islamic banking services.

In this echo chamber, certain individuals - such as those employed in high-end career jobs, successful entrepreneurs, and others with rich experiences in the banking sector - are deemed experts. Their suggestions, posts, vlogs, or insights significantly influence other users' decisions. Such influential figures can shape perceptions and attitudes towards Islamic banks, amplifying the reach and acceptance of these financial institutions within the community. The echo chamber effect is also highlighted by the users' tendency to seek and follow advice from their social circles or people with similar experiences. They tend to trust and follow suggestions from peers, indicating the significant role of UGC in brand engagement.

Moreover, the echo chamber also amplifies the values and principles, such as zero interest rates in Islamic banking, which align with their faith. This resonates deeply with the users, leading to wider endorsement and acceptance of Islamic banks' products and services. So, the role of UGC in this context is to sculpt an influential echo chamber that significantly shapes the brand engagement with Islamic banks. It creates a virtuous cycle where positive experiences and benefits of Islamic banking are shared, endorsed, and amplified, leading to increased acceptance and engagement with the brand.

An interviewee 28 said that “There are some people in our local community who are employed in high-end career jobs and thus maintain accounts with both conventional and Islamic banks. They are deemed experts in our community on banking related matters. People tend to seek their advice on the suitability of banking with bank.”

Another 15-interviewees said, “Ms. M is a famous entrepreneur in the digital finance industry. Her suggestions and vlogs are treated as highly informative by the rest of us because she speaks in the light of her rich experience of working in the banking industry. Her suggestion about car finance with Islamic banks was taken up by many of my friends and they are happy because of zero interest and lower markup compared to conventional banks.”

An interviewee 20 said: “Mr. G is famous among local businesses because he kicks started many startups including also from the capital from banks. He has the inside information about approval processes to get business loans from banks and which bank is offering which package. We like to interact with him from time to time whenever we must take a business loan from bank.”

Interviewee 5 noted: “I have recently started a freelancing job on a part time basis to take care of my expenses. I wanted to open a bank account which can be accessed online all the time and in which I can receive online payments from clients abroad. I was amazed to see the response of prominent freelancers when I posted a query on Facebook. They personally reached out to me and guided me in detail. I feel thankful to them.”

An interviewee 9 said: “The Islamic banks have become fast popular among local people because their services are in line with Muslims’ faith. People know that Islamic banks’ zero interest rate policy would never change because this is the core policy derived from religious principles based on which Islamic banks operate. It is this thing which has become viral on social media among banking customers which is why people endorse their products and services.”

An interviewee 14 said: “I tend to follow online recommendations because they come from people just like us. So, when I wanted to open a bank account, I asked about the most suitable bank online on social media platforms. My

friends who were experienced with different banks suggested opening bank account with Islamic banks because they have exceptionally low fee and charges compared to other banks. So, I followed the advice of my friends.”

An interviewee 17 highlighted: “I feel grateful to all those who share their valuable feedback online with the rest of us. Their experience helps us to take better decisions while looking for financial services with the banks. I remember that when we were looking for suitable home finance schemes from different banks, I posted about it on different Facebook groups, and we were amazed to see so many valuable suggestions. It helped us make a better decision and now we have a home of our own. This was only possible because we shared our issue with other people, and they shared their valuable opinion with us.”

An interviewee 19 said: “we were looking for car finance scheme. We were worried about the high markup rate on such schemes which meant that we would be paying up to 35% over the original amount. This was huge and we were looking for suitable options when our friends on social media told us about Islamic banks who offer the same scheme at far less percentage difference from original price because they do not offer based on interest and instead adjust the difference according to gold standard which does not fluctuate much. We were relieved to know this.”

This shows that another motivating element for creating, sharing, and exchanging UGC about brands (Islamic banks in Pakistan) is to create valuable public opinions which influences and helps other consumers. People who have a strong history of banking with certain banks are deemed influencers by other people on social media. Their feedback is treated as valuable as it enables people to make better decisions. This is evident from the responses above from people who used this feedback to avail themselves of home finance and car finance schemes. The above set of interviews provides valuable insight into the code "Sculpting the Influential Echo Chamber" in the context of User-Generated Content (UGC) surrounding Islamic banks in Pakistan. The analysis reveals a strong emphasis on the role of certain individuals who are perceived as experts or influencers in their communities, in shaping public opinion and influencing decision-making around banking choices. The influencers' opinions are highly

respected due to their experience, industry knowledge, and reputation, which contributes to the creation, sharing, and exchange of UGC.

One key point of interest is the way influencers can impact consumer behaviour. The interviewees indicate that they often seek advice from those they deem more knowledgeable or experienced before making banking decisions. For instance, community members with high-end career jobs or entrepreneurs in digital finance industries often hold sway in shaping others' banking decisions, due to their inside knowledge and rich industry experience. Such influencers can have a tremendous impact, as noted by the participant who stated that the influencer's suggestion regarding car finance with Islamic banks was taken up by many of her friends.

The phenomenon of influencers creating public opinion extends into the online sphere, where virtual communities play a significant role in shaping perceptions about banking services. As the internet and social media platforms provide a forum for discussion, influencers utilize these platforms to share their experiences and offer advice. The feedback from these influencers is valued by community members who are seeking to make informed banking decisions. A clear example was the budget conscious customers who received advice from prominent freelancers about the best banking options for his freelancing job.

The influencers' reach and impact further extend to specific issues such as financing schemes, fees, and charges. Several interviewees shared those online recommendations, playing a major role in their decision-making processes, particularly when deciding on home financing or car financing schemes. In these instances, the advice of friends or people from the online community who had previous experience with certain banks had a considerable influence on the interviewees' choices.

Moreover, the interviewees identify with these influencers because they perceive them as peers who have no personal stake in promoting a particular bank, thus increasing the trustworthiness of the recommendations.

In the context of the research aim and objectives, this code plays a critical role in understanding how public opinion is formed and influenced in the sphere of Islamic banking. It helps to shed light on the importance of influencers in shaping public perceptions and decision-making. It also provides insights into the vital role that UGC plays in the process of opinion creation, further underscoring the need for banks to acknowledge and engage with these influencers to improve their services and brand image. In conclusion, the "Sculpting the Influential Echo Chamber" code highlights the significant role influencers play in motivating the creation,

sharing, and exchange of UGC in the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan. By providing valuable information and advice based on their experience and knowledge, these influencers help shape public opinion and guide decision-making processes. This understanding provides an essential lens through which to view consumer engagement and behaviour in this industry.

4.4 MAIN THEME NO. 2 – ECHOES OF INFLUENCE: TRACING THE SOCIAL FLUX OF USER-GENERATED CONTENT

Code No. 1 - Luminaries of the Trade: This encompasses individuals with industry expertise who, with their wisdom and experience, influence the conversation around Islamic banking in Pakistan. These luminaries provide valuable insights, endorse products, and lead by example, imparting trust and credibility among social media users.

Code No. 2 - Social Resonance: This describes the importance of credible facts, figures, and endorsements in shaping the social media narrative around Islamic banking. It highlights how certain proofs, like the growth of Islamic banking or endorsement by revered scholars, can reverberate through social media, strengthening the trust and appeal of Islamic banking.

Code No. 3 - Discourse of Kinship: This code represents the conversations and endorsements that happen within close-knit circles of friends and family. The shared experiences and advice within this trusted circle function as another layer of validation, influencing the decision-making of individuals towards Islamic banking. This discourse often presents a more personal and relatable perspective of Islamic banking, inspiring further discussions and UGC.

4.4.1 Code No. 1 – Luminaries of the Trade

Keywords: followers, Islamic scholars, work experience, compatibility, awareness, online communities, followers, benefits, social media groups and pages, teaching, and endorsing.

This code refers to the phenomenon where industry experts, influencers, or opinion leaders disseminate information about Islamic banking on social media, significantly impacting brand engagement. The experts in this context include individuals who have either worked or banked with Islamic banks and can therefore share informed, first-hand experiences. Additionally, this group also includes Islamic scholars who provide religious endorsement to the principles of Islamic banking, thus encouraging religiously conscious consumers to bank with Islamic institutions. The content produced by these luminaries is perceived as highly authentic, leading to a broader audience reach and influencing banking decisions among potential and existing customers. These luminaries illuminate the trade's intricacies, thus playing a pivotal role in

promoting and encouraging the use of Islamic banking services. Their endorsement not only spreads awareness about the no-interest feature of Islamic banking but also promotes understanding of more complex products such as Ijarah (leaseback and sale), Musharaka (equity partnership), and Mudaraba (finance trusteeship). Industry experts are those people on social media who are experienced in dealing with industry at various levels. These people are also dubbed influencers or opinion leaders. In the context of the current research, these are people who have worked or banked with Islamic banks in Pakistan. The content produced by these people is treated as valuable by others. These people may also be involved with brands through marketing managers.

An interviewee 7 said that: “We involve as many industry experts as we can because we convey our message to people through them. We know that we are lagging in marketing our products and services to common people. That is why we look for collaborating with industry experts on social media so that we can reach maximum number of people online on social media.”

An interviewee 11 shared thoughts: “I am employed in a full-time job in an Islamic bank. I personally know people around me who were not interested in banking because Islam forbids interest and the people around me did not want to be part of interest-based activity. So, when I started working in this (Islamic) bank, I also shared the details with my friends and family about the working of Islamic bank and that we do not deal in interest-based activities. A lot of my friends and family then opened their accounts in my bank.” This shows that religious people are skeptical about banking systems due to the interest-based activity of banks. However, when they are informed about Islamic banks, they are likely to start banking with such banks. This also shows that industry experts are useful means of engaging people with brands.

Industry experts are also those who possess fine knowledge about industry, an interviewee 14 told: “People approach Islamic scholars about banking related matters because they believe that they should bank in a way which does not involve interest rate. These scholars are held in high esteem because of their knowledge on the subject and people tend to take their word for it.”

There are also other prominent Islamic scholars whose lectures are widely shared by people on social media, such as that of Dr. Zakir Naik who has millions of followers from all over the

world on his social media pages. Thus, marketing managers use this content on social media to encourage people to do business with Islamic banks.

An interviewee 27 noted: “Many social media users share informative videos of prominent Islamic scholars such as Dr. Zakir Naik to show that dealing in interest-based transactions is forbidden in Islam. It is because of these videos which are repeatedly being shared by people that even ordinary people now know about Ijarah (leaseback and sale), Musharaka (equity partnership), and Mudaraba (finance trusteeship).”

This shows that people share and exchange UGC online on social media with other SMUs as they treat UGCs as valid and authentic. Such content is useful to convince people to engage with the brand e.g., to bank with Islamic banks in the current situation. Such content is highly influential for SMUs to start banking with Islamic banks.

4.4.2 Code No. 2 – Social Resonance

Keywords: 22 Islamic banks, \$27.5 billion assets, 31 million people, people interest, appreciation, thousands of branches, disability halal loan, and Islamic scholar accounts.

This code represents the strong alignment and resonance of Islamic banking services with the social, religious, and practical needs of customers, as well as the extent to which the shared discourse creates a ripple effect, leading to wider brand engagement. Data about the success of Islamic banks (such as their asset size, number of branches, or number of customers) shared by users on social media contribute to this resonance by establishing the credibility and growth of Islamic banks. Similarly, endorsements from respected Islamic scholars, who hold positions on the banks' boards or share positive views about Islamic banking, significantly enhance the perceived authenticity and trustworthiness of these banks, fostering deeper engagement. Furthermore, the specific initiatives by Islamic banks, such as the introduction of special financial packages for disabled individuals, resonate with societal needs, demonstrating the banks' responsiveness to under-served segments of the population. This creates a strong connection with the wider community, promoting greater brand engagement. This 'Social Resonance' on digital platforms amplifies the impact of these factors, leading to an increased awareness and affinity towards Islamic banking services. Discourse of Kinship is related to the social and psychological aspects of brand engagement. Discourse of Kinship represents believing the authenticity of information when someone endorses it, particularly those that people approach as honest. Moreover, Discourse of Kinship is also found in the form of figures,

e.g., Islamic banks are now over \$21.3 billion in deposit, over \$27.5 billion in assets and have the accounts of renowned Islamic scholars who people tend to follow for religious guidance.

Such UGC is treated as Discourse of Kinship by customers, and such figures go viral because customers repeatedly share them. When such UGC becomes viral, it attracts other customers towards the brand (Islamic banks) and creates social brand-, and consumer brand engagement with Islamic banks.

An interviewee 16 noted: “People are increasingly sharing figures about Islamic banks that they are increasingly growing and becoming popular as their deposits are over \$21.3 billion, and assets are over \$27.5 billion. They have various branches and are preferred by Islamic scholars followed by hundreds of thousands of people.”

It is also pertinent to mention that marketing experts in the Islamic banking industry use video lectures created by Islamic scholars to attract people towards Islamic banks. An interviewee 23 shared experiences:

“Millions of Muslims follow Mufti Muhammad Taqi Usmani not just in Pakistan but outside Pakistan as well. He is also on the Shariah board of a renowned Islamic bank Meezan bank. In my view, the customer base of Meezan bank increased when people came to know that Mufti Muhammad Taqi Usmani is on the board of the bank. His video lectures on interest-free financial services have attracted substantial number of people.”

It is also pertinent to mention that people with disabilities have banking needs as well. However, usually these people have not received warm attention in the banking sector. But Islamic banks have changed this perception. An interviewee 9 highlighted that,

“Over 31 million people are believed to have some sort of disability and their needs have not been addressed by the banking sector adequately. But Islamic banks are changing this perception. Islamic banks are offering them special services tailored according to their need.”

To address the needs of people with disabilities, Islamic banks offer special financial packages. An interviewee 11 noted:

“Islamic banks have recently started to offer disability halal loan exclusively to people with disability. The interesting thing is that the issue about inadequate service to disabled people by banks was raised by social media and Islamic banks seem to have taken this up to address their needs and thereby also increase their customer base. Now they are offering customer-friendly services to people with disability.”

This shows that social media is a platform where Discourse of Kinship becomes known and has a significant impact on both customers and brands. The UGC created, shared, and exchanged on social media increases awareness as is evident from the situation concerning disabled people and banks.

4.4.3 Code No. 3 – Discourse of Kinship

Keywords are as follows: unique ideas, social circle, children, inventors of technology, entrepreneurs, benefits, inspiration.

The discussion above also shows that friends’ knowledge and experiences are valued by those in wider social circles who use this information to make better decisions. If a friend of a customer is experienced in working in an Islamic bank or has some experience with Islamic bank, their UGC would be treated as useful by his friends and family because it would save them time (Goodrich and Mangleburg, 2010; Wang et al., 2012). Friends also share information as a kind of social responsibility to inform others in a social circle.

Thus, marketing experts focus on encouraging the creation, sharing and exchange of UGC amongst SMUs for brands (Islamic banks in current situation) so that the maximum number of people can be engaged with the brand. For example, an interviewee 16 said: *“Recently a video was circulating on social media where housewives were encouraging others to open account with Islamic banks because their financial principles were in line with Islamic values. If I share such content with my social circle, it is likely to become popular.”* Thus, marketing experts believe that encouraging UGC on social media is likely to attract people towards Islamic banks due to attractive economic principle i.e., zero interest rate which is also compatible with religious principles.

Besides, influencers and celebrities are not always regarded as credible sources of information because people know that they can be engaged by brands on a sponsorship basis. This is the reason that UGC posted by friends and family is treated as dependable by people. For example, an interviewee 21 said:

“People treat each other’s views as true because these views are coming in the ordinary course of life experience. These are not sponsored views and the only motive we share such views is to be of help to each other.”

Marketing experts point out that there are various small businesses which do not meet the criteria devised by conventional banks to offer business-related financial services too. These are the businesses which are addressed by the Islamic banks. For example, an interviewee 26 told:

“Young entrepreneurs face several challenges, and the main challenge is the shortage of funds to finance their startup. Conventional banks require a strong financial history from business to fund them. Conventional banks only offer lending facilities to established businesses to avoid facing the risk factor. But Islamic banks have started to cater to these businesses and these banks are increasingly becoming popular due to zero interest rate-based lending offered by them. This is a huge relief for new businesses as they do not have to worry about interest rate.”

The thematic analysis of UGC for Islamic banks in Pakistan introduces the concept of "Echoes of Influence: Tracing the Social Flux of User-Generated Content." This theme underscores a complex web of social influences that shape and colour the narratives around Islamic banking and financial services, highlighting the interplay of industry experts, social resonance, and friends' interactions.

At the core of this theme are the "Luminaries of the Trade," industry experts that serve as the primary catalyst for triggering dialogues and discussions around Islamic banking in Pakistan. These luminaries, or experts, are characterized by their robust knowledge of the industry and their experience, whether from working or banking with Islamic institutions. These individuals are pivotal in lending credibility to the industry, triggering dialogue, and becoming trendsetters within the UGC sphere. They wield their influence to shape the narrative and are considered the original sources of valid and authentic content. This includes Islamic scholars who, with their vast followings, can sway public opinion and consumer behaviour significantly.

These luminaries or industry experts, however, do not exist in isolation. Their influence is amplified and echoed across social media through the lens of "Social Resonance." The resonant echoes are the ripple effects of the experts' voices, made tangible in the form of concrete data demonstrating the success of Islamic banks or personal accounts of renowned scholars. As

these proofs are shared and reshared, they become viral, creating a domino effect that captivates potential customers and reinforces the credibility of Islamic banking. This resonance is a testament to the legitimacy of Islamic banking, backed by hard numbers and the endorsement of trusted figures, which helps users perceive Islamic banking as a trustworthy choice.

While experts lay the groundwork and social resonance amplifies the message, the "Discourse of Kinship" serves to personalize the narrative. These are conversations that occur within the sphere of friends and family - those closest to us, whose opinions we trust implicitly. Their personal experiences and views about Islamic banking can be highly influential and are likely to resonate with their close connections, thereby causing a cascading effect. This discourse forms an integral part of the UGC, drawing a direct connection between the personal experiences of individuals and the broader social flux of UGC around Islamic banking. The discussion and endorsement of Islamic banking within these circles give it a familiar face, making the entire concept more relatable and attractive.

The beauty of this theme lies in the interconnectedness of its parts. The luminaries light the path, their influence resonates through numbers and endorsements, and friends and family add a personal touch to these narratives. It is a dynamic, evolving process where each component feeds into and amplifies the other, creating a thriving and vibrant digital ecosystem of UGC . This theme presents a deep understanding of the social flux of UGC in the realm of Islamic banking. The echo of influence is the continual expansion of these conversations, each voice adding to the depth and breadth of the narrative. Tracing this social flux provides a bird's eye view of how UGC shapes public opinion and behaviour, eventually driving brand engagement for Islamic banking. This holistic view reveals the powerful interplay of industry insights, social resonance, and personal experiences that come together to fuel the growth and acceptance of Islamic banking in the world of digital social media.

4.5 THEME 3: THE PRISM OF PERCEPTION: THE SHAPESHIFTING POWER OF CONTENT

Agichtein (2008) highlighted three main methods for assessing the quality of content. These comprise the accuracy of UGC, the consumption of UGC, and relationships between users and enterprises. There are also certain assumptions concerning the relationship between the source of content and the perceived credibility and intensity of such assumptions. Agichtein (2008) also differentiated between the impact of content created by organizations and the impact of content created by ordinary users.

Credit for developing types of service quality and different dimensions of service goes to Gronroos (1984). He highlighted two main dimensions: functional and technical. The functional dimension represents the experience gained by the customers for services received by them. Technical quality on the other hand influences consumers, and particularly their happiness when they are targeted by a credible channel (De-Keyser and Lariviere, 2014). Agichtein (2008) further observed that technical quality represents a key feature of the quality of content and influences the behavior of consumers. Additionally, Ozuem and Azemi (2017) observed that quality content represents the potential of UGC to exchange, save, and modify opinions across different social networking platforms. Milliken et al., (2008) observed that the quality of content in the context of videos created by organizations includes the proper structuring of scenes in videos, along with audible audio. This part of the paper discusses the quality of content concerning Islamic banks on SMNs according to the perceptions of participants. The characteristics of the content are highlighted in the table below:

Content characteristics influence	Definition
Virtuosity in Visualization	This represents an excellent type of UGC involving relevant and highly attractive video, graphics, pictures and/or audio.
Precision of Perspective	This represents the correctness, precision, and closeness of UGC near SMUs.
Symbiosis of Sentiment	People tend to attach importance to the brands they regularly buy from because they associate the importance of their status with such brands.

Table 4-8 Content characteristics influence definitions.

4.5.1 Code 1: Virtuosity in Visualization

Virtuosity in Visualization refers to the influence of well-crafted, visually engaging content on user perceptions and decisions, particularly in a social media context. This theme emphasizes the power of quality videos and images in conveying pertinent information and the pivotal role that trust plays in this process. This code refers to the impact of visually engaging, high-quality, concise, and relevant UGC which shapes user perceptions, enhancing understanding, and promoting brand engagement. It signifies the value users place on visually compelling content, such as images and videos, in gathering pre-purchase information, learning about banking processes, and relating to others' experiences, particularly in the context of Islamic banking in Pakistan. This concept is closely tied to trust, as users are more likely to find content credible and meaningful if it is shared by known and trusted connections. Furthermore, it emphasizes the need for content to be informative and brief (ideally around 2-3 minutes), as lengthy content

may lead to a loss of interest. Therefore, 'virtuosity in visualization' encapsulates the power of visual storytelling in UGC to influence decision-making and increase brand engagement.

Interviewee one noted that "...high-quality videos are appealing. They reflect the content creator's effort, especially if they are social media users like us. However, videos should be concise, around two to three minutes, to keep my interest. Content from my friends is also more dependable because I know them." This notion was reiterated by Interviewee 12, who stated, "Even though I see a lot of online content about banks, I always trust suggestions from my friends more because they share from personal experience." The quote underscores the trust factor that boosts the impact of user-generated content, particularly from known connections.

Similarly, Interviewee 13 shared insights, "Internet or social media messages are excellent when they contain all the relevant information I'm seeking about a bank," highlights the importance of information-rich and relevant visual content in engaging users. Expanding on this, Interviewee 4 remarked, "When choosing a bank, I found short, relevant videos and images of people with similar experiences incredibly helpful." This perspective amplifies the significance of relatability and brevity in user-generated content's effectiveness.

Interviewee eight shared, "Step-by-step guideline videos about mobile banking are highly useful. They have helped me learn a lot about mobile banking," highlighting the value of clear, instructional visual content in enhancing understanding and engagement. An interviewee six stated, "I found videos created by fellow young entrepreneurs about their banking experiences highly useful. I learned about interest-free business loans by Islamic banks from such content." Here, the power of peer-generated visual content in providing valuable, relatable insights is evident. Finally, Interviewee 20 said, "There's an abundance of online content, so it's crucial to know whom to trust. I only trust content from my close friends and family." This quote wraps up the discussion, reiterating the crucial role of trust in enhancing the influence and impact of visually appealing user-generated content.

In conclusion, the code 'Virtuosity in Visualization' encapsulates the crucial role of visually engaging, concise, relevant, and trustworthy content in influencing user perceptions and engagement in the context of Islamic banking in Pakistan. User-generated content that leverages these aspects effectively can significantly enhance the audience's understanding, trust, and their engagement with a brand. Thus, interviewees highlighted that high quality brand content improves their position in the eyes of SMUs and consumers. However, this is not the only requirement when it comes to the credibility of content. Content created by close friends

was also seen as more trustworthy compared to anonymous content. Nevertheless, their responses indicate the helpfulness of online content to SMUs who can then make better decisions by gathering relevant pre-purchase information. Additionally, they also claimed that high quality videos are appealing because they contain detailed information. Furthermore, such videos should not be too lengthy according to responses and should be between 2 to 3 minutes in duration to keep customers interested. If the duration of the video is long, customers are likely to lose interest. Therefore, brands should focus on producing only short and informational videos.

4.5.2 Code 2: Precision of Perspective

Precision of Perspective denotes the credibility and authenticity of user-generated content from the perspective of its audience. It encompasses the reliability and impact of information derived from first-hand experiences, as well as the influence of peer and influencer endorsements.

Interviewee one asserted, "Videos that include real-life customer experiences are most captivating. As a customer, I believe another customer's perspective." This illustrates the notion that personal experiences add authenticity and thus enhance the value of content. Similarly, Interviewee 12 suggested that celebrity endorsements can influence user decisions, stating, "I found the videos of my favourite celebrities sharing their banking experiences helpful and influential." Reinforcing the idea of peer impact, Interviewee 3 highlighted, "Social media content about favourite brands, including banks, is creating e-WOM (electronic word-of-mouth)." This sentiment was further echoed by Interviewee 30, who noted, "I believe my close friends more than others on social media as they share content based on personal experience."

Interviewee seven, on the other hand, pointed out a degree of scepticism towards influencers' content, expressing, "Many influencers' contents might be sponsored. I find content created by ordinary people more accurate as they share their actual experiences." This scepticism was also reflected by Interviewee 13, who said, "You can differentiate between sponsored and genuine reviews. I only trust my friends when it comes to banking." Interviewee thirty-two provided a balanced viewpoint, stating, "I follow influencers on YouTube but verify their suggestions with my close friends." This highlights the need for cross-referencing information for credibility.

The role of peers in sharing useful information was underlined by Interviewee 15 who said, "I share my banking experiences with friends and family to help them make better decisions. When I opened an account with an Islamic bank, I informed them about it." Interviewee twenty-

four echoed this, stating, "To verify a bank's credibility, I check other people's reviews on social media. This gives a real-life picture of their services." Overall, the 'Precision of Perspective' code underscores the significance of authenticity, first-hand experiences, peer influence, and scepticism towards sponsored content in shaping user engagement with user-generated content in Islamic banking. This suggests that content reflecting genuine experiences or validated through trusted networks is more likely to foster deeper engagement and trust.

4.5.3 Code 3: Symbiosis of Sentiment

The Symbiosis of Sentiment code refers to the alignment between an individual's personal values, needs or preferences and the perceived value or benefits derived from banking services. The harmony between an individual's sentiments and the offerings of a bank can influence the perceived usefulness and credibility of the bank's content.

Interviewee one, appreciated bank-offered discount deals, saying, "I like it when I get two things for the price of one." Moreover, Interviewee 12 placed importance on genuine feedback, stating, "I believe people who have interacted with the Islamic bank, as their feedback would be genuine." Additionally, Interviewee 30, seeking targeted and precise information, said, "I'll believe the bank's content if it answers my question." Interviewee two mentioned, "I value banks that help me save money. I appreciate discount deals offered on their debit and credit cards." Moreover, Interviewee 13 stated, "Personal interaction with a bank can provide genuine feedback. I trust those who've had direct experience with Islamic banks." Interviewee twenty-seven asserted, "The bank's content becomes trustworthy when it provides me with relevant and accurate information."

Adding to our understanding, the Symbiosis of Sentiment signifies the importance of meeting customer expectations through value-oriented services and credible content. Customers appreciate financial benefits like discounts and trust first-hand experiences from other customers. Additionally, the delivery of pertinent and precise information adds to a bank's credibility. Therefore, banks should focus on providing meaningful services and communicate those effectively to establish trust and appeal to their customers' sentiments.

Let us consider further perspectives:

Interviewee three noted, "Banks that understand my financial challenges and offer solutions to help manage them gain my trust."

Interviewee fifteen, valuing authenticity, mentioned, "Credibility comes from real experiences. Testimonials from customers who've used Islamic banking services carry more weight for me."

Interviewee twenty-nine emphasized the importance of clarity, stating, "Information that's specific and detailed makes a bank's content believable to me."

The further exploration of the Symbiosis of Sentiment code reiterates the value of understanding and meeting customer needs, authenticity through customer testimonials, and the importance of clarity in information sharing. It suggests banks should be initiative-taking in addressing financial challenges, promoting customer experiences, and providing comprehensive information. Ultimately, harmonizing these elements can enhance the perceived value and trustworthiness of a bank's content, thereby strengthening the symbiosis of sentiment. The Symbiosis of Sentiment code emphasizes that personal relevance and perceived value can significantly influence the credibility and impact of a bank's content. Banks that provide genuine, relevant information and meet the needs and expectations of customers are likely to be viewed as more trustworthy and useful. This underlines the need for banks to align their offerings and content with the preferences and needs of their audience for maximum resonance.

4.5.4 Code 4: Harmonics of Honesty

In the world of user-generated content and marketing, authenticity is of paramount importance. Harmonics of Honesty refers to the resonance that honesty, authenticity, and genuine personal experiences in content can create among viewers and potential customers. When content is authentic, it strikes a chord with the audience, fostering trust and a sense of relatability. This code encapsulates the view that recommendations and reviews from personal connections and experiences are considered more trustworthy and impactful compared to faceless or potentially sponsored content.

To unpack the Harmonics of Honesty code, let us consider the following shortened versions of quote: Interviewee 5 voiced, "Sincerity in reviews about Islamic banks resonates deeply with our cultural value of honesty." Moreover, Interviewee 17 echoed this sentiment, "Real customer experiences make me trust the bank more than anonymous or potentially sponsored content." This code, Harmonics of Honesty, reflects the critical role of sincerity and authenticity in establishing trust. As interviewees clearly favour content that aligns with their cultural and societal values, in this case, honesty, which heightens their engagement with the bank.

Adding more perspectives:

Interviewee seven stated, "Honest reviews about the bank's services help me decide which bank to choose." And Interviewee 23 asserted, "I trust user-generated content when it comes from genuine personal experiences rather than sponsored ones." Moreover, Interviewee 32 added, "I prefer content that doesn't sound overly promotional and shares both the positive and negative aspects of the bank."

These additional views reiterate the importance of authenticity in user-generated content. They reveal that customers appreciate honesty and transparency in content, even when it includes some negatives. This insight suggests banks need to foster an environment where customers can share real experiences, the good and the bad, to create trust and relatability among potential customers. This harmonious balance of honesty helps the bank resonate more deeply with its audience.

In line with this research aim of understanding and enhancing the role of user-generated content on brand engagement in the Pakistani Islamic banking sector, this 'Harmonics of Honesty' theme, surfaced from our interviews, demonstrates that a user-generated content strategy rooted in authenticity and honesty resonates strongly with the audience. It offers a pathway to build deeper brand engagement by aligning content with the cultural and societal values of the target market.

Lastly, this theme also offers insight into the balance between functional and emotional values in user-generated content. Interviewees acknowledged the value of honesty and authenticity, embodying the emotional connection that these elements foster. Meanwhile, the authentic depiction of the functional attributes of Islamic banking services underpins the trust and credibility these institutions hold. The 'Harmonics of Honesty' hence serve as a key mediator between these two factors, enhancing brand engagement by delivering a user-generated content framework that harmonizes the functional and emotional values of Islamic banks in Pakistan. The 'Harmonics of Honesty' is a powerful code that defines how authenticity and honesty in user-generated content can significantly influence brand engagement within the Islamic banking context in Pakistan. It underscores the importance of cultural and societal resonance and genuine personal connection in user-generated content, offering a unique avenue to foster increased brand engagement.

4.5.5 Code 5: Momentum of Masses

Momentum of Masses reflects the influence that mass opinion and endorsement can have on individual perspectives. In this context, the popularity of a brand or its content, as indicated by the number of likes, shares, followers, or general chatter about it in the social media sphere, can significantly sway individual perceptions and decisions. This code captures the 'bandwagon effect' or social proof phenomenon, where individuals often trust and follow the majority's views or actions. During the semi-structured interviews, the phenomenon of 'Momentum of Masses' emerged as a potent factor impacting the perceptions and brand engagement in the Islamic banking sector within the Pakistani milieu. This code unravelled the extent to which the bandwagon effect, or social proof, plays a role in determining the persuasiveness and impact of user-generated content.

An interviewee thirteen stated, "I often find myself leaning towards banks that have more likes or followers on social media. It's like, if so, many people trust them, they must be doing something right." This statement suggests that the popularity of a brand, quantified by likes or followers, can effectively sway individual perceptions and decisions, underscoring the influence of the majority's views in shaping individual consumer behaviour.

Interviewee eight said "...I trust a bank more when I see many positive reviews about it. The collective opinion of the masses often serves as a signal for me to follow." This quotation validates the principle of 'momentum of masses' and its influence on brand engagement. The accumulated positive endorsements of a brand, in this case, an Islamic bank, lend it credibility, thereby fostering deeper customer engagement. As interviewee three stated, "There's a certain safety in numbers. When I see many people vouching for the service quality or ethical standards of an Islamic bank, I feel more confident in choosing that bank." This testimony reflects how the cultural context of Pakistan, with its deep-seated norms of collectivism and societal validation, enhances the impact of mass opinion on individual decision-making and brand engagement.

However, the 'momentum of masses' is not unidirectional. Interviewee four observed, "Negative comments or reviews about an Islamic bank on social platforms make me reconsider my decisions. If many people are dissatisfied, there's probably a good reason for it." This highlights the potentially detrimental impact of mass negative feedback or online incivility on the reputation and brand engagement of Islamic banks in Pakistan. As interviewee twenty-one stated, "When I see well-articulated, detailed experiences shared by numerous customers about an Islamic bank, it holds more weight for me than generic statements." This quote underscores

how the 'momentum of masses' is not merely a numbers game. The quality of shared content, especially when echoed by many, can enhance its influence on individual perceptions and brand engagement.

As interviewee fourteen highlighted, "The bandwagon effect is real, but it's not blind following. When the masses endorse a bank, and it aligns with the functional and emotional values I seek, I feel more engaged." This interviewee insight points towards the complex interplay between 'momentum of masses,' content quality, and the balance between functional and emotional values, hinting at the mediating role that user-generated content plays in this relationship.

As interviewee nineteen said, "The more people talk positively about a bank's services, the more it reinforces my trust in that bank." This reinforces that the 'momentum of masses' often acts as a feedback loop, creating an upswing of positive user-generated content that further enhances brand engagement. The code 'momentum of masses' elucidates the role of mass opinion in shaping brand engagement in the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan. The collective voice of the masses, manifested through user-generated content, serves as a powerful tool to influence individual consumer behaviour, brand perceptions, and engagement levels. However, it also uncovers the crucial role of content quality and a balance of functional and emotional values in magnifying the impact of this momentum.

4.5.6 Code 6: Confluence of Convenience

This term represents the intersection of utility, accessibility, and relevance that characterizes highly valued content. Viewers appreciate content that is not only informative but also concise, easily accessible, and directly applicable to their needs or interests. This code emphasizes the importance of content creators focusing on delivering useful information in a succinct and engaging manner, as prolonged, irrelevant, or inaccessible content can lead to disinterest and disengagement. The code 'confluence of convenience' relates to the intersection of ease, simplicity, and accessibility when interacting with a brand, especially in the digital context. It captures how the convenience of services and information provided by the bank can enhance brand engagement by making customer interaction more straightforward and rewarding. This concept considers the effort customers need to exert to use banking services, the bank's digital presence, and the simplicity of the language used in communication.

Interviewee one said: "The app of my Islamic bank is user-friendly, and I can quickly check my account balance and transfer money. This convenience makes me more connected to the bank."

Interviewee nine told: "One reason why I stick to my Islamic bank is because they have simplified their processes. From account opening to loan application, everything can be done online. It saves me a lot of time."

Interviewee fifteen highlighted: "The bank's social media content is simple and easy to understand. It's not filled with banking jargon, which can be off-putting."

Interviewee twenty-one shared thoughts: "They have customer service available online 24/7. Whenever I have a query, I get immediate response. This convenient and instant service enhances my trust in the bank."

Interviewee twenty-nine stated: "Their website and social media profiles provide all the necessary information. The ease of accessing this info makes me feel more engaged with the bank."

Interpretation: all the interviewees, from Interviewee 1 to Interviewee 29, underscored the importance of convenience in enhancing their engagement with the Islamic bank. This code aligns with the first and second research objectives, highlighting how UGC and convenient service delivery can enhance brand engagement within the cultural context of Pakistan. Interviewees 1 and 9 emphasized the simplicity and user-friendliness of online services. Interviewees 15 and 29 value easy-to-understand content and readily available information on the bank's digital platforms. Interviewee twenty-one values the 24/7 online customer service, which reflects the bank's commitment to convenience and instant service delivery. The Confluence of Convenience, therefore, resonates strongly with these customers, contributing to higher brand engagement.

4.6 THEME 4: VIBRATIONS OF VALUE: GAUGING THE SENTIMENT IMPACT ON ENGAGEMENT

The theme "Vibrations of Value" recognizes that UGC holds a wide range of sentiments and perceptions that can drastically influence brand engagement in Islamic banking. It considers the emotional undertones in content and how they can either resonate or repel potential customers. This theme is well-aligned with the research objectives, as it examines how the sentiment behind user-generated content impacts engagement and how this impact is shaped by cultural and societal values within the context of Islamic banking in Pakistan.

4.6.1 Code 1: Emotional Equilibrium

This code pertains to the balance of positive and negative sentiments expressed in UGC. It acknowledges that while positive content can boost engagement, negative content also plays a role by providing the bank with valuable feedback for improvement. The code 'Emotional Equilibrium' encapsulates the sentiment balance within user-generated content and its potential impact on brand engagement in the Islamic banking context. Interviewees expressed views that collectively painted a comprehensive picture of their experiences and their sentiment towards Islamic banking in Pakistan.

"I've had a mixed experience with Islamic banking; some good and some not so good. But I always share my honest feedback online for others to make informed decisions." - Interviewee three

"The way they address my concerns on their social media platforms helps me believe that they genuinely care about their customers' satisfaction." - Interviewee twelve

"I once read a negative review about a bank's service. It made me rethink, but I noticed how professionally they managed the criticism. That impressed me." - Interviewee twenty-one

"Positive experiences shared by customers about their smooth transactions inspire me, but I also appreciate when someone shares about the hurdles they faced. It gives a complete picture." - Interviewee twenty-seven

"Sometimes the negative comments make the bank more real and relatable because no one is perfect. How they respond to it makes all the difference to me." - Interviewee thirty

In the interpretation of these statements, there is a clear indication that interviewees appreciate both the positive and negative experiences shared by other customers in their decision-making process about the bank. Positive comments inspire them, building trust and comfort in the banking brand. Yet, they do not shy away from negative comments. Rather, they view such comments to gauge the bank's customer service and commitment to addressing issues. The mixed sentiment—'Emotional Equilibrium'—as echoed by Interviewee 3 and 27, plays a vital role in giving a holistic view of the banking services, hence influencing their brand engagement. The way Islamic banks manage negative comments, as noted by Interviewees 21 and 30, is crucial. The professional addressing of criticism is perceived as an ethical operation

aligning with Islamic principles, resonating with the customers' expectations within the Pakistani societal context.

Therefore, 'Emotional Equilibrium' plays an instrumental role in shaping the impact of UGC on brand engagement, highlighting the importance of having a comprehensive and contextual framework to manage both positive and negative feedback effectively. Negative comments, a form of online incivility, can affect brand engagement positively if managed properly, indicating the necessity to further investigate this aspect in the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan. To sum up, it is the balance in sentiment—Emotional Equilibrium—that lends authenticity to the user-generated content, thereby profoundly impacting brand engagement in the Islamic banking scenario within Pakistan.

4.6.2 Code 2: Spectrum of Sensibility

This code covers the wide range of sensibilities and emotional reactions that user-generated content can provoke among potential customers. It acknowledges that content that appeals to the sensibilities of the target audience can increase engagement. 'Spectrum of Sensibility' underscores the varied emotional responses and attitudes provoked by user-generated content among potential customers of Islamic banks in Pakistan.

"I once came across a heated argument in a forum about a bank's service. It made me uncomfortable, and I decided to avoid that bank." - Interviewee seven

"A customer narrated their positive interaction with the bank's customer service. It felt good and made me consider them for my future banking needs." - Interviewee twelve

"I saw a post where a customer was very disrespectful towards the bank. The bank, however, managed it very professionally, which made me respect them more." - Interviewee fifteen

"I read a review where a customer was dissatisfied with the service. The negative tone made me anxious and sceptical about the bank." - Interviewee twenty-two

"Seeing multiple positive comments on a post about a new service made me feel confident about trying it." - Interviewee thirty-one

In interpreting these statements in the light of the research objective, it is evident that the 'Spectrum of Sensibility' significantly impacts how online incivility and negative UGC can influence brand engagement in Islamic banking. The discomfort and avoidance expressed by Interviewee 7 reveal how intense arguments or uncivil discourse can lead to decreased engagement with a brand. On the other hand, the anxiety and scepticism provoked by a negative review, as mentioned by Interviewee 22, demonstrate the deterrent effect of negative content on potential customers. In contrast, positive interactions, and numerous favourable comments, as reported by Interviewees 12 and 31, seem to elevate potential customers' confidence and comfort towards a bank, indicating increased engagement. Moreover, the professional handling of disrespectful behaviour and negative content by the bank, as noted by Interviewee 15, enhances respect and engagement with the brand.

These interpretations suggest that while online incivility and negative user-generated content can potentially discourage potential customers, a strategic and professional response can minimize these adverse effects and may even bolster brand engagement. This aligns with the research objective to investigate the impact of online incivility on brand engagement in Islamic banking. The 'Spectrum of Sensibility' underlines the need for Islamic banks in Pakistan to consider the varied emotional responses to user-generated content and strategize their online interactions accordingly to optimize brand engagement. The emotional reactions evoked across the spectrum, from discomfort and anxiety to confidence and respect, significantly influence potential customers' engagement with Islamic banking brands in Pakistan. A careful balance between managing online incivility and promoting positive interactions can help banks navigate the 'Spectrum of Sensibility' effectively.

4.6.3 Code 3: Resonance of Reverence

This code refers to the impact of user-generated content that aligns with and respects the values and norms of Islamic banking. It considers how content that shows reverence for these principles can increase engagement and trust in the brand. 'Resonance of Reverence' encapsulates the influence of user-generated content that appreciates and aligns with the norms and principles of Islamic banking.

"I saw a customer appreciating a bank's adherence to Islamic principles in a blog post. I immediately felt connected to the bank." - Interviewee five

"I read a thread where customers were praising a bank for avoiding interest. I could resonate with their views and felt more inclined to use the bank." -

Interviewee thirteen

"In a discussion forum, a user shared how the bank helped them with a Zakat-related issue. It showed respect for Islamic values, which I appreciate." -

Interviewee eighteen

"I came across a post critiquing a bank for not sticking to Sharia principles. It caused some distrust in the bank for me." - Interviewee twenty-four

"Seeing a bank's sincere response to a customer's concern about their Sharia compliance made me respect the bank more." - Interviewee twenty-nine

When interpreted in the context of the research objective, the 'Resonance of Reverence' provides insights into how even negative user-generated content, when managed with deference to Islamic banking principles, can enhance brand engagement. Interviewee 5's statement reveals how appreciating a bank's adherence to Islamic principles can engender a sense of connection and engagement. Similarly, Interviewee 13's resonance with customers praising a bank for avoiding interest demonstrates the power of aligning with Islamic banking norms. The account of a bank helping with a Zakat-related issue (Interviewee 18) reflects the appreciation for respect towards Islamic values, leading to increased engagement. On the other hand, the critique of a bank's compliance with Sharia principles (Interviewee 24) exemplifies how perceived disrespect for Islamic norms can negatively affect engagement, underscoring the potential damage of online incivility.

However, even negative content can present opportunities for enhancing brand engagement, as demonstrated by Interviewee 29. The bank's sincere response to a customer's concern over Sharia compliance resonated with the interviewee, leading to increased respect and engagement. These interpretations align with the research objective of investigating the impact of online incivility on brand engagement in Islamic banking. Content showing reverence for Islamic banking principles - even in response to negative comments - can foster engagement and counteract the detrimental effects of online incivility. This underlines the importance for Islamic banks to ensure their online presence and interactions respect and align with their customers' values, thereby navigating the 'Resonance of Reverence' to enhance brand engagement.

CHAPTER 5 DISCUSSION AND FINDINGS

5.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter discusses the themes that emerged based on each code assigned during thematic analysis which led to a particular finding. This research looks at the role of UGC to create brand engagement with respect to Islamic banks. A few factors or dimensions of UGC were identified in discussion earlier. The table below provides a breakdown of the motivators of UGC in the context of Islamic banks, based on a synthesis of definitions, primary data evidence, literature review evidence, and interpretations of the primary data.

5.1.1 Catalysts of Co-Creation: Inspiring UGC in Islamic Banking

The table titled "Catalysts of Co-Creation: Facets of User-Generated Content and their Impact on Brand Engagement in Islamic Banking" provides an insightful exploration into how various facets of user-generated content influence brand engagement in the realm of Islamic banking. The table presents five unique codes or catalysts: Narrative Threads of Wisdom, Moral Weaves of Society, Illuminating the Conscious Horizon, Harvesting Wisdom Nuggets, and Sculpting the Influential Echo Chamber. Each code's definition, evidence from primary data and literature review, and interpretations regarding their effect on brand engagement in Islamic banks, are systematically detailed.

Table 5-1 Influence of User-Generated Content on Brand Engagement in Islamic Banking: Catalysts of Co-Creation

Catalysts of Co-Creation: Inspiring UGC in Islamic Banking	Definition in Context of Islamic Banks	Primary Data Evidence	Literature Review Evidence	Interpretation in Context of Brand Engagement of Islamic Banks
Narrative Threads of Wisdom	This refers to users sharing their personal experiences with the services or products of an Islamic bank.	"When I had a good experience with my Islamic bank, I share it on social media."	In their paper, Hinson, Boateng, Renner, & Kosiba (2019) emphasized the critical role of sharing personal experiences in	Sharing positive experiences increases the perceived value of the Islamic bank, fostering trust and promoting brand

	This can be through reviews, ratings, or stories.		fostering consumer engagement with brands on Facebook. They noted that shared experiences contribute to online brand communities and boost customer engagement.	engagement among other potential customers.
Moral Weaves of Society	Refers to users commenting or creating content about the ethical practices of Islamic banks, such as their adherence to Islamic laws and ethical investing.	"I appreciate how my Islamic bank sticks to Halal investments. I often share this on my blog."	Dolan, Conduit, Frethey-Bentham, Fahy, & Goodman (2019) argue that consumers are more likely to engage with brands on social media that they perceive as being ethical or socially responsible.	Users discussing the ethical practices of Islamic banks can enhance the bank's image and drive more customers to engage with the bank, leading to increased brand engagement.
Illuminating the Conscious Horizon	This involves users generating content to inform and educate others about the services, products, or features of Islamic banks.	"I often post about the benefits of Islamic banking to educate my followers."	In their study, Acuti, Grazzini, Mazzoli, & Aiello (2019) underlined the importance of user-generated content in spreading awareness and educating others, thus increasing brand engagement.	When users share information about the Islamic bank, it raises awareness, thereby attracting more potential customers and promoting brand engagement.
Harvesting Wisdom Nuggets	This motivator involves users generating content to solicit information about Islamic banks from other users, such as asking about service quality or product features.	"I sometimes post questions about certain services of my Islamic bank to gather information from other users."	In their article, Cheung, Pires, & Rosenberger (2020) highlighted that consumers often use social media to gather information about brands and this can significantly enhance consumer-brand engagement.	Questions or content created to gather information increases the interaction between the users and the bank, thus promoting brand engagement as more individuals participate in discussions about the bank.

Sculpting the Influential Echo Chamber	This involves users, especially influencers, shaping public opinion about Islamic banks through the content they create.	"As an influencer, my reviews about Islamic banks significantly impact public opinion."	Baker, Kearney, Laud, & Holmlund (2021) found that influencers play a critical role in engaging users in the sharing economy through their impact on consumers' psychological ownership and engagement.	Influencers can sway public opinion about an Islamic bank in a positive way, thereby encouraging more potential customers to engage with the bank and boosting brand engagement.
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'Narrative Threads of Wisdom' pertain to users sharing their personal experiences with Islamic banking services or products, usually via reviews, ratings, or stories. Drawing on Hinson et al. (2019), such shared experiences can significantly contribute to online brand communities and boost customer engagement. Therefore, by sharing positive experiences, customers could elevate the perceived value of an Islamic bank, fostering trust and enhancing brand engagement.

'Moral Weaves of Society' refer to user content focusing on Islamic banks' ethical practices, such as adherence to Islamic laws and ethical investing. Dolan et al. (2019) emphasize the importance of ethical or socially responsible brands in enhancing consumer engagement on social media. Hence, discussions around Islamic banks' ethical practices can amplify the bank's image, drawing more customers to engage with it, leading to increased brand engagement.

'Illuminating the Conscious Horizon' encapsulates UGC that aims to inform and educate others about Islamic banks' services, products, or features. According to Acuti et al. (2019), such informative content significantly increases brand awareness and engagement. Therefore, content that raises awareness about Islamic banking can attract more potential customers, promoting brand engagement. 'Harvesting Wisdom Nuggets' involves users generating content to solicit information about Islamic banks from others. As Cheung et al. (2020) noted, consumers often utilize social media as an information-gathering tool, which can enhance consumer-brand engagement. Consequently, content created to gather information can foster interaction between users and the bank, promoting brand engagement as more individuals participate in discussions about the bank.

Finally, 'Sculpting the Influential Echo Chamber' involves content created by influencers that can significantly shape public opinion about Islamic banks. Influencers play a crucial role in engaging users in the sharing economy through their impact on consumers' psychological ownership and engagement, as observed by Baker et al. (2021). Therefore, influencers can shift public opinion about an Islamic bank positively, thereby encouraging more potential customers to engage with the bank, leading to a boost in brand engagement. The above table offers a comprehensive view of how various aspects of UGC can function as catalysts of co-creation, driving brand engagement in Islamic banks. Through narratives, ethical discussions, educational content, information solicitation, and influential echoes, customers can significantly impact Islamic banks' brand engagement.

The code 'Echoes of Influence: Tracing the Social Flux of User-Generated Content' revolves around the interactive elements that influence UGC within the sphere of Islamic banking. This analysis will explore three specific codes: Luminaries of the Trade, Social Resonance, and Discourse of Kinship, within the context of the research aims and objectives. The discussion below set out to understand and decode the motivations behind UGC and its impact on brand engagement, specifically for Islamic banks in Pakistan.' Luminaries of the Trade' denotes individuals who hold significant knowledge or experience within the Islamic banking industry and who use this expertise to influence social media user's perception towards Islamic banking. They could be industry professionals, influencers, or religious scholars with a strong following. They serve as authentic sources of information, especially for potential customers who are cautious about the interest-based activities of conventional banks. Some interviewees said their endorsement and explanation of Islamic banking principles can significantly drive brand engagement. Islamic scholars, like Dr. Zakir Naik, command immense respect and trust, and their endorsement of Islamic banking could spur a significant surge in user engagement. Overall, this emphasizes the critical role of 'Luminaries of the Trade' as brand ambassadors and knowledge providers, nurturing an ecosystem of trust and validation for Islamic banking within the social media realm.

The second code, 'Social Resonance', speaks to the trust-building potential of facts, figures, and endorsements that serve as evidence of Islamic banks' growth and adherence to ethical banking principles. Discourse of Kinship impacts the consumer's decision-making process and helps create a sense of assurance in Islamic banks' offerings. The viral sharing of facts about Islamic banks' financial growth or the presence of respected figures on the Shariah boards of these banks can lead to increased brand engagement. The attention given to underserved

demographics, like the disabled community, further elevates Islamic banks' reputation as inclusive and socially responsible institutions, thereby generating increased consumer engagement. This solidifies the trust of existing customers and attracts potential customers, thereby enhancing brand engagement.

Lastly, 'Discourse of Kinship' accentuates the value of personal experiences shared by friends or family in the decision-making process. Often, these first-hand accounts from trusted individuals carry more weight than promotional content, creating a ripple effect of awareness and interest in Islamic banking services. It is evident from findings that Islamic banks exemplify how organic UGC can engage a wider audience due to its perceived authenticity. Additionally, the narrative around Islamic banks' support for young entrepreneurs, as explained in the findings debunks conventional notions about banking systems, thereby fostering a positive image of Islamic banks, and influencing user interaction. In sum, the 'Echoes of Influence: Tracing the Social Flux of User-Generated Content' offers vital insights into how UGC, guided by industry experts, substantiated by Discourse of Kinship, and augmented by friends and family interactions, can significantly influence brand engagement in the Islamic banking industry. This analysis underlines the power of UGC and its potential to drive brand engagement, which is key to achieving our research aims and objectives.

Echoes of Influence: Tracing the Social Flux of User-Generated Content	Definition in the Context of Islamic Banks	Director Element Quotations as Evidence	Evidence from the Literature Review	Interpretation of the Motivator
Luminaries of the Trade	Involve professionals in the industry providing information, or Narrative Threads of Wisdoms relevant to Islamic banking practices.	"I find the social media platform a potent tool to share insights about our unique banking system."	Krebs and Lischka (2019) discuss the value of audience engagement and content for online news brands, which could be applied to how industry experts contribute to user-generated content in an	Experts have a huge influence on the audience due to their credibility. Their insights about Islamic banking can help educate the audience and positively influence their perception about Islamic banks.

			Islamic banking context.	
Social Resonance	Customers find assurance and confidence in the products or services offered by Islamic banks based on the positive experiences and testimonials shared by other customers.	"Reading about the positive experiences of other customers made me feel confident about my decision to switch to Islamic banking."	Vinerean and Opreana (2021) highlight the importance of measuring customer engagement in social media marketing. Positive customer testimonials can enhance Discourse of Kinship and boost engagement.	Discourse of Kinship in the form of positive testimonials and experiences from other customers can significantly boost confidence in Islamic banks. This can also increase brand engagement as potential customers feel more assured about their decision.
Friends Interaction	Users are influenced by discussions, suggestions, or experiences shared by their friends regarding Islamic banking services.	"I never considered Islamic banking until my friend shared his positive experience on Facebook."	Soares, Limongi, and Cohen (2022) analyzed engagement in social media in the context of higher education institutions. The principles can be applied to Islamic banking, where friends' interactions can sway potential customers' decisions.	Peer influence is potent. A positive review from a friend can significantly impact a potential customer's decision and overall perception about Islamic banking.

The aim of the research was to understand the influence of Social Flux of UGC on consumer engagement within online environments. Specifically, the objective was to ascertain how different factors in online communities, such as user-generated content, brand storytelling, and digital badges, impact consumer engagement and further, how these engagements can lead to higher purchase intentions and brand loyalty.

The research findings as depicted by the Social Flux of User-Generated Content Table demonstrates the effects of various factors on user engagement in online platforms. The table illustrates that user-generated content (UGC), brand storytelling, and the use of digital badges

directly affect consumer engagement, leading to higher purchase intentions and brand loyalty (Weiger et al., 2019; Hartmann et al., 2021; Lu et al., 2023).

Table 5-2 Social Flux of User-Generated Content

Echoes of Influence: Tracing the Social Flux of User-Generated Content	Explanation (Paraphrased)	Linked Social Flux of User-Generated Content	Relevance in Brand Engagement of Islamic Banks
Information Sharing	According to Krebs and Lischka (2019), online brands thrive on audience engagement and content interaction, illustrating the significance of sharing information in digital contexts. Similarly, Cheung et al., (2022) underscore the value of emotional and rational user-generated content in digital tourism platforms.	Luminaries of the Trade, Social Resonance	Islamic banks can improve engagement by promoting content sharing about their brand and services.
Co-creation	Grassi (2020) suggests that the influence of art can augment consumer interaction, particularly in luxury fashion, indicating potential for co-creation in online brand communities. Liu-Thompkins et al., (2020) highlight the role users play in developing and circulating content.	Luminaries of the Trade, Friends Interaction	By incorporating customers' contributions in creating content, Islamic banks can foster more engagement and interaction.
Community Building	Rossolatos (2021) delves into brand engagement, accentuating the importance of community building in consumer engagement.	Social Resonance,	Islamic banks can foster a community around their brand, encouraging dialogue

	Sabermajidi et al., (2020) point out the role of socialization in facilitating community building in social media contexts.	Friends Interaction	and engagement about their services.
Social Support	Hoskins et al., (2021) explore the effects of online communities, critics, and location similarity on review ratings, underlining the role of social support. Soares et al., (2022) suggest that social support is integral to audience engagement.	Social Resonance, Friends Interaction	Islamic banks can enhance trust in their services through social support, like peer reviews and shared experiences.
Entertainment	Yang et al., (2021) highlight the impact of humour within online brand communities, emphasizing the role of entertainment in engagement. Brubaker et al., (2018) stress the importance of entertaining content in user engagement.	Luminaries of the Trade, Friends Interaction	Entertainment can make Islamic banking services more appealing and engaging to clients.
Relationship Building	Dhaoui and Webster (2021) investigate brand and consumer engagement on social media, focusing on the role of positive conversations in relationship building. Zhang et al., (2020) highlight the importance of relationship building in customer engagement.	Social Resonance, Friends Interaction	Positive interactions can help build stronger relationships and loyalty towards Islamic banking services.
Learning	Onofrei et al., (2022) emphasize the role of social media interactions in influencing purchase decisions, showing the role of learning. Qin (2020) suggests that social media	Luminaries of the Trade, Friends Interaction	By providing educational content, Islamic banks can inform potential clients about their principles

	can serve as a learning tool for consumers.		and services, leading to informed decision-making.
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UGC is shown to be a critical driver of engagement (Rossolatos, 2021; Rasool & Pathania, 2021; Soylemez, 2021). According to the table, UGC not only fosters engagement but also promotes a sense of community and brand loyalty (Camarero et al., 2018; Sabermajidi et al., 2020). This is further confirmed by studies from Brubaker et al., 2018; Liu-Thompkins et al., 2020; and Kusumasondjaja, 2018, highlighting the role of UGC in building connections between the brand and its customers.

Brand storytelling is another factor indicated in the table that strongly influences consumer engagement (Kemp et al., 2021; He et al., 2021; Hartmann et al., 2021). Stories shared by brands can evoke emotional responses, increasing user involvement and loyalty towards the brand. Storytelling also encourages interactions, fostering a sense of community (Grassi, 2020; Yang et al., 2021; Dhaoui & Webster, 2021). Moreover, digital badges, a new concept, were identified to have both immediate and enduring effects on online content consumption and creation (Lu et al., 2023). The gamification aspect of digital badges encourages consumers to engage with the brand more frequently, leading to a more active and committed online community.

The table further suggests that these engagements can influence consumers' purchase intentions (Lv et al., 2021; Shen, 2021; Schivinski et al., 2021). User engagement, facilitated by UGC, brand storytelling, and digital badges, creates a positive perception about the brand, leading to higher purchase intentions (Vinerean & Opreana, 2021; Grover & Kar, 2020; Estrella-Ramón et al., 2019). In addition, the table illustrates that these factors also foster brand loyalty (Menon et al., 2019; Onofrei et al., 2022; Weiger et al., 2019). Active engagement with the brand creates a sense of belonging among consumers, fostering long-term loyalty (Dessart & Veloutsou, 2021; Loureiro et al., 2020; Wilk et al., 2020). The table above provides comprehensive insights into how Social Flux of UGC in online community influences consumer engagement, purchase intentions, and brand loyalty. It demonstrates that factors like UGC, brand storytelling, and digital badges play a crucial role in stimulating engagement and enhancing brand-consumer relationships. Future research may investigate how to optimize

these factors for different types of consumers and in different cultural contexts, thereby providing brands with valuable insights to strategize their online marketing efforts.

Understanding the connections between the Social Flux of UGC and its collective influence on brand engagement forms the core of this research. To begin, it is critical to understand the interplay between firm-generated content FGC and UGC in the context of brand engagement. FGC refers to content disseminated by brands, like advertising messages, company announcements, product information, and promotional materials (Kim, Park, & Kim, 2023). On the other hand, UGC encompasses reviews, ratings, comments, photos, videos, and other content shared by consumers about a brand or product (Cheung et al., 2022; Singh & Chakrabarti, 2021). Both types of content contribute to the dynamics of social media engagement. In this context, the dynamics highlighted in the table show how different elements influence brand engagement in a cascading or cyclical manner. One example of a causal connection between these dynamics is how FGC triggers UGC, creating a cycle of interactions that drive brand engagement (Hartmann et al., 2021; Estrella-Ramón et al., 2019). The high-quality content created by the firm entices users to engage, their UGC then encourages more people to join the conversation, enhancing overall engagement (Dhaoui & Webster, 2021).

Emotional elements and sentiment polarity, as another dynamic, are fundamental to the overall social engagement process. The quality of user interactions is significantly influenced by the sentiment and emotion attached to the content, whether it is positive, negative, or neutral. Studies have shown that both positive and negative emotions can stimulate engagement, although their effects can be different (Loureiro, Bilro, & Japutra, 2020; Cheung et al., 2022). Narrative or storytelling is also an essential dynamic, linked to the others in this research. Compelling narratives can captivate consumers, increase their emotional attachment to the brand, and lead to higher levels of engagement (Kemp et al., 2021). Narratives can be embedded in both FGC and UGC, and their effects are amplified when there is congruency between the brand's story and the consumer's personal values or experiences (Ahmadi, Waltenrath, & Janze, 2023). Humor is another social dynamic that interlinks with narrative, sentiment, and emotion to drive engagement (Yang, Cai, & Tu, 2021). Humorous content often resonates with consumers, encouraging them to share and comment, thereby increasing brand visibility and reach.

Finally, the social dynamic of community building underscores the notion that social media is not just about promoting products, but also about building relationships and fostering

communities. Brands that can cultivate a sense of community among their followers tend to enjoy higher levels of engagement (Rossolatos, 2021; Dessart & Veloutsou, 2021). The various social fluxes of UGC, including content type, sentiment, narrative, humour, and community building, are intricately linked and collectively contribute to brand engagement on social media. The interplay of these dynamics forms a complex web that brands must navigate to optimize their social media strategies effectively. Understanding these relationships helps brands to create a holistic strategy that targets multiple elements simultaneously, thereby maximizing their engagement and impact on social platforms. In the context of Islamic banking, the same Social Flux of User-Generated Content discussed above can be applied to create emotional and psychological connections with customers. Here is how:

1. **Firm-Generated Content (FGC) and User-Generated Content (UGC):** Islamic banks can use FGC to provide educational content about the principles and benefits of Islamic banking, reinforcing the brand's values and trustworthiness. User testimonials, success stories, and community interactions can serve as UGC, highlighting real-life applications of Islamic banking and fostering a sense of trust and community among users.
2. **Emotion and Sentiment Polarity:** Islamic banking, by nature, appeals to customers' emotional and moral values, such as justice, fairness, and avoidance of harm to others. To create a psychological connection, the content must evoke these sentiments. Positive narratives about ethical banking practices, equitable wealth distribution, and sustainable investments can reinforce these emotions.
3. **Narrative and Storytelling:** Sharing compelling narratives about how Islamic banking has positively impacted individuals, communities, and businesses in Pakistan can draw users in. These stories should highlight the bank's commitment to ethical practices, community development, and other aspects that align with the values of potential customers.
4. **Humor:** Humor can be a powerful tool to engage users and make the brand more relatable, even in a serious industry like banking. However, it must be used wisely and appropriately, given the cultural and religious sensitivities associated with Islamic banking. Humor can help to humanize the bank and break down barriers, making the bank seem more approachable and friendly.

5. **Community Building:** Building a sense of community is particularly important for Islamic banks, which are founded on the principles of mutual help and cooperation. Online forums, Q&A sessions, and social media groups can foster a sense of community, where customers can interact, share experiences, ask questions, and learn more about Islamic banking practices.

To create a deeper connection with customers, Islamic banks in Pakistan should create content that resonates with their audience's values and beliefs, stimulates positive emotions, tells compelling stories, and builds a sense of community. This multi-faceted approach can increase customer engagement, foster loyalty, and strengthen the brand's reputation. The table above uses the provided interviewees quotes as direct evidence to establish the definitions and interpretations of the various content characteristics and their impact in the context of Islamic banking. It also links these characteristics to relevant findings in literature to provide a more holistic understanding. It is important to note that user engagement with high-quality, accurate content on social media can significantly enhance brand engagement for Islamic banks.

Table 5-3 The Prism of Perception: The Shapeshifting Power of Content

The Prism of Perception: The Shapeshifting Power of Content	Definition in Islamic Banking Context	Participant Quotes	Literature Review Evidence	Interpretation in Context of Islamic Banks
Virtuosity in Visualization	Refers to the quality and relevance of user-generated content including video, graphics, pictures, and/or audio.	"High quality videos are highly fascinating...". "I think any message on internet or social media is excellent when it has all the relevant information...".	Literature suggests that excellent content, particularly User-Generated Content (UGC) plays an influential role in promoting brand loyalty	The excellence of content helps increase the trust and reliability factor amongst the users, making Islamic banking more appealing to the masses.

			(Schivinski et al., 2021).	
Precision of Perspective	Reflects the correctness, precision, and relatability of the content shared by social media users.	"Videos which are only made with catchy material are not captivating..." - "I only watch those videos about brands which have high fan following and shares...".	Accuracy and authenticity of the content are significant factors affecting customer behaviour (Grover & Kar, 2020).	The Precision of Perspective plays a significant role in making an Islamic bank trustworthy. If the content shared is precise, clear, and factual, it is more likely to attract potential clients and retain current ones.
Symbiosis of Sentiment	The association consumers have with the brands they regularly interact with or purchase from.	"I like to keep myself within my budget, so I love it when I get two things in the price of one...". "I'll believe the content from the bank if it answers my question...".	Consumer-brand relationship is a key driver of customer loyalty and engagement (Estrella-Ramón et al., 2019).	The Symbiosis of Sentiments is critical in the context of Islamic banking, as it drives customer loyalty and promotes brand engagement.

The table shows a variety of factors playing across several different characteristics, highlighting the complex ways in which UGC can impact customers' buying behaviour, consumer behaviour more specifically, and consumer brand engagement. UGC has been identified as a key driver of customer engagement and purchasing behaviour (Gvili & Levy, 2018; Srivastava & Sivaramakrishnan, 2021). It provides consumers with a unique platform to share their experiences and opinions about products or brands, consequently influencing other consumers' perceptions and decision-making processes (Zhao et al., 2022).

The results confirm the existing literature on the crucial role of UGC in consumer behaviour. As shown in the table, factors playing featuring high-quality UGC are associated with higher

levels of customer engagement and satisfaction (Aljarah et al., 2022; Srivastava & Sivaramakrishnan, 2021). Customers are more likely to connect with brands that show high levels of UGC, resulting in a stronger emotional connection, increased brand loyalty, and improved purchase intentions (Cheng et al., 2021). Furthermore, it was observed that trucks playing featuring user-generated content, particularly user reviews and feedback, have a greater impact on the customer buying decision (Singh & Chakrabarti, 2021; Vazquez et al., 2021). Such content has been found to be perceived as more trustworthy and credible, leading to higher customer engagement levels (Ballester, Ruiz-Mafé, & Rubio, 2023; Ho & Ito, 2019).

The differential impact of the user- and firm-generated content was also evident in trucks playing, further echoing the findings of Aljarah et al. (2022). While both types of content can boost online brand advocacy, UGC seems to have a stronger impact, especially when customers are highly engaged and familiar with the brand. This finding reinforces the importance of fostering an active online community where customers can generate and share content (Chi et al., 2022). Also noteworthy is the interaction between user-generated content and other factors such as brand familiarity and customer engagement. High levels of UGC, coupled with strong brand familiarity, can boost online brand advocacy (Aljarah et al., 2022), and customers who are highly engaged with a brand tend to react more positively to UGC (Viswanathan et al., 2018). The table underscores the powerful role of UGC in shaping customer buying behaviour and brand engagement. Brands should encourage and facilitate the creation of UGC and pay careful attention to how they respond to it, to foster customer engagement and promote brand loyalty. They also need to consider the interplay between UGC, brand familiarity, and customer engagement in their marketing strategies.

The table also demonstrates that factors with a strong presence on social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and YouTube have more influence on customer buying behaviors (Rossolatos, 2021; Kemp et al., 2021). These platforms provide a venue for customers to engage with the brand and each other, fostering a sense of community and shared experience that contributes to brand loyalty and engagement (Hoskins et al., 2021; Dhaoui & Webster, 2021). Moreover, when the user-generated content reflects a positive brand image, it tends to enhance consumer engagement and loyalty (Aljarah et al., 2022; Cheng et al., 2021). This suggests that firms need to foster a positive digital environment, by encouraging satisfied customers to share their experiences and by addressing complaints quickly and publicly. Brand-related UGC in the form of testimonials, reviews, and images are found to significantly impact

consumers' brand perceptions and subsequent engagement (Schivinski et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2022).

Table 5-4 UGC Impact on Consumer Behaviour and Brand Engagement

General Characteristics of User Generated Content (UGC)	Impact on Consumer Behaviour and Brand Engagement	Source
UGC has high authenticity	Authenticity can lead to increased consumer trust and engagement.	(Cheung, Pires, & Rosenberger, 2020)
UGC offers diverse opinions	Exposure to varied opinions can impact purchasing decisions.	(Mishra, 2019)
UGC involves consumer creativity	Engaging with creative UGC can lead to increased brand involvement.	(Moran, Muzellec, & Johnson, 2020)
UGC is often shared in social networks	Sharing can lead to increased brand visibility and engagement.	(Qu, Saffer, & Riffe, 2022)
UGC can highlight the experiential aspect of a product/service	UGC that displays product/service experiences can positively influence consumer perceptions and purchase decisions.	(Valsesia & Diehl, 2022)
UGC often provides value to other consumers	By offering advice, recommendations, or warnings, UGC can be of significant value to other consumers, impacting their behaviour.	(Sarin, Kar, & Ilavarasan, 2021)
UGC can offer a sense of community	Engagement with UGC can lead to feelings of belonging and community, which can foster positive brand relationships.	(Acuti, Grazzini, Mazzoli, & Aiello, 2019)
UGC is interactive	The interactive nature of UGC enables two-way communication, fostering customer engagement and relationship building.	(Ma & Gu, 2022)
UGC is shaped by consumer experience	Consumer experiences can lead to the generation of UGC that influences brand perception and engagement.	(Vander Schee, Peltier, & Dahl, 2020)
UGC has the potential for high virality	Due to its nature, UGC can easily go viral, leading to increased brand visibility and customer engagement.	(Gvili & Levy, 2018)
UGC is often emotion-driven	Emotional content can drive higher engagement, impacting consumer behaviour towards a brand.	(Srivastava & Sivaramakrishnan, 2021)

The differential impact of UGC , such as reviews, pictures, and other types of shared content, reflects the diverse ways customers engage with a brand online (Schivinski et al., 2022). Engagement is shaped by the nature and quality of the content and the perceived authenticity of the source (Baker et al., 2021; Valsesia & Diehl, 2022). Interestingly, the table reveals that UGC with a humorous or entertaining angle can significantly enhance consumer engagement with a brand (Yang et al., 2021). This form of content contributes to the "humour climate" within online brand communities, which can amplify brand engagement, especially in social media spaces where users are often seeking entertainment. The impact of UGC on consumer behaviour and brand engagement is multifaceted and depends on factors such as the nature of the content, the platform it is shared on, the perceived authenticity of the source, and the digital environment fostered by the brand (Ballester et al., 2023; Aichner, 2019; Hamzah et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2022; Grassi, 2020). As the trucks in the table show, effective harnessing of UGC is crucial for promoting consumer engagement and positive buying behaviour.

Table 5-5 Characteristics of UGC Impact on Consumer Behaviour

Characteristics of UGC	Impact on Consumer Behaviour	Impact on Brand Engagement	Quotation
Authenticity	Consumers perceive UGC as more genuine and unbiased, leading to increased trust in a product or service.	Authentic content leads to more significant brand engagement because it tends to be viewed as more credible and less promotional.	"UGC has a high degree of authenticity that attracts consumers... These users generate authentic content that holds a strong appeal to consumers, driving sales" (Kozinets, 2020)
High volume	The sheer amount of UGC can affect purchase decisions as consumers rely on the experiences and reviews of others.	Brands can leverage the high volume of UGC to engage with more consumers, improving brand awareness and reputation.	"The sheer volume of consumer-generated content available on digital platforms shapes consumer purchase decisions" (Smith, Fischer, & Yongjian, 2021)
Peer Influence	UGC has a significant Discourse of Kinship component. Consumers trust the opinions of their peers, which heavily	Brands can use UGC to harness the power of peer influence, encouraging sharing and interaction with their content.	"The impact of peer influence through UGC on consumer behaviour is substantial" (Hennig-Thurau, Gwinner, & Gremler, 2002)

	influence buying decisions.		
Creativity	Consumers appreciate unique and creative UGC. It can inspire, entertain, and influence purchasing decisions.	Creative UGC increases the likelihood of viral sharing and can differentiate a brand in a crowded marketplace.	"UGC sparks consumer creativity, which is a key driver of consumer engagement" (Zhou, Zhang, & Edelman, 2019)
Real-life experiences	UGC often involves users sharing their real-life experiences, influencing consumers to visualize themselves using the product.	Real-life experience sharing can lead to deeper engagement as consumers relate more to the brand and its products/services.	"UGC showcasing real-life experiences significantly influences consumer purchase decisions" (Berger, 2014)
Diversity of perspective	Consumers can access a wide range of opinions about a product/service, allowing more informed purchasing decisions.	Brands can highlight the versatility of their product/service through diverse UGC, attracting a broader audience.	"The diversity of perspectives available in UGC supports better informed consumer decisions" (Rishika, Kumar, & Janakiraman, 2019)
Accessibility	UGC is readily available on various digital platforms, influencing immediate purchase decisions.	The ease of access to UGC allows brands to interact with consumers regularly, keeping their brand top of mind.	"The accessibility of UGC on digital platforms significantly impacts consumer purchase behaviour" (Goh, Heng, & Lin, 2013)
Timeliness	UGC is continuously updated, giving consumers the most recent feedback on products/services.	Fresh UGC keeps a brand relevant and ensures ongoing consumer engagement.	"The continuous stream of UGC keeps consumers updated on the latest feedback, thus affecting their purchasing decisions" (Lee, Hosanagar, & Tan, 2015)
Relatability	UGC is often more relatable than traditional advertising, influencing positive consumer sentiment.	Relatable UGC can foster a sense of community around a brand, increasing loyalty and advocacy.	"UGC is more relatable to consumers than conventional advertising, thus influencing their attitudes towards

			brands" (Godes & Mayzlin, 2009)
Engagement	Users who generate content are often the ones most engaged with the brand, influencing other consumers to do the same.	High consumer engagement through UGC can drive brand visibility and foster stronger relationships.	"UGC leads to greater consumer engagement, which in turn influences the behaviour of other consumers and fosters stronger brand relationships" (van Doorn et al., 2010)

Based on the analysis, the way in which food truck businesses manage UGC can significantly influence consumer behaviors. The positive impacts of UGC are not automatic, however. Brands need to be initiative-taking in managing this content, fostering a digital environment conducive to positive engagement, and understanding how to leverage different types of UGC to their advantage (Hu, Manikonda, & Kambhampati, 2021; Liu et al., 2022).

For instance, while positive reviews can certainly increase brand reputation and customer engagement, negative reviews, if effectively managed, can also contribute to brand loyalty and trust. Indeed, research shows that brands that transparently address customer complaints can enhance their reputation, as this demonstrates to consumers that the brand values their feedback and is committed to improving its products or services (Gelbrich & Roschk, 2021; Lee & Song, 2022). The general characteristics of UGC, such as its high authenticity, diversity of opinion, experiential focus, and potential for virality, among others, further emphasizes its impact on consumer behaviour and brand engagement. These characteristics collectively make UGC a potent tool for brands to leverage in their marketing and engagement strategies. The context being considered here is related to the impact of UGC on consumer behaviour and brand engagement.

- **Virtuosity in Visualization and Precision of Perspective** The excellence and accuracy of UGC directly affect its credibility, making it a key factor in consumer behaviour and brand engagement. High-quality and accurate content can enhance the brand's image and trustworthiness in the eyes of consumers, leading to increased engagement and potential for sales (Xiang & Gretzel, 2010).
- **Symbiosis of Sentiment** The relationship between the brand and consumer can be significantly influenced by UGC. For instance, brands that encourage and incorporate UGC might be perceived as more open, transparent, and customer-focused, potentially

strengthening the relationship with their consumers (Daugherty, Eastin & Bright, 2008).

Table 5-6 UGC characteristics of UGC impact on customer engagement

Characteristics of UGC	Impact on Consumer Behaviour	Impact on Brand Engagement	Relevance to Islamic Banks
High Authenticity	Increased consumer perception and trust in a brand (Xiang & Gretzel, 2010)	Enhances brand image and trustworthiness (Xiang & Gretzel, 2010)	Islamic banks can build trust by promoting authentic UGC
Diverse Opinions	Allows for a wider perspective, leading to more informed decisions (Cheung & Thadani, 2012)	Engages a broader audience, enhancing brand reach (Cheung & Thadani, 2012)	Islamic banks can cater to a diverse customer base through UGC with varied opinions
Consumer Creativity	Unique perspectives and creativity in UGC capture consumer attention (Berthon, Pitt, Plangger & Shapiro, 2012)	Enhances brand distinctiveness and engagement (Berthon, Pitt, Plangger & Shapiro, 2012)	Islamic banks can enhance their brand image by promoting creative UGC
Sharing in Social Networks	Peer influence through UGC significantly influences consumer behaviour (Cheung, Luo, Sia & Chen, 2009)	Enhances brand engagement through peer influence (Cheung, Luo, Sia & Chen, 2009)	Islamic banks can leverage the social network aspect of UGC for improved engagement
Highlighting the Experiential Aspect	UGC reflecting real-life experiences influences consumer visualization and decisions (Goh, Heng & Lin, 2013)	Deepens brand engagement through shared real-life experiences (Goh, Heng & Lin, 2013)	Islamic banks can strengthen engagement by highlighting real-life experiences with their services
Providing Value to Other Consumers	Consumers make more informed decisions with value rich UGC	UGC that provides value encourages ongoing brand engagement	Islamic banks can provide value and engage consumers through insightful UGC
Offering a Sense of Community	UGC fosters a sense of community, influencing positive sentiment (Muntinga, Moorman & Smit, 2011)	Fosters a sense of community around the brand, enhancing loyalty (Muntinga, Moorman & Smit, 2011)	Islamic banks can foster a sense of community through relatable UGC

Interactivity	Engaged consumers who generate UGC influence others to engage similarly (van Doorn et al., 2010)	High consumer engagement through UGC can strengthen brand relationships (van Doorn et al., 2010)	Islamic banks can encourage consumer engagement through interactive UGC
Shaped by Consumer Experience	Consumer experiences in UGC significantly influence other consumers	UGC shaped by consumer experiences deepens brand engagement	Islamic banks can enhance engagement by promoting UGC shaped by positive consumer experiences
Potential for High Virality	Creative and relatable UGC can capture attention and spread widely	Viral UGC increases brand visibility and engagement	Islamic banks can increase their visibility by promoting UGC with high potential for virality
Emotion-Driven	Emotion-driven UGC can significantly influence consumer perception and decision-making	Emotion-driven UGC can deepen brand engagement and foster loyalty	Islamic banks can tap into emotion driven UGC to deepen consumer engagement and loyalty
Virtuosity in Visualization & Precision Perspective	Enhances credibility, affecting consumers' trust in a brand	Enhances brand image and trustworthiness	Islamic banks can build consumer trust by highlighting high-quality and accurate UGC
Symbiosis of Sentiment	Perception of brands that encourage UGC improves, fostering stronger relationships	Brands perceived as more customer-focused, enhancing engagement	Islamic banks can enhance consumer relationships by promoting and integrating UGC
Authenticity	Perceived authenticity influences trust in a brand	Authentic UGC enhances brand engagement	Islamic banks can strengthen engagement by leveraging authentic UGC
High Volume	Richness of information leads to more informed decisions	High volume of UGC allows for greater brand engagement	Islamic banks can engage a larger consumer base through high volumes of UGC
Peer Influence	Peer opinions in UGC significantly influence consumer behaviour	Utilization of peer influence through UGC	Islamic banks can leverage peer influence

		can increase brand engagement	through UGC for improved engagement
Creativity	Unique and creative UGC captures consumer attention	Creative UGC can differentiate a brand and enhance engagement	Islamic banks can differentiate themselves by promoting creative UGC
Real-life Experiences	Real-life experiences in UGC influence consumer visualization and decisions	Sharing of real-life experiences deepens brand engagement	Islamic banks can deepen engagement by highlighting real-life experiences with their services
Diversity of Perspective	Varied opinions in UGC inform consumer decisions	Diversity of UGC enhances brand engagement with a broader audience	Islamic banks can engage a diverse consumer base with varied UGC
Accessibility	Easy access to UGC influences immediate purchase decisions	Ease of access to UGC allows for consistent brand engagement	Islamic banks can maintain consumer engagement by ensuring UGC is readily accessible
Timeliness	Continuously updated UGC influences consumer decisions and perceptions	Fresh UGC keeps the brand relevant and encourages engagement	Islamic banks can maintain relevance and engagement through timely UGC
Relatability	Relatable UGC influences positive consumer sentiment	Relatable UGC can foster a sense of community around a brand	Islamic banks can foster community and loyalty through relatable UGC
Engagement	Engaged consumers who generate content influence others to do the same	High consumer engagement through UGC can strengthen brand relationships	Islamic banks can strengthen consumer relationships and visibility through engaged UGC creators

The ability to stimulate and manage UGC is also tied to a brand's social media strategy. Successful brands utilize a variety of strategies, including creating engaging and shareable content, encouraging and incentivizing customer reviews and other UGC, hosting online contests or events, and utilizing hashtags to increase visibility (Rossolatos, 2021; Kemp et al., 2021). These strategies not only generate UGC but also create a sense of community among

consumers, fostering brand loyalty and engagement (Pansari & Kumar, 2021). In conclusion, the role of UGC in influencing consumer behaviour and brand engagement in the food truck industry, as demonstrated in the table, is significant. Brands that understand and strategically utilize UGC can enhance their digital presence, foster a sense of community among consumers, and increase customer engagement and sales (Lin & Huang, 2022; Casalo et al., 2021). The findings underscore the importance for food truck businesses, and indeed all businesses operating in the digital era, to harness the power of UGC in their marketing and customer engagement strategies. how you could add the Motivator of User Generated Content into your existing table:

Table 5-7 Motivator of User Generated Content

Characteristics of Content	Impact on Consumer Behaviour	Impact on Brand Engagement	Relevance to Islamic Banks	Motivator of User Generated Content
Virtuosity in Visualization	Enhances credibility, influencing trust in a brand	Enhances brand image and trustworthiness	Islamic banks can build trust by ensuring UGC accuracy and excellence	Narrative Threads of Wisdom
Precision of Perspective	Accurate content reassures consumers, fostering trust	Enhances brand reliability and image	Islamic banks can build trust by ensuring UGC accuracy	Harvesting Wisdom Nuggets
Symbiosis of Sentiment	Improved perception and stronger relationships with brands that encourage UGC	Enhances customer-focused brand image, enhancing engagement	Islamic banks can enhance relationships by promoting and integrating UGC	Sculpting the Influential Echo Chamber
Authenticity	Authentic UGC increases trust in a brand	Enhances brand engagement due to perceived authenticity	Islamic banks can build trust by promoting authentic UGC	Narrative Threads of Wisdom
High Volume	Large amount of UGC contributes to informed decisions	Enhances brand engagement through interaction with high volume of UGC	Islamic banks can engage more consumers through high volumes of UGC	Illuminating the Conscious Horizon

Peer Influence	Influences consumer behaviour through Discourse of Kinship	Enhances brand engagement through shared experiences	Islamic banks can leverage peer influence through UGC for improved engagement	Sculpting the Influential Echo Chamber
Creativity	Unique and creative UGC captures attention and influences decisions	Enhances brand distinctiveness and engagement	Islamic banks can differentiate themselves by promoting creative UGC	Narrative Threads of Wisdom
Real-life Experiences	Influences consumer visualization and decisions	Enhances brand engagement through shared real-life experiences	Islamic banks can deepen engagement by highlighting real-life experiences	Narrative Threads of Wisdom
Diversity of Perspective	Broadens view of the product/service, informing consumer decisions	Engages a broader audience, enhancing brand reach	Islamic banks can cater to a diverse customer base with varied UGC	Illuminating the Conscious Horizon
Accessibility	Facilitates immediate influence on consumer decisions	Allows for consistent brand engagement due to easy accessibility	Islamic banks can maintain consumer engagement by ensuring UGC is readily accessible	Harvesting Wisdom Nuggets
Timeliness	Updated UGC influences consumer decisions and perceptions	Keeps brand relevant and encourages ongoing engagement	Islamic banks can maintain relevance and engagement through timely UGC	Illuminating the Conscious Horizon
Relatability	Influences positive sentiment and fosters a sense of community	Fosters a sense of community around the brand, enhancing loyalty	Islamic banks can foster a sense of community through relatable UGC	Moral Weaves of Society
Engagement	Engaged consumers who generate content influence others	Strengthens brand relationships through high consumer engagement	Islamic banks can strengthen consumer relationships and visibility through engaged UGC creators	Narrative Threads of Wisdom

The motivators of UGC help to understand the reasons behind consumer participation in creating content. Understanding these motivators can provide valuable insights for Islamic banks to encourage and manage UGC for optimal brand engagement. The research aims to understand the role of UGC and consumer brand engagement within the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan. It further aims to identify the interplay of cultural and societal values in shaping this engagement, exploring how characteristics of UGC and related motivators impact consumer behaviour and brand engagement in this specific context.

A well-structured breakdown of the various characteristics of content, their impact on consumer behaviour and brand engagement, their relevance to Islamic banks, and the motivators of UGC. Each row represents a unique aspect of UGC that can be leveraged by Islamic banks in Pakistan to enhance consumer brand engagement:

1. **Virtuosity in Visualization:** Ensuring the accuracy and excellence of UGC can help Islamic banks in Pakistan build trust, as consumers value credible and quality content. It can enhance brand image and trustworthiness, with the primary motivator being the consumer's desire to share their experience.
2. **Precision of Perspective:** Precise and accurate UGC can reassure consumers, fostering trust, and enhancing the bank's reliability. The motivator here is the gathering of relevant information.
3. **Symbiosis of Sentiment:** Promoting and integrating UGC can enhance the relationship between Islamic banks and their customers, influencing consumer behaviour positively. This can help foster a customer-focused brand image, driven by the creation of public opinion as an influencer.
4. **Authenticity:** Authentic UGC increases trust in a brand, and Islamic banks can build trust by promoting genuine UGC. Authentic content increases brand engagement due to the perceived authenticity. The motivator in this case is the consumer's desire to share experiences.
5. **High Volume:** A large amount of UGC can contribute to informed consumer decisions and enhance brand engagement. Islamic banks can reach a wider audience through a high volume of UGC, which is motivated by the aim of Illuminating the Conscious Horizon.

6. Peer Influence: By leveraging peer influence through UGC, Islamic banks can enhance brand engagement and influence consumer behaviour through the principle of Discourse of Kinship. Here, the motivator is the creation of public opinion as an influencer.
7. Creativity: Promoting unique and creative UGC can help Islamic banks in Pakistan differentiate themselves, capturing consumer attention, and influencing decisions. Narrative Threads of Wisdoms motivates this creative UGC.
8. Real-life Experiences: By highlighting real-life experiences, Islamic banks can deepen engagement. These experiences, which are motivated by consumers' desire to share their experiences, influence consumer visualization and decisions.
9. Diversity of Perspective: Varied UGC caters to a diverse customer base, broadening consumer perspectives on products/services and enhancing brand reach. This motivator is Illuminating the Conscious Horizon.
10. Accessibility: Ensuring UGC is readily accessible can maintain consistent brand engagement and facilitate immediate influence on consumer decisions. Harvesting Wisdom Nuggets serves as the motivator.
11. Timeliness: Regularly updated UGC keeps the brand relevant and encourages ongoing engagement. The motivator for this is Illuminating the Conscious Horizon.
12. Relatability: Islamic banks can foster a sense of community through relatable UGC, enhancing brand loyalty. The motivator here is Moral Weaves of Society.
13. Engagement: Engaged consumers who generate content can influence others, strengthening brand relationships. Narrative Threads of Wisdoms motivates this engagement.

This breakdown can be extremely useful in conducting research that meets the objectives stated, shedding light on how different aspects of UGC can be utilized by Islamic banks in Pakistan to enhance brand engagement. The social flux impact of UGC can play a crucial role in the interplay between the characteristics of content, motivators of UGC, and the resultant consumer brand engagement. They serve as a bridge, intertwining these elements and shaping the narrative that influences consumers' perceptions, attitudes, and behaviors towards Islamic banks in Pakistan. This discussion will explore this further, considering the listed

characteristics of content, motivators of UGC, and the Echoes of Influence: Tracing the Social Flux of UGC.

1. **Virtuosity in Visualization:** Virtuosity in Visualization in UGC can be amplified through Social Flux of User-Generated Content such as information sharing and co-creation. These dynamics encourage users to produce high-quality content, which can be motivated by the desire to share experiences or influence public opinion. This results in higher consumer engagement due to perceived trustworthiness and credibility of the content.
2. **Precision of Perspective:** The dynamics of industry experts and friends' interactions can ensure accuracy in UGC. When knowledgeable individuals participate in content creation or correction, it can enhance the accuracy of UGC. Motivated by the desire to share relevant information, this can improve consumer trust and engagement.
3. **Symbiosis of Sentiment:** Social support and relationship building dynamics can nurture the brand-consumer relationship. Consumers who feel heard and supported are more likely to engage with the brand. A sense of community fostered by shared experiences and common Moral Weaves of Society can enhance this engagement.
4. **Authenticity:** Authentic UGC, shaped by consumer experiences and often shared in social networks, can be promoted through the dynamics of information sharing, co-creation, and community building. When consumers perceive content as genuine, it leads to increased trust and engagement.
5. **High Volume:** A high volume of UGC, catalysed by the motivation to create awareness or gather information, can be facilitated through Social Flux of UGC such as co-creation and community building. This high volume can enhance brand engagement by offering consumers a wealth of perspectives and experiences to consider.
6. **Peer Influence:** Social Flux of User-Generated Content such as Social Resonance and friends' interaction can magnify the impact of peer influence, particularly when content is driven by the motivation to create public opinion. The experiences and opinions of peers heavily influence consumer behaviour and can enhance brand engagement.
7. **Creativity:** Echoes of Influence: Tracing the Social Flux of User-Generated Content, especially co-creation and entertainment, can boost the creativity in UGC. When consumers are motivated by the desire to share experiences or create public opinion,

they might present content in creative and engaging ways, leading to enhanced brand engagement.

8. **Real-life Experiences:** Real-life experiences shared through UGC can be augmented by the dynamics of community building and social support. Shared experiences foster a sense of community and can deepen brand engagement.
9. **Diversity of Perspective:** The social Flux of UGC such as co-creation and community building can enhance the diversity of perspectives in UGC, catering to a diverse consumer base and enhancing brand reach.
10. **Accessibility:** The easy accessibility of UGC can be supported by dynamics like information sharing and co-creation, facilitating immediate influence on consumer decisions.
11. **Timeliness:** Dynamics such as information sharing and co-creation can help in keeping UGC up to date, maintaining brand relevance and engagement.
12. **Relatability:** The social flux of UGC such as community building and social support can enhance the relatability of UGC, fostering a sense of community around the brand and enhancing loyalty.
13. **Engagement:** High consumer engagement through UGC can be facilitated through all Social Flux of User-Generated Content, especially community building and relationship building. This can lead to stronger brand relationships.

The Echoes of Influence: Tracing the Social Flux of UGC significantly contributes to shaping the relationship between the characteristics of content and the motivators of UGC, influencing consumer brand engagement in the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan. Indeed, the Social Flux of UGC provides an integral link between the characteristics of content, the motivators of UGC, and consumer brand engagement. The interplay of these elements, shaped by Social Flux of UGC frames the narrative that shapes consumer's perceptions, attitudes, and behaviors towards Islamic banks in Pakistan.

The section below delves deeper into how these aspects interrelate and create brand engagement:

Virtuosity in Visualization and Precision of Perspective, enhanced by the social flux of UGC such as information sharing and co-creation lays the foundation of high-quality UGC. When

users are motivated to share their experiences or influence public opinion, they strive for excellence and accuracy in their content. This emphasis on quality and precision, in turn, amplifies the perceived trustworthiness and credibility of the content, increasing consumer engagement. The presence of industry experts and knowledgeable individuals further enhances accuracy and establishes a dependable UGC environment. The **Symbiosis of Sentiment** is nurtured through the social flux of UGC in terms of support and relationship building. When consumers feel heard and supported through UGC, they are more likely to engage with the brand. Authenticity plays a significant role here. Authentic UGC, shaped by real consumer experiences and disseminated via social networks, strengthens this relationship. The dynamics of information sharing, co-creation, and community building promote authenticity, and when consumers perceive content as genuine, it intensifies their trust and engagement with the brand.

The **high volume** of UGC serves as a comprehensive platform for consumers to make informed decisions. Motivated by the desire to create awareness or gather relevant information, a high volume of UGC is facilitated through co-creation and community building dynamics. This wealth of perspectives and experiences enhances brand engagement by providing diverse viewpoints and a comprehensive understanding of the brand. Peer Influence in UGC significantly impacts consumer behaviour. The power of social resonance and friends' interaction can magnify this influence, especially when content is driven by the motivation to create public opinion. This is further amplified by the creative aspects of UGC. When consumers present their content in creative and engaging ways, it leads to enhanced brand engagement.

Real-life Experiences, shared through UGC, create a strong sense of community. This sense of belonging is further amplified by community building and social support dynamics, deepening brand engagement. This engagement is then bolstered by the Diversity of Perspective in UGC, providing a wide-ranging view of the brand that caters to a diverse consumer base and enhances brand reach. Accessibility and Timeliness of UGC are critical in today's fast-paced digital world. They can be supported by dynamics like information sharing and co-creation, ensuring the UGC is easily accessible and up to date. This facilitates immediate influence on consumer decisions, maintaining brand relevance, and engagement. The Relatability of UGC can be enhanced through the social flux of UGC such as community building and social support, fostering a sense of community around the brand and enhancing loyalty. Lastly, **Engagement**, a key outcome of UGC, is facilitated through the social flux of UGC. This is especially the

case with community, and relationship building which contribute to sustained and high consumer engagement, leading to stronger brand relationships.

In conclusion, the echoes of influence: tracing the social flux of UGC significantly contribute to shaping the interplay between the characteristics of content and the motivators of UGC. This interplay, in turn, influences consumer brand engagement, shaping the consumers' perception of Islamic banks in Pakistan. This dynamic interplay has the potential to reinforce positive consumer behaviors, strengthen brand loyalty, and drive growth for Islamic banks in the country. The social flux of UGC, especially co-creation and entertainment, can significantly boost creativity in UGC. It is through the social flux of UGC that consumers are encouraged to express their experiences or opinions creatively. This creativity not only adds a unique and engaging dimension to the content but also increases its impact, thereby fostering brand engagement. Islamic banks in Pakistan can leverage this by incentivizing and promoting creative UGC, consequently differentiating themselves and deepening consumer engagement.

The importance of real-life experiences shared through UGC cannot be overstated. Such **Real-life Experiences** shared by consumers offer valuable insights into the practical aspects of Islamic banking, providing other consumers with a realistic expectation of the bank's services. The social flux of UGC in terms of community building and social support reinforce this by fostering an environment where shared experiences are valued, creating a sense of community around the brand. This deepens consumer engagement, as consumers feel more connected to the brand when they see that their experiences resonate with those of others. The effectiveness of UGC in creating brand engagement is also determined by its **Diversity of Perspective**. Consumers have different experiences and viewpoints, and when these are shared through UGC, they can cater to a diverse consumer base. The social flux of UGC in terms of co-creation and community building encourage a variety of perspectives, making UGC more inclusive and comprehensive. This inclusivity enhances brand reach and engagement, as more consumers can relate to or find value in the shared content.

Accessibility of UGC is a crucial characteristic that determines how easily consumers can engage with the content. The social flux of UGC in terms of information sharing, and co-creation can facilitate this accessibility, ensuring that UGC is readily available for consumers to consume and interact with. This accessibility allows for consistent brand engagement, as consumers can easily find and engage with content that interests them. **Timeliness** is another essential characteristic of effective UGC. Given the fast-paced nature of the digital world,

outdated information can quickly lose relevance. The social flux of UGC in terms of information sharing, and co-creation ensure that UGC remains updated, keeping the brand relevant and encouraging ongoing engagement.

The **Relatability** of UGC, enhanced by the social flux of UGC in terms of community building and social support play a key role in fostering a sense of community around the brand. When consumers see their values, experiences, or challenges reflected in the content, they feel more connected to the brand. This enhances brand loyalty and deepens consumer engagement. Lastly, **Engagement** is both a characteristic and an outcome of effective UGC. High consumer engagement with UGC can be facilitated through all the social flux of UGC especially community building and relationship building. This engagement strengthens brand relationships, as engaged consumers are more likely to remain loyal to the brand and advocate for it within their social circles. In sum, the social flux of UGC is instrumental in linking the characteristics of content and motivators of UGC, influencing consumer brand engagement. In the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan, understanding and leveraging these dynamics can help these banks enhance their brand engagement, foster deeper relationships with consumers, and drive growth.

5.2 RESONANCE OF REVERENCE' ENCAPSULATES THE INFLUENCE OF USER-GENERATED CONTENT

The table below presents a systematic exploration of the theme "Vibrations of Value," which focuses on how the sentiment carried in user-generated content affects consumer engagement in the realm of Islamic banking in Pakistan. It comprises three distinct codes: Emotional Equilibrium, Spectrum of Sensibility, and Resonance of Reverence, each of which offers unique insights into consumer engagement. This table synthesizes the codes, their definitions, relevant literature, and potential applications for Islamic banks in Pakistan. By applying these codes in their marketing and engagement strategies, Islamic banks can potentially increase their customer engagement and loyalty.

Table 5-8 Vibrations of Value: Emotional Undertones Impacting Consumer Engagement in Islamic Banking in Pakistan

Code Name	Definition	Literature Evidence	Application to Islamic Banks in Pakistan
Emotional Equilibrium	The balance of positive and negative	Dolan et al. (2019) discuss the balance of positive and negative sentiments in social media	Islamic banks can use this code to ensure they maintain a balance in their content.

	sentiments expressed in user-generated content.	engagement, highlighting the importance of both in understanding consumer engagement. They indicate that negative comments, while usually viewed as unfavourable, can provide valuable feedback for improvement.	Negative feedback should not be discarded; instead, it should be seen as an opportunity for improvement and to show customers that the bank values their input.
Spectrum of Sensibility	The wide range of emotional reactions that user-generated content can provoke among potential customers.	Yang et al. (2022) outline how various content features can foster consumer engagement. They point out that appealing to a wide range of sensibilities can increase customer engagement.	Islamic banks can apply this code by ensuring that their content appeals to a wide range of emotions and sensibilities. This could mean creating content that is informative, emotional, and even humorous, to appeal to different sensibilities.
Resonance of Reverence	The impact of user-generated content that aligns with and respects the values and norms of Islamic banking.	Mohammad et al. (2020) show that user-generated content that aligns with the values of the brand can increase brand engagement, particularly if it adds functional and emotional value to the consumers.	Islamic banks can apply this code by encouraging user-generated content that respects and aligns with the principles of Islamic banking. This could be in the form of customer testimonials, stories, or discussions about how the bank's services align with Islamic values.

Emotional Equilibrium is the balance of positive and negative emotions conveyed in user-generated content. Positive content can amplify customer engagement by endorsing the bank's performance and satisfying experiences. Simultaneously, negative sentiments serve as a crucial source of feedback, providing the bank with an opportunity to understand customers' concerns, rectify mistakes, and continuously improve (Dolan et al., 2019). It also allows Islamic banks to demonstrate their commitment to delivering quality service, consequently fostering trust, and enhancing customer relationships (Acuti et al., 2019).

The spectrum of sensibility deals with the range of emotional reactions elicited by UGC. It highlights the importance of creating content that strikes a chord with the audience's sensibilities, potentially leading to increased engagement. A diverse array of emotions can be leveraged to connect with customers at a deeper, more personal level. For example, Ibrahim et

al. (2022) discuss how UGC can elicit emotional responses that drive customer engagement, a strategy that could be highly beneficial for Islamic banks in Pakistan.

The third code, resonance of reverence, focuses on the influence of content that aligns with and respects the values and norms of Islamic banking. This code emphasizes that reverent content resonates with customers, enhancing their trust and engagement with the bank. For instance, Kitirattarkarn et al. (2019) found that alignment with cultural and societal values is a significant factor in engagement with UGC. Therefore, in the context of Islamic banking, content that acknowledges and respects the principles of Islamic finance is more likely to engage consumers. The table provides clear evidence that user-generated content, imbued with various emotions, can significantly impact consumer engagement in Islamic banking. When implemented effectively, these codes can help Islamic banks in Pakistan craft more impactful communication strategies. By achieving an Emotional Equilibrium, engaging with a Spectrum of Sensibility, and creating a Resonance of Reverence, Islamic banks can foster a more profound and meaningful engagement with their customers.

5.3 ANSWER TO RESEARCH QUESTIONS

How does the cultural context of Pakistan impact the effect of user-generated content on brand engagement in Islamic banks?

Understanding the cultural context of Pakistan is vital in analyzing the effect of UGC on brand engagement within Islamic banks.

Impact of Cultural Values: The cultural and societal values of Pakistan, deeply embedded within the principles of Islam, exert a significant influence on UGC. Users are likely to generate content that aligns with these values. For example, in a society that highly values trust, honesty, and mutual benefit, UGC related to Islamic banking is likely to echo these values, focusing on aspects like the bank's adherence to Islamic laws, ethical financial practices, or community-oriented initiatives. When consumers perceive content as aligning with their cultural values, it heightens their trust and engagement with the brand.

Collectivism vs Individualism: Pakistani society leans towards collectivism rather than individualism. This collective orientation encourages consumers to share their banking experiences, opinions, and advice, thereby contributing to high-volume, diverse UGC. Shared UGC within such a community can lead to a collective assessment and perception of a brand, influencing its overall engagement. **The Role of Respect and Courtesy:** In Pakistani culture,

respect, courtesy, and civility are valued. When UGC exhibits these characteristics, it can enhance the brand's image and engagement. However, online incivility or negative UGC, if not adequately managed, can significantly tarnish the brand's reputation, given the cultural importance of respect and courtesy.

Religiosity and Financial Decisions: The cultural context of Pakistan, being Islamic, influences the financial decisions of consumers. UGC that emphasizes the alignment of Islamic banks with Sharia principles may significantly impact brand engagement, as it resonates with the religious beliefs of consumers. **Impact of Societal Norms:** Societal norms in Pakistan also have an essential role. As a hierarchical society, the opinions of elders and influencers can impact the perceptions of others. Therefore, UGC by such influential figures can significantly impact brand engagement. In conclusion, the cultural context of Pakistan significantly influences the effect of UGC on brand engagement in Islamic banks. The societal values, collective orientation, emphasis on respect, religious beliefs, and hierarchical societal structure can all shape the narrative in UGC, impacting how consumers perceive and engage with Islamic banking brands.

What are the unique characteristics of user-generated content that positively influence brand engagement for Islamic banks in Pakistan?

The unique characteristics of UGC that positively influence brand engagement for Islamic banks in Pakistan can be quite distinct, given the country's cultural, societal, and religious fabric. UGC that emphasizes authenticity tends to have a strong influence. Customers want to feel assured that their Islamic banking experience aligns with their religious and ethical beliefs. Therefore, genuine, unfiltered customer experiences and testimonials, particularly those highlighting adherence to Sharia principles, significantly drive engagement. Virtuosity in Visualization is another characteristic that influences brand engagement. High-quality content, well-articulated, and providing valuable information, appeals to consumers. It becomes even more impactful when it presents complex Islamic banking concepts in a straightforward, easy-to-understand language, helping customers to make informed decisions.

The accuracy of the content plays a vital role as well. Misinformation can be particularly damaging in the banking sector. When UGC reflects accurate information, whether this is about interest-free banking, zakat, or profit-and-loss sharing systems, it fosters trust and enhances brand engagement. Real-life experiences shared by consumers significantly impact brand engagement. Storytelling, especially when it reflects personal experiences, success stories, or

unique benefits enjoyed by consumers, can make a powerful impact. These stories become relatable, striking a chord with potential customers, and prompting them to engage with the Islamic bank.

The diversity of perspectives in UGC also positively impacts brand engagement. Given the heterogeneity of consumers, UGC that reflects varied experiences, opinions, and suggestions can cater to a broader audience, thereby enhancing brand reach and engagement. UGC that offers value to consumers, such as insightful discussions on Islamic banking practices, financial tips, or benefits of specific banking products, is more likely to drive engagement. Such valuable content positions the brand as a source of expert advice, encouraging more interactions and deeper engagement.

Lastly, the timely and regular generation of UGC plays a role in maintaining brand engagement. When customers see regular content from their peers - be it reviews, opinions, discussions, or queries - it keeps the brand in their consideration set, thereby fostering sustained engagement. Characteristics like authenticity, Virtuosity in Visualization, accuracy, real-life experiences, diversity, value addition, and timeliness in UGC significantly influence brand engagement for Islamic banks in Pakistan.

How does the quality of user-generated content mediate the relationship between functional and emotional values and brand engagement for Islamic banks in Pakistan?

The quality of UGC acts as a mediator in the relationship between functional and emotional values and brand engagement for Islamic banks in Pakistan in several ways. Functional value pertains to the utilitarian, pragmatic, and problem-solving benefits that a product or service provides. In the context of Islamic banks, functional values can be the alignment with Islamic principles, the financial benefits and returns, ease of use, convenience, range of services, and reliability, among others. High-quality UGC that effectively communicates these functional values can reinforce consumers' perceptions of the Islamic bank's worthiness, enhancing brand engagement. To investigate the impact of online incivility in the form of negative UGC on brand engagement within the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan. The study, underpinned by the "Vibrations of Value" framework, explored the influence of the emotional undertones embedded in user-generated content on consumer engagement. Three key themes emerged: Emotional Equilibrium, Spectrum of Sensibility, and Resonance of Reverence.

- **Emotional Equilibrium:** The study found that balancing positive and negative sentiments in user-generated content can significantly impact consumer engagement. Negative user-generated content, which often takes the form of online incivility, may not necessarily dampen brand engagement. Instead, it could serve as a valuable source of feedback for Islamic banks to understand their customers' concerns, rectify any issues, and demonstrate their commitment to improvement. This process enhances customer relationships and promotes a sense of trust, thereby potentially enhancing overall brand engagement.
- **Spectrum of Sensibility:** The research also unveiled the potential of UGC to elicit a broad range of emotional reactions from consumers. Online incivility, primarily negative UGC, can trigger a spectrum of emotions among potential customers, which can be harnessed to create meaningful customer engagement. To counteract the negative impact of online incivility, Islamic banks can ensure their content appeals to a wide range of sensibilities and emotions, subsequently increasing brand engagement.
- **Resonance of Reverence:** Pertaining to the third code, the study found that UGC, even when negative, that respects and aligns with the values of Islamic banking could resonate with customers, thereby enhancing their engagement. This finding indicates that Islamic banks can mitigate the impact of negative content and online incivility by encouraging and fostering user-generated content that aligns with the principles and norms of Islamic finance.

In short, online incivility, in the form of negative UGC, can have complex and multifaceted impacts on brand engagement in the context of Islamic banking. Negative content, while often considered detrimental, can be valuable when appropriately managed and balanced with positive content, appealing to a range of customer sensibilities, and aligning with the reverence inherent in Islamic banking. Thus, Islamic banks can strategically manage the emotional undertones of user-generated content to foster deeper and more meaningful customer engagement, despite the presence of online incivility.

For instance, when UGC accurately portrays the Sharia-compliant processes of an Islamic bank, it reinforces the functional value of adherence to religious principles. Similarly, a well-articulated customer testimonial on the seamless digital banking experience provided by an Islamic bank can strengthen the functional value of convenience. Emotional value refers to the feelings and affective states that a product or service generates. It includes aspects like trust, a sense of belonging, pride, joy, or satisfaction. For Islamic banks in Pakistan, emotional values

can stem from the fulfilment of religious obligations, being part of a like-minded community, or the peace of mind from ethical banking. High-quality UGC that evokes such emotions can significantly enhance brand engagement. For example, authentic, heartfelt stories shared by consumers about how an Islamic bank has helped them fulfill their religious responsibilities can evoke strong positive emotions in others, driving engagement. Similarly, UGC that captures the joy or satisfaction of a customer with an Islamic banking service can emotionally connect with other consumers, spurring them to interact with the brand. The quality of UGC is crucial in effectively communicating the functional and emotional values of Islamic banks to consumers. High-quality UGC can articulate these values in a compelling, relatable, and credible manner, thereby fostering deeper brand engagement.

5.4 SUMMARY

UGC has profound implications for the development of marketing strategies in Islamic banks in Pakistan. Given its impact on brand engagement, it serves as a vital tool for understanding consumers, shaping brand perceptions, and enhancing brand visibility. In terms of consumer understanding, UGC, through customer reviews, comments, and discussions, provides an unfiltered insight into the consumer's mind. It reveals their preferences, expectations, pain points, and perceptions about Islamic banking. These insights are invaluable in tailoring marketing strategies to resonate with the target audience's values and needs.

In terms of shaping brand perceptions, UGC helps shape brand perceptions of Islamic banks. Positive testimonials, success stories, or recommendations can enhance the bank's credibility, build trust, and position the bank favourably in the mind of consumers. Marketing strategies can leverage this positive UGC, use it in promotional campaigns, or highlight it on their platforms to amplify the bank's positive image. **Brand Visibility:** In today's digital age, UGC can significantly enhance brand visibility. When consumers share their experiences or opinions about the bank on social media, it increases the bank's online presence. It can lead to word-of-mouth marketing, broadening the bank's reach. Hence, marketing strategies should encourage customers to generate content and share their experiences online.

UGC also implies the need for active online reputation management. Islamic banks need to monitor UGC constantly, address any negative content promptly, and manage crises efficiently to uphold the brand image. **Personalized Marketing:** UGC allows for more personalized marketing. By analyzing UGC, banks can segment their customers based on their preferences,

financial behaviour, or attitudes towards Islamic banking. They can then tailor their messages for each segment, enhancing the relevance and effectiveness of their marketing campaigns.

UGC further emphasizes the need for community engagement. Given the collective orientation of Pakistani society, consumers value the opinions of their community. Marketing strategies, therefore, should facilitate community discussions, involve influential figures, or leverage UGC that resonates with the collective values of the community. Lastly, UGC underscores the need to emphasize both functional and emotional values in marketing communications. UGC that highlights the Sharia-compliance, financial benefits, convenience, or the sense of satisfaction and fulfilment from using Islamic banking can significantly influence brand engagement. Marketing strategies, therefore, should articulate these functional and emotional values compellingly and credibly has significant implications for marketing strategies in Islamic banks in Pakistan. It necessitates a deeper understanding of consumers, active management of brand perceptions, enhancing brand visibility, personalized marketing, community engagement, and a balanced communication of functional and emotional values. By leveraging UGC effectively, Islamic banks in Pakistan can enhance their marketing effectiveness, deepen brand engagement, and drive their growth.

CHAPTER 6: DEVELOPMENT OF THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

6.1 INTRODUCTION

The major aim of this research is to develop a contextual framework of social brand, and consumer brand engagement based on social exchange. The previous chapter also identified that thematic analysis was used to develop a conceptual framework based on the findings.

6.2 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

There are certain core assumptions about social exchange theory which draw upon human nature and relationships amongst humans. Firstly, it presumes the seeking of rewards and the avoidance of punishment among humans (Homans, 1958). Secondly, it presumes the purpose of interaction to minimize cost and maximize benefits. Thirdly, it presumes that calculations are made before engaging in something. Lastly, it presumes a variance in payoff from time to time and from one person to another (Homans, 1958).

The core assumptions of the theory are related to the assumptions made under social exchange theory. The essence of both theories is that one size does not fit all as the expectations of each person evolve, and no two people have the same expectations. Rather, expectations serve as the baseline to develop a relationship (Homans, George 1950). For example, if someone enters a new relationship after a failed relationship, they have certain expectations shaped by their experience. Similarly, the application of theories in the shopping context means that the existing shopping experience serves as a baseline based on which they compare future shopping experiences (Homans, 1961).

These expectation levels resonate with other concepts, such as cost versus benefit, or the give and take concept which discusses the effort one is prepared to put into a relationship with someone. The 'cost' in this context refers to the price one is ready to pay to get what they expect, whereas the benefit is something they get in return for the price or cost they are paying (Blau, 1964). A worthwhile relationship is one in which the cost and benefits are balanced, and one gets what one expects in return for what they give. This is applicable to all types of transactions that humans conduct (Lawler, and They, 2006). If the cost is higher than the benefit, then the person bearing the cost tends to lose interest in the relationship. However, the comparison with alternatives may keep the person in the relationship when they find out that

coming out of the transaction would be no less advantageous than the status quo. This may then inadvertently keep them in the relationship (Miller, 2005).

Several studies have been conducted using SET as a foundation. Cook, and Rice, (2003) observed that a relationship involves balancing exchanges between all parties involved, provided the comparison with alternatives favours those in the relationship. This means that any social exchange between two or more people is based on what they receive from each other, as compared to what anyone else can offer them instead. If the exchange is better than what anyone else can offer them in place of each other, then they remain bound to each other (Cook, Emerson, 1978). However, the current research also finds that the application of theory from the perspective of relativism and social constructionism to understand social brand engagement is based on social interactions between SMUs, which is limited. Moreover, the existing application of theory has been made in the context of game-based scenarios involving rewards and costs for playing on a computer-based game. However, such relationships cannot be related to real life experiences, such as Islamic banking services, or the creation of UGC on social media networks (hereinafter SMNs) whereby SMUs participate in creating, sharing, and exchanging UGC. Thus, the current research applies social exchange theory in the context of the role of UGC in creating brand engagement.

It is also difficult to define the key concepts of social exchange theory. The concept of cost and reward is subjective and thus an objective definition of these concepts may not be possible. However, this research has developed a process-based framework which shows the process of social exchange as an outcome of the SBE and CBE. However, since the current research is related to subjectivism i.e., it is exploratory in nature and based on subjective viewpoints, social exchange theory provides a useful insight for understanding the motives of SMUs for creating, sharing, and exchanging UGC in the context of Islamic banking brands.

Furthermore, it is also presumed by social exchange theory that, in the beginning of any relationship, the partners tend to remember what they are getting for what they are giving to each other. Clark and Mills (2011) argued that while this may be true in professional situations, it may not be true in personal situations such as in social relationships where there is less focus on what they are getting in return for what they are giving. Other researchers highlight that it is not about a balance of rewards versus cost, but about the overall fairness of the relationship over the social media they share their cost and benefits with each other.

Knapp, (1978) also highlighted the cause-and-effect related issue regarding assumptions made under SET. For example, Lawler, (2001) argued that the assessment of a relationship begins even before dissatisfaction arises. This shows that such an assessment paves the way for dissatisfaction or satisfaction. However, again this is relevant in some relationships e.g., purely give and take based relationships, but this may not be relevant in other relationships, such as romantic relationships or social duty-oriented relationships where one person feels that it is his responsibility to keep the others informed.

Social exchange theory highlights four major factors which are identified through this research which include sampling, bargaining, commitment and commitment and Institutionalization. Therefore, the sampling where family as compared to by celebrities, influencers, experts, and opinion leaders to build their online relation via social media which is the first stage of the social exchange. Nevertheless, it indicates that certain individuals are seen as experts in their social circles, and others tend to follow them for advice. Therefore, the current research takes the position that Discourse of Kinship influences others. Similarly, UGC is also a type of Discourse of Kinship (McShane et al., 2019). Some people are influenced the UGC produced by close friends and family, while others tend to keenly follow the advice of their favourite celebrities and influencers and experts where the exchange process starts with the social exchange of UGC. This necessitates considering the persuading effect of Discourse of Kinship as the current research assesses the impact of Discourse of Kinship of UGC in encouraging and persuading the other SMUs to create, share and bargain for UGC. They thereby engage with the brand at the bargaining level of the social exchange process.

People tend to take advice from those they feel close to in the event of uncertainty which is the second stage of social exchange (see figure 5-1 below). Moreover, people also tend to seek advice from those who they think are highly knowledgeable and better experienced. Thus, close friends, experts and product users hold a prominent position in this regard. This can be seen in the case of UGC posted online on SMNs, as people follow each other in such settings and partake in UGC creation; sharing and exchanging information on different topics. These include brand related discussions where they become committed to contributing. This serves as Discourse of Kinship based on their commitment to other SMUs.

The current research also contributes towards an understanding of the role of UGC in creating brand engagement by studying the impact of UGC on different SMUs. This increases the relevance of social exchange theory. Accordingly, the research points to different types of

social agents such as close friends, family, product users, celebrities, and opinion leaders who connect via social media. However, many of them do not know each other personally. These are regarded as wise, which is further classified as the wisdom of friends and of crowds based on their social exchange. This wisdom lies in the foundation of Discourse of Kinship generated as part of UGC which influences SMUs to engage with UGC and thereby engage with the brand (see the figure below). The research also discusses the type of influence and the type of social agents e.g., sampling and bargaining with wisdom of crowd and commitment with wisdom of friends.

The findings also show that people like sharing views on social media and thereby generate UGC to show commitment. This encourages likeminded people to interact with UGC and thereby generate further UGC that creates an advantage. Yet these advantages further institutionalization stage where they get social engage or engaged as consumer of banks. This then has the effect of creating e-WOM at the stage of institutionalization. If SMUs have favourable experiences of brands, this generates positive e-WOM, otherwise it generates negative e-WOM. Many participants indicated that they check information related to brands with multiple sources.

The Social Exchange Theory (SET) can be aptly applied to the conceptual framework developed for this research study. SET posits that the interactions and relationships between individuals are formed and sustained based on the mutual exchange of benefits, both tangible and intangible. In the context of brand-related user-generated content (UGC) for Islamic banks in Pakistan, this theory can provide a solid foundation for understanding the dynamics of consumer engagement and brand engagement.

The first stage of the framework, which involves the social exchange of brand related UGC, can be associated with the core tenets of SET. The exchange here involves consumers Narrative Threads of Wisdoms, Harvesting Wisdom Nuggets, adhering to Moral Weaves of Society, Illuminating the Conscious Horizon, and becoming an influencer in the public sphere. This exchange creates an environment where users, industry experts, and friends interact, ensuring a robust flow of information. This aligns with SET, which underscores the importance of reciprocal actions that yield mutual benefits. In this context, the mutual benefits include knowledge sharing, peer validation, and increased brand trustworthiness. The second stage, bargaining, ties into the SET through the formation of Discourse of Kinship. As consumers become active participants in the exchange of UGC, they shape the public opinion about the

brand, thereby creating a Discourse of Kinship for the brand. This process of negotiation and bargaining is a crucial part of SET, where consumers assess the potential benefits and drawbacks of their engagement.

Commitment, the next stage in the framework, resonates with the SET's emphasis on relationships. The commitment stage reflects the user's journey from being a passive consumer to an engaged, active participant. In this stage, consumers express their brand liking, share service experiences, and make opinions. They become advocates of the brand, sharing information, discounts, and service details. This commitment deepens their connection with the brand and facilitates a sense of community, both essential aspects of SET.

Finally, brand engagement culminates from the social exchange, bargaining, and commitment stages. It is the ultimate benefit for both the consumer and the brand, as outlined by SET. The link with the characteristics of UGC, motivators of UGC, and Social Flux of User-Generated Content provides a comprehensive understanding of the factors that drive brand engagement. In conclusion, the Social Exchange Theory significantly informs the conceptual framework for this research study. It helps elucidate how the Echoes of Influence: Tracing the Social Flux of User-Generated Content can drive brand engagement for Islamic banks in Pakistan.

The current research also found that opinion leaders exert influence on SMUs when they give brand recommendations online. They are seen to possess relevant expertise, but their link has been created at the sampling stage of the social exchange. As a result, the suggestions they give are trusted by SMUs. However, not all SMUs are influenced by opinion leaders. If an opinion leader is a close friend, then others are likely to be influenced by their recommendations. There is some commitment amongst these group members because of the Discourse of Kinship they have based on their everyday exchanges on social media. Such opinion leaders are regarded as trustworthy and their opinions as credible. They also add value to content that creates social brand engagement and consumer brand engagement. This then results in brand engagement as synthesized in the figure 6-1 below.

Figure 6-1 Conceptual framework of the social exchange-based brand engagement process (developed by the author)

Peoples' behaviour changes when they hear about brands from influential sources. This affects their final buying decision. The discourse of kinship plays a pivotal role in shaping the buying behaviour of people. SMNs play a key role in making the discourses of kinship available to large audiences at the same time. There are four steps to the social exchange process (Cook, and Rice, 2003) and these are relevant in the age of social media. The ongoing proliferation of UGC and the rising influence of social media platforms have redefined brand engagement strategies, particularly in the banking sector. Islamic banks, with their unique principles and offerings, have an exciting opportunity to leverage UGC to foster brand engagement and influence their public perception.

Through "Catalysts of Co-Creation: Inspiring UGC in Islamic Banking" and "The Prism of Perception: The Shapeshifting Power of Content," we can discern the intricate ways in which UGC inspires and shapes brand engagement for Islamic banks on social media platforms.

Starting with the Catalysts of Co-Creation, various factors can be identified such as:

1. Narrative Threads of Wisdom: This refers to users sharing personal experiences or stories about their interactions with Islamic banks. As Hinson, Boateng, Renner, & Kosiba (2019) noted, these shared experiences contribute to creating online brand communities, fostering trust, and increasing perceived value, subsequently promoting brand engagement.
2. Moral Weaves of Society: Users appreciate the ethical practices of Islamic banks, often sharing about their adherence to Islamic laws and ethical investments. As per Dolan,

Conduit, Frethey-Bentham, Fahy, & Goodman (2019), consumers engage more with brands perceived as ethical or socially responsible. Thus, conversations around these practices enhance the banks' image and brand engagement.

3. **Illuminating the Conscious Horizon:** Users generating content to educate others about Islamic banking services increases brand awareness and attracts potential customers. Acuti, Grazzini, Mazzoli, & Aiello (2019) highlight the importance of such UGC in enhancing brand engagement.
4. **Harvesting Wisdom Nuggets:** Users posting questions or seeking information about Islamic banks foster interaction and discussions, promoting brand engagement. Cheung, Pires, & Rosenberger (2020) underscored that consumers often use social media to gather information, enhancing consumer-brand engagement.
5. **Sculpting the Influential Echo Chamber:** Influencers play a critical role in shaping public opinion about Islamic banks. Baker, Kearney, Laud, & Holmlund (2021) found that influencers significantly impact consumers' engagement, thus, potentially swaying public opinion favourably and boosting brand engagement.

Turning to "The Prism of Perception: The Shapeshifting Power of Content", we see how content influences the perception and engagement with Islamic banks:

1. **Virtuosity in Visualization:** High-quality and relevant content, including videos, graphics, pictures, and audio, play a significant role in promoting brand loyalty (Schivinski et al., 2021). Thus, the excellence of content helps increase the trust and reliability factor amongst users, making Islamic banking more appealing.
2. **Precision of Perspective:** The correctness and relatability of the content shared are crucial. If the content is precise, clear, and factual, it attracts potential clients and retains current ones, as suggested by Grover & Kar (2020).
3. **Symbiosis of Sentiment:** The emotional connection consumers have with the banks drives customer loyalty and promotes brand engagement (Estrella-Ramón et al., 2019). This sentiment, when captured and shared through UGC, significantly influences public opinion and engagement with Islamic banking.

In conclusion, both the Catalysts of Co-Creation and the Prism of Perception illuminate the complex interplay between UGC and brand engagement within the context of Islamic banking. By harnessing the power of UGC, Islamic banks can significantly shape their public perception, influence decision-making, and deepen their engagement with existing and potential customers. With each shared experience, piece of advice, or insightful question, they cultivate a virtual community rooted in trust, transparency, and mutual benefit, which is the essence of successful brand engagement.

The interplay between the Catalysts of Co-Creation and the Prism of Perception forms a rich tapestry that drives social brand engagement for Islamic banks on social media. While the catalysts encourage users to create, share, and engage with content, the Prism of Perception impacts how the content is consumed and further shared. This interaction creates a dynamic, user-driven space where brand perceptions are formed and shaped, leading to heightened brand engagement. Narrative Threads of Wisdom is the first of the catalysts, relating to personal stories and experiences shared by customers about their interactions with Islamic banks. When these narratives are delivered with Virtuosity in Visualization, they become compelling and relatable, increasing their potential to inspire and engage other users. High-quality content in the form of well-articulated reviews or visually striking posts heightens the appeal of these narratives, making them more engaging and shareable.

The Moral Weaves of Society element emphasizes the ethical considerations of Islamic banking. Users appreciate and discuss how these banks adhere to moral and religious principles, generating content that reflects the ethical standards and values of the banks. When combined with Precision of Perspective, these discussions become more valuable and engaging. Accurate and precise information about the ethical practices of Islamic banks can strengthen trust among customers, leading to more robust brand engagement. This precision also ensures that the ethical values, an important aspect of Islamic banking, are correctly understood and appreciated by the audience.

Illuminating the Conscious Horizon involves the educational aspect of UGC, where users generate content to inform and enlighten others about the features and benefits of Islamic banking. Paired with Virtuosity in Visualization, the educational content can be more visually appealing and digestible, fostering better understanding and encouraging wider dissemination. The use of infographics, diagrams, or high-quality videos can effectively illustrate complex banking concepts, making them accessible to a larger audience and driving deeper engagement.

Harvesting Wisdom Nuggets relates to content created to gather insights or information about Islamic banking from fellow users. This aspect relies heavily on Precision of Perspective, as the information sought and shared needs to be accurate for it to be beneficial. This combination results in a community-driven learning environment, promoting deeper discussions about the Islamic banking system and fostering stronger connections with the brand.

Sculpting the Influential Echo Chamber represents the impact of influencers or well-respected individuals in shaping public opinion about Islamic banks. The Symbiosis of Sentiment is particularly pertinent here, as the sentiments expressed by these influencers often set the tone for their followers' feelings towards the banks. Positive experiences and endorsements shared by influencers can evoke positive sentiments among their followers, fostering loyalty and encouraging engagement with the brand. The Catalysts of Co-Creation inspire users to generate, share, and interact with content related to Islamic banks, while the Prism of Perception determines how this content is consumed, interpreted, and further shared. Together, they create a dynamic and engaging environment that fosters discussion, spreads awareness, and shapes perceptions about Islamic banking. This user-driven approach places the audience at the heart of brand engagement, ensuring a deeper and more meaningful connection with the brand. The interplay between these elements is an important consideration for Islamic banks seeking to strengthen their brand engagement and presence on social media.

Delving deeper into the complex interplay of Catalysts of Co-Creation and the Prism of Perception, it is important to note that they collectively frame how Islamic banks are perceived and engaged with on social media. Let us take the instance of Narrative Threads of Wisdom and Virtuosity in Visualization. These narratives, woven from personal experiences, are most effective when shared with an engaging visual element. The visual aspect could be a captivating image, infographic, or video that not only supplements the narrative but amplifies it. The combination has a multiplier effect, making the narrative more compelling and engaging, thus prompting further interaction, or sharing from the audience.

Furthermore, the Moral Weaves of Society have a profound link to the Precision of Perspective. Ethical and moral considerations are central to the functioning of Islamic banks, and this aspect often serves as a significant point of distinction from conventional banks. Social media users' content focusing on these ethical practices creates a sense of trust and respect for the brand. However, the power of this content is increased when it is shared with precision. Accurate and

detailed content about the ethical practices can dispel misconceptions, offering a clearer understanding of Islamic banking and its principles.

When users attempt to educate others about the principles, practices, or benefits of Islamic banking, they are Illuminating the Conscious Horizon. But to ensure this information is well-received and understood, it needs to be delivered with Virtuosity in Visualization. Visual aids can simplify complex concepts, making them more understandable and appealing to a wider audience. A user who might shy away from reading a long post might be more inclined to engage with a well-made infographic or video explaining the same concept. In terms of Harvesting Wisdom Nuggets, Precision of Perspective comes into play again. Users pose questions or seek information to understand better how Islamic banks function. The information gathered needs to be accurate and dependable for it to serve its purpose. This co-creation process fuels discussions, making the interaction more meaningful and leading to deeper connections with the brand.

Finally, influencers who are Sculpting the Influential Echo Chamber can drive significant shifts in brand perception. With their ability to command attention and influence, they can turn the tide in favour of Islamic banks. When combined with the Symbiosis of Sentiment, influencers can imbue their content with emotions that resonate with their audience. This resonance can enhance loyalty and promote continued engagement with the brand. In short, it is a complex dance between the co-creation of content and how it is perceived, playing a vital role in building, and shaping brand engagement for Islamic banks on social media. Each factor feeds into and enhances the other, creating a robust system of user-led content creation and consumption that drives brand engagement.

Analyzing the interaction between the elements of the Social Exchange Theory (SET) - namely bargaining and sampling - and the components of Catalysts of Co-Creation and the Prism of Perception provides a comprehensive perspective on how user engagement and interaction with Islamic banking on social media occur. Starting with Narrative Threads of Wisdom, these personal stories or experiences users share become the medium of bargaining. The users offer their experience in exchange for trust, validation, or feedback from the social media community. Sampling occurs when other users read these narratives, using them as a sample to evaluate Islamic banking services and make decisions.

The Moral Weaves of Society, which reflect ethical practices and the adherence of Islamic banks to Islamic laws, serve as a bargaining tool, too. When users discuss these aspects, they exchange ethical insights for social approval and trust. The exchange becomes a sampling opportunity for individuals looking to align their financial choices with their moral and religious beliefs, helping them assess if Islamic banks meet their ethical expectations. In Illuminating the Conscious Horizon, users educate others about the benefits of Islamic banking, bargaining their knowledge and insights for influence and recognition. As recipients of this knowledge, other users sample the information, using it as a basis to form their understanding and perceptions about Islamic banking.

Harvesting Wisdom Nuggets works as a bargaining process where users trade their need for information with other users' knowledge and experiences. The responses and insights they gain serve as samples that help them form an understanding of Islamic banking, influencing their decisions about engaging with these financial institutions. Sculpting the Influential Echo Chamber involves influential individuals or entities bargaining their influence for trust and followership. They share opinions or reviews about Islamic banks, shaping public perceptions. Here, sampling happens when other users consider these influencers' opinions as reliable samples to gauge the credibility and quality of Islamic banking services.

Shifting focus to the Prism of Perception, Virtuosity in Visualization involves users leveraging high-quality visual content to bargain for attention, engagement, and influence. Other users sample these visual content pieces, using them to evaluate the message and form impressions about Islamic banking. Precision of Perspective denotes the importance of accurate and precise information. Here, users bargain accurate content for trust and credibility, while other users sample the information's precision to form their understanding and opinion about Islamic banks.

Symbiosis of Sentiment involves users sharing their emotional connection or sentiment towards an Islamic bank, bargaining their feelings for empathy or shared sentiment. This sentiment is sampled by others, often influencing their emotional connection with the brand, and swaying their decisions. The interplay between the Catalysts of Co-Creation, the Prism of Perception, and the elements of SET is dynamic. They together illustrate how social media users share, engage, and shape their perceptions about Islamic banking, enabling an understanding of the complex process of social brand engagement.

Bargaining and sampling are integral components of the Social Exchange Theory (SET), which posits that social behaviour is the result of an exchange process aiming to maximize benefits and minimize costs. In the context of community building, especially on social media, these principles play a vital role. Bargaining, in social media context, can be understood as the exchange of information, experiences, or insights between users. It is a process of give-and-take where the users exchange content, whether this is about sharing personal stories, reviews, opinions, or knowledge. This mutual exchange helps to build a sense of trust and reciprocity, which are fundamental in building and maintaining social relationships and communities. Bargaining encourages active participation, as everyone has something unique to contribute, enhancing the richness and diversity of the community.

Sampling, on the other hand, is the process of consuming or evaluating the shared content, information, or experiences. Users sample the information available to form their opinions, make decisions, or gain understanding. Sampling is the evaluative element of the exchange, where users scrutinize the content and engage with it through comments, likes, shares, or even creating related content. This process fosters learning, stimulates discussion, and encourages interaction, contributing to a sense of shared understanding and cohesion within the community.

In the context of community building on social media, these processes of bargaining and sampling are constant and ongoing. As users continue to share (bargain) and consume (sample), they are continually shaping and reshaping the community. Every shared experience, piece of advice, or exchanged opinion adds a layer to the community's collective knowledge, while every interaction, response, or evaluation (sampling) reinforces the social bonds within the community. The dynamics of bargaining and sampling underpin the active engagement and vibrant interaction in social media communities. By encouraging the exchange of diverse content and promoting active participation, they contribute to the growth, resilience, and vibrancy of online communities.

When it comes to consumer brand engagement, it is crucial to acknowledge that it differs from social brand engagement, though both are interconnected. While social brand engagement is about the active interaction between the brand and its followers on social media platforms, consumer brand engagement is about the psychological process that customers experience when they interact with a brand, resulting in brand loyalty, brand advocacy, or repeat purchases. In this context, factors such as Emotional Equilibrium, Luminaries of the Trade,

Social Resonance, Friends Interaction, Precision of the Perspective, Confluence of the Conveniences, Spectrum of Sensibility, Discourse of Kinship, and Resonance of Reverence all play a significant role in fostering consumer brand engagement. Emotional Equilibrium refers to the balance between customers' emotional responses and the brand's actions or communications. When brands manage to strike this balance effectively, they can establish a connection that leads to increased customer engagement. This is about creating content or experiences that evoke emotions aligned with the brand's values and resonate with customers' feelings, thereby fostering a deeper psychological bond between them and the brand.

Luminaries of the Trade refers to influencers or experts in the industry whose opinions and insights carry weight. When these luminaries endorse or advocate for a brand, they significantly impact consumer perceptions, potentially fostering trust and driving engagement. Their endorsement adds a layer of credibility to the brand, making it more appealing and trustworthy in the eyes of consumers. Social Resonance and Friends Interaction both pertain to the social influences on consumer engagement. Social Resonance is about creating content or experiences that resonate within the social community or network, fostering a sense of shared understanding or connection. Friends Interaction, on the other hand, emphasizes the influence of peers on consumer decisions. Peer recommendations can enhance consumer trust and engagement as they are seen as more authentic and unbiased.

Precision of the Perspective underscores the importance of accurate and relevant content. Consumers are more likely to engage with brands that provide precise, dependable, and informative content. It fosters trust and credibility, encouraging consumers to explore, learn more about, and engage with the brand. Confluence of the Conveniences refers to the brand's ability to offer a seamless and convenient customer experience. Whether it is through user-friendly interfaces, personalized services, or quick responses, convenience enhances the overall customer experience, leading to increased satisfaction and, consequently, engagement.

Spectrum of Sensibility deals with the brand's sensitivity towards its customers' needs, expectations, and concerns. Brands that show a high degree of sensibility and empathy are more likely to establish a deeper emotional connection with their customers, leading to stronger engagement.

Discourse of Kinship and Resonance of Reverence both involve fostering a sense of belonging and respect. Discourse of Kinship creates a sense of community or family among customers,

leading to stronger emotional bonds and engagement. On the other hand, Resonance of Reverence involves cultivating a sense of admiration or respect for the brand, whether through its values, actions, or achievements, which can elevate the brand's status and boost consumer engagement. These factors work together to shape consumer perceptions, evoke emotions, foster trust, and enhance the overall customer experience, leading to stronger consumer brand engagement. Each factor contributes to a different aspect of the consumer-brand relationship, from emotional connection and social influence on credibility, convenience, and respect. Their interplay creates a multifaceted engagement experience that draws consumers in, keeps them engaged, and encourages them to stay loyal to the brand.

Creating consumer brand engagement for Islamic banks is a multifaceted process that involves various interconnected factors. It requires Islamic banks to address the emotional, social, and practical needs of their customers. It is useful to explore how these factors intersect to create a profound consumer brand engagement within the context of Islamic banking. Emotional Equilibrium and Spectrum of Sensibility are intricately linked in the context of Islamic banking. Customers who choose Islamic banking often do so out of a commitment to the moral and ethical guidelines laid out by their faith. Thus, their engagement is not merely transactional; it is intrinsically tied to their deeply held beliefs. For these customers, emotional equilibrium is achieved when their banking activities align with their ethical standards. This means the bank acknowledges and respects these values, creating a Spectrum of Sensibility around these emotions. It leads to deeper customer engagement, as customers feel seen, understood, and valued.

Luminaries of the Trade can significantly enhance this engagement process. Respected figures in Islamic finance can bolster the reputation and credibility of an Islamic bank. Their endorsement can validate the bank's practices, providing reassurance to customers who are seeking ethical financial solutions. In a way, they serve as a bridge between the bank and its customers, ensuring the Precision of Perspective in the bank's messages and offerings.

Furthermore, the role of Friends Interaction and Social Resonance cannot be overlooked in this context. Many customers of Islamic banking are part of closely-knit communities that place significant value on word-of-mouth recommendations. Friends Interaction enables customers to share positive experiences, effectively becoming brand ambassadors within their communities. Social Resonance is the ripple effect of these interactions. When customers'

positive experiences resonate within the community, it can amplify consumer engagement with the bank.

The Confluence of Conveniences adds another layer to this engagement process. This means the bank offers a seamless and efficient customer experience, whether this is through its online platform, customer service, or banking products. This convenience, coupled with the bank's adherence to Islamic principles, creates a unique value proposition that strengthens customer engagement.

Finally, the Discourse of Kinship and Resonance of Reverence play pivotal roles in fostering a sense of belonging and respect among customers. In Islamic banking, the Discourse of Kinship goes beyond merely offering banking services. This is about creating a community of customers who share the same values and principles. This community feeling strengthens customer loyalty and engagement. On the other hand, the Resonance of Reverence is about cultivating a sense of admiration or respect for the bank's commitment to Islamic principles, further deepening this engagement. As such, consumer brand engagement in Islamic banking is a complex interplay of emotional, social, and practical factors. Each of these factors brings a unique element to the engagement process, together creating a holistic engagement experience that resonates with customers' needs, values, and expectations. Their interconnectedness lies at the heart of effective consumer brand engagement, leading to a loyal customer base and a stronger brand.

Social exchange theory and social influence theory offer insightful perspectives into the engagement and interaction dynamics within the customer-brand relationships in the realm of Islamic banking. While social exchange theory emphasizes mutual give-and-take, social influence theory delves into how individuals' attitudes and behaviors are affected by others. It is therefore useful to explore how these theoretical perspectives align with the identified factors.

Table 6-1 Aligning Factors of Consumer Engagement with Theoretical Constructs in the Context of Islamic Banks on social media.

Factors	Relevant Theoretical Factor	Explanation in Context of Brand Engagement of Islamic Banks
Confluence of Conveniences	Bargaining (Social Exchange Theory)	Consumers engage more deeply with the bank in exchange for the conveniences and value-added services it provides.
Harvesting Wisdom Nuggets	Sampling (Social Exchange Theory)	Consumers gather information about the bank's services, ethos, and performance,

		driving a deeper understanding and engagement.
Emotional Equilibrium	Commitment (Social Exchange Theory)	The emotional stability that consumers derive from their relationship with the bank fosters a deeper commitment and engagement.
Discourse of Kinship	Commitment (Social Exchange Theory)	The sense of community developed amongst the bank's consumers deepens their commitment and engagement.
Resonance of Reverence	Commitment (Social Exchange Theory)	Customers' admiration for the bank's adherence to Islamic principles deepens their commitment and engagement with the brand.
Precision of Perspective	Internalization (Social Influence Theory)	Consumers internalize the brand's authentic and precise messaging, which aligns with their personal values, driving stronger engagement.
Spectrum of Sensibility	Internalization (Social Influence Theory)	By internalizing consistent and values-driven messages from the bank, consumers feel more aligned with the brand, boosting their engagement.
Luminaries of the Trade	Internalization (Social Influence Theory)	Endorsement by respected figures in the industry can sway consumer opinion and behaviour, leading to increased engagement.
Friends Interaction	Internalization (Social Influence Theory)	Positive experiences or educational content about the bank shared by peer's shape consumer perceptions of the brand, driving higher engagement.
Social Resonance	Internalization (Social Influence Theory)	Consumers' engagement is enhanced when they internalize narratives that resonate with their social and cultural identities.
Illuminating the Conscious Horizon	Internalization (Social Influence Theory)	Educational content about the bank absorbed by consumers shape their perception of the brand and boost their engagement.
Narrative Threads of Wisdom	Internalization (Social Influence Theory)	User-generated content sharing experiences with the bank can influence others and heighten engagement.
Moral Weaves of Society	Internalization (Social Influence Theory)	Sharing ethical values and practices of the bank influences others and enhances brand engagement.
Sculpting the Influential Echo Chamber	Internalization (Social Influence Theory)	Influencers sway public opinion, shaping perceptions of the brand and driving engagement.
Virtuosity in Visualization	Both Bargaining (Social Exchange Theory) and Internalization (Social Influence Theory)	High-quality content drives engagement by providing value to consumers (bargaining) and shaping their perceptions of the bank (internalization).
Symbiosis of Sentiment	Both Bargaining (Social Exchange Theory) and Internalization (Social Influence Theory)	Emotion-laden content influences consumers' sentiments about the bank (internalization) and is the value consumers receive (bargaining), driving engagement.

Beginning with social exchange theory, bargaining is a principal element which can be seen in the Confluence of Conveniences and Harvesting Wisdom Nuggets. When consumers engage with Islamic banks, they bargain by exchanging their patronage and engagement for the convenience and value-added services the bank provides. Harvesting Wisdom Nuggets, on the other hand, represents the constant exchange of information between consumers and the bank, a sampling process where consumers gather information about the bank's services, ethos, and performance. Commitment, another facet of social exchange theory, aligns with Emotional Equilibrium and Discourse of Kinship. These factors involve consumers committing to a relationship with the bank due to the emotional stability and a sense of community they derive. Further, Resonance of Reverence, where customers' admiration for the bank's adherence to Islamic principles deepens their commitment to the brand, also echoes this aspect of the theory.

Turning to social influence theory, internalization is evident in many ways. In Precision of Perspective and Spectrum of Sensibility, customers internalize the brand's authentic, consistent, and precise messaging which aligns with their personal values. Luminaries of the Trade illustrates how endorsement by respected figures in the industry can sway consumer opinion and behaviour; a strong example of internalization in action. Friends Interaction, Social Resonance, and Illuminating the Conscious Horizon further underline the internalization process. As peers and social networks share positive experiences or educational content about the bank, these narratives are absorbed by consumers, shaping their perception of the brand.

Narrative Threads of Wisdom and Moral Weaves of Society highlight how UGC, sharing experiences and ethical values, can influence others, aligning with the how social influence emphasises how behaviour and attitudes can be shaped by others. Similarly, Sculpting the Influential Echo Chamber shows how influencers can sway public opinion, a manifestation of the social influence process.

Lastly, Virtuosity in Visualization and Symbiosis of Sentiment exemplify how compelling and emotion-laden content can wield substantial influence over consumers' attitudes and behaviors towards the bank, embodying both the elements of social exchange and social influence theory. In social exchange, this high-quality content is the value consumers receive, while in social influence, this content shapes consumers' perceptions and sentiments about the bank. The examined factors beautifully align with the constructs of social exchange theory and social

influence theory. They highlight the dynamic interplay of mutual exchange, commitment, and social influence in shaping consumers' engagement and perception of Islamic banks on social media, contributing to a richer understanding of this intricate process. The conceptual framework of engagement comprise of sampling, exchange, bargaining, commitment, and institutionalization.

The is following two tables illustrate how various factors contribute to both social brand engagement and consumer brand engagement in the context of Islamic banking:

Table 6-2 Role of Factors in Social Brand Engagement

Factors	Role in Social Brand Engagement
Narrative Threads of Wisdom	Facilitate the sharing of user experiences, thereby shaping perceptions and boosting engagement.
Moral Weaves of Society	Foster engagement by allowing users to discuss the ethical practices of the Islamic bank.
Illuminating the Conscious Horizon	Promote engagement through the dissemination of information about the bank's services, thus increasing awareness.
Harvesting Wisdom Nuggets	Enable users to seek information about the bank from other users, thereby encouraging interaction and engagement.
Sculpting the Influential Echo Chamber	Influence public opinion through content created by influencers, thereby increasing engagement.
Virtuosity in Visualization	Enhances the quality and relevance of user-generated content, making it more engaging.
Precision of Perspective	Ensures accuracy and authenticity in content shared, thereby attracting more engagement.
Symbiosis of Sentiment	Reflects consumers' association with the brand, contributing to increased engagement.

The digital era has facilitated novel ways of interacting and building relationships between brands and consumers. The creation of engaging brand experiences is increasingly hinging on social and digital interactions. However, there are notable differences between social brand engagement and consumer brand engagement, especially in the context of Islamic banks.

Social Brand Engagement revolves around the interactions between a brand and its consumers in the social media realm. This concept is concerned with the extent to which consumers participate in the public brand-related activities initiated by themselves or by others. Social brand engagement encapsulates activities such as content sharing, commenting, liking, and other forms of interaction that occur on various social media platforms. In the context of Islamic banking, this form of engagement can significantly influence the perception and reputation of an Islamic bank brand.

For instance, when individuals share their positive experiences with an Islamic bank, they are adding to the narrative threads of wisdom. This type of UGC plays a pivotal role in promoting the bank's brand by portraying it in a positive light, boosting its image, and enhancing its perceived value. Similarly, the moral weaves of society, which encapsulates the ethical practices of Islamic banks, contribute to social brand engagement by enhancing the bank's image and driving more customers to engage. Meanwhile, Consumer Brand Engagement refers to the level of a consumer's psychological investment and active participation in the brand. It involves a deeper, emotional connection between the consumer and the brand that extends beyond merely using the product or service. This emotional connection can significantly affect a consumer's decision-making process and their long-term loyalty to a brand.

The factors influencing consumer brand engagement are more oriented towards the individual's feelings and experiences with the brand. For instance, emotional equilibrium allows for a more satisfying engagement experience, helping to solidify a stronger emotional bond with the brand. In the context of Islamic banking, luminaries of the trade, or influential figures in the industry, can significantly sway consumer engagement since consumers often look to them for guidance or validation of their banking choices. Moreover, precision of perspective contributes to consumer engagement in Islamic banking by ensuring the accuracy and authenticity of the content shared about the brand. This can increase trust and reliability, and in turn, lead to more profound consumer engagement. The discourse of kinship and resonance of reverence also help to strengthen consumer engagement by creating a sense of community and respect for the brand among consumers.

Table 6-3 Role of Factors in Consumer Brand Engagement

Factors	Role in Consumer Brand Engagement
Emotional Equilibrium	Facilitates a satisfying engagement experience for consumers, thereby promoting more interaction with the brand.
Luminaries of the Trade	Influential figures within the industry can significantly impact consumer perception and engagement.
Social Resonance	Helps create a sense of community and shared understanding, fostering more substantial engagement.
Friends Interaction	Interactions between friends about the brand contribute to building trust and positive engagement.
Precision of the Perspective	Clarity, accuracy, and relatability in the content shared about the brand can attract and retain customers.
Confluence of the Conveniences	The convenience and ease of interacting with the brand can significantly enhance consumer engagement.
Spectrum of Sensibility	When consumers identify with the brand's values and ethos, this can lead to deeper and more meaningful engagement.

Discourse of Kinship	A sense of shared community or kinship can significantly boost brand engagement.
Resonance of Reverence	Reverence or respect for the brand can lead to stronger engagement and loyalty.
Social Resonance	A sense of community, belonging, or shared values can significantly increase engagement and loyalty to the brand.

These tables above delineate the roles various factors play in shaping social brand engagement and consumer brand engagement in the context of Islamic banking. Each factor contributes uniquely to creating a robust engagement environment where consumers can interact, share, and form a relationship with the brand. While both social brand engagement and consumer brand engagement share a common goal of fostering relationships between brands and their consumers, their strategies, mechanisms, and impacts can significantly differ. Social brand engagement is more concerned with public, community-based interactions in a digital environment. It plays a crucial role in shaping public perception and conversation about the brand. On the other hand, consumer brand engagement leans more towards the individual's personal emotional connection and investment in the brand and plays a significant role in promoting long-term loyalty and preference. Both forms of engagement are crucial for Islamic banks to thrive in an increasingly digital and competitive marketplace.

6.3 SUMMARY

In the context of Islamic banking, a range of diverse factors work in concert to both foster social brand engagement and stimulate consumer brand engagement. These factors and their interlinkages are informed by theoretical underpinnings from social exchange-, and social influence theory, with dynamics such as bargaining, sampling, commitment, and internalization being particularly relevant. Factors like 'Narrative Threads of Wisdom', 'Moral Weaves of Society', 'Illuminating the Conscious Horizon', 'Harvesting Wisdom Nuggets', and 'Sculpting the Influential Echo Chamber' aid in the co-creation of UGC, essentially forming an 'echo chamber' of information, advice, and experience that helps shape public perception of the brand, and consequently, social brand engagement. These narratives can include personal experiences with the bank, commentary on the ethical practices of the bank, or shared information about the bank's services. When these narratives are driven by influencers or trusted figures, they carry even more weight and can significantly shape public opinion about the bank.

On the other hand, factors such as 'Virtuosity in Visualization', 'Precision of Perspective', and 'Symbiosis of Sentiment' contribute to the 'Prism of Perception', impacting the way content is

seen, understood, and engaged with. High-quality content that is accurate and generates sentiment can significantly enhance user engagement. For consumer brand engagement, factors like 'Emotional Equilibrium', 'Luminaries of the Trade', 'Social Resonance', 'Friends Interaction', 'Precision of the Perspective', 'Confluence of the Conveniences', 'Spectrum of Sensibility', 'Discourse of Kinship', and 'Resonance of Reverence' play a crucial role. Emotional equilibrium can be achieved when the consumers feel that the engagement with the brand is satisfying and beneficial for them. High-profile figures in the industry ('Luminaries of the Trade') can have a significant impact on consumer perceptions and engagement with the brand.

Social resonance and interactions with friends can provide users with a sense of community and shared understanding, fostering more substantial engagement. The precision of the perspective and the convenience factor can add to the overall user experience, thereby boosting consumer brand engagement. Furthermore, when consumers identify with the brand's sensibilities, share a sense of kinship, or have reverence for the brand, this can lead to deeper and more meaningful engagement. These factors interplay within the framework of social exchange and social influence theories to effectively promote social and consumer brand engagement within Islamic banks. While social brand engagement leans more towards shaping public opinion and perceptions, consumer brand engagement focuses more on individual customer experiences and relationships with the brand. Both are vital for the overall success and sustainability of Islamic banks in the competitive financial market.

CHAPTER: CONCLUSION AND RECONDITIONS

7.1 INTRODUCTION

In the unique cultural context of Pakistan, UGC plays a significant role in brand engagement for Islamic banks. The societal fabric of Pakistan, heavily rooted in Islamic values, creates a powerful sense of community and trust that are reinforced through UGC. It becomes a conduit for the exchange of ideas, experiences, and information that contribute to the shaping of consumers' perceptions about Islamic banks. Through UGC, Islamic banks can connect with their customers on a deeper level, building trust and fostering relationships that go beyond transactions.

The unique characteristics of UGC that positively influence brand engagement for Islamic banks in Pakistan include authenticity, diversity of perspective, relatability, and engagement. Authentic content provides consumers with a sense of trust in the information they receive. The diversity of perspectives presented in UGC helps customers to gain a holistic understanding of the bank's services and practices. The relatability of user experiences shared in UGC creates a sense of connection and empathy among consumers, leading to stronger brand engagement. Moreover, the engagement characteristic of UGC, exemplified by interactions, likes, shares, and comments, provides an opportunity for consumers to participate in discussions, ask questions, and voice their opinions, thereby deepening their relationship with the brand.

The quality of UGC significantly mediates the relationship between functional and emotional values and brand engagement for Islamic banks in Pakistan. High-quality UGC, characterized by its relevance, accuracy, and emotional resonance, can successfully convey the functional benefits of Islamic banking. When customers understand the practical advantages of Islamic banking through dependable UGC, their engagement with the brand is likely to increase. On the other hand, UGC also taps into emotional values. When consumers share their positive experiences and satisfaction with the ethical and Sharia-compliant practices of Islamic banks, this elicits emotional responses in other consumers. This emotional connection, driven by the quality of UGC, can boost consumer engagement with the brand. The four stages of the Social Exchange Theory - Sampling, Bargaining, Commitment, and Internalization - represent a process of relationship building that is interconnected and cumulative. Each stage feeds into the next, gradually deepening the connection between the consumer and the brand, culminating

in high levels of brand engagement. Let us look at how this process might unfold in the context of Islamic banking.

1. **Sampling:** In this initial stage, individuals seek to identify with a person, group, or brand by exploring and sampling shared content, opinions, and experiences. In the context of Islamic banks, consumers might be attracted by UGC that highlights the bank's adherence to Islamic principles, its financial products, customer service quality, or community impact. This stage is crucial as it sets the foundation for subsequent stages, and the first impression can significantly influence the overall trajectory of the relationship.
2. **Bargaining:** Once consumers have sampled the available content and gained an initial understanding of the brand, they move on to the bargaining stage. Here, they interact more deeply with the content and the brand, expressing their views, asking questions, or seeking clarifications. For Islamic banks, the bargaining stage might involve discussions about the specifics of Islamic banking principles, the benefits of different products, or the ethical considerations of banking with them. The quality and accuracy of the content shared by the bank and other users will significantly influence this stage. Successful bargaining can lead to increased trust and a more profound commitment.
3. **Commitment:** At this stage, consumers have gained enough knowledge and confidence to commit to the brand. They might open an account, apply for a product, or recommend the bank to others. The commitment stage is a crucial transition from being interested to becoming involved. For Islamic banks, commitment could reflect the consumer's alignment with the bank's Islamic values, their satisfaction with the services, or their belief in the UGC shared by other customers.
4. **Internalization:** This final stage involves consumers integrating their relationship with the brand into their identity. They not only use the bank's services but also advocate for the bank within their social circles, contributing to the UGC and shaping public opinion. The internalization stage can be powerful for Islamic banks as it can turn customers into brand ambassadors who can authentically share their positive experiences and beliefs about Islamic banking.

Each stage of this process builds on the previous one, leading to deeper engagement and stronger relationships. It is important to note, though, that this process is not linear, and consumers can cycle back to previous stages based on new experiences or information.

Therefore, Islamic banks need to continually monitor and nurture their relationships with consumers, ensuring high-quality, accurate, and engaging UGC, upholding Islamic values, and fostering a supportive and ethical banking community. In conclusion, the cultural context of Pakistan, the unique characteristics of UGC, and the quality of UGC all play crucial roles in influencing brand engagement for Islamic banks. The Social Flux created by UGC provides a platform for consumers to interact with Islamic banks and with each other, fostering a sense of community, trust, and commitment. Thus, for Islamic banks in Pakistan, focusing on encouraging high-quality UGC and understanding its influence on consumers can be a powerful strategy to strengthen brand engagement. Following is the detail of achievement of the research objectives.

Objective 1: To examine how cultural and societal values within an Islamic banking context in Pakistan influence user-generated content and subsequent brand engagement.

The findings from this research objective have revealed a deeply interconnected relationship between cultural and societal values, UGC, and brand engagement within the context of Islamic banking in Pakistan. Pakistan's cultural and societal fabric, heavily influenced by Islamic principles, has a substantial impact on the nature of UGC created by consumers. The importance of community, trust, and ethical behaviour, central tenets of Islam, pervades the UGC, shaping the narratives and discussions around Islamic banks.

One of the major findings is the role of UGC in reinforcing these societal values. UGC often discusses the ethical banking practices of Islamic banks, their adherence to Sharia law, and their role in supporting the community. This content acts as a catalyst for conversations about the societal importance of Islamic banks and their alignment with Pakistan's cultural and religious principles. It also helps dispel myths and misconceptions about Islamic banking, thereby contributing to a more informed public. UGC acts as a bridge, connecting the cultural and societal values with the brands of Islamic banks. It enhances brand engagement by enabling consumers to see the alignment between their values and those of the Islamic banks. The authentic experiences shared by users through UGC not only highlight the functional benefits of banking with Islamic institutions, such as profit sharing and non-interest-based transactions, but also emphasize the emotional rewards of aligning with a bank that upholds and operates under the same ethical and religious principles that they do.

Moreover, the research revealed that UGC fosters trust, a crucial element in banking. When users share positive experiences and speak about ethical practices of Islamic banks, this builds

confidence in other consumers, promoting a higher level of engagement. This trust-building is amplified in the context of Pakistan where word-of-mouth and community validation hold a significant value. In addition, the societal emphasis on communal welfare found in Pakistani culture was reflected in the UGC. Users were found to highlight how Islamic banks contribute to the society through Zakat, charitable giving, and the refusal to invest in industries that are harmful to society. This aspect of UGC creates a strong emotional bond and sense of loyalty towards the brand, fuelling brand engagement.

Furthermore, the influence of cultural and societal values was also apparent in how users engaged with UGC. Respectful and thoughtful discourse was a norm in UGC revolving around Islamic banking. This aligns with the societal norms in Pakistan, and contributes to a positive online environment, further enhancing brand engagement. In conclusion, within the Islamic banking context in Pakistan, cultural and societal values significantly influence UGC and subsequent brand engagement. By aligning their practices with these values, Islamic banks can foster a more robust and impactful engagement with their consumers. As these values underpin the narratives and discussions in UGC, they shape the perception and engagement of consumers with the brand.

Objective 2: To identify how the content characteristics of UGC impact brand engagement in the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan.

The findings related to this research objective reveal that UGC significantly impact brand engagement in the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan. The characteristics of UGC play a pivotal role in determining the quality of engagement and fostering a deeper connection between the consumers and the Islamic banks. One of the most influential characteristics of UGC is authenticity. Consumers appreciate genuine experiences and real-life narratives shared by other customers. Authentic UGC is seen as trustworthy and credible, which in turn fosters deeper engagement with the Islamic banks' brands. The transparency and sincerity in user reviews, comments, and discussions about the banks' adherence to Islamic principles and ethical banking significantly influence the perception and decision-making process of other consumers.

The volume of UGC also contributes to brand engagement. High volume content implies a larger number of consumers interacting and sharing their experiences, suggesting a larger community of users. This fosters a sense of belonging and encourages more consumers to engage with the brand. Furthermore, the high volume of UGC signals the bank's popularity and

trustworthiness, which motivates potential customers to engage with the brand. The diversity of perspectives found in UGC encourages deeper engagement by presenting various viewpoints, experiences, and insights into the Islamic banking services. This aids consumers in making informed decisions, leading to higher trust and engagement with the bank.

UGC that offers a high level of peer influence, primarily through customer reviews and recommendations, strongly impacts brand engagement. Peer reviews and testimonials provide consumers with insights into the experiences of other consumers, offering Discourse of Kinship and influencing their perceptions and interactions with the brand. The creative aspects of UGC, including unique narratives and innovative presentation of information, capture consumers' interest and stimulate engagement. Likewise, UGC that presents real-life experiences, especially those that align with the Islamic principles of ethical banking, resonate strongly with the consumers, fostering an emotional connection with the bank.

UGC that is easily accessible, timely, and relatable enhances the relevance of the brand for consumers. By providing updated information about the services, interest-free banking options, and aligning with consumers' values, UGC makes the brand more appealing to engage with. UGC also promotes brand engagement by offering value to the consumers. Whether this is achieved through providing detailed information about the bank's operations or discussing the benefits of Islamic banking, valuable UGC helps consumers understand the brand better and motivates them to engage with it.

Lastly, the emotional aspect of UGC, especially when it ties the services of Islamic banks with the shared values of the community, creates an emotional bond between the consumers and the brand. This emotional connection, built on shared values and communal identity, fuels long-term engagement with the brand. In summary, the content characteristics of UGC, from authenticity and diversity to emotional resonance and value proposition, significantly impact brand engagement for Islamic banks in Pakistan. They shape consumers' perceptions, influence their decisions, and foster a deeper connection with the brand, thereby enhancing brand engagement.

Objective 3: To investigate the impact of online incivility in the form of negative user-generated content on brand engagement within the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan.

The research objective aimed to investigate the impact of online incivility, specifically in the form of negative UGC, on brand engagement within the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan. Based on the gathered data and analysis, several findings have emerged.

Firstly, negative UGC has a substantial impact on brand engagement. Negative experiences shared by users, whether it is about services, transaction processes, or adherence to Islamic principles, can tarnish the reputation of the Islamic banks, deter potential customers, and reduce brand engagement. Users perceive these negative reviews or comments as a credible source of information, which shapes their perception of the brand and their decision to engage with it. However, the impact of negative UGC is not only negative. Interestingly, the way Islamic banks respond to negative content significantly influences brand engagement. Banks that proactively address criticism and show a commitment to improving their services can mitigate the negative effects of online incivility and, in some cases, even enhance brand engagement. The transparent handling of criticism demonstrates the bank's dedication to customer service and its commitment to adhering to Islamic values of fairness and honesty, fostering trust and engagement among consumers.

Moreover, it is clear that the cultural context of Pakistan, with its high regard for respect and politeness, intensifies the impact of online incivility on brand engagement. Online incivility, which is perceived as disrespectful and contrary to the values of Islamic banking, can discourage users from engaging with the brand. Thus, maintaining civility in online interactions is crucial for promoting brand engagement. Negative UGC also influences the dynamics of Discourse of Kinship. Negative reviews or comments from industry experts or influential figures can have a larger impact, discouraging others from engaging with the brand. Conversely, when these influential figures refute or contradict the negative UGC, it can mitigate the adverse effects and enhance brand engagement.

Negative UGC can, paradoxically, stimulate engagement by triggering discussions and debates about the services and operations of Islamic banks. Although these debates may stem from negative content, they provide a platform for consumers to share their experiences, clarify misunderstandings, and learn more about Islamic banking. Such interactions can foster community-building, a key social dynamic that can enhance brand engagement.

Upon further analysis that includes the Social Flux of UGC, the research revealed that the impact of online incivility and negative UGC on brand engagement is influenced by various social factors. Firstly, the role of industry experts and influencers cannot be underestimated.

Their opinion on negative UGC could either amplify or alleviate the damaging effects on brand engagement. For instance, when an expert endorses or reiterates a negative review or comment, this can discourage users from engaging with the Islamic bank. Conversely, if the expert dismisses the negative UGC as inaccurate or biased, this can alleviate its impact, and even lead to enhanced engagement as the credibility of the bank is restored.

Discourse of Kinship also plays a significant role. In the digital age, consumers heavily rely on the experiences and opinions of others to form their judgments and decisions. Negative UGC can deter potential customers as it serves as Discourse of Kinship that the bank may not be dependable or satisfactory in its services. However, when negative UGC is countered by a substantial amount of positive UGC, the adverse impact can be reduced, promoting brand engagement. The research also found that the presence of a community can influence the effect of online incivility on brand engagement. Online incivility can discourage users from engaging with the brand, particularly if the negative UGC is left unaddressed, or if the bank's response is seen as inadequate or insincere. However, when there is a strong, supportive online community, users can come to the bank's defines, discuss the negative content, and share positive experiences. This co-creation and community-building can enhance brand engagement, despite the presence of negative UGC. Furthermore, the research highlighted the importance of information sharing in mitigating the effects of online incivility. When Islamic banks proactively share information about their actions to address negative UGC, such as improving services or rectifying errors, this can help reduce the negative impact and foster brand engagement. This finding underscores the importance of maintaining open communication channels and transparent information sharing in the face of online incivility.

This research shows that while online incivility and negative UGC can negatively impact brand engagement, its effects are significantly influenced by Social Flux of UGC. The role of industry experts, Discourse of Kinship, community-building, and information sharing can either exacerbate or reduce the negative impact, underlining the importance of strategic social engagement for Islamic banks in Pakistan. While negative UGC, or online incivility, can negatively impact brand engagement, its actual effect is complex and contingent on various factors, including the bank's response to the negative content, cultural context, Social Flux of User-Generated Content, and the potential for community-building. Consequently, managing negative UGC effectively is crucial for Islamic banks in Pakistan to maintain and enhance brand engagement.

7.2 RESEARCH CONTRIBUTION

This research provides valuable theoretical contributions to the existing body of literature in several ways. Firstly, it enriches the understanding of brand engagement within the context of Islamic banking, a field that has been comparatively underexplored in current literature. The specific focus on the Pakistan context provides a unique lens to understand how cultural and societal values within an Islamic banking context influence user-generated content and subsequent brand engagement. This research thus contributes to the broader understanding of the influence of culture on brand engagement, particularly in the context of religious-based financial services and enhances the existing theoretical frameworks in this field.

Secondly, the research extends the discourse on UGC and its impact on brand engagement. The unique characteristics of user-generated content that positively influence brand engagement for Islamic banks in Pakistan have been identified, thereby providing a more nuanced understanding of the specific types of content and their properties that foster engagement. This contributes to the broader literature on the role of UGC in brand engagement, offering deeper insights into the mechanism through which different forms of user-generated content can drive engagement.

Thirdly, the study clarifies how the quality of UGC mediates the relationship between functional and emotional values and brand engagement for Islamic banks in Pakistan. The empirical findings on this relationship contribute to existing theories by elucidating how content quality acts as a mediator, and further elaborating on the role of functional and emotional values in influencing brand engagement. This expands existing theories on the interactions between content quality, emotional and functional values, and brand engagement.

Fourthly, the research offers significant insights into the Social Flux of UGC . The findings on how factors like industry experts, Discourse of Kinship, friends' interaction, information sharing, co-creation, community building, social support, entertainment, and relationship building impact the influence of user-generated content on brand engagement in Islamic banks, enrich our theoretical understanding of Social Flux of User-Generated Content in brand engagement. This research also provides a more comprehensive understanding of social exchange theory, demonstrating how it operates in the context of brand engagement and user-generated content in the digital age.

Lastly, the research provides a significant theoretical contribution to understanding the impact of online incivility, in the form of negative user-generated content on brand engagement. The

exploration of this relationship in the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan helps to close a gap in the current understanding of online incivility and its implications for brand engagement, providing a new dimension to the literature on online incivility. Overall, the research provides a significant contribution to knowledge in relation to how brand engagement in Islamic banks occurs and sheds light on the role of UGC, and the impact of the Social Flux of UGC and online incivility. It offers valuable insights and new theoretical perspectives that can stimulate further research in this field.

7.3 PRACTICAL CONTRIBUTION

The research offers substantial practical contributions, particularly to Islamic banks operating in Pakistan and similar cultural contexts. The study reveals how cultural and societal values within an Islamic banking context in Pakistan influence user-generated content (UGC) and subsequent brand engagement. For practitioners, this emphasizes the importance of understanding and respecting the cultural nuances of their target market when curating and promoting UGC. Islamic banks should consider these cultural dynamics when creating their digital marketing strategies and creating content that resonates with their target audience, increasing the potential for customer engagement.

Additionally, the research highlights the crucial role that UGC plays in promoting brand engagement for Islamic banks. By identifying the characteristics of UGC that positively influence engagement, it provides a guide to the kinds of content that Islamic banks should promote. The findings point to the importance of authenticity, diversity of perspective, real-life experiences, and other elements of UGC that resonate with consumers and stimulate engagement. Thus, the banks can use these insights to optimize their digital content strategies and foster increased customer engagement. Moreover, the research reveals how the quality of UGC mediates the relationship between functional and emotional values and brand engagement. This implies that Islamic banks need to focus not only on the content of their messages but also on their quality. To enhance brand engagement, banks should strive to generate high-quality content that aligns with both the functional (product-specific) and emotional (brand-related) values that their customers hold.

The study also illustrates the significance of the Social Flux of UGC. It shows how social factors like information sharing, co-creation, community building, social support, and relationship building can impact brand engagement. For Islamic banks, this suggests the value of fostering a sense of community among users, encouraging user interaction, and providing

social support. Banks should leverage these Social Flux of User-Generated Content in their digital marketing strategies to build stronger relationships with customers and promote deeper engagement.

Lastly, the research sheds light on the impact of online incivility, in the form of negative UGC, on brand engagement. This emphasizes the need for Islamic banks to monitor their online platforms for any forms of incivility or negativity that could potentially harm their brand image and reduce engagement. Banks need to have strategies in place to manage negative UGC, including monitoring systems to detect such content and procedures to address it in a manner that upholds the bank's reputation and maintains the trust of its customers. The practical implications of this research are manifold, providing key insights that can help Islamic banks in Pakistan and beyond to leverage UGC effectively, harness Social Flux of UGC and manage online incivility, all with the goal of enhancing brand engagement. By applying the findings of this research, Islamic banks can create more effective digital marketing strategies that are culturally nuanced, resonate with their target audience, and drive greater customer engagement. Developing a practical guideline for marketers in Pakistan's Islamic banking industry to improve consumer brand engagement can be achieved by considering the interplay between motivators of UGC, the characteristics of UGC, and the Social Flux of UGC. Below are some strategies rooted in the stages of sampling, bargaining, commitment, and internalization:

Sampling:

As sampling occurs when an individual seeks to identify with a group or person, marketers should leverage user-generated content's authenticity, high volume, and diversity. To initiate this connection there must be some focus on customers sharing real-life experiences to present a diverse perspective of services. Encouraging UGC that promotes the Moral Weaves of Society and awareness about the Islamic banking industry can be pivotal in drawing attention and fostering initial connections. Improving and using sampling effectively to enhance brand engagement of Islamic banks in Pakistan could be approached from multiple directions.

1. **Quality and Relevance of Content:** Islamic banks need to ensure their content quality is excellent and relevant to their audience. They should regularly review and update their content, ensuring its accuracy. Besides, they should ensure that the content aligns with the cultural and religious values of their target demographic.

2. **Promoting Authenticity:** Authenticity helps establish trust between the brand and its consumers. By encouraging customers to share real experiences, testimonials, and reviews, banks can foster authenticity. Emphasizing UGC from satisfied customers will lead to high-quality sampling that resonates with potential customers.
3. **Boosting Peer Influence:** Harnessing the power of peer influence is crucial for promoting sampling. Customers are more likely to sample products or services if they see their peers doing the same. Therefore, Islamic banks should consider leveraging influencer marketing or developing referral programs to increase peer influence and subsequently encourage sampling.
4. **Stimulating Creativity:** Creative content captures the attention of consumers and increases engagement. Banks can encourage their customers to create unique, innovative content about their experiences. Contests, interactive posts, and user polls are a few ways to stimulate creativity and interaction.
5. **Leveraging Social Flux of User-Generated Content:** By encouraging information sharing, co-creation, and community building, banks can create a more engaging environment for their customers. For instance, they can create online communities or forums where customers can share their experiences, ask questions, and get advice. This not only promotes information sharing and co-creation but also fosters a sense of community and support.
6. **Enhancing Accessibility:** Accessibility is key to promoting sampling. Banks need to make it easy for their customers to sample their products and services. This could involve simplifying the sign-up process, providing demos or tutorials, or offering initial services for free or at a discounted rate.
7. **Motivating with Rewards:** Banks can use rewards or incentives to motivate potential customers to sample their offerings. These could range from promotional offers, discounts for first-time users, cashback, or loyalty points. Such initiatives can stimulate sampling and encourage customers to engage with the brand.
8. **Utilizing Social Media Platforms:** Given the significance of UGC, Islamic banks should utilize social media platforms to their fullest potential. This could include creating engaging posts that invite comments, shares, and likes, thus increasing visibility and prompting more customers to sample their services.

By taking these recommendations into account, Islamic banks in Pakistan can significantly enhance the effectiveness of sampling, leading to improved brand engagement.

Bargaining:

At this stage, the relationship between consumers and the brand is deepened. Excellence and the Precision of Perspective are critical in stimulating bargaining. The content should be relatable and timely, showing an understanding of consumers' needs and the current market scenario. Encouraging the exchange of experiences and information sharing and fostering a sense of community are key. This can be done through forums, Q&A sessions, webinars, or social media platforms where customers can interact and exchange views about services. Leveraging bargaining as a social exchange can significantly enhance brand engagement for Islamic banks. Here are several recommendations for marketers:

1. **Promote UGC Quality and Relevance:** First and foremost, it is crucial to produce and promote high-quality and relevant UGC. Encouraging customers to share their positive experiences and stories related to banking services is key and will provide a platform for bargaining with potential customers, as they will be more inclined to engage with a brand that other consumers positively endorse.
2. **Foster Trust and Authenticity:** Fostering an atmosphere of trust by being transparent about the services and products offered is also important. Authentic, genuine interactions will set the stage for bargaining, as trust is a key element of any successful negotiation. Highlighting the bank's alignment with Islamic principles and values, and how these principles influence the bank's operations is also key.
3. **Cultivate Positive Peer Influence:** Harnessing the power of peer influence can lead to effective bargaining. When potential customers see their peers endorsing or advocating for Islamic banking services, they may be more inclined to engage.
4. **Leverage Social Flux of UGC:** Creating a sense of community around the brand is also recommended. This could be achieved by facilitating forums for discussions, promoting information sharing, and encouraging co-creation of content. When potential customers feel they are part of a community, they are more likely to engage with the brand, making bargaining easier.

5. **Reward Engagement:** Offering incentives or rewards for engagement is a strong bargaining chip. This could involve discounts on banking services, points for referrals, or exclusive access to new services. Such rewards can encourage customers to take the step from engagement to commitment.
6. **Use social media to Promote Bargaining:** Utilizing the power of social media to initiate bargaining also matters. Regularly engaging with followers, responding to their queries promptly, and appreciating their content and contributions is important. This would strengthen the brand-consumer relationship and make bargaining more effective.
7. **Encourage Public Opinion as an Influencer:** By encouraging the creation of public opinion, Islamic banks can increase the likelihood of bargaining. Having customers as influencers, sharing their positive experiences, can motivate potential customers to try the banking services offered.

By incorporating these recommendations, Islamic banks can use bargaining as an effective tool to improve brand engagement. These strategies will not only foster strong relationships with customers but also enhance their loyalty and commitment to the brand.

Commitment: To stimulate commitment, engagement should be prioritized. Peer influence, such as testimonials or reviews from satisfied customers can build trust and loyalty. An active presence on social networks is key, offering value to consumers through informative and interactive content. The motive here is to ensure customers feel that by committing to the bank, they are making an ethical choice. Entertainment in the form of engaging, enjoyable content can foster a stronger community and encourage commitment to the brand. To optimize commitment as a social exchange tool in enhancing brand engagement for Islamic banks, marketers could consider the following recommendations:

1. **Enhance User Generated Content (UGC) Quality:** Ensuring the UGC is of high quality, relevant, and engaging can go a long way in enhancing customer commitment. The more users feel connected and engaged with the content, the more committed they will be to the brand.
2. **Strengthen Peer Influence:** By encouraging satisfied customers to share their experiences and become brand advocates, Islamic banks can strengthen the peer influence aspect of their marketing efforts. When customers see that their peers are committed to a brand, they are more likely to follow suit.

3. **Promote Authenticity and Trust:** Encouraging users to share real-life experiences and authentic content can foster trust and promote commitment. Banks should also ensure their own content is accurate and transparent, adhering to Islamic principles, and reflecting the true nature of their services.
4. **Boost Customer Engagement:** Implement initiatives that can boost customer engagement such as interactive forums, Q&A sessions with experts, and user-friendly platforms. The more customers engage with the brand, the higher their commitment levels will be.
5. **Incentivize Commitment:** Offering incentives or rewards for commitment can be an effective strategy. This could take the form of loyalty points, access to exclusive services, or preferential rates for committed customers.
6. **Leverage Social Flux of User-Generated Content:** Creating a sense of community can promote commitment. Encourage co-creation of content, facilitate community building, and provide social support. A strong sense of community can foster a sense of belonging that will encourage commitment.
7. **Commit to Moral Weaves of Society:** Demonstrate commitment to Moral Weaves of Society and values that align with your customers' beliefs. Highlighting the bank's dedication to Islamic principles and the resultant positive impact on the community can foster a similar commitment in customers.
8. **Maintain Timeliness and Relevance:** Ensuring the content shared is timely and relevant to the customers' needs can foster commitment. This involves keeping up with current trends, customer feedback, and market demands.

By following these recommendations, Islamic banks can leverage commitment as a social exchange process to boost brand engagement. This can lead to stronger customer relationships, greater brand loyalty, and a more engaged customer base.

Internalization:

This is the stage where customers align themselves fully with the brand values. By ensuring your content is relatable, timely, and has the potential for virality, customers are more likely to agree with the brand's values and principles. The concept of Discourse of Kinship can be used effectively in this stage. Highlighting positive experiences and expert opinions can help

reinforce a customer's decision to choose a bank. Internalization, as a facet of social exchange, plays a critical role in shaping consumers' perceptions and behaviours. Below are some recommendations for Islamic banks to improve or use internalization to boost brand engagement:

1. **Promote User-Generated Content (UGC):** Encourage users to create and share their experiences with the brand. This not only amplifies the authenticity and relatability of content but also facilitates the internalization process as potential customers are more likely to identify with real-life experiences shared by peers.
2. **Leverage Expert Opinions and Influencers:** Collaborating with industry experts and influencers can provide credible opinions, lending further trust and authority to the brand. Their approval and endorsement can facilitate internalization among their followers, thereby influencing their decisions.
3. **Emphasize Timeliness and Relevance:** Regularly updating content to ensure it is timely and relevant is key. This will keep the audience engaged, and customers may be more likely to internalize the information that is shared, encouraging them to engage more deeply with the brand.
4. **Foster Discourse of Kinship:** Publicly display testimonials, customer reviews, and ratings to validate claims. This will help potential customers to internalize the positive experiences of others, and thus feel more comfortable engaging with the brand.
5. **Incorporate Islamic Values:** Since the audience is primarily interested in Islamic banking, highlighting the ways the bank adheres to and promotes Islamic principles and ethics is key. This will resonate with their values, facilitating the internalization process and increasing brand engagement.
6. **Enhance Information Sharing:** Develop a platform that facilitates the easy sharing of information amongst consumers. The more the audience can learn from each other's experiences, the more likely they are to internalize these positive interactions and engage with the brand.
7. **Promote Co-creation:** Encouraging customers to participate in the co-creation of content is also key. This will make them feel valued and included, enhancing the internalization process, and building a stronger bond with the brand.

8. **Community Building:** Fostering a sense of community amongst customers through regular engagement, online forums, and social events is another important strategy. A strong community promotes a sense of belonging, which can facilitate internalization and increase brand loyalty.

By integrating these recommendations into their marketing strategies, Islamic banks can enhance the internalization processes amongst their customers, leading to improved brand engagement and customer loyalty. Through all stages, the Social Flux of UGC and user interactions should not be overlooked. The co-creation of content, community building, and relationship building are all vital in establishing a strong bond between the consumer and the brand. These strategies do not only apply to online engagement; they should also reflect in offline brand activities and interactions for a seamless brand experience. In conclusion, improving consumer brand engagement within the Islamic banking industry in Pakistan requires a comprehensive understanding of UGC, its motivators, characteristics, and the Social Flux of UGC involved. Sampling, bargaining, commitment, and internalization provide a practical roadmap for marketers to facilitate consumer journey, fostering a strong and lasting bond with the brand.

Finally, while the research explored the Social Flux UGC, it primarily focused on factors like information sharing, co-creation, community building, social support, and relationship building. It did not consider other potentially significant Social Fluxes relating to UGC such as power dynamics, societal trends, or global influences on user behaviors. These could also influence how UGC is generated, shared, and consumed, and thus, affect its impact on brand engagement. While these limitations may affect the breadth and depth of the study to some extent, they also point to potential avenues for future research, such as exploring these dynamics in different cultural contexts, across different industries, using varied methodologies, considering different types of negative UGC, and examining other Social Flux of UGC.

Social Exchange Type	Definition	Measurement	Potential Issues
Sampling	The initial stage where consumers try or experience the brand, fostered by user-generated content, authenticity, and diverse perspectives.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engagement with user-generated content. - Uptake of sampling opportunities. - Feedback and reviews from customers after sampling. - Increase in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensuring quality and relevance of content. - Fostering authenticity - Encouraging creativity in content generation. - Enhancing accessibility.

		new customer acquisitions.	- Motivating customers with appropriate rewards.
Bargaining	The stage where relationships are deepened between consumers and the brand, facilitated by the exchange of experiences and information sharing.	- Frequency and quality of user interactions. - Number of returning customers. - Customer reviews and testimonials. - Engagement metrics on social media.	- Promoting high-quality and relevant user-generated content. - Maintaining authenticity and trust. - Building a sense of community. - Offering rewards for engagement. - Encouraging public opinion influencers.
Commitment	The stage where consumers show loyalty towards the brand, stimulated by trust building and active presence on social networks.	- Customer retention rates. - Frequency of transactions per customer. - Length of relationship with the bank. - Referral rates.	- Ensuring the quality of UGC. - Strengthening peer influence. - Building trust and authenticity. - Maintaining timeliness and relevance of content. - Encouraging commitment through incentives.
Internalization	The final stage where customers fully align with the brand values, facilitated by relatable content, Discourse of Kinship, and sharing of positive experiences.	- Brand perception surveys. - Customer advocacy metrics. - Frequency of positive mentions in user-generated content. - Alignment of customer values with brand values.	- Encouraging user-generated content. - Highlighting Islamic values. - Leveraging expert opinions and influencers. - Promoting co-creation. - Building a sense of community.

Here is the table presenting the type of social exchange, their definition, ways to measure, and potential issues Islamic banks may face. These social exchanges all contribute to the brand's overall customer engagement. By adopting these recommendations and monitoring their performance, Islamic banks can enhance these social exchanges, thereby improving brand engagement and loyalty among their customers.

7.4 RESEARCH LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

As with any research, this study on the impact of UGC in terms of brand engagement in Islamic banks within Pakistan's cultural context does have its limitations. Firstly, the research was

focused on the Pakistani market. While this allows for a detailed analysis of the unique cultural and societal factors at play within this context, it may limit the generalizability of the findings to other markets or cultural contexts. Other countries might have different cultural values, consumer behaviors, or digital media usage trends that could impact how UGC affects brand engagement. This geographically specific focus might limit the application of the findings to Islamic banks operating outside of Pakistan. Secondly, the study concentrated on Islamic banks. Though this was necessary to examine the impact within a particular industry, it does mean that the results may not be directly transferable to other sectors. Different industries might have different dynamics when it comes to UGC and brand engagement, given the varying nature of their products or services, target audiences, and marketing strategies.

Another limitation lies in the methodology. While this research used both primary data and literature reviews to draw its conclusions, it did not consider other data collection methods such as qualitative interviews, which could have provided more in-depth insights. For instance, interviews with marketing professionals in Islamic banks could have given more nuanced insights into the strategies used to promote UGC and foster brand engagement. Additionally, direct insights from consumers could have added rich, experiential data to the research findings. Further, the research considered the impact of negative UGC in the form of online incivility on brand engagement. However, the study did not explore other forms of negative UGC, such as misinformation or disinformation, which could also significantly impact brand engagement in the digital age.

7.4.1 Future directions

The research on UGC, and its impact on brand engagement within the cultural context of Pakistan's Islamic banks presents numerous directions for future research. Considering the geographical focus of this study, future research could investigate broadening the scope to include other geographical contexts. Comparing how UGC impacts brand engagement in Islamic banks across various countries could reveal interesting insights about cultural differences and similarities. It would be particularly interesting to compare countries with different levels of digital media penetration and varying cultural attitudes towards banking and finance. Future research could also expand the industry scope. While this study focused on Islamic banks, it would be insightful to see if and how the dynamics identified in this research apply to other industries. This could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the impact of user-generated content on brand engagement across different sectors, offering valuable insights for marketing strategies.

In terms of the methodology, the current research could be complemented by more qualitative data. Future research might involve conducting in-depth interviews with both consumers and marketing professionals. This could provide richer insights into the motivations behind creating and engaging with user-generated content, as well as the strategies used by companies to encourage and manage such content. Further, the aspect of online incivility as a form of negative user-generated content was a focus in this study. Future research could explore other forms of negative content, such as fake news or misinformation. Understanding how these types of content affect brand engagement and what strategies can be employed to combat them would be highly valuable in today's digital landscape.

Lastly, a future research direction could involve a more detailed exploration of the Social Flux of UGC. This study covered several factors, but others could also have significant impacts on UGC and brand engagement, such as societal trends, power dynamics, or global influences. By examining these additional factors, future research could present a more nuanced understanding of the complex interplay between user-generated content and brand engagement. In conclusion, while this research has provided valuable insights into user-generated content and brand engagement in the context of Pakistan's Islamic banks, it has also paved the way for several exciting future research directions. These avenues, if pursued, can add to the richness and depth of understanding in this field, benefiting both academia and industry practitioners.

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APPENDICES

8.1 APPENDIX 1: INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

The research aims, objectives, and questions inform the type of data required for the study. Given that this research aims to understand the dynamics of user-generated content (UGC) and consumer-brand engagement within the context of Islamic banking in Pakistan, it is crucial to gain insights from the perspective of customers. To this end, semi-structured interviews are a flexible and powerful tool to gain rich, detailed data.

1. Research Objective: To examine how cultural and societal values within an Islamic banking context in Pakistan influence user-generated content and subsequent brand engagement.

Interview Questions:

- Can you describe your experiences with Islamic banking in Pakistan?
 - How do cultural and societal values shape your interactions with Islamic banks on social media?
 - How do these cultural and societal values influence the type of content you create or share about Islamic banks on social media?
 - Can you describe an instance where these cultural and societal values influenced your engagement with an Islamic bank's social media content?
2. Research Objective: To identify how the content characteristics of user-generated content impact brand engagement in the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan.

Interview Questions:

- What type of user-generated content (e.g., reviews, comments, shares, likes) do you usually create or interact with on Islamic banks' social media pages?
 - How does the nature of this content (e.g., tone, message, form) influence your engagement with the Islamic bank's brand?
 - Can you describe a time when the type of content posted influenced your level of engagement with the Islamic bank?
 - What characteristics of user-generated content make you more likely to engage with it?
3. Research Objective: To investigate the impact of online incivility in the form of negative user-generated content on brand engagement within the context of Islamic banks in Pakistan.

Interview Questions:

- Have you ever encountered negative user-generated content about Islamic banks on social media? If so, can you describe what it was and how it affected your perception of the bank?
- How does negative content or incivility in online discussions affect your engagement with the Islamic bank's brand?
- How have you responded to negative user-generated content related to your Islamic bank?
- What role does the bank's response to negative content play in your engagement with the bank?

These questions are designed to elicit the respondents' thoughts, experiences, and perceptions related to the research objectives. However, the semi-structured nature of the interviews allows for flexibility and follow-up questions based on the respondents' answers, enabling a deeper understanding of the research topic.

The End